

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

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**DELIVERABLE
D2.1 ANALYSIS REPORT ON RECENT CLIMATIC
CHARACTERISTICS AND CLIMATIC TYPES FOR STECCI
CASE STUDY SITES**

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WP Lead	UNSA
Authors	Nusret Drešković (UNSA), Snežana Radulović (UNSPMF)
Contributing authors	Edin Hrelja (UNSA), Ahmed Dzaferagic (UNSA), Maja Novkovic (UNSPMF), Saida Ibragić (UNSA)
Reviewers	Siniša Bizjak (UMAS) Ivana Vojinović (UDG)
Abstract	<p>This document is a Report of on part of Task 2.1 and T2.2 Analysis and interpretation of climate database for the recent climate period Analysis of a long-term and contemporary ERA5-Land, ECAD gridded datasets; Analysis of STECCI meteorological station data that are closest to the selected sites, for defining the most recent climatic characteristics for the areas of selected sites for monitoring and conservation; Compiling and optimising climate GIS database for the areas of selected sites for monitoring and conservation. In this way, at the very start, this task will provide necessary repository data for the next research stages. Analysis of the most recent climate elements (for the period from 1991 to 2020), for the areas of selected sites for monitoring and conservation, based on the main climatic elements: solar radiation, altitude, temperature and precipitation and wind speed; Defining a more accurate and more comprehensive depiction of fine-grained climatic conditions of recent climate types based on Koppen's climate classification for wider areas of selected sites for monitoring and conservation and Development of the most optimised GIS sets of thematic maps in GRID format</p>
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No.	Participant Organisation name	Steering committee	Country	Organisation type
1	Univerzitet u Sarajevu	Nusret Dreskovic (Coordinator) Saida Ibragic (Project manager)	B&H	University
2	Heritage Malta	Anthony Cassar	MT	National Agency
3	Univerzitet Donja Gorica Podgorica	Andjela Jaksic- Stojanovic	MNE	University
4	Universität für angewandte Kunst Wien	Gabriela Krist	AT	University
5	Stiftung Preussischer Kulturbesitz	Stefan Simon	DE	Cultural Heritage Foundation
6	Zentrum für soziale Innovation GmbH Wien	Pamela Bartar	AT	Institute
7	Sveučiliste u Splitu, Umjetnicka akademija	Siniša Bizjak	HR	University
8	University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences	Snezana Radulovic	SRB	University
9	Institut Mines-Telecom	Vincent Thiery	FR	University

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The STECCI project focuses on safeguarding medieval limestone tombstones (stećci) and other carbonate rock monuments across 13 culturally significant sites in Europe, primarily sacred cemeteries dating to the 12th–16th centuries. These sites, recognized as candidates, and some of them UNESCO World Heritage candidates, face accelerating degradation due to climate change, microclimatic stressors, and biogeographical factors. The project integrates interdisciplinary research to evaluate environmental impacts (Work Package 2) and conduct condition assessments (Work Package 3), aiming to develop adaptive conservation strategies.

Significant risks to cultural heritage sites, particularly stećak tombstones (limestone monuments), through extreme weather events like intense rainfall, flooding, and landslides. These events accelerate physical and chemical weathering, threatening structural integrity and historical preservation. Communication with national meteorological stations has been vital for assessing site-specific climate impacts, with studies highlighting increased soil saturation and erosion risks linked to projections of rising rainfall extremes (IPCC, 2018). Key literature reveals that research on climate impacts remains Eurocentric, with limited global collaboration and a focus on physical degradation (e.g., salt crystallization, freeze-thaw cycles) rather than adaptation strategies. Over 80% of studies use quantitative methods (modelling, field tests), while social science approaches are underrepresented. Gaps include insufficient attention to intangible heritage and unclear timelines for environmental changes. Recommendations stress urgent international cooperation, enhanced monitoring, and integrating heritage preservation into climate adaptation frameworks. Open-access publishing dominates (55% of studies), facilitating knowledge dissemination. Overall, safeguarding these sites requires multidisciplinary efforts to address both immediate threats and long-term climate resilience. This review found that most studies were limited to the use of one climate change scenario and one climate model without considering the potential uncertainties in how the climate might evolve. During the stage of analyzing the referred literature and determining a possible extreme influence of CC on limestone monuments using current and long-term ERA5-Land, ECAD gridded datasets, analysis of stecci meteorological station data closest to the selected sites was also completed. That provided a foundation for compiling and optimizing the climatic GIS dataset for the areas designated for monitoring and conservation.

The tombstones, predominantly carved from limestone and dolomite, are vulnerable to physical, chemical, and biological degradation processes. Physical weathering, driven by thermal stress and freeze-thaw cycles, causes surface cracking and structural instability, particularly in alpine and continental regions like Blidinje, Bosnia (1,245 m altitude), and Unsleben, Germany. Chemical dissolution, exacerbated by acidic rainfall (pH <5) from industrial pollutants (e.g., sulfur dioxide,

nitrogen oxides), corrodes stone surfaces, a critical issue at urbanized sites such as the National Museum of Bosnia and Herzegovina in Sarajevo. Biological decay, fueled by lichen, algae, and microbial colonization, is rampant in humid Atlantic and Mediterranean zones, including Saint John Cemetery in Caen, France, and Mdina Rabat, Malta.

The 13 demo-case sites span four European biogeographical regions, each presenting unique climatic and ecological challenges. In the **Atlantic region** (e.g., Caen, France, and Kleinbardorf, Germany), mild winters and frequent storms promote prolonged moisture retention, accelerating salt crystallization and frost shattering. Vegetation, such as oak-beech forests and coastal heathlands, moderates microclimates but also introduces root penetration and organic acid secretion. The **Mediterranean region** (e.g., Radimlja, Bosnia, and Split-Marjan, Croatia) contends with arid summers and erratic rainfall, leading to salt efflorescence and groundwater fluctuations that destabilize foundations. Sclerophyllous vegetation, including holm oak and olive scrub, provides partial shade but harbours biodeteriogens like endolithic fungi. **Continental sites** (e.g., Mramorje, Serbia) experience sharp seasonal temperature contrasts, with winter lows plummeting to -15°C and summer highs exceeding 30°C . These extremes induce thermal fatigue in limestone, while beech-oak forests on mesotrophic soils buffer acidity but contribute to humic acid formation. In the **Alpine region** (e.g., Ravanjska vrata, Bosnia, and Žabljak, Montenegro), high-altitude conditions amplify UV radiation and freeze-thaw cycles, with spruce-fir forests and oligotrophic soils offering limited protection against glacial meltwater erosion.

Climate change intensifies these threats. Increased frequency of extreme rainfall events, as projected by the IPCC (2018), heightens landslide risks at sloped necropolises like Križeviči, Bosnia ($5,080\text{ m}^2$), while rising temperatures intensify biological growth and salt weathering in Mediterranean sites. Alpine regions face reduced snowfall, disrupting natural moisture regulation and exposing stones to abrasive winds. Vegetation shifts, such as the northward expansion of thermophilic species like *Pistacia lentiscus*, further alter microclimates, accelerating stone decay. Geospatial factors critically influence degradation patterns. High-altitude sites like Dugo polje, Bosnia (1,245 m), endure UV-induced surface exfoliation, while lowland sites like Radimlja, Bosnia (60 m), accumulate urban pollutants. Limestone karst systems, prevalent in Split-Marjan, Croatia, channel acidic groundwater into monument foundations, while clay-rich soils in Mramorje, Serbia, expand and contract with moisture, destabilizing stone structures.

Climatic Characteristics of Europe and Project Necropolises

The climatic framework of Europe and STECCI research sites is a product of intricate interactions between geographical, atmospheric, and oceanic dynamics. This analysis synthesizes the continent's climatic diversity, focusing on the broader spatial zones of designated necropolises, and highlights the methodologies and findings of the STECCI project.

Europe's Climatic Foundations

Five climate drivers were considered:

1. **Physico-Geographical Position:** Spanning latitudes 36°S (Cape Tarifa) to 71°N (North Cape), Europe's triangular shape-bounded by the Atlantic Ocean, Mediterranean Sea, and Ural Mountains-facilitates maritime air penetration while moderating polar and tropical influences.
2. **Topography:** Dominated by lowlands (e.g., Pannonian Basin) and young folded mountains (Alps, Dinarides, Pyrenees), Europe's relief shapes air mass trajectories, precipitation patterns, and thermal contrasts
3. **Land-Sea Distribution:** The indented coastline (37,200 km) and inland seas (Mediterranean, Baltic) amplify regional climatic differentiation.
4. **Atmospheric Circulation:** Zonal (west-east) airflows from the Atlantic dominate, while meridional (north-south) currents drive Arctic air southward.
5. **Ocean Currents:** The Gulf Stream moderates northwestern Europe's climate, while the Mediterranean's thermal inertia influences southern regions.

Thermal and Pluviometric Regimes

January Isotherms: Range from -12°C (northeastern Europe) to 10°C (southern Mediterranean).

Coastal zones (e.g., Atlantic facade) exhibit northward-curving isotherms due to maritime warmth.

July Isotherms: Follow a northwest-southeast gradient, from <10°C (Arctic) to >25°C (Mediterranean). Continental interiors (e.g., Pannonian Basin) experience intense summer heating.

Annual Temperature Amplitudes: Vary from 7°C (maritime zones) to 25°C (continental interiors).

Annual Isohyets: Decline eastward from 640 mm (London) to 160 mm (Astrakhan). Mountain regions (Alps, Dinarides) exceed 1,500–2,000 mm due to orographic uplift.

Seasonality: Dual maxima in autumn (September–November) and spring (March–May), with Mediterranean zones shifting to winter-dominated rainfall.

Project Sites: Climatic Specifics

The necropolises span two Broader Spatial climatic zones:

Northern Temperate Zone: Includes sites like *Ravanjska vrata* (Bosnia, 1,650 m) with mean annual temperatures ~9°C.

Northern Subtropical Zone: Encompasses Mediterranean sites (e.g., *Mdina Rabat*, Malta) with mean annual temperatures ~14°C.

Key findings were presented as:

Thermal Variability: Hypsometric contrasts range from 4°C (mountain basins) to 15°C (coastal lowlands).

Precipitation Extremes: Annual totals vary from 700 mm (Sava/Danube basins) to 3,000 mm (Balkan coastal mountains).

Köppen Climate Classification

The results show that the project sites fall into **two classes**:

1. Class C (Temperate):

Cfa (No dry season): Warm summer (July $\geq 22^{\circ}\text{C}$), Radimlja, Mramorje Perućac.

Cfb (No dry season): Hot summer (July $\geq 18^{\circ}\text{C}$), Caen, Klainberdor, Unsleben, Križeviči, Kopošići, Sarajevo, Hundskirche.

Csa (Mediterranean): Hot summers with drought (prolonged), Split, Velika Cista, M'dina Rabat.

2. Class D (Continental):

Dfb (Humid boreal): Cold winters (January $\leq -3^{\circ}\text{C}$), Ravanjska vrata, Dugo polje, Žabljak.

Climatic Subtypes and Variants were identified

Moderately Warm Climates (Cf)

Cfax''s: Moderately warm and humid climate with hot summer and no dry period.

Hot summers (July $\geq 22^{\circ}\text{C}$), e.g., Pannonian Basin.

Precipitation: 750–800 mm annually, dual maxima (spring/summer and autumn).

Thermal Stress: High daily amplitudes ($>23^{\circ}\text{C}$) due to anticyclonic stagnation and radiative cooling.

Cfbx'' s: Moderately warm and humid climate with warm summer and no dry period

Warm summers (July $18\text{--}22^{\circ}\text{C}$), e.g., Central Balkans.

Precipitation: ~1,000 mm, maximum in late spring/early summer.

Key Feature: Transitional zones along river valleys (e.g., the River Sava basin, mountain regions).

Mediterranean Climates (Cs)

Csax'': Mediterranean climate with hot summer and a summer dry period

Hot summers (July $\geq 22^{\circ}\text{C}$), e.g., Adriatic coast (*Mostar*).

Precipitation: 1,550 mm, winter maxima (November–December).

Dry Period: 4 months (June–September) with $<30\%$ annual rainfall.

Continental Climates (Df)

Dfbx''w: Forest-snow climate with warm summer and no dry period

Warm summers (July $\geq 18^{\circ}\text{C}$), very cold winters (January $\leq -3^{\circ}\text{C}$), e.g., Dinaric highlands.

Precipitation: ~1,300 mm, maxima in autumn (October–November).

Inversion Effects: Cold air pooling in mountain basins intensifies winter cooling.

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1. LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES AND DELIVERABLES

To effectively address the impact of climate change on cultural assets, STECCI takes a comprehensive and pluralistic approach, hence WP2 and Task 2.1 are deeply connected to the other critical project activities (Table 1.1). Because warming in continental Europe is higher than the global average, STECCI WP 2 addresses the protection of cultural heritage in areas that are already characterized by warmer climate types: Cfa (humid subtropical climate), Csa (hot-summer Mediterranean climate), Cfb (warm-summer moderate warm and humid climate), and Dfb (warm-summer humid continental climate). It is highly probable that numerous areas currently characterized by cooler and temperate climates may eventually encounter these climatic patterns. Hence, in conjunction with climate data obtained from pertinent databases (e.g., ECA&D, ECMWF, EUROCORDEX, ESGF, COPERNICUS) and regional climate models, individual researchers gathered local meteorological and environmental data. That is the base for compiling and optimising the climate GIS dataset for the areas of selected sites for monitoring and conservation.

Simultaneously, the air pollution (air quality) impact database compilation and analysis of the main types of air quality impact (CO_x, NO_x, SO_x and PM_x) will be developed (T2.2), enabling the modelling of spatial and temporal distribution of air pollution impact within the selected sites. Following database compilation, two reference climatic scenarios for the European continent will be utilized to construct GRIDs format, following the IPCC AR6 recommendations. These will be delivered in the form of an interactive, digital STECCI CLIMATE ATLAS. The GIS platform ArcGIS Pro software will be used to combine data from various sources and formats, support data visualization (developed within WP4), advanced analysis, and authoritative data maintenance in 2D, 3D, and 4D, and compile large collections of imagery such as drones, satellites, lidar, and other scientific analytical tools to identify patterns and predictions.

WP2 aims to determine the association between the decay of stećak tombstones and other stone structures and two reference climatic scenarios (T2.4 and Task 2.5). This will allow for the development of PRESERVATION GUIDELINES (a protocol for monitoring and conservation), which will be designed in WP 3. Furthermore, within WP6, a report on the cost-benefit analysis of the protective activities of tombstones under the effects of several climate change scenarios will be developed to improve the understanding of the economic benefits arising from the recommended activities (completed cost-benefit analysis based

on outputs from WP2, WP3 and WP5). Promoting open science and policy impact (T7.5, T7.7, T7.8), the STECCI database and results will be made available on the STECCI Platform (T7.5), Sketchfab, and Mendeley.

Table 1.1 Links with other project activities and deliverables

WP2	2.2 Analysis and interpretation of climate database for the recent climate period	D2.1 Analysis report on recent climatic characteristics and climatic types for STECCI case study sites	M18
	2.3 Collection, analysis, and interpretation of data for air pollution impact	D2.2 The spatial-temporal distribution database and modelling of selected air pollution impact within the selected STECCI case study sites	M18
	2.4 Climate change analysis and selected climate scenarios modelling	D2.3 Interactive digital STECCI Climate Atlas	M36
	2.5 Correlation model development for the Preservation Guidelines		
WP3	3.4 Sensor materials for the outdoor monitoring of limestone surfaces	D3.3 Conservation report	M42
	3.5 Interdisciplinary workshop and knowledge spill-over on the enhanced application of analytical methods in conservation science		
	3.6 Development of conservation concepts and in situ conservation treatments on chosen stećci from necropoles in Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia		
	3.7 Development of Preservation Guidelines	D3.4 Preservation Guidelines	M44
WP4	4.1 Acquisition of 3D models (all sites)	4.1 Acquisition of 3D models (all sites)	M36
WP6	6.2 Development of an economic model for assessment of stecci monitoring and preservation costs	D 6.2 Report on the cost-benefit analysis of the protective activities of tombstones under the effects of different climate change scenarios	M36
WP7	7.5 Development, promotion, and logistics of the STECCI Platform	D 7.6 STECCI internet Platform and the data repository export	M24
	7.7 Open Science promotion	D 7.5 Policy Brief 1	M18
	7.8 Policy Roundtables	D 7.5 Policy Brief 2	M48
	7.6 Scientific conferences		

2. LITERATURE REVIEWING

2.1 SOURCES

The sources used to create the report are listed and described in this section. It is also shown how the information was extracted and examined. The information sources have been classified (Figure 2.1.) into four major groups:

- I. Climate change agencies (Table 2.1.)
- II. STECCI Request for Local Information (Table 2.4.)
- III. Scientific sources (List of reference)

Figure 2.1. Scheme of the main sources of information reviewed

2.1.1 CLIMATE CHANGE AGENCIES

Climate change agencies play an important role in worldwide efforts to combat the negative consequences of global warming and work toward a more sustainable future. Their principal mission includes conducting comprehensive research, developing policies, implementing strategies, and promoting technical developments to combat and mitigate the effects of climate change. One of their primary responsibilities is to conduct scientific studies to further our understanding of climate change. This includes researching trends, forecasting future events, and investigating potential solutions. The findings of this study serve as an evidence base for informed decision-making, policy creation, and strategic planning.

Climate change agencies also play a critical role in policy development and advocacy. They work towards formulating, implementing, and enforcing regulations aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting renewable energy, encouraging sustainable practices, and protecting natural resources. These policies, in turn, guide the activities of governments, businesses, and communities. Furthermore, these organizations are working to promote sustainable technologies and behaviors. They invest in and promote innovation in sustainable energy, energy efficiency, and carbon capture, among other areas. These technological breakthroughs are critical for shifting to a low-carbon economy. Education and public engagement are also important components of their role. Climate change organizations work to increase awareness of the causes, effects, and solutions to climate change. They work with a variety of stakeholders, including the general public, industry, academics, and policymakers, to encourage proactive action against climate change.

They play an important role in the worldwide response to an existential crisis that impacts all aspects of human life and the environment. Some examples of global climate agencies (Table 2.1.) include the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), and the World Meteorological Organization (WMO).

Table 2.1. List of Global Climate change agencies

Agency name	Short description
Intergovernmental Panel of Climate Change (IPCC)	IPCC provides comprehensive assessments of the state of scientific, technical and socio-economic knowledge on climate change, including, <i>inter alia</i> , its causes, potential impacts and response strategies.
United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)	UNFCCC is a Rio Convention, one of two opened for signature at the Rio Earth Summit in 1992. The Convention acknowledges the vulnerability of all countries to the effects of climate change and calls for special efforts to ease the consequences.
United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)	UNEP is the leading global environmental authority that sets the global environmental agenda, promotes the coherent implementation of the environmental dimension of sustainable development within the United Nations system, and serves as an authoritative advocate for the global environment.
World Meteorological Organization (WMO)	WMO is the UN system's authoritative voice on the state and behavior of the Earth's atmosphere, its interaction with the land and oceans, the weather and climate and the resulting distribution of water resources.

Simultaneously, European climate change agencies and organizations (Table 2.2.) play a vital role in carrying out research, implementing policy decisions, and raising awareness of environment-related issues, including climate change, across the European continent.

Table 2.2. European climate change agencies utilized as information sources.

Agency name	Short description
European Environment Agency (EEA)	EEA provides sound, independent information on the environment for those involved in developing, adopting, implementing and evaluating environmental policy, and also for the general public.
European Environmental Bureau (EEB)	EEB is Europe's largest network of environmental citizens' organizations.
EU Climate Action	The Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA) leads the European Commission's efforts to fight climate change at EU and international level.
Climate Action Network Europe (CAN Europe)	CAN Europe is Europe's leading NGO coalition fighting climate change.
EU Climate, Infrastructure And Environment Executive Agency (CINEA)	CINEA supports the EU in transitioning to a sustainable, green, climate-resilient, and resource-efficient economy.

European Climate Foundation (ECF):	The ECF is a non-profit organization aiming to promote policies that mitigate the impacts of climate change. It makes strategic investments in solutions to help Europe transition to a low-carbon economy.
Copernicus	Copernicus is the European Union's Earth observation Programme coordinated and managed by the European Commission in partnership with the European Space Agency (ESA), the EU Member States and EU agencies.
European Centre for of the medium-Range Weather in Forecasts (ECMWF)	ECMWF is an independent intergovernmental organization supported by most European nations. It operates one of the largest supercomputer complexes in Europe and the world's largest archive of numerical weather prediction data.

Apart from that, EU developed a program for Latin America, called EUROCLIMA+: This program promotes environmentally sustainable development in Latin America, focusing on climate change. It is financed by the European Union and works on climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies.

2.1.2 LOCAL STECCI CLIMATE DATA

Communication with National Meteorological Stations has been crucial to understand how climate change is affecting each nominated STECCI site and what are the most relevant impacts related to extreme events (Table 2.3.).

Table 2.3. STECCI partners and associated stecci monitoring sites.

	Partner	STEECI SITE	METEOROLOGICAL STATION/SOURCE
1.	UNSA/BIH	Dugo polje, Radimlja, Sarajevo, Ravanjska vrata, Križeviči, Kopošići	Sarajevo, Zenica, Mostar, Bugojno, Ivan Sedlo
2.	HM/MT	Mdina Rabat	Dingli Station, Luqa Station <i>Source: Malta Airport Met Office</i>
3.	UDG/MNE	Žugića bare	Žabljak station <i>Source: Institute of Hydrometeorology and Seismology Montenegro HMS CG</i>
4.	UAA/AT	Hundskirche	Weissensee-Gatschach <i>Source: GeoSphere Austria</i>
5.	SPK/DE	Unsleben Jewish Cemetery, Kleinbardorf Jewish Cemetery	Stations 02680 for Kleinbardorf, Station 03836 for Unsleben, plus 01374 Fladungen-Heufurt, 01621 Geroda-Platz, 02268 Hofheim, 02597 Kissingen, Bad, 04377 Sandberg <i>Source: wetterzentrale.de</i>

7.	UMAS/HR	Velika Cista, Split	Station Sinj, Station Šestanovac DHMZ Croatian Meteorological and Hydrological Service
8.	UNSPMF/S RB	Perućac, Mramorje	Loznica, Bajina Bašta <i>Source: RHMZ Serbia Republic Hydrometeorological Service of Serbia</i>
9.	IMT/FR	Caen	Station Caen <i>Source: Meteo France</i>

ICOMOS recognizes climate change as “one of the most significant and fastest growing threats to people and their cultural heritage worldwide,” calling for urgent integration of heritage preservation into climate adaptation and mitigation strategies (ICOMOS, 2019). Similarly, UNESCO highlights that climate change poses a serious threat to World Heritage sites and stresses the importance of enhancing resilience and embedding cultural heritage considerations within broader climate action frameworks (UNESCO, 2021).

2.1.3 SCIENTIFIC SOURCES ON CLIMATE CHANGE AND CULTURAL HERITAGE - SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

What is a systematic literature review? (Petticrew & Roberts 2006) systematic literature review goes beyond a conventional literature review: a systematic literature review’s main aim is not simply to be ‘comprehensive’ but to address a specific question, reduce bias in the selection and inclusion of studies, to appraise the quality of the included publications, and to objectively summaries them. First, the specific question is what is the “extreme” value? According to the literature, an occurrence is considered extreme if the value of a variable exceeds (or sits below) a threshold (Seneviratne *et al.* 2021). Naturally, climate is a major stressor and a big factor in how limestone-based monuments, like the stećci mediaeval tombstones that are abundant in Southeast Europe, deteriorates due to the slow changes but specially due to extreme values. It changes how salt weathering, biological growth, and the water systems that help karst dissolve and mechanical erosion happen (Grossi et al., 2007; Viles, 2002; Turkington & Paradise, 2005;). Temperature extremes, precipitation intensity and seasonality, relative humidity, freeze-thaw cycles, and solar radiation are all examples of climatic factors that directly affect the weathering of materials (dissolution, crystallisation, thermal expansion), the colonisation of biological organisms (lichens, algae), and the physical erosion of materials (Camuffo, 2019; Brimblecombe & Grossi, 2007).

The Köppen-Geiger climate classification system is an important tool for putting heritage sites in wider bioclimatic regions. Recent improvements using high-resolution datasets (Beck et al., 2018), following by Beck et al. 2023, with Version 2 of the 1-km Köppen - Geiger maps, upgraded to CMIP6, offering both historical (four periods from 1901 to 2020) and future projections (2041–2070 and 2071–2099) under multiple SSPs. It quantifies climate zone shifts across scenarios (5-13% of global land) and provides confidence metrics and unmatched spatial detail that is essential for mapping out the different ecosystems that STECCI sites can be found in across the Dinaric Alps and Central-Eastern Europe.

These sites have a range of climates, from sub-Mediterranean lowlands (with hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters) to humid continental interiors (with big changes in temperature between seasons) and alpine/montane areas, which have a lot of rain and freeze-thaw cycles (Mihailovic et al. 2013, 2015, 2016, 2018). Peel et al. (2007) stress how important it is to have updated global maps to find baseline climate regimes. Beck et al. (2018) help find small changes in climate boundaries that are important for long-term heritage risk assessment. At the same time, high-resolution reanalysis products like ERA5-Land (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021) give the time depth (about 1950 to now) and spatial accuracy (about 9 km resolution) to look at recent climate trends (1981 to now) and anomalies that are important to historic sites that are spread out. Another paper assessing precipitation in Greece (2010–2020) found ERA5-Land had lower biases and RMSE than ERA5 across diverse climatic regions (Alexandridis et al. 2023). Faezehsadat et al. 2023 study compared ERA5, ERA5-Land, and MERRA-2 in snow modeling highlighted added value of ERA5-Land in snow estimates. In the Qilian Mountains (China), ERA5-Land captured daily max/min temperature and extreme indices (TXx, TX90p, FD0) accurately, though elevation mismatch caused biases (Peng et al 2023) and using over East China, it represented near-surface air temperature (Lijuan et al 2025).

The IPCC (2021) risk framework displays that these records are necessary for figuring out how much exposure a site has to climate hazards. Increasingly, researchers are using paleoclimatology, regional climate modelling (Drešković & Đug 2012), and legacy material studies/atlas of climate changes to predict what will happen in the future (Sabbioni et al., 2010). Finding "climate threat hotspots" is a key idea. These are places where rapid changes in different climate factors (higher temperatures, changed rainfall patterns, and more extreme events) have a big effect on vulnerable heritage assets (Fatorić & Seekamp, 2017). A study by

Beniston and Stephenson (2004) provided detailed accounts of the probable extreme weather events due to climate change. Moreover, extreme weather events happening at the same time, like a heat wave and a drought or heavy rain on soil that is already dry, are new and not well understood dangers (IPCC, 2021, Gariano, S. L., & Guzzetti 2016). More intense rainstorms cause physical erosion and surface runoff, while longer droughts may make salt crystallisation pressures and soil shrinkage/swelling worse, which might affect the stability of structures (Grossi et al., 2007, Turkington & Paradise, 2005; IPCC, 2021). One of the most comprehensive literature reviews on climate change impacts on cultural heritage was provided by Sesana et al. (2021).

Microclimates and site-specificity

Limestone is naturally weak, and the STECCI locations are in areas where the climate is changing and is sensitive to global warming. Regional classifications and models are significant, but the microclimate around the heritage piece is often the main cause of its deterioration. The local terrain, direction, vegetation cover, and distance from water bodies all create important microclimatic variables that affect how much moisture is held, how much sunlight is received, and how much temperature changes (Camuffo, 2019). To accurately assess vulnerability and come up with targeted conservation plans for the scattered STECCI monuments, it's important to understand these site-specific microclimates.

Climate change is causing noticeable shifts in weather patterns around the world, and the Balkan Peninsula is no exception. Some of the impacts of climate change on the region, as indicated in climatic models and related to the Köppen Climate Classification system, include:

1. The region is expected to experience a significant increase in average annual temperatures. This could shift some Csb (warm-summer Mediterranean climate) and Cfb (temperate oceanic climate) zones more towards a Csa (hot-summer Mediterranean climate) classification. This rise in temperature can have cascading effects on ecosystems, agriculture, and water availability.
2. Regions with a Mediterranean Climate (Csa/Csb) are expected to experience more frequent and more severe periods of drought and heatwaves during summer months. These conditions can exacerbate wildfires, which have already seen an increase in the region.

3. Many models indicate wetter, warmer winters and drier, hotter summers, particularly in regions with a Mediterranean climate. In inland regions, designated as Dfa (Hot-summer humid continental climate) or Dfb (Warm-summer humid continental climate), changes may be more variable, with increases in heavy rainfall events leading to flooding.
4. The implications of climate change for coastal areas in the Balkans are severe. Rising sea levels may lead to the flooding of low-lying areas especially along the eastern Adriatic Sea.
5. Climate change, by altering temperature and precipitation patterns, can critically impact areas of unique biodiversity in the Balkans, which include many endemic species (Drešković & Mirić 2012, Drešković & Mirić 2017)

2.2 LIMITATIONS OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW - GAPS

It is well known that climate-heritage research has been done in the Western Europe, but there are significant lack of studies focused on the Dinaric Alps and the Balkan Peninsula, especially when it comes to limestone monoliths in different types of terrain (Orr et al. 2021). Orr et al systematically reviewed 165 publications released from 2016 to 2020 to assess what advancements had been made in the field of climate change impact on cultural heritage. One of the key findings of the study was the continued growth and increasing disciplinary diversity of the research field. However, the authors also highlighted a predominance of research focused on certain countries and noted a relative lack of international collaboration in this domain. While there is a substantial body of literature, it remains geographically fragmented, leading to noticeable regional gaps, most notably in the Balkans. For example, in the comprehensive review by Orr et al. (2021), only two out of 165 relevant studies referred to the broader Balkan region, and notably, none addressed areas where *stećci* are predominant. In this context, the present analysis constitutes the first study of its kind to examine the vulnerability of these specific heritage landscapes to climate-related stressors, filling a critical gap in both regional and thematic coverage.

2.3 BIG DATA ANALYSIS

The initial step taken by UNSPMF and UNSA involved identifying relevant and accessible datasets suitable for use in WP2, Task 2.1 (Drešković et al., 2024). These datasets serve as the foundation for subsequent analyses and modeling efforts in Deliverable 2.4. These included daily gridded observational dataset for precipitation, temperature and wind speed in

Europe called E-OBS. Another available data was ERA5 land reanalysis data from the Copernicus data store.

The next step was downloading E-OBS data on UNSPMF server, creating a database (Figure 4) and testing them. The E-OBS data is daily based. The daily data were used for calculating the total annual precipitation, annual temperature at 2m and Keppen climate classification in period 1991-2020 (Figure 2.2.).


```

(meteo) axiom.pmf.uns.ac.rs — Konsole
File Edit View Bookmarks Settings Help
-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5883230344 nov 18 00:58 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_1996.nc
-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155964 nov 18 02:29 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_1997.nc
-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155960 nov 18 03:58 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_1998.nc
-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155964 nov 18 05:17 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_1999.nc
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-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155960 nov 17 17:13 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_2001.nc
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-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155960 nov 17 23:58 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_2005.nc
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-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155960 nov 18 02:58 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_2007.nc
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-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155960 nov 17 20:35 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_2013.nc
-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155960 nov 17 21:56 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_2014.nc
-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155964 nov 18 00:29 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_2015.nc
-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5883230344 nov 18 02:03 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_2016.nc
-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155960 nov 18 03:28 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_2017.nc
-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155960 nov 18 04:58 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_2018.nc
-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5867155960 nov 18 06:27 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_2019.nc
-rw-rw-r-- 1 meteo meteo 5883230344 nov 17 14:17 ./era_land_temp/t2m_ceo_2020.nc
[meteo@axiom stecci]$ ls
E_OBS era_dew_temp era_land_gp era_land_prec era_land_rad era_land_temp era_land_u era_land_v
[meteo@axiom stecci]$ cd E_OBS
[meteo@axiom E_OBS]$ ll
total 27685287
drwxrwxr-x 2 meteo meteo 10 cen 21 13:37 ./
drwxrwxr-x 10 meteo meteo 10 nov 4 09:10 ../
-rwxrwxr-x 1 meteo meteo 560714 cen 21 13:37 elev_ens_0.1deg_reg_v27.0e.nc*
-rwxrwxr-x 1 meteo meteo 1818512440 cen 21 13:06 fg_ens_mean_0.1deg_reg_v27.0e.nc*
-rwxrwxr-x 1 meteo meteo 7515261299 cen 21 13:09 hu_ens_mean_0.1deg_reg_v27.0e.nc*
-rwxrwxr-x 1 meteo meteo 1618958915 cen 21 13:09 qq_ens_mean_0.1deg_reg_v27.0e.nc*
-rwxrwxr-x 1 meteo meteo 1643911815 cen 21 13:10 rr_ens_mean_0.1deg_reg_v27.0e.nc*
-rwxrwxr-x 1 meteo meteo 4343333576 cen 21 13:12 tg_ens_mean_0.1deg_reg_v27.0e.nc*
-rwxrwxr-x 1 meteo meteo 5752420318 cen 21 13:14 tn_ens_mean_0.1deg_reg_v27.0e.nc*
-rwxrwxr-x 1 meteo meteo 5664046079 cen 21 13:16 tx_ens_mean_0.1deg_reg_v27.0e.nc*
[meteo@axiom E_OBS]$

```

Figure 2.2. E-OBS data set on UNSPMF server (Author: Zorica Podračanin)

2.3.1 ERA5 LAND REANALYSIS

The next data set identified as usable is ERA5 land reanalysis. Downloading ERA5 land reanalysis data from the Copernicus data store typically involves accessing weather and climate information collected and processed using the ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts) model. This model provides comprehensive atmospheric

reanalysis data that includes various parameters such as temperature, wind, precipitation, and more, on a global scale.

ERA5 land was downloaded on an hourly basis, essentially acquiring detailed information for each hour within a specified time range. This granular data is quite comprehensive but can be extensive and complex to handle for certain analyses or applications. To simplify the dataset and make it more manageable for specific purposes, we aggregated the hourly data into daily data. This aggregation process involves combining the information for each parameter (temperature, precipitation, etc.) across the 24 hours of a day to create daily averages, totals, or other statistical summaries (Figure 2.3.).

```

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File Edit View Bookmarks Settings Help
zorica@kubuntu:~$ !ssh
ssh meteo@axiom.pmf.uns.ac.rs
meteo@axiom.pmf.uns.ac.rs's password:
Permission denied, please try again.
meteo@axiom.pmf.uns.ac.rs's password:
Last failed login: Tue Dec 5 13:27:33 CET 2023 from 10.6.0.89 on ssh:notty
There was 1 failed login attempt since the last successful login.
Last login: Thu Nov 30 13:21:38 2023 from 10.6.0.89

----- /usr/share/Modules/modulefiles -----
compss          devtoolset/9      openmpi/3.1.6-cuda
cuda/10.1        java              openmpi/4.0.5
cuda/10.2        module-info       openmpi/4.1.4
cuda/11.3        modules           openmpi/4.1.4-cuda
cuda/11.5        openblas          petsc-slepc
devtoolset/10   openmpi/1.10.1    python/miniconda3
devtoolset/11   openmpi/1.8.8     python/miniconda3.10
devtoolset/7    openmpi/3.1.3     stacks/2.62
devtoolset/8    openmpi/3.1.3-cuda

[meteo@axiom ~]$ cd stecci/
[meteo@axiom stecci]$ ls
E_OBS      era_land_gp      era_land_rad     era_land_u
era_dev_temp  era_land_prec   era_land_temp    era_land_v
[meteo@axiom stecci]$ du -h
509G      ./era_land_rad
1011G     ./era_dev_temp
27G       ./E_OBS
1.4T     ./era_land_temp
433G     ./era_land_prec
199G     ./era_land_u
827K     ./era_land_gp
234G     ./era_land_v
3.8T     .
[meteo@axiom stecci]$

```

Figure 2.3. ERA5 land data set on UNSPMF server (Author: Zorica Podračanin)

By aggregating ERA5 reanalysis data from an hourly to a daily basis for the entire European region, a more manageable dataset was created while still retaining valuable insights into the climate and weather conditions across the continent over a given timeframe. The available data were used to make usable and reproducible Google earth file.

Important note: During this phase big climate data were collected (7TB downloaded on STECCI UNSPMF server) and tested. They will be used in line with GA for D2.4 within the next steps involved:

1. testing ERA5 data for Keppen climate classification maps.
2. Calculation of extreme indices and their comparison with provided station data.
3. Producing maps and codes that can be reusable.

2. 4. ANALYSIS OF THE MOST RECENT CLIMATE ELEMENTS FOR THE AREAS OF STECCI SELECTED SITES

During the stage of analyzing the referred literature and determining a possible extreme influence of CC on limestone monuments using current and long-term ERA5-Land, ECAD gridded datasets, analysis of stecci meteorological station data closest to the selected sites was also completed. That provided a foundation for compiling and optimizing the climatic GIS dataset for the areas designated for monitoring and conservation (Table 2.4.).

Table 2.4. STECCI partners and associated STECCI monitoring sites.

	Partner	STECI SITE	METEOROLOGICAL STATION/SOURCE
1.	UNSA/BiH	Dugo polje, Radimlja, Sarajevo, Ravanjska vrata, Križevići, Kopošići	Sarajevo, Zenica, Bugojno, Ivan Sedlo, Mostar
2.	HM/MT	Mdina Rabat	Dingli Station, Luqa Station <i>Source: Malta Airport Met Office</i>
3.	UDG/MNE	Žugića bare	Žabljak station <i>Source: Institute of Hydrometeorology and Seismology Montenegro HMS CG</i>
4.	UAA/AT	Hundskirche	Weissensee-Gatschach <i>Source: GeoSphere Austria</i>
5.	SPK/DE	Unsleben, Kleinbardorf	Stations 02680 for Kleinbardorf, Station 03836 for Unsleben, plus 01374 Fladungen-Heufurt, 01621 Geroda-Platz, 02268 Hofheim, 02597 Kissingen, Bad, 04377 Sandberg <i>Source: wetterzentrale.de</i>
7.	UMAS/HR	Velika Cista, Split	Station Sinj, Station Šestanovac DHMZ Croatian Meteorological and Hydrological Service
8.	UNSPMF/SRB	Perućac, Mramorje	Loznica, Bajina Bašta <i>Source: RHMZ Serbia Republic Hydrometeorological Service of Serbia</i>
9.	IMT/FR	Caen	Station Caen <i>Source: Meteo France</i>

3. STECCI DEMO-CASE SITES – OVERVIEW AND CHARACTERISTICS

3.1. INTRODUCTION

The project's STECCI demo-case sites represent sacred objects – cemeteries where tombstones were erected during specific historical periods, and which today form part of the cultural-historical heritage of a particular region/country. The exception is the Hundskirche site (Austria), which features an upright triangular limestone-dolomite rock inscribed with ornaments from the 17th and 18th centuries.

The tombstones were constructed from various types of carbonate rocks that, under microclimatic conditions and the influence of biological growth, began to degrade superficially and structurally (eroding and/or cracking) due to several processes: physical (thermal and frost weathering), chemical dissolution, and biological decay. To assess the impact of atmospheric conditions, biological environments, and air pollutants on the monuments at the STECCI demo-case sites, research was conducted (WP2). In the project's first phase, the condition assessment research was carried out to evaluate their current state (WP3).

The influence of meteorological-climatic elements on the intensity of rock degradation is highly complex and depends on several factors: geospatial position, mineralogical-petrographic characteristics of the rock mass, general and local geomorphological specificities of the necropolises' immediate and broader surroundings, and biogeographic features of the necropolises' direct and wider environments.

The geospatial position's influence for all researched STECCI demo-case sites is defined through basic location parameters of the WGS84 geographic coordinate system. In the following text, positional parameters are presented via indicators of climatic-geographic positioning, i.e., the necropolises' position relative to the climatic zone they belong to. This highlights the foundational influence of locational factors on potential degradation of stone heritage at the necropolises.

Geomorphological (primarily morphological) terrain specificities represent one of the fundamental climatic factors that modify the intensity of meteorological elements' impact on stone heritage. The general orographic structure of the terrain primarily alters the basic physical properties of air masses relative to their source zones. A distinct orographic influence can occur through the formation of temperature inversions, which, in addition to thermal effects,

also act by increasing concentrations of gaseous, liquid, and solid air pollutants in the local atmosphere. This causes moisture in the air (water droplets) to become acidic and aggressively attack stone heritage. This factor has recently become highly significant in urbanized environments.

Biogeographic terrain characteristics represent a primary climatic factor, particularly regarding microclimatic features in the immediate vicinity of necropolises. The key biogeographic factor according to Koppen classification is vegetation cover, which plays a dual role in climatological research: it is both a fundamental climatic factor and a climatic indicator (based on which the type and spatial boundaries of the climate can be estimated). Due to its importance for the general eco-climatic features of the terrain at the project's necropolis sites, basic parameters of vegetation cover at the level of biogeographic regions and provinces are also presented in the following text.

3.2. GEOSPATIAL POSITION OF STECCI DEMO-CASE SITES

3.2.1. NATIONAL MUSEUM OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA, SARAJEVO

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 43^{\circ}51'18.98''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 18^{\circ}24'11.37''\text{E}$; $H = 533 \text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 817 \text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.1. Geoposition and immediate environment of National Museum of B&H

3.2.2. KOPOŠIĆI, ILIJAŠ, B&H

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 44^{\circ}00'15.53''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 18^{\circ}20'42.46''\text{E}$; $H = 966 \text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 215 \text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.2. Geoposition and immediate environment of Kopošići, Ilijaš.

3.2.3. KRIŽEVIĆI, OLOVO, B&H

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 44^{\circ}08'50.38''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 18^{\circ}31'12.24''\text{E}$; $H = 610 \text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 5,080 \text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.3. Geoposition and immediate environment of Križevići, Olovo.

3.2.4. GEOPOSITION AND IMMEDIATE ENVIRONMENT OF DUGO POLJE, B&H

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 43^{\circ}39'47.85''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 17^{\circ}32'35.46''\text{E}$; $H = 1,245 \text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 3,050 \text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.4. Geoposition and immediate environment of Dugo polje, Blidinje.

3.2.5. RAVANJSKA VRATA, KUPRES, B&H

Geographical position: $\varphi = 43^{\circ}51'48.68''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 17^{\circ}18'44.44''\text{E}$; $H = 1,157 \text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 4,670 \text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.5. Geoposition and immediate environment of Ravanjska vrata, Kupres.

3.2.6. RADIMLJA, STOLAC, B&H

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 43^{\circ}05'31.52''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 17^{\circ}55'26.22''\text{E}$; $H = 60\text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 6,000\text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.6. Geoposition and immediate environment of Radimlja, Stolac.

3.2.7. UNSLEBEN, GERMANY

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 50^{\circ}22'33.21''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 10^{\circ}16'30.77''\text{E}$; $H = 300\text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 1,370\text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.7. Geoposition and immediate environment of Unsleben.

3.2.8. KLEINBARDORF, GERMANY

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 50^{\circ}16'21.00''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 10^{\circ}24'39.13''\text{E}$; $H = 408\text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 3,200\text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.8. Geoposition and immediate environment of Kleinbardorf.

3.2.9. HUNDSKIRCHE, AUSTRIA

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 46^{\circ}40'23.12''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 13^{\circ}31'16.09''\text{E}$; $H = 1,035\text{ m}$.

Fig. 3.9. Geoposition and immediate environment of Hundskirche.

3.2.10. MDINA RABAT, MALTA

Geographical position:

$\phi = 35^{\circ}53'7.45''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 14^{\circ}23'59.89''\text{E}$; $H = 190\text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 2,110\text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.10. Geoposition and immediate environment of Mdina Rabat.

3.2.11. SAINT JOHN CEMETERY, CAEN, FRANCE

Geographical position:

$\phi = 49^{\circ}10'25.36''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 00^{\circ}21'04.11''\text{W}$; $H = 190\text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 7,300\text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.11. Saint John Cemetery, Caen.

3.2.12. VELIKA CISTA (VELIKA I MALA CRLJIVICA), CISTA PROVO, CROATIA

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 43^{\circ}30'56.99''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 16^{\circ}55'36.95''\text{E}$; $H = 478\text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 2,900\text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.12. Velika i Mala Crljivica, Cista Provo.

3.2.13. ŽUGIĆA BARE, ŽABLJAK, MONTENEGRO

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 43^{\circ}05'40.63''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 19^{\circ}08'56.88''\text{E}$; $H = 478\text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 820\text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 3.13. Žugića bare, Žabljak

3.2.14. MRAMORJE, BAJINA BAŠTA, SERBIA

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 43^{\circ}57'27.87''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 19^{\circ}25'49.28''\text{E}$; $H = 235 \text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 3.470 \text{ m}^2$.

Slika 3.14. Mramorje, Bajina Bašta.

3.2.15. SPLIT, MUSEUM OF CROATIAN ARCHAEOLOGICAL MONUMENTS

Geographical position:

$\varphi = 43^{\circ}57'27.87''\text{N}$; $\lambda = 19^{\circ}25'49.28''\text{E}$; $H = 235 \text{ m}$; $P_{\text{Necr}} = 160 \text{ m}^2$.

Slika 3.15. Split, Museum of Croatian Archaeological Monuments.

4. BIOGEOGRAPHICAL REGIONS AND GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VEGETATION COVER IN THE WIDE AREA OF THE PROJECT'S STECCI DEMO-CASE SITES

According to Article 1(c)(iii) of the Council Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (commonly known as the Habitats Directive, adopted on 21 May 1992), five biogeographical regions are officially delineated for conservation purposes: Alpine, Atlantic, Continental, Macaronesian and Mediterranean. These biogeographical regions serve as the fundamental spatial units for assessing and reporting habitat types and species conservation status under both the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) and the EMERALD Network, established under the Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats (the Bern Convention).

Complementing the biogeographical classification, the vegetation zones referenced in this study are based on the *Map of the Natural Vegetation of Europe* (scale 1:2,500,000), which depicts the form, diversity, and spatial distribution of primary vegetation units across Europe. This map serves as a key reference for understanding the continent's natural biological diversity in a spatially explicit manner (Bohn et al., 2000/2003).

4.1. ATLANTIC BIOGEOGRAPHICAL REGION

The Atlantic biogeographical region spans parts of western Europe, including the United Kingdom, Ireland, western France, the Netherlands, Belgium, northern Spain, and parts of Portugal and Germany (Map 4.1.). Due to the ocean's moderating effect, the climate is characterized by mild winters and cool summers. Average temperatures in the winter seasons are generally above freezing (0–7°C), and summer is distinguished by moderate temperatures, typically between 15–22°C. The North Atlantic Drift (Gulf Stream) strongly influences the climate, which keeps temperatures milder than other regions at the same latitude. Precipitations are evenly distributed throughout the year, and they vary from 800–2,000 mm annually, depending on location. Frequent cloud cover and high humidity are typical along coastal areas. This region is exposed to strong winds and Atlantic storms, and coastal areas frequently experience high winds and rough seas, particularly in autumn and winter.

This climate supports lush vegetation, extensive forests, and wetlands, making the region ecologically rich. Most of the European Atlantic plant communities are similar to those common in the Eurosiberian region. Dominated types of forests are temperate broadleaf and mixed

forests of oak and beech (*Querc-Fagetea*), mesic and xeric scrubs of buckthorns and blackthorn (*Rhamno-Prunetea*), the mown meadows and mesic pastures of purple moor-grass and false oatgrass (*Molinio-Arrhenatheretea*), the dry grasslands of fescue and meadow brome (*Festuco-Brometea*) etc. Such vegetation is submitted to land uses of the same type, producing a landscape quite similar to that prevailing in temperate Europe. Among the vegetation types having a relevant meaning for characterizing this European Atlantic province, there are two worth mentioning: the heaths of *Calluno-Ulicetea* and the coastal vegetation.

Map 4.1. Biogeographic regions of Europe and spatial position of STECCI demo-case sites (authors: S. Radulović, S. Đug).

The Atlantic decalcified fixed dunes (*Calluno-Ulicetea*) are confined to nutrient-poor, acidic soils, and the core of their species composition includes stress-tolerant dwarf shrubs and hemicryptophytes. These plants are poor competitors, which tend to disappear after nutrient enrichment under pressure of taller grasses. These heaths originated in the western and northwestern areas of the Iberian Peninsula, where it is found its maximal diversity across Europe, with the highest concentration of species in restricted areas. This suggests that this vegetation originated under relatively warm temperatures and high rainfall conditions, very probably during Tertiary. The long shoreline of Atlantic Europe can be divided into three main types: cliffs and shingle beaches, sand dunes, and estuarine salt marshes. The former occupy long stretches of coast, particularly in some regions such as the Galician and the Cantabrian Shores, Brittany, south England or Norway, while the low coast is dominant in other parts such as Aquitanie, Germany or The Netherlands. All these communities are adapted to the particular tidal and surge regime of the European Atlantic coast, as well as to its specific climatic conditions. Due to isolation in many populations, there is an important group of stenochorous plants specific to the European Atlantic coasts which characterize several phytosociological units. It is the case of the sea cliffs, with a pair of endemic alliances in the *Crithmo-Staticetea* such as *Silenion maritimae* and *Cochleario officinalis-Armerion maritime*.

Sampling sites for STECCI project is situated in the Franco-Atlantic sector. It extends over central and western France occupying a large extent due to the strong influence of the Atlantic Ocean across the French western plain. It comprises the coastal line of Picardie, Normandy, Brittany, Loire Atlantique and Charente and expands to inland to the western foothills of the Central Massif and the northern piedmont of the Pyrenees, limiting in the south with the Aquitanian areas where the Mediterranean influence is noteworthy. The abundance of Atlantic elements, particularly in heathlands, is notably higher than in the previous sector.

Below is an overview at the level of the associated sites.

4.1.1. THE SITE CAEN-CARPIQUET (FRANCE)

This site is located in the zone Norman-Belgian (sessile oak-) beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica*, *Quercus petraea*) with *Ilex aquifolium*, *Luzula sylvatica*, partly *Luzula forsteri*. The stands have a relatively dense leaf canopy and a shrub layer in which *Ilex aquifolium* dominates and which can form dense, high shrubs. Undergrowth with sweet grasses and acidophilic mosses on silicate substrate (Map 4.1.). They are developed in the plains and gentle hills, at lowlands, to

ca. 350 m of altitude. Soils are sandy-loamy, often skeletal, fresh to moist, acidic, oligotrophic, oligo-mesotrophic (to mesotrophic). Beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) play a dominant role in the tree layer, accompanied by *Quercus petraea*, and *Quercus robur* (rarely with its hybridogene variety *Quercus x rosacea*), comparatively rarely *Betula pendula*, *Populus tremula*. Dominant and most frequent species in shrub layer are *Ilex aquifolium*, *Sorbus aucuparia*, *Frangula alnus*, *Betula pendula*, *Populus tremula*, *Malus sylvestris* and *Mespilus germanica*; on moist soils *Betula pubescens*. The most important species in the herb layer are *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Deschampsia flexuosa*, *Luzula sylvatica*, *Luzula pilosa*, *Anthoxanthum odoratum*, *Holcus mollis*, *Carex pilulifera*, *Melampyrum pratense*, *Teucrium scorodonia*, *Hypericum pulchrum*, *Solidago virgaurea*, *Polypodium vulgare*. Moss layer (incl. lichens) is represented by *Rhytidiadelphus loreus*, *Rhytidiadelphus triquetrus*, *Dicranum scoparium*, *Hypnum cupressiforme*, *Polytrichum formosum*, *Thuidium tamariscinum*, *Leucobryum glaucum*. Substitute communities in this area make grasslands (meadows, pastures, herb-rich communities)

Sporadically, here are also developed stands of the West and Central European alder-ash forests (*Fraxinus excelsior*, *Alnus glutinosa*) or ash-elm forests (*Ulmus minor*, *Fraxinus excelsior*), partly in combination with moist pedunculate oak-hornbeam forests (*Carpinus betulus*, *Quercus robur*) and alder (*Alnus glutinosa*). The occurrence of Atlantic-sub-Atlantic species (*Salix atrocinerea*, *Ilex aquifolium*, *Carex strigosa*, *C. pendula*, *Chrysosplenium oppositifolium*) is usual. This vegetation type is developed in the lowland to submontane belt up to 500 m, on fluvial sediments (Holocene). Soils are silty-sandy to clayey; mostly fine-grained, silt or clay-rich loamy sands and sandy loams; with coarse-grained soils only if they are loamy/clayey underlayered, wet to periodically moist, fresh, weakly acidic to neutral, mesotrophic to eutrophic, regarding fertility. Its habitat is still being deforested and used as grassland to the extent that small residual strips are all that remain along the river courses.

Dominant species in the tree layer are *Alnus glutinosa*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, partly *Quercus robur*, *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Ulmus glabra*, and occasionally *Acer platanoides*. In the shrub layer important species are *Prunus padus*, *Corylus avellana*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Rubus idaeus*, *Salix fragilis*, *Salix caprea*, *Prunus spinosa*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Ribes rubrum*, *Viburnum opulus*, *Euonymus europaea*; *Ribes spicatum*, and *Frangula alnus*. Typical species in the herb layer are *Aegopodium podagraria*, *Athyrium filix-femina*, *Caltha palustris*, *Carex remota*, *Carex brizoides*, *Deschampsia cespitosa*, *Chaerophyllum hirsutum*, *Crepis paludosa*, *Cirsium*

oleraceum, Festuca gigantea, Filipendula ulmaria, Galium aparine, Impatiens noli-tangere, Iris pseudacorus, Lysimachia vulgaris, Oxalis acetosella, Rumex sanguineus, Senecio ovatus, Stachys sylvatica, Stellaria nemorum, Urtica dioica, Chrysosplenium alternifolium, Circaea lutetiana, Geum urbanum, Galium palustre, Geranium robertianum, Lamium maculatum. Moss layer (incl. lichens) includes species *Plagiomnium undulatum, Brachythecium rutabulum.*

4.2. MEDITERRANEAN BIOGEOGRAPHICAL REGION

The Mediterranean region borders the Atlantic region in the west, the Continental region in several places to the north while in the east the region is linked to both the Black Sea region and the Anatolian region (Map 2.1.). In the mountain reaches of the Pyrenees, the Alps, the Balkans, the Dinaric and Rhodopinal Alps as well as in the Caucasian Alps the Mediterranean region neighbors the Alpine sub-regions, creating a mosaic in species composition and habitat types.

The Mediterranean biogeographical region and the Mediterranean Sea constitute a frontier zone between Europe, Asia, and Africa in terms of climate and species. The region covers 11 % of Europe's territory and stretches over more than 4,000 km from Lisbon in the west (Portugal) to Adana in the east (Southern Turkey). The total coastal length is more than 46,000 km. The climate is warm with hot summers and mild winters. Arid and desert conditions are increasing, and water will become more and more scarce. Soils are low in humus, and the erosion risk is great in most areas. The very variable topography and the complex geology with many isolated areas, together with favorable climatic conditions over long periods have made the Mediterranean basin a centre of diversification for fauna and flora species of great importance. The number of indigenous species is still the highest in Europe, the wider Mediterranean area being one of the two hotspots for species in Europe. The region also has the highest number of endemic habitat types listed by the EU Habitats Directive. Special centers of endemism are found in the Turkish part of the region, in most of Greece, Cyprus, and Corsica as well as in southeastern Spain.

The tree, bush and dwarf shrub-dominated habitat types (forest, scrub and heathlands) occupy more than half of the region's landscape. Formerly widespread dry grasslands and traditional agro forestry are decreasing, and the areas turned to intensive agriculture or abandoned to scrub formation. The intensive agriculture, vegetable growing and the large citrus orchards require intensive irrigation. Oaks are important, and natural old forests are scarce. Many of the

dominant broadleaved tree species are sclerophyllous (evergreen with leathery leaves), such as: holm oak (*Quercus ilex* and Spanish subspecies *Quercus rotundifolia*), cork oak (*Quercus suber*) and Turkey oak (*Quercus cerris*). These have for the last two-three millennia progressively replaced deciduous trees, which are now mostly found at higher altitudes or in areas with higher humidity. Forests in Mediterranean mountain ranges also contain endemic or rare conifer species of *Abies*, *Pinus*, *Juniperus* and *Taxus*. Holm oak (in forests) encircles the whole Mediterranean Sea, as does kermes oak (*Quercus coccifera*, in maquis). Cork oak (in maquis) and the Mediterranean oak (*Quercus canariensis*) are more westerly in distribution. Mediterranean coasts are very varied, even within short distances, with rocky stretches and sandy and gravelly beaches or coves, including habitats such as rocks and sea cliffs, dunes, caves, lagoons and deltas (mentioned under bogs, mires, and fens above). Vast areas of dunes and wetlands have disappeared. However, some of Europe's most important wetlands for birds migrating between Europe and Africa are found both in the eastern and western parts.

4.2.1. MEDITERRANEAN SCLEROPHYLLOUS FORESTS AND SCRUB

This vegetation type includes communities of xero-morphic evergreen tree and shrub species, especially of the genera *Quercus* (subgenus *Sclerophyllodrys*), *Pinus*, *Juniperus*, *Olea* and *Pistacia* (Map 4.2.) The dominance of a single tree or shrub species is common. Sclerophyllous forests and scrub occur on a wide variety of substrates on all slopes and expositions, though sites influenced by groundwater tend to be avoided. Stand structure depends on the abiotic site factors and the species composition, but especially on the current and previous use of the stand.

Most evergreen broadleaved forest species can grow as trees or shrubs, depending on external influences; some are also genetically predisposed to one or the other form. Stands with a dense canopy are dark and tend to be species poor. The sparse undergrowth of such dense forests and thickets is composed of scattered small shrubs, grasses, lianas, geophytes, ferns and seedlings of the trees and shrubs. Open stands are much more common. These occur naturally on steep slopes, though as a rule, they arise from various forms of use, such as removal of timber and grazing. Stands degraded through unregulated logging possess scrub or bush forest structures (macchia, maquis). Stands that are patchy and opened by grazing or interdigitated with dwarf shrub and herbaceous vegetation are referred to as garrigue.

Map 4.2. Ecological regions of Europe and spatial position of STECCI demo-case sites (*authors: S.Radulović, S.Đug*)

Grazed woodlands consist of single-stemmed rather than coppiced multi-stemmed trees, have a more open canopy, uneven stand structure and an internal architecture rich in ecotonal effects. Mediterranean evergreen broadleaved forests have a long history of anthropogenic destruction and degradation. In areas favorable for agriculture, this began already during the Neolithic period; in agriculturally less favorable regions it occurred especially during times of human population growth through the extensive, unregulated removal of timber and grazing with goats and sheep. They were to be replaced by various cultural landscapes. Secondary small shrub communities arose in areas that were extensively grazed. If a regressive

syndynamic pattern persisted, geophyte - and annual-rich dry grasslands and heaths developed. With the receding pressure of human use in recent times, one can observe self-regenerating ever-green broadleaved vegetation in most countries along the northern rim of the Mediterranean. The dynamic potential of such stands, especially the temporal process of progressive succession and the corresponding climax forest community, are to a great extent site-dependent and are still not understood in detail.

The tree composition of Mediterranean evergreen broadleaved forests is mainly rather uniform. A single species typically dominates the canopy, often one of the evergreen oak species (subgenus *Sclerophyllahys*). The holm oak (*Quercus ilex*) is most competitive in sub-humid regions. It is represented on the Iberian Peninsula (except for Cantabria and Catalonia) by *Q. ilex* subsp. *rotundifolia* (= *Q. rotundifolia*, *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota*), in the remainder of the Mediterranean region by *Q. ilex* subsp. *ilex*. In drier regions with somewhat colder winters, *Q. ilex* is replaced by the kermes oak (*Quercus coccifera*). The latter species is more tolerant of browsing than the holm oak. *Quercus coccifera* forms forests especially in the eastern Mediterranean region (where it is traditionally segregated by some authors under the synonym *Q. calliprinos*), while in the west it scarcely grows taller than 2 m. In meso-Mediterranean regions and especially in the transition zone to sub-Mediterranean climates, deciduous species begin to play a greater role. In the west, this includes especially oak species such as *Quercus faginea* and *Q. pubescens*, in the east *Q. cerris*, *Q. frainetto*, *Fraxinus ornus* and *Carpinus orientalis*. Grazed oak forests and macchia with anthropogenically lower proportions of oak often possess a dense evergreen shrub layer, which can be composed of *Erica arborea*, *Arbutus unedo* or *A. andrachne*. *Laurus nobilis* and *Myrtus communis* can occur on humid sites. Much less widely distributed than the *Quercus ilex* or *Q. coccifera* communities are the forests composed of *Quercus* species of the subgenus *Cerris*. In thermo-Mediterranean region, evergreen oaks are restricted to special habitats or climatically moderate montane localities. Here, the often-dominant tree on sandy soils in coastal areas and on limestone is *Pinus halepensis* (*Pinus brutia* in the Aegean and in Mediterranean parts of Asia Minor). Owing to their tough bark and high regenerative capacity through seed production, *P. halepensis* and *P. brutia* tolerate fire more than other tree species and are thereby favoured by forest fires. Where fires are frequent, the pine species may begin to suppress the oaks as the main tree species, even in meso-Mediterranean areas.

In many areas, the most common shrub of the thermo-Mediterranean sclerophyllous scrub formation is, with or without a *Pinus* canopy, *Pistacia lentiscus*. This species is mainly a shrub under 2 m, rarely a tree up to 6 m. It often grows together with the wild form of the olive tree (*Olea europaea subsp. oleaster*) and carob (*Ceratonia salvia*). As far as is presently known, neither *Olea* nor *Ceratonia* belongs to the original European flora but rather were cultivated in their indigenous Middle Eastern ranges and spread from there into the Mediterranean, where they subsequently escaped from cultivation and have long since become well-established in the natural vegetation. Other important, stand-forming and widely distributed woody species in the thermal-Mediterranean region include *Junipers phoenicea* (including the subsp. *torhinata*), which mainly forms scrub in coastal areas, and *J. oxycedrus* subsp. *macrocarpa*, which in its arborescent form colonises coastal sands.

While anthropogenically thinned sclerophyllous forests can exhibit high numbers of species in a small area, stands that have gone for a longer time without or with only minimal disturbance are dense and conspicuously poor species.

The formation of Mediterranean evergreen broadleaved forests and scrub corresponds for the most part with the phytosociological class *Quercetea ilicis*. The order *Pistacio lentisci-Rhamnetalia alaterni* consists of shrub communities and *Pinus* and *Junipers*, which stand chiefly in the thermo-Mediterranean zone. The further classification into alliances and associations has begun in parts of the range (e.g., Spain); however, most proposals are based on relatively small databases, and none of them consider all European sub-ranges. The alliance *Oleo-Ceratonion* was long considered to correspond to the most highly developed thermo-Mediterranean vegetation.

Evergreen broadleaved forests and scrub grow in regions with a pronounced Mediterranean rainy winter climate, in other words with warm, dry summers and cool, moist winters. Hard frosts are absent, and in thermo-Mediterranean regions frost in general is rare. The precipitation peaks are mainly in November/December and in February/March. During the summer months — in the dry southern areas already starting in May and lasting until and including September — there is little or no precipitation. In the case of pronounced relief, the windward-leeward effects provide for local climatic differentiation. To this can be added fluctuations in the distribution and the sum of annual precipitation. The mean annual precipitation at sea level lies between 400 and 900 mm, more rarely over 1200 mm (e.g., Kerkira) or under 400 mm (south-eastern Spanish dry area, south-eastern Crete). The mean

temperature of the warmest month lies between 25 and 28 °C, and that of the coldest month is between 6 and 13 °C. Especially on the smaller islands and on exposed coasts wind is a decisive factor for the vegetation and its structure: it lessens the competitiveness of hygrially demanding woody evergreen species and locally hinders the formation of the tree habit, even without anthropogenic influence. This results in the favoring of low scrub and shrub forests.

4.2.2. SITE SPLIT-MARJAN (CROATIA)

This site is located in the vegetation zone of Dalmatian-Albanian meso-Mediterranean holm oak forests (*Quercus ilex*) with *Myrtus communis*, *Pistacia lentiscus*, *Juniperus phoenicea*, *Lonicera implexa*, *Hippocrepis emerus subsp. emeroides*, partly in combination with *Pinus halepensis* forests on carbonate rocks-

4.2.3. SITES VELIKA CISTA (CROATIA) AND RADIMLJA (BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA)

These sites are located in the vegetation zone of East Adriatic montane hop-hornbeam-downy oak forests (*Quercus virgiliana*, *Ostrya carpinifolia*) with *Quercus cerris*, *Acer hyrcanum* subsp. *intermedium*, *Spiraea decumbens*, *Pulmonaria visianii*. Soils are humus carbonate soils and brown soils above limestone; (rendzic leptosols; chromic cambisols), loamy, stony, moderately dry, weakly acidic to neutral, and meso-eutrophic fertility.

4.2.4. SITE MDINA RABAT (MALTA)

Site is located in the vegetation zone of Middle Mediterranean wild olive-locust tree forests (*Ceratonia siliqua*, *Olea europaea* subsp. *oleaster*, *Pistacia lentiscus*), partly with *Chamaerops humilis*. Soils are lime-rich (partly also decalcified) and Mediterranean terra rossa, Mediterranean brown soils. Soils are loam, sand, stony, rocky, dry, very dry, and weakly acidic to alkaline, with mesotrophic to eutrophic fertility.

4.3. CONTINENTAL BIOGEOGRAPHICAL REGION

The Continental region extends in a central east-west band over most of Europe. A relatively narrow fringe of land separates it from the Atlantic Ocean in the west; in the east, it reaches as far as the border of Asia, just south of the Ural Mountains. It reaches Denmark and Sweden in the north, Italy, and the Balkan Peninsula in the south. The region is not entirely contiguous: the Alps act as a barrier, isolating the part of the region on the Apennine Peninsula (Map 2.1.).

The Continental region surrounds the Pannonian region as well as the Carpathian Mountains, which belong to the Alpine region. In countries such as Slovenia, Croatia, Serbia, and Bosnia-Herzegovina the shifts from one region to another occur over short distances. The Czech Republic is fully within the region except for a small area in the southeast. Luxembourg is wholly within the region.

The Continental region includes the middle courses of a large number of Europe's most important rivers: the Danube, Desna, Dnepr, Dnestr, Elbe, Loire, Oder, Pripyat, Rhine, Vistula and Volga. These rivers have played a determining role in the formation of the landscape and its subsequent biodiversity. They have also been decisive for important parts of the basic settlement structure and infrastructure.

The Continental biogeographical region has some of the continent's most productive ecosystems. It is the transition zone on the N–S axis between the woodland-dominated coniferous Boreal region and the open Steppic region. Agriculture covers more than half the area, in addition to which there is a significant proportion of grasslands, mostly semi-natural. Forests are much less prominent than in the Boreal region but still cover around 27 % of the area. Former widespread heathlands on sandy soil in the northern part have been cultivated or afforested. Large bog and mire areas have been drained and cultivated. Only 4 % of the region is urban or constructed, but the area is spreading. The change in land use is leading to an increasing fragmentation of habitats and the creation of barriers, which isolate species populations.

Forests cover around 27 % of the region. The climatic conditions and the soils are in many places best suited for deciduous forests, with different species being predominant according to geographical location. As a whole, however, conifer forests dominate in several countries of the region, having to a considerable extent replaced local deciduous species in managed forests. The forests contain a large proportion of all the species present in the region. In Germany for instance 50 % of all indigenous vascular plants grow in forests or other wooded land. Deciduous forests on alkaline soils may house around 340 vascular plant species, second only to the dry grasslands with 382 species. The beech forests are rich in animals closely connected to forests: two-thirds of all Continental region beetles occur in forests, 20 % of them being dependent on dead or rotten wood. The beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) is especially characteristic of the southern and western parts of the region. The limits of the distribution of elm (*Ulmus glabra*), lime (*Tilia cordata*), and ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*) correspond in general to

the eastern border of the Continental region, the Ural Mountains, and in the southeast reach the borders of the Russian steppes via a belt of forest-steppe. Deciduous trees become more and more sporadic going north towards the transition zone to the boreal forest. Coniferous forests are more abundant towards the east and are also in many areas favored for forestry, especially on sandy soil or at higher elevations. Poland is noted for Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) and the eastern slopes of the Vosges in France and the Black Forest in Germany for Norway spruce (*Picea abies*), which is also generally present in the limited sub-alpine belts of the mountains. European silver fir (*Abies alba*) becomes more and more important towards the east (from Belarus to the Russian Federation and Ukraine).

Riparian vegetation is developed in the floodplains along rivers, with species like willow (*Salix alba*), poplar (*Populus nigra*), and alder (*Alnus glutinosa*). Wetlands and grasslands could be found in the floodplains, hosting diverse plant species. The continental region is critical for biodiversity, especially due to its forests, river ecosystems, and wetlands. Threats include deforestation, river regulation, urbanization, and pollution. Agricultural activities are prominent here.

4.3.1. SITES UNSLEBEN AND KLEINBARDORF (GERMANY)

These sites are located in the vegetation zone of Central European beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica*) with *Lathyrus vernus*, *Hepatica nobilis* in combination with *Cephalanthera*-beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica*) (Map 2.2.). They are developed on stony to clayey loam, fresh to dry, weakly acidic, neutral, alkaline soils, which are mesotrophic, to meso-eutrophic fertility. They form two main vegetation communities. One is mostly two-layered, with closed stands. The beech grows well to very well. The shrub layer is sparse with often grass-rich herb layer (hemicryptophytes, also geophytes). It covers fresh sites at higher altitudes both on slopes of all exposures and on flat surfaces. At lower altitudes, it is restricted to shaded slopes, slope hollows, lower slopes and flat surfaces. The second plant community make primarily beech with additions of sessile oak, sycamore, field maple, ash, hawthorn, and wild service tree. The trees grow moderately well. The shrub layer is species and individual-rich, but usually only low and loose. The herb layer is mostly loose, interspersed and species-rich, and consists mostly of thermophilous and drought-resistant herbaceous plants (hemicryptophytes, geophytes). The moss layer is sparse. The community occurs mainly on shallow, south-exposed limestone slopes.

The dominant and most frequent species in the tree layer in the first plant community type is *Fagus sylvatica*, with sporadically present *Quercus petraea*, and *Fraxinus excelsior*, while in the second plant community, the most abundant are: *Fagus sylvatica*, *Acer campestre*, *Quercus petraea*, *Sorbus aria*, *Sorbus torminalis*, and locally *Taxus baccata*. In the shrub layer of the first plant community type, the most abundant are *Daphne mezereum*, *Crataegus laevigata*, *Lonicera xylosteum*, and *Corylus avellana*; while in the second plant community type the most abundant are: *Cornus sanguinea*, *Rosa arvensis*, *Hippocrepis emerus*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Viburnum lantana*, *Rhamnus cathartica*. In the herb layer dominant role play: *Lathyrus vernus*, *Asarum europaeum*, *Hepatica nobilis*, *Lilium martagon*, *Hordelymus europaeus*, *Galium odoratum*, *Bromus benekenii*, *Mercurialis perennis*, *Sanicula europaea*, *Lamium galeobdolon*, *Convallaria majalis*, *Viola reichenbachiana*, *Melica uniflora*, *Carex sylvatica*, *Brachypodium sylvaticum*, *Galium sylvaticum*, *Dactylis polygama*; and thermophilous or drought resistant species: *Carex montana*, *Carex flacca*, *Brachypodium pinnatum*, *Cephalanthera rubra*, *Cephalanthera damasonium*, *Neottia nidus-avis*, locally *Carex alba*, and *Sesleria albicans*.

4.3.2. SITE MRAMORJE (SERBIA)

This site is located in the vegetation zone of moderately high, three-layered forests, sometimes with an upper and lower tree layer, with many thermophilous and some mesophilous species. This vegetation belongs to the Illyrian-west Moesian Balkan oak-bitter oak forests (*Quercus cerris*, *Quercus frainetto*, partly *Quercus pubescens*, *Quercus petraea* agg.) with *Genista* species and *Crocus veluchensis*. Soils are acidic brown and parabrown soils; (chromic luvisols; dystric, vertic cambisols; pellic vertisols), clayey, clayey-loamy, dry, weakly acidic, mesotrophic fertility.

The dominant association is *Quercetum frainetto-cerris* (Georgescu 1945) Rudski 1949 with different regional variants. The forests are medium- to tall-growing and two- to three-layered, with *Quercus cerris* and *Q. frainetto* predominating in the upper tree layer. Depending on the region, there is a varied admixture of *Quercus petraea*, *Q. dalechampii*, *Q. polycarpa*, *Q. pubescens*. Furthermore, *Acer tataricum*, *A. campestre*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, *Ulmus minor*, *Pyrus pyraster*, *Carpinus bembires*, *Sorbus domestica*, *S. torminalis*, and *Tilia tomentosa* are found in the lower tree layer. The usually well-developed shrub layer consists mainly of *Crataegus monogyna*, *Ligustrum vulgare* and *Cornus mas*, and locally also of *Rosa gallica*, *Rhamnus cathartica*, *Euonymus verrucosa*, *Cotinus coggygria*, *Viburnum lantana*, and

Ruscus aculeatus. In the herb layer thermophilous species are predominant. These include *Lathyrus niger*, *Silene coronaria*, *S. viridiflora*, *Potentilla micrantha*, *Helleborus odorus*, *Lithospermum purpurocaeruleum*, *Polygonatum hirtum*, and *Lathyrus laxiflorus*, along with acidophilous species (including *Luzula luzuloides* and *L. forsteri*), furthermore, species characteristic of periodically dry sites (*Cares praecox*, *Fesluca heterophylla*) and mesophilous species (*Brachypodium sylvaticum*, *Stellaria holastea*, *Euphorbia amygdaloides*, *Anemone ranunculoides*).

4.4. ALPINE BIOGEOGRAPHICAL REGION

The Alpine biogeographical region in Europe is characterized by high-altitude landscapes, harsh climatic conditions, and unique ecosystems. It includes the Alps, Pyrenees, Carpathians, Dinaric Alps, and parts of the Balkan and Scandinavian mountains (Map 2.1.). This region is one of Europe's most biodiverse but fragile areas, requiring strong conservation efforts. It is characterized by a relatively cold and harsh climate, high altitudes, and an often complex, varied topography.

Forests and semi-natural grasslands envelop the lower slopes but, as the altitude increases and the temperature drops, trees become scarcer and eventually give way to alpine grasslands, fells, and scrub heath communities. At the very top, amongst the rocks and snow, the vegetation is reduced to only a handful of highly adapted plants able to tolerate such extreme conditions. Almost two-thirds of the plants on the European continent are present here. The high peaks harbor many endemics whilst, on the lower slopes, species diversity is heavily influenced by its transition with other biogeographical regions and the long history of compatible human land uses. Annex I of the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) lists in total 198 habitat types of which 119 Annex I habitat types are found in the Alpine region. Two Annex I habitats are only present in the region: permanent glaciers (habitat 8340) and alpine *Larix decidua* and/or *Pinus cembra* forests (9420). In addition, 107 plants, and 161 animal species listed in the Habitats Directive are found in the Alpine Region.

This biogeographical region exhibits a complex geomorphology and an array of microclimates that contribute to a wide variety of habitats and high levels of biodiversity. Half of the region is covered by forests, being composed by a relatively low number of tree species. The main conifers are silver fir (*Abies alba*), Norway spruce (*Picea abies*), larch (*Larix decidua*), Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*), Alpine pine (*P. cembra*, *P. uncinata*, *P. mugo* and *P. nigra*). These

conifer species are the main species forming the alpine forests. Alpine grasslands are characterized by the domination of two plant families, grasses and sedges. After hundreds of years of traditional grazing, only a limited part of the biomass has been exhausted, and the flora is hardly altered at all. With an increasing altitude the vegetation in the nival zone becomes more and more scarce; ca 150 flowering plants can be found above 2 900 m, 50 species at 3 500 m and only ca 10 species above 4 000 m. Bryophytes and lichens however thrive under severe conditions, more than 200 species have been recorded. Vegetation inhabiting rocky habitats exhibits a high proportion of endemism (Map 2.2.). In the Alps, 35–40 % of all endemic species are found on rocks and in screes; half of the 40 plant species endemic to the Maritime Alps are rock inhabiting (rupicolous). Mountains supply the European continent with much of its freshwater resources. They intercept water from air masses and store it as snow or in the lakes, glaciers, and reservoirs before disbursing it into the lowlands via some of Europe's major rivers. Five major European rivers are originating from the Alps: Rhone, Rhine, Danube, Adige and Po. More than 2 % of the area of the Alps is covered by the ice of 1,300 glaciers. In spring and summer especially, the mountains play a vital function in supplying water for agricultural irrigation and human consumption across much of Europe. In general, the Alpine biogeographic region exhibits a great variety of ecosystems and habitat types, of which 90 % are natural or semi-natural. Forests cover more than 40 % of the region's area and grasslands cover 25 %. More than 7 000 species of plants are registered and most of the mountain areas have a high degree of endemism. The region is of great importance as refuges for plants and especially so for animals with large area requirements. It further constitutes an in-situ gene bank for numerous species.

Climate change causes a general upward movement of the tree line. This will have consequences for land use, such as grazing and tourism. Arctic and alpine areas already witness a general increase in shrub or tree growth in high-altitude sites. This will reduce areas of alpine heaths in mountains and change summit floras on high mountains, among others, by reducing the available land area for cold-adapted organisms (summit trap phenomenon). Most of the species that are new in these high-alpine sites are characteristic of ecosystems at lower altitudes on the mountains, such as from the alpine grassland zone.

4.4.1. SITES KOPOŠIĆI AND KRIŽEVIĆI (BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA)

These sites are located in the vegetation zone of Dinaric beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica*, *Fagus sylvatica* subsp. *moesiaca*) with *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Acer platanoides*, *Lonicera alpigena*,

Rhamnus alpina subsp. fallax, *Mercurialis perennis*, *Hordelymus europaeus*. These forests contain mainly Central European species and have a weakly developed shrub layer with *Lonicera alpigena*, *Lonicera formanekiana*, *Rhamnus alpina subsp. fallax*. The herb layer covers almost 100 % of the surface, within which dominate basiphilous to neutrophilous species of vegetation order *Fagetalia*, such as *Mercurialis perennis*, *Galium odoratum*, *Hordelymus europaeus*, *Viola reichenbachiana*, *Prenanthes purpurea*, *Mycelis muralis*, *Paris quadrifolia*, *Campanula trachelium*, *Luzula sylvatica*, *Anemone nemorosa*, *Dryopteris filix-mas*, *Lamium galeobdolon*, and *Lathyrus vernus*. Moss layer is barely developed. Illyrian species disappear or are absent. Soils are mountain-rendzines, base-rich brown soils; (rendzic leptosols; chromic and eutric cambisols), with loamy to clayey, often stony to rocky texture, fresh to moderately dry, and with neutral to weakly alkaline reaction.

4.4.2. SITES RAVANJSKA VRATA AND BLIDINJE – DUGO POLJE (BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA)

These sites are located in the vegetation zone of Illyrian-Dinaric altimontane beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica*), partly with *Acer pseudoplatanus*, and *Saxifraga rotundifolia*, *Ranunculus platanifolius*, *Polystichum lonchitis*, partly *Adenostyles alliariae*.

4.4.3. SITE ŽUGIĆA BARE (MONTENEGRO)

Site is located in the vegetation zone of Illyrian-west Balcanic montane spruce forests (*Picea abies*) with *Abies alba*, *Galium rotundifolium*, *Goodyera repens*, *Aremonia agrimonoides*. The spruce dominates in the tree layer, the silver fir and less frequently beech are admixtures. A shrub layer is hardly present while the herb and moss layers are well developed. Typically, there are many *Abieti-Piceenion* species as well as species of mesophilous deciduous forests with broad ecological-coenotic amplitudes. To the east, the proportion of "boreal" species decreases. The western formation types are characterised by south-east European-Illyrian species, while the eastern ones are characterised by Balkan and south-east European species and are geographically differentiated.

Dominant and most frequent species in the tree layer is *Picea abies* dominating, admixed *Abies alba*, isolated *Fagus sylvatica s. l.*, and *Acer pseudoplatanus*. Typical species in the shrub layer are *Salix silesiaca*, *Daphne blagayana*, *Daphne mezereum*, *Rosa pendulina* among others. In the herb layer grow: *Galium rotundifolium*, *Blechnum spicant*, *Luzula luzuloides*, *Luzula pilosa*, *Veronica officinalis*, *Oxalis acetosella*, *Circaea alpina*, *Deschampsia flexuosa*, *Vaccinium*

myrtillus, *Luzula sylvatica*, *Calamagrostis arundinacea*, *Homogyne sylvestris*, *Lycopodium annotinum*, *Lycopodium clavatum*, *Moneses uniflora*, *Cardamine trifolia*, *Primula veris subsp. columnae*, *Primula acaulis*, *Sanicula europaea*, and *Helleborus odorus*. In the moss layer (incl. lichens) grow: *Plagiochila asplenioides*, *Bazzania trilobata*, *Polytrichum formosum* among others. Soils are loamy sand to clayey loam, stony, fresh to moist, partly moderately dry, strongly to weakly acidic (neutral), and oligotrophic to mesotrophic fertility.

4.4.4. SITE HUNDSKIRCHE (AUSTRIA)

Site is located in the vegetation zone of Fir-beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica*, *Abies alba*), partly with *Picea abies*, with *Anemone trifolia*, *Lamium orvala*, *Cardamine enneaphyllos*, *Hacquetia epipactis*, *Omphalodes verna*, *Vicia oroboides* in the south(east) Alps and Illyria. Frequently pure beech forests, at least at the northern descent of the southern Alps (Carinthia) and in Styria, however, there are also fir-beech forests with spruce, without an appreciable shrub layer and with a moderately covering herb layer that is species-rich and characterised by Illyrian species in particular. At snow-rich altimontane sites there are sabre-formed pure beech forests. Dominant and most frequent species in tree layer is *Fagus sylvatica*, admixed *Abies alba*, (*Picea abies*), *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Acer obtusatum*, *Acer platanoides*, and *Ulmus glabra*. In the shrub layer grow rejuvenation of tree species and *Daphne mezereum*, *Daphne laureola*, *Lonicera xylosteum*, *Lonicera alpigena*, *Rosa pendulina*, *Euonymus latifolia*, *Corylus avellana*, and *Rubus hirtus*. The most important plant species in the herb layer are: *Anemone trifolia*, *Aposeris foetida*, *Helleborus niger*, *Aremonia agrimonoides*, *Cardamine trifolia*, *Cardamine enneaphyllos*, *Cardamine bulbifera*, *Cardamine pentaphyllos*, *Hacquetia epipactis*, *Homogyne sylvestris*, *Epimedium alpinum*, *Prenanthes purpurea*, *Veronica urticifolia*, *Polygonatum verticillatum*, *Oxalis acetosella*, *Neottia nidus-avis*, *Lamium flavidum*, *Festuca drymeja*, *Vicia oroboides*, *Polystichum aculeatum*, *Mercurialis perennis*, *Euphorbia amygdaloides*, *Euphorbia carniolica*, *Cyclamen purpurascens*, *Salvia glutinosa*, *Calamagrostis varia*, *Carex alba*, *Sanicula europaea*, *Galium aristatum*, *Scopolia carniolica*, *Aruncus dioicus*, *Lathyrus vernus*, *Hepatica nobilis*, *Cephalanthera damasonium*, and *Cephalanthera longifolia*. In the moss layer (incl. lichens) grow *Ctenidium molluscum*, *Fissidens dubius*, *Plagiochila porelloides*, and *Plagiomnium undulatum*. Soils are loamy, fresh to moderately dry, weakly acidic to neutral, and (limestone-oligotrophic) meso-eutrophic, and eutrophic fertility.

5. ANALYSIS OF THE MOST RECENT CLIMATE ELEMENTS FOR THE AREAS OF SELECTED SITES

5.1 BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA SELECTED SITES

5.1.1 KOPOŠIĆI

5.1.1.1 INSOLATION

Analysis of collected meteorological data for insolation has determined that the average monthly insolation for Kopošići for the period 1992–2022 is 133 h. The lowest average monthly insolation was recorded in December, amounting to 47.5 hours, while the highest average insolation was recorded in July, reaching 243.3 hours.

Fig. 5.1. Average monthly insolation for the period 1992-2022.

In accordance with influencing factors, there are significant differences in the amount of insolation (sunshine hours) during different periods of the year. The average insolation for the winter is 69.0 hours, with the lowest number of sunshine hours recorded in Kopošići in December (47.5 hours) and the highest in February (91.1 hours). The average total sunshine duration for the spring is 138.0 hours, with the lowest insolation recorded in March (109.5 hours) and the highest in May (169.4 hours). During the summer, the average sunshine

duration is 215.2 hours, with the highest insolation recorded in July (243.3 hours) and the lowest in June (214.9 hours). The average monthly sunshine duration in the autumn is 109.9 hours, with maximum values in September (130.4 hours) and a minimum in November, which has less than 78.1 hours of sunshine.

Fig. 5.2. Average sunshine duration by seasons for the period 1992-2022.

The increase in sunshine duration over the past thirty years (1992-2022) has been continuous and correlates with the rise in radiation and air temperatures. The general trend of increasing sunshine duration is best represented by a linear trend.

Fig. 5.3. Total annual insolation for the period 1992-2022.

Based on the linear trend, it has been determined that sunshine duration has increased by 158 hours over the given period. Within this thirty-year period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of sunshine duration. The average multi-year sunshine duration is 1,596.3 hours. Sixteen years had annual sunshine duration above the long-term average, while fifteen years recorded values below the multi-year average. In the last ten years, seven years had higher insolation, while only three years recorded lower values compared to the long-term average. The highest average annual insolation of 1,849.5 hours was recorded in 2022, while the lowest average annual insolation of 1,352.5 hours was recorded in 1996.

5.1.1.2 RADIATION

Solar radiation in Kopošiči during the analysed thirty-year period (1992-2022) correlates with insolation and air temperatures. The average monthly radiation value for the period 1992 – 2022 is 90.0 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly solar radiation was recorded in December at 34.6 kWh/m², while the highest average radiation was measured in July at 170.1 kWh/m².

The average radiation for the winter is 45.4 kWh/m², with the lowest in December (34.6 kWh/m²) and the highest in February (57.9 kWh/m²). The total average radiation for the spring is 102.4 kWh/m², with the lowest in March (73.4 kWh/m²) and the highest in May (132.2 kWh/m²). During the summer, the average radiation is 150.9 kWh/m², with the highest in July (170.1 kWh/m²) and the lowest in August (123.7 kWh/m²). The average monthly radiation in the autumn is 61.3 kWh/m², with maximum values in September (79.4 kWh/m²) and a minimum in November (39.5 kWh/m²).

Fig. 5.4. Average monthly radiation for the period 1992-2022.

The linear trend analysis indicates an increase in radiation at the Kopošiči locality from 1992 to 2022, with an increase of 98 kWh/m². The average multi-year radiation value is 1079.8 kWh/m². Sixteen years out of the thirty-year period had a higher annual radiation than the multi-year average, while fifteen years recorded values below it. In the last 10 years, 7 years had higher radiation, and 3 years had lower radiation compared to the multi-year average.

Fig. 5.5. Annual radiation for the period 1992-2022.

The maximum and minimum annual radiation values correlate entirely with solar insolation. The highest average annual radiation of 1257.9 kWh/m² was recorded in 2022, while the lowest average annual radiation of 928.8 kWh/m² was registered in 1996.

5.1.1.3 AIR TEMPERATURE

The average monthly temperature for Kopošiči for the period 1992–2022 is 8.4°C. The lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January at -1.5°C, while the highest was recorded in July at 18.4°C. The average temperature for the winter is -0.7°C, with the lowest recorded in January at -1.5°C and the highest in February at 0.0°C. For spring, the average temperatures are 7.8°C. The lowest average temperature in spring is in March at 3.2°C, while the highest is in May at 12.3°C. During the summer, the average temperature is 17.8°C. The average monthly temperature recorded in July is 18.4°C, making it the highest average monthly temperature of the summer. The lowest average monthly temperature in the summer is in June, at 16.7°C. The average monthly temperature in autumn is 8.8°C. The coldest month is November, at 4.2°C, while the warmest is September, at 13.4°C.

Fig. 5.6. Average monthly temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

In the last thirty years (1992–2022), temperatures have been steadily increasing. The general trend of rising temperatures is best represented by a linear trend, which serves as a dynamic midpoint of the entire temperature data series. Based on the linear trend, it has been determined that the temperature has increased by 1.6°C.

Fig. 5.7. Average annual temperature values for the period 1992–2022.

Within this thirty-year period, there have been certain annual fluctuations in temperature increases and decreases. The long-term average temperature is 8.4°C. In 18 years the average annual temperature was above the long-term average, while in 13 years, it was below. Over the last 15 years (except for 2011), the average annual temperatures have been higher than the long-term average. The highest recorded average annual temperature was 9.5°C in 2022, while the lowest was 6.9°C in 2005. In addition to the overall temperature increase based on the linear trend, a temperature rise (with varying values) has been identified for all seasons.

Specifically, the temperature increase for the summer is 1.9°C, for autumn 1.6°C, for spring 1.0°C, and for winter 1.7°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter is 3.1°C, recorded in 2014, while the minimum temperature is -3.9°C, recorded in 2012. The maximum average annual temperature during the spring is 9.7°C, recorded in 2018. The lowest average annual temperature for the spring is 5.6°C, recorded in 1997. The maximum average annual temperatures for the summer are 20.7°C, recorded in 2012, while the minimum temperature values were recorded in 2006, with an average of 15.9°C. During the winter, the maximum temperatures were recorded in 2019, with an average of 11.1°C, while the minimum temperature values of 6.0°C were registered in 2007.

Fig. 5.8. Average temperature values per seasons for the period 1992–2022.

The average maximum monthly temperature at the Kopošiči location for the period 1992–2022 is 22.6°C. The lowest average maximum monthly temperature was recorded in January at 11.6°C, while the highest was recorded in August at 33.0°C. The average maximum air temperature for the winter is 12.3°C. The average maximum temperatures measured in December (11.7°C) and January (11.6°C) are nearly identical, while in February, the average maximum monthly temperature is slightly higher at 13.6°C. The average maximum temperature measured for the spring is 22.7°C. The lowest average maximum temperature in spring occurs in March at 18.3°C, while the highest is in May at 26.9°C. During the summer, the average maximum temperature is 32.3°C. The highest recorded average maximum monthly temperature in August is 33.0°C, while the lowest maximum temperatures in summer occur in June at 31.0°C. The average maximum monthly temperature during autumn is 23.1°C. The coldest month is November at 17.9°C, while the warmest is September at 27.9°C.

Fig. 5.9. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average values of the maximum recorded temperature for the period 1992-2022 is 27.2°C. The highest air temperature at the Kopošiči location was 36.6°C, recorded on August 23, 2007. The lowest maximum temperature was recorded on December 31, 2009, and was 15.7°C. During this thirty-year period, extreme maximum temperature values were recorded for: January 16.4°C (2007), February 19.9°C (2021), March 24.2°C (2001), April 27.4°C (2003),

May 30.5°C (2008), June 36.2°C (2021), July 36.2°C (2021), August 36.6°C (2007), September 35.9°C (2015), October 26.0°C (2013), November 22.3°C (2022), December 15.7°C (2009).

Fig. 5.10. Maximum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The linear trend has determined a 2.4°C increase in maximum annual air temperature for the period 1992–2022. The average value of the maximum measured temperatures in Kopošiči during this period is 33.5°C. The highest maximum temperature of 36.6°C was recorded in August 2007, while the lowest maximum temperature of 30.0°C was recorded in August 2018. In general, extreme maximum temperature values show a rising trend.

Fig. 5.11. Maximum annual air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

At the Kopošiči site, available data on the number of days with maximum air temperatures falling within the following thresholds were analysed: $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum temperatures of $T_{\max} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a mean monthly value of 2.6 days. The maximum number of days with $T_{\max} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 11.7 days, with the highest value recorded in January. The months from April to November do not have any maximum temperatures below 0.0°C . Extreme maximum temperatures of $T_{\max} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a higher mean monthly number of days compared to the previously analysed indicator. The mean monthly value is 7.0 days, with the maximum number of days with $T_{\max} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ reaching 22.5 days. The highest value for this temperature indicator was recorded in July, while August has an almost identical mean value (22.4 days). December, January, and March do not experience extreme maximum air temperatures of $T_{\max} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum air temperatures of $T_{\max} \geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a mean monthly value of 1.8 days, with the peak in August, averaging 9.0 days. The months of January, February, March, April, October, November, and December do not record any days with a maximum air temperature of $T_{\max} \geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.12. Average annual values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

During the period 1992–2022, on an annual scale, maximum air temperatures below 0.0°C had a mean number of 2.6 days, with a minimum of an average of 1 day recorded in 2014 and a maximum of an average of 9.3 days in 2011. The mean number of days with this temperature indicator shows a decreasing trend of approximately 0.8 days over the analysed period. Maximum air temperatures of $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ were recorded on average for 7 days annually. This temperature indicator reached a maximum of an average of 7.4 days in 2019, while the minimum of 6.3 days was recorded in 2013. A linear trend over the 30-year period indicates an increasing tendency in the mean number of days by 1.5 for this temperature indicator. Air temperatures of $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ were recorded on average for 1.8 days annually, with a rising trend in the last seven years by 0.5 days. The maximum mean number of days (4.4) was recorded in 2012, while the minimum mean of 0.3 days was measured in 1995.

Fig. 5.13. Average annual values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average minimum monthly temperature for the period 1992–2022 is -3.2°C . The lowest average minimum monthly temperature was recorded in January, at -14.0°C , while the highest temperature was recorded in July, at 6.7°C . The average minimum temperature for the winter is -12.5°C , with the lowest temperatures recorded in January, and the highest in December at -11.7°C . The measured average minimum temperatures for the spring are -4.0°C , with the lowest temperatures in March at -8.7°C and the highest in May at 0.6°C . During the summer, the average minimum temperatures are 6.1°C . The average monthly minimum temperature during this season was recorded in June at 4.8°C , while the highest was in July at 6.9°C . The average minimum monthly temperatures during the autumn are -2.5°C , with the coldest month being November at -6.8°C and the warmest being September at 2.1°C .

Fig. 5.14. Average minimum monthly temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average value of extreme minimum temperature for the period 1992–2022 is -9.5°C . The lowest recorded average minimum temperature at Kopošići was -24.0°C in January 2017.

Fig. 5.15. Minimum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The highest average minimum temperature occurred in July 2000, at 3.1°C. During this thirty-year period, extreme average minimum monthly temperatures were recorded as follows: January -24.0°C (2017), February -22.1°C (2012), March -19.2°C (2005), April -8.6°C (2003), May -2.8°C (2019), June -1.3°C (1997), July 3.1°C (2000), August 2.6°C (1995), September -1.6°C (2018), October -9.8°C (1997), November -12.9°C (1995), and December -18.5°C (1999). These indicators show that, in the last 10 years, record low values were observed in four months, while the remaining extreme minimum values were recorded in the first two decades of the observed period. The average minimum temperature at Kopošići for the period 1992–2022 is -16.3°C. The lowest extreme minimum temperature of -16.3°C was recorded on December 23, 1998. The lowest minimum temperature of -24.0°C was recorded on January 8, 2018. In general, extreme values of minimum temperatures have a tendency to increase. A linear trend analysis indicates a temperature increase of 1.2°C, which is significantly lower compared to the trend of increasing extreme maximum temperatures.

Fig. 5.16. Minimum annual air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

Based on collected data over a 30-year period (1992–2022), an analysis was conducted on the number of days with extreme minimum air temperature values falling within the following thresholds: $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme minimum temperatures of $T_{\text{min}} \leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a mean monthly value of 0.4 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was recorded in January, averaging 3.3 days. The months from April

to November do not experience minimum temperatures $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme minimum temperatures of $T_{\text{min}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a slightly higher mean monthly number of days compared to the previously analysed threshold. The mean monthly value is 8.0 days, with the highest number of days with temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ recorded in January, averaging 25.3 days. The months of May, June, July, August, and September do not experience minimum temperatures below 0.0°C . At the Kopošiči site, no extreme minimum temperatures of $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ were recorded during the analysed period. Indicators of the number of days with extreme minimum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 5 cm above the ground surface (T_{min5}) show values almost identical to those of $T_{\text{min}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. The mean monthly number of days is 8.5, with the highest number of days recorded in January, averaging 26.8 days. In June, July, and August, there were no recorded days with temperatures below 0.0°C at 5 cm above the ground surface.

Fig. 5.17. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

During the period 2015–2022, on an annual scale, minimum air temperatures of $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ had a mean number of 0.0 days, with a minimum of 0 days recorded in 2021 and a maximum of an average of 0.9 days in 2017. The mean number of days with this temperature indicator shows a decreasing trend of approximately 0.3 days over the analysed period. During the period 1992–2022, minimum air temperatures below 0.0°C were recorded on average for 8 days annually. This temperature indicator reached a maximum of an average of 10.9 days in 1997,

while the minimum of 2.8 days was recorded in 2011. A linear trend over the 30-year period indicates a decreasing tendency of 3 days on average for this temperature indicator. Air temperatures below 0.0°C at 5 cm above the ground surface recorded an average of 8.5 days, with a stable linear trend over the 8-year period. The maximum mean number of days with this temperature indicator was 9.8, recorded in 2015, while the minimum mean of 7 days was measured in 2019.

Fig. 5.18. Average annual values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.1.4 RELATIVE HUMIDITY KOPOŠIČI

The average monthly relative humidity for Kopošiči from 1992 to 2022 is 76.3%. The lowest average monthly relative humidity was recorded in April at 69.9%, while the highest relative humidity was recorded in December at 84.4%. Monthly relative humidity values are slightly higher during the winter and autumn periods compared to the summer and spring periods.

Specifically, the average relative humidity for the winter is 82.1%, with the lowest value in February at 78.3% and the highest in December at 84.4%. The average relative humidity for the spring is 71.6%, with the lowest value in April at 69.9%, and the highest value in March at 74.1%. During the summer, the average relative humidity is 71.1%. The highest value was recorded in August at 72.6%, while June (70.4%) and July (70.3%) had nearly identical values. The average monthly relative humidity values during the autumn are 80.5%, with the lowest value in September at 77.5% and the highest in October at 82.3%. The average value of the highest maximum average relative humidity for the Kopošiči locality from 1992 to 2022 is 87.5%. The highest average relative humidity recorded during this thirty-year period was 96.8%, measured in December 2015. The lowest maximum average relative humidity was recorded in May 2002, at 79.6%.

Fig. 5.19. Average monthly relative humidity values for the period 1992–2022.

During the analysed period (1992-2022), the maximum values of average relative humidity were: January 89.3% (2009), February 87.0% (1996), March 86.5% (2008), April 82.1% (2008), May 79.6% (2002), June 81.5% (2008), July 81.7% (2008), August 89.9% (1995), September 88.4% (1995), October 93.5% (2007), November 93.7% (1999), and December 96.8% (2015). As with other locations, it can be observed that in the last ten years only one month had the

highest average relative humidity, while all other highest monthly values were recorded in the previous two decades.

Fig. 5.20. Maximum average relative humidity values for the period 1992–2022.

At the Kopošići locality, the average value of the minimum average relative humidity for the period 1992-2022 is 63.0%. The highest minimum average relative humidity during the reference period was 77.6%, measured in January 2005. The lowest minimum average relative humidity (46.7%) was recorded in August 2012. During the analyzed period, the lowest values of monthly average relative humidity were January 77.6% (2005), February 68.9% (2021), March 59.1% (2022), April 52.5% (2020), May 59.3% (2021), June 55.8% (2012), July 56.6% (2012), August 46.7% (2012), September 65.3% (2012), October 68.9% (1993), November 70.6% (2002), and December 74.4% (2016). Unlike the monthly maximum average relative humidity, which have not been recorded in the last ten years, the minimum average values show the opposite trend. The analyzed data clearly show that in the last ten years, nine months have the lowest average relative humidity values, while only three minimum monthly values were recorded in the previous two decades. This contrasts with the recorded maximum average relative humidity values.

Fig.5.21. Minimum average monthly relative humidity values for the period 1992–2022.

During the reference period, the relative humidity at the Kopošići locality has been steadily decreasing. The linear trend analysis shows a decline of 2.8% in relative humidity from 1992 to 2022. Within this thirty-year period, there have been certain annual fluctuations, with the maximum oscillation reaching 13.5%.

The average multi-year relative humidity value for the Kopošići locality is 76.3%. Of the 30 years in the period, 17 years had relative humidity values above the multi-year average, while 14 years had values below it. In the last 10 years, only two years recorded values higher than the multi-year average. The highest average annual relative humidity of 83.4% was recorded in 1995, while the lowest average annual value of 69.9% occurred in 2012.

Fig. 5.22. Average annual relative humidity values for the period 1992–2022.

5.1.1.5 PRECIPITATION

An analysis of monthly average precipitation values indicates significant fluctuations on a monthly level in this parameter in the Kopošiči area. The average annual precipitation for the period 1992–2022 is 92.0 mm.

Fig. 5.23. Average monthly precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

The lowest average precipitation occurs in July (76.2 mm), while the highest precipitation is recorded in December (114.9 mm). During the winter, an average of 90.0 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum in December (114.9 mm) and a minimum in February (73.8 mm). In the spring, the average precipitation is also 90.1 mm, with a maximum in May (97.5 mm) and a minimum in March (82.5 mm). During the summer, the average precipitation is 81.8 mm, with the highest amount recorded in June (91.4 mm) and the lowest in July (76.2 mm). In the autumn, an average of 106.1 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum in September (111.0 mm) and a minimum in November (102.2 mm).

In addition to the overall annual precipitation pattern, a linear trend analysis on an annual scale for the period 1992–2022 has identified seasonal increases (during spring and summer) or decreases (during autumn and winter) in precipitation amounts. Specifically, during the period 1992–2022, precipitation amounts in the autumn climatological season decreased by 34 mm, while summer precipitation decreased by 6 mm. Over the same period, winter precipitation increased by 8 mm, whereas spring precipitation increased by 12 mm.

Fig. 5.24. Average precip. amounts by climatological season for the period 1992–2022.

An analysis of annual precipitation levels for Kopošiči over the period 1992-2022, based on a linear trend, indicates a decline of 54 mm. Within this 30-year period, there are certain annual fluctuations in precipitation amounts, both increasing and decreasing. The long-term average precipitation amounts to 1103.8 mm. The highest annual precipitation sum was recorded in 1999, reaching 1555.5 mm, while the lowest value of 795.6 mm was recorded in 2011. In the analyzed dataset, 17 years had annual precipitation amounts above the long-term average, while 14 years had precipitation levels below the long-term average.

Fig. 5.25. Annual precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly values of the maximum precipitation for the period 1992-2022 at the Kopošiči locality are 27.6 mm. The highest precipitation values are recorded in September, with an average of 35.5 mm. The lowest average monthly value for maximum precipitation was recorded in March, at 22.9 mm. For the winter, the average monthly maximum precipitation is 25.7 mm, with the lowest values recorded in February (23.6 mm) and the highest in December (29.3 mm). The average monthly maximum precipitation for the spring is 24.7 mm, with the lowest values in March (22.4 mm) and the highest in May (29.2 mm). During the summer, the average maximum precipitation amounts are slightly lower, at 25.7 mm, with the highest recorded in August (26.9 mm) and the lowest in July (24.1 mm). The average monthly maximum precipitation amounts are highest during the autumn, with an average of 34.5 mm. The maximum precipitation occurs in September (35.5 mm), while the minimum is recorded in November (33.7 mm).

Fig. 5.26. Average monthly maximum precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The average values of the maximum precipitation for the Kopošići locality for the period 1992-2022 are 73.3 mm. The highest recorded amount of precipitation was 145.7 mm, registered in October 2003. The lowest maximum precipitation value of 47.9 mm was recorded in July 1993. During the 30-year period, extreme maximum precipitation values were recorded as follows: January: 52.0 mm (2007), February: 73.8 mm (2012), March: 50.3 mm (1993), April: 56.2 mm (2017), May: 84.1 mm (2014), June: 63.3 mm (2009), July: 47.9 mm (2016), August: 55.4 mm (2005), September: 76.9 mm (1996), October: 145.7 mm (2003), November: 75.7 mm (2021), December: 98.7 mm (1999).

Fig. 5.27. Maximum precipitation with dates for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the maximum recorded annual precipitation for the period 1992-2022 is 60.1 mm. The highest recorded maximum precipitation for the year was 145.7 mm, measured in 2003, while the lowest maximum value of annual precipitation was 38.1 mm, recorded in October 2000. A linear trend analysis shows a slight decrease in the maximum precipitation values, which correlates with the decrease in the annual total precipitation amounts. The analysis determined that the maximum precipitation values have decreased by 7.5 mm over the 30-year period from 1992 to 2022.

At the Kopošiči site, based on collected and analysed data, significant differences are observed in the average number of days with precipitation amounts of ≥ 0.1 mm, ≥ 1.0 mm, ≥ 5.0 mm, ≥ 10.0 mm, ≥ 20.0 mm, and ≥ 50.0 mm. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is 16.5. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 18.7, which represents the average monthly value for December, while the minimum value of 13.7 days was recorded in August. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm is slightly lower, at 12.4 days, with a maximum in May (an average of 13.8 days) and a minimum in

August (an average of 10.3 days). Precipitation amounts of ≥ 5.0 mm occur on an average of 6.4 days per month.

The highest number of days with this precipitation threshold was recorded in December (7.3 days on average), while the lowest was in September (5.4 days on average). The average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 4.4.

Fig. 5.28. Maximum precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm was recorded in December (4.9 days on average), while the minimum was in February (3.48 days on average). Precipitation amounts of ≥ 20.0 mm occur on an average of 1.4 days per month. The maximum number of days with ≥ 20.0 mm of precipitation is 2 days (the average monthly value for December), while the minimum is 0.8 days (the average for February). The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm is 0.04. The maximum number of days with this precipitation amount is 0.3, which represents the average monthly value for May and November.

On an annual basis, precipitation of ≥ 0.1 mm occurs on an average of 16.5 days, with a maximum of 19 days recorded in 1995 and a minimum of 14 days in 2000. Precipitation of ≥ 1.0 mm is recorded on an average of 12.4 days per year. The maximum value of 14.6 days

was registered in 2005, while the minimum of 10.6 days was observed in 2022. An average of 6.4 days per year recorded precipitation of ≥ 5.0 mm, with a peak of 8.2 days in 2018 and a low of 5.3 days in 2017. Precipitation of ≥ 10.0 mm occurs on an average of 4.4 days per year. The maximum of 5.6 days was recorded in 1999, while the minimum of 3.2 days was observed in 2022. On average, 1.4 days per year recorded precipitation of ≥ 20.0 mm. The maximum of 2.1 days was registered in 2017, while the minimum of 0.9 days was recorded in 2003. Precipitation of ≥ 50.0 mm occurs on an average of 0.04 days per year, with an observed maximum of 0.2 days in both 2018 and 2021.

Fig. 5.29. Aver. monthly values of the number of days with precip. for the 1992-2022.

A linear trend analysis at the annual level indicates an increasing rate of 0.1 days for precipitation amounts of ≥ 0.1 mm and 0.1 days for ≥ 50.0 mm. Conversely, a decreasing trend was observed, with reductions of 0.4 days for ≥ 1.0 mm, 0.7 days for ≥ 5.0 mm, 0.2 days for ≥ 10.0 mm, and 0.2 days for ≥ 20.0 mm.

Fig. 5.30. Average annual values of the numb. of days with precip. for the 1992-2022.

The average monthly snowfall for the period 2015-2022 is 7.4 cm. The months without any snow cover are May, June, July, August, September, and October. The highest amount of snowfall occurs in January, with an average monthly value of 21.0 cm. During the winter, an average amount of snow is 18.5 cm, with a maximum in January (21.0 cm) and a minimum in February (14.7 cm). In the spring, average amount of snow is 9.4 cm, with the highest snowfall in March (17.5 cm) and no snowfall in May (0 cm). There is no snowfall during the summer. During the autumn, only November records snowfall, with an average monthly value of 5.3 cm.

Fig. 5.31. Average monthly snow cover height for the period 2015-2022.

A linear trend analysis has determined a decrease in snow cover height by 33.4 cm over the period 2015-2022. Within the analyzed period, there are annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of snow cover height. The long-term average snow cover height is 89.0 cm. The maximum annual snowfall was recorded in 2017, amounting to 150 cm, while the minimum value was recorded in 2016, measuring 52.4 cm.

The average maximum snow cover height for the period 2015-2022 is 17.6 cm. During this period, the highest recorded extreme monthly snow cover height was 52.9 cm, which occurred in March 2015. The months without snow cover are May, June, July, August, September, and October.

Fig.5.32. Average annual snow cover height for the period 2015-2022.

Within this seven-year period, during which snow cover height measurements were conducted at neighboring meteorological stations, allowing for data interpolation, the maximum monthly values recorded were: January: 33.5 cm (2017), February: 23.6 cm (2020), March: 52.9 cm (2015), April: 35.8 cm (2017), November: 16.3 cm (2021), December: 48.6 cm (2017)

Fig. 5.33. Maximum monthly snow cover height for the period 2015-2022.

Fig. 5.34. Maximum annual snow cover height for the period 2015-2022.

A linear trend analysis has shown a decrease in precipitation, and using the same methodological concept, it has been determined that the maximum values of snow cover height decreased by 22.2 cm in the period from 2015 to 2022.

5.1.2 KRIŽEVIĆI

5.1.2.1 INSOLATION

An analysis of meteorological data collected for Križeviči has determined that the average monthly sunshine duration for the period 1992–2022 is 152.1 hours. The lowest average monthly sunshine duration was recorded in December, totaling 43.6 hours, while the highest average was observed in July, reaching 272.7 hours.

Fig. 5.35. Average monthly insolation for the period 1992-2022.

There are significant variations in sunshine duration across different seasons in the analyzed area. The average sunshine duration for the winter is 66.6 hours, with the lowest recorded in December and January at 43.6 hours and the highest in February at 96.8 hours. The average total sunshine duration for the spring is 175.7 hours, with the lowest in March at 145.3 hours and the highest in May at 210.2 hours. During the summer, the average monthly sunshine duration is 252.6 hours, with the highest in July (272.7 hours) and the lowest in June (237.2 hours). In the autumn, the average monthly sunshine duration is 113.7 hours, with a maximum in September (157.9 hours) and a minimum in November (64.3 hours).

Fig. 5.36. Average sunshine duration by seasons for the period 1992-2022.

Based on the linear trend analysis, sunshine duration has been steadily increasing over the past thirty years (1992–2022). During this period, the total sunshine duration for the Križeviči area has increased by 229 hours.

Fig. 5.37. Total annual solar radiation for the period 1992-2022.

However, there have been certain annual fluctuations in sunshine duration, with periods of both increases and decreases. The average long-term sunshine duration is 1,825.8 hours. Among the analyzed years, 18 years had sunshine durations above the long-term average, while 13 years were below this threshold. Over the last decade, 8 years experienced higher-than-average sunshine duration, while only 2 years had values below the long-term average. The highest annual average sunshine duration was recorded in 2022 at 2,128.7 hours, while the lowest was observed in 2010 at 1,574.5 hours.

5.1.2.2 RADIATION

The average monthly solar radiation for the Križeviči over the period 1992–2022 is 103.6 kWh/m². The lowest recorded average monthly radiation was in December, measuring 31.8 kWh/m², while the highest was in July, reaching 190.6 kWh/m². The average radiation for the winter is 43.7 kWh/m², with the lowest value in December (31.8 kWh/m²) and the highest in February (61.6 kWh/m²). The total average radiation for the spring is 130.1 kWh/m², with the lowest value in March (97.4 kWh/m²) and the highest in May (164.1 kWh/m²). During the summer, the average radiation amounts to 176.6 kWh/m², with July recording the highest value (190.6 kWh/m²) and August the lowest (163.4 kWh/m²). The average monthly solar radiation during autumn is 64.1 kWh/m², peaking in September (96.1 kWh/m²) and reaching its minimum in November (32.6 kWh/m²).

Fig. 5.38. Average monthly radiation for the period 1992-2022.

The linear trend analysis indicates an increase in solar radiation at the Križeviči site from 1992 to 2022, of 150 kWh/m². The average long-term radiation value is 1243.6 kWh/m². Among the analyzed years, 16 years had higher annual radiation than the long-term average, while 15 years recorded values below the average. In the last 10 years, 8 years had higher radiation, while 2 years had lower radiation compared to the long-term average. The last 6 years have consistently shown higher solar radiation than the annual average. The highest recorded average annual radiation of 1450.2 kWh/m² was in 2022, while the lowest recorded annual solar radiation was 1071.9 kWh/m² in 2010.

Fig. 5.39. Annual radiation for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.2.3 AIR TEMPERATURE

The average monthly temperature for the period 1992–2022 at the location of Križeviči is 10.1°C. The lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January at -0.2°C, while the highest monthly temperatures were recorded in July (20.14°C) and August (20.05°C), which have nearly the same values. The average temperature for the winter is -0.8°C, with the lowest

recorded temperature in January at -0.2°C , while the average temperatures for December and February are 1.3°C . The average recorded temperature for the spring is 9.6°C . The lowest average temperature in the spring is in March at 4.9°C , while the highest is in May at 14.3°C . During the summer, the average temperature is 19.4°C . The average monthly temperature recorded in June is 18.0°C , while the temperatures in July and August are almost identical and represent the highest average monthly temperatures of the summer, as well as the highest temperatures for the entire year. The average monthly temperature in the autumns 10.5°C . The coldest month is November at 5.7°C , while the warmest is September at 15.3°C .

Fig. 5.40. The average monthly temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Over the past thirty years (1992–2022), temperatures at the Križević locality have been steadily increasing. Based on a linear trend, it was determined that the temperature has increased 1.5°C . Within this 30-year period, there have been annual fluctuations in temperature increases and decreases.

Fig. 5.41. The average annual temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

The average multi-year temperature is 10.1°C. In 17 years, the average annual temperatures were above this multi-year average, while in 14 years they were below it. In the last 11 years (2012–2022), the annual average temperatures have been higher than the multi-year average: 2012 – 10.5°C, 2013 – 10.6°C, 2014 – 11.1°C, 2015 – 10.3°C, 2016 – 10.4°C, 2017 – 10.4°C, 2018 – 10.9°C, 2019 – 11.1°C, 2020 – 10.7°C, 2021 – 10.6°C, and 2022 – 11.2°C. The highest average annual temperature of 11.2°C was recorded in 2022, while the lowest average annual temperature of 8.6°C was recorded in 2005.

In addition to the overall increase in temperatures, the linear trend indicates an increase in temperatures across all seasons (winter, spring, summer, and autumn). Specifically, the temperature increase during the summer is 1.9°C. In the autumn, over the analyzed 30-year period, the temperature has risen by 2.1°C. During the spring, temperatures have increased by 1.0°C, while in the winter, temperatures have risen by 1.8°C. The maximum average annual temperature in the winter was 4.7°C, recorded in 2014, while the minimum temperature was -2.4°C, recorded in 2012. The maximum average annual temperature in the spring was 11.5°C, recorded in 2018, and the lowest average temperature for the spring was 7.4°C, recorded in 1997. For the summer, the maximum average annual temperature was 22.3°C, recorded in 2012, while the minimum temperature was recorded in 2005 with an average value of 17.5°C.

In the winter, maximum temperatures were recorded in 2019 with an average value of 12.9°C, while the minimum temperature of 7.7°C was recorded in 2007.

Fig. 5.42. Average seasonal temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum monthly temperature at the Križeviči for the period from 1992 to 2022 is 23.4°C. The lowest maximum average monthly temperature was recorded in January, with a value of 12.9°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in August, reaching 34.7°C. The average maximum temperature for the winter is 13.8°C, with the highest recorded in February at 14.9°C, and the lowest recorded in January at 12.9°C. The average maximum temperature for the spring is 24.5°C. The lowest maximum temperature in spring was in March at 19.9°C, while the highest was recorded in May at 29.0°C. During the summer, the average maximum temperature is 33.9°C, with the highest monthly maximum recorded in August at 34.7°C, and the lowest values recorded in June at 32.4°C. The average maximum temperature during the autumn is 24.8°C. The lowest average maximum temperature in the autumn is in November at 19.4°C, while the highest is in September, with an average of 29.8°C.

Fig. 5.43. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum temperature for the period from 1992 to 2022 at the Križevíci site is 28.9°C. The highest recorded temperature at Križevíci was 38.3°C, measured on August 23, 2007. The lowest maximum temperature was recorded on December 31, 2009, and it was 17.6°C. Extreme maximum temperature values during this thirty-year period were recorded in the following months: January: 17.7°C (2007), February: 21.2°C (2021), March: 25.8°C (2001), April: 29.1°C (2003), May: 32.5°C (2008), June: 37.5°C (2021), July: 38.0°C (2021), August: 38.3°C (2007), September: 37.8°C (2015), October: 27.9°C (2013), November: 23.7°C (2022), December: 17.6°C (2009).

Fig.5.44. Monthly maximum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The extremes of maximum recorded temperatures at Križeviči have a rising trend. The linear trend indicates an increase in the maximum annual air temperatures by 2.4°C for the period from 1992 to 2022. The average maximum temperature measured at Križeviči during this period is 35.6°C. The highest recorded maximum temperature of 38.3°C occurred in August 2007, while the lowest maximum temperature of 31.7°C was recorded in August 2018.

In contrast to the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures, which show the highest values during the winter months, the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures reaches its peak during the summer months, except for $T_{max} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, which follows the same trend as extreme minimum temperatures. An analysis of the available data reveals significant differences in the number of days with maximum temperatures of: $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum temperatures of $T_{max} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ occur on average for 1.9 days per month. The highest number of days with $T_{max} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was recorded in January, with an average of 8.6 days. From April to November, there are no days with $T_{max} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.45. Annual maximum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Extreme maximum temperatures of $T_{max} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a higher average monthly value compared to the previously analyzed indicator. The monthly average number of days is 8.2. The highest number of days with $T_{max} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was recorded in July, with an average of 24.8 days. December, January, and March do not record extreme maximum temperatures of $T_{max} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Extreme maximum temperatures of $T_{max} \geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ occur on average for 2.7 days per month, with the highest average number of days (12.2) recorded in August. January, February, March, April, October, November, and December have no days with $T_{max} \geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

From 1992 to 2022, on an annual basis, maximum air temperatures of $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average of 1.9 days per year, with a minimum of 0.5 days in 2014 and a maximum of 8.2 days in 2011. The average number of days with this temperature indicator has shown a decreasing trend of about 0.6 days over the analyzed period. Maximum air temperatures of $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have been measured on average for 8.2 days per year. This indicator reached its maximum in 2022, with an average of 8.8 days, while the minimum was recorded in 2017, with an average of 7.1 days.

Fig. 5.46. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

A linear trend over the 30-year period shows a tendency for the average number of days with $T_{\max} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ to increase by 1 day.

Fig. 5.47. Average annual values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Air temperatures of $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ are recorded on average for 2.7 days per year, with an increasing trend over the last 8 years, showing an increase of 2 days. The maximum average number of days, 5.5, was recorded in 2012, and the minimum average, 0.8 days, was measured in 1995.

The average minimum monthly temperature at Križeviči for the period from 1992 to 2022 is -1.5°C . The lowest average monthly minimum temperature was recorded in January at -12.7°C , while the highest temperature was recorded in July at 8.7°C . The average minimum temperature for the winter is -11.0°C . During this season, the lowest temperature is recorded in January, while the highest is in December, at -9.7°C . The average minimum temperature for the spring is -2.2°C , with the lowest in March at -7.1°C and the highest in May at 2.6°C . In the summer, the average minimum temperature is 7.7°C . The lowest temperature during this season was recorded in June at 6.1°C , while the highest was in July at 8.7°C . The average minimum monthly temperature during the autumn is -0.7°C . The coldest month is November with -5.3°C , while the warmest month is September with 4.0°C .

Fig. 5.48. Average monthly minimum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average values of extreme minimum temperature recorded at Križeviči for the period 1992–2022 is -7.9°C . The lowest extreme minimum temperature recorded was -22.7°C in January 2017, while the highest extreme minimum temperature was 4.9°C , recorded in July

2000. During the analyzed 30-year period, the extreme minimum temperatures for each month were: January: -22.7°C (2017), February: -19.8°C (2012), March: -17.6°C (2005), April: -6.9°C (2003), May: -0.8°C (2019), June: 0.0°C (1997), July: 4.9°C (2000), August: 4.3°C (1995), September: 0.3°C (2018), October: -7.9°C (1997), November: -11.5°C (1995), December: -16.6°C (1999). As observed in other locations across Bosnia and Herzegovina, the data indicates that four of the record-low temperatures occurred within the last 10 years, while the remaining minimum values were recorded in the first two decades of the analyzed period.

Fig. 5.49. Monthly minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Extreme minimum temperatures show an increasing trend, through the reduction of the magnitude of negative temperatures. A linear trend analysis indicates an increase of 0.9°C , which is significantly lower than the warming trend observed for extreme maximum temperatures. The average recorded extreme minimum temperature at Križeviči for the period 1992–2022 is -14.8°C . The highest extreme minimum temperature of -10.0°C was recorded on December 16, 2007, while the lowest extreme minimum temperature of -22.7°C was observed on January 8, 2017.

Fig. 5.50. Annual minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Based on the available data, significant differences can be observed in the number of days with the following extreme minimum temperatures: $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 5 cm above the ground ($T_{\min 5}$). Extreme minimum temperatures $T_{\min} \leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$: The average monthly value is 0.3 days. The maximum number of days with $T_{\min} \leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 2.5 days, recorded in January. From April to November, there are no days with temperatures $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. The extreme minimum temperatures $T_{\min} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a slightly higher average monthly value of the number of days compared to the previously analyzed indicator. The average monthly number of days is 6.9 days. The maximum number of days with a temperature $T_{\min} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 22.6 days, recorded in January. June, July, August, and September do not have minimum temperatures below 0.0°C . Extreme minimum temperatures $T_{\min} \geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 0.2 days, with the highest average number of days in October (0.7 days). The months of January, February, March, April, November, and December do not have days with a minimum temperature of $T_{\min} \geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Indicators for the number of days with extreme minimum temperatures $T_{\min} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 5 cm ($T_{\min 5}$) above the ground are quite similar to $T_{\min} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperatures. The average monthly number of days is 7.2 days. The maximum value of the number of days with $T_{\min 5} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was recorded in January at 24.9

days. June, July, and August are months in which no day had temperatures below 0.0°C at 5 cm above the ground.

Fig. 5.51. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

At the Križeviči site, from 2015 to 2022, the annual average number of days with air temperatures $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 0.3 days, with a minimum of 0 days in 2021 and a maximum of 0.8 days in 2017. The average number of days with this temperature indicator shows a declining trend of approximately 0.4 days over the analyzed period. In the period from 1992 to 2022, the annual average number of days with air temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was 6.9 days. The highest number was recorded in 1997 with an average of 9.4 days, while the minimum average number of days, 2.1, was observed in 2011. A linear trend analysis over the 30-year period shows a decline of 2.2 days per year for this temperature indicator. On average, the air temperature $> 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ occurs on 0.2 days annually, with a minimum of 0 days (for most years), and only in 2007 (1 day) and 2019 (2 days) were there days when the temperature exceeded this threshold. A decline of 0.3 days per year was also recorded for this temperature indicator. Temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 5 cm above the ground are recorded on average 7.2 days per year, with a decline of 0.6 days over the 8-year period. The highest average number of days with this temperature indicator was 8.5 days in 2015, while the minimum average was 6.3 days recorded in 2019.

Fig. 5.52. Average annual values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.2.3 RELATIVE HUMIDITY

The average monthly relative humidity for the period 1992–2022 at the Križeviči site is 74.6%. Monthly values of relative humidity are relatively consistent throughout the year. The lowest average monthly relative humidity was recorded in July, at 68.4%, while the highest was recorded in December, at 80.9%. The average relative humidity for the winter is 78.5%, with the lowest recorded in February at 75.5%, and the highest in December at 80.9%. For the spring, the average relative humidity is 71.4%, with the lowest recorded in April at 70.6%, and the highest in May at 72.0%. During the summer, the average relative humidity is 69.6%. June (70.2%) and August (70.4%) have nearly identical values, while July records a slightly lower value of 68.4%. In the autumn, the average relative humidity is 79.1%. The lowest values occur in September at 76.0%, while October (80.8%) and November (80.5%) have nearly identical values.

Fig. 5.53. Average monthly values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum relative humidity at the Križeviči for the period 1992–2022 is 85.6%. The highest average relative humidity during this 30-year period was recorded in December 2015, at 92.7%. The lowest recorded maximum average relative humidity occurred in July 2008, at 79.4%. During this period, the highest average relative humidity values were recorded in the following months: January: 84.7% (2009), February: 83.9% (1996), March: 83.6% (2008), April: 83.0% (2008), May: 80.9% (2002), June: 81.3% (2008), July: 79.4% (2008), August: 87.1% (1995), September: 86.7% (1995), October: 91.8% (2007), November: 92.4% (1999), December: 92.7% (2015). The highest values of relative humidity were mainly observed between 1995 and 1999, with December 2015 being the only month in the last decade to record maximum average relative humidity.

Fig. 5.54. Maximum average monthly values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum relative humidity at the Križeviči for the period 1992–2022 is 85.6%. The highest average relative humidity during this 30-year period was recorded in December 2015, at 92.7%. The lowest recorded maximum average relative humidity occurred in July 2008, at 79.4%. During this period, the highest average relative humidity values were recorded in the following months: January: 84.7% (2009), February: 83.9% (1996), March: 83.6% (2008), April: 83.0% (2008), May: 80.9% (2002), June: 81.3% (2008), July: 79.4% (2008), August: 87.1% (1995), September: 86.7% (1995), October: 91.8% (2007), November: 92.4% (1999), December: 92.7% (2015). The highest values of relative humidity were mainly observed between 1995 and 1999, with December 2015 being the only month in the last decade to record maximum average relative humidity.

Fig. 5.55. Minimum average monthly values of rel. air humidity for 1992-2022.

The collected and analyzed data show a consistent decline in the relative humidity at the Križeviči site over the past thirty years (1992–2022). The linear trend indicates a decrease of 2.5% in relative humidity during this period. Within this thirty-year period, there have been certain annual fluctuations in relative humidity values, with the maximum fluctuation being 13.2%. The average long-term relative humidity at Križeviči is 74.6%. Over this period, 17 years recorded relative humidity values above the long-term average, while 14 years recorded values below the average. In the last 10 years, only two years have seen higher values compared to the long-term average. The maximum average annual relative humidity of 81.6% was recorded in 1995, while the minimum average annual relative humidity of 68.4% was observed in 2012.

Fig. 5.56. Average annual values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.2.4 PRECIPITATION

The average annual precipitation at the Križevíci locality for the period 1992–2022 is 81.7 mm. These climatic characteristics are the result of the predominant continental influence. The smallest average amount of precipitation occurs in February (59.5 mm), while the highest precipitation is recorded in June (104.0 mm).

Fig. 5.57. Average monthly precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

During the winter, an average of 76.8 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum in December (96.4 mm) and a minimum in February (59.5 mm). In the spring, the average precipitation is 79.7 mm, with the maximum occurring in May (93.2 mm) and the minimum in March (65.1 mm). During the summer, the average precipitation is 86.9 mm, with the highest recorded in June (104.7 mm) and the lowest in August (74.2 mm). In the autumn, the average precipitation is the highest at 83.7 mm, with the maximum in September (95.4 mm) and the minimum in October (74.9 mm).

In different climatological seasons, a nearly balanced trend of precipitation is observed, with certain seasonal increases and decreases in precipitation levels during the period from 1992 to 2022. Over the thirty-year period, an increase in precipitation was observed during the spring and winter seasons, while precipitation decreased during the summer and autumn seasons. Specifically, from 1992 to 2022, the amount of precipitation during the autumn decreased by 17 mm, while precipitation during the summer decreased by 6 mm. During the analyzed period, precipitation during the winter increased by 9 mm, and the same 9 mm increase in precipitation was observed during the spring.

Fig. 5.58. Average precipitation amounts by climatological seasons for the period 1992-2022.

Analyzing the annual precipitation at the Križeviči site for the period from 1992 to 2022, the linear trend shows a decrease of 46 mm. Within this thirty-year period, there have been annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of precipitation amounts. The average long-term value is 980 mm of precipitation. The highest annual precipitation was recorded in 1999, with a total of 1291.8 mm, while the lowest amount was 714.8 mm in 2022. Out of the analyzed period, there were 15 years with annual precipitation exceeding the long-term average, while 16 years had lower amounts.

Fig. 5.59. Annual precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of the maximum recorded precipitation for the period from 1992 to 2022 at the Križeviči is 27.0 mm. The highest precipitation values occur in June, with an average maximum of 42.7 mm. The lowest average monthly value of maximum precipitation was recorded in March, at 17.4 mm. The average monthly maximum precipitation for the winter is 22.5 mm, with the lowest recorded in February at 15.1 mm, and the highest in December at 27.6 mm. The average monthly maximum precipitation for the spring is 24.4 mm, with the lowest in March (17.4 mm) and the highest in May (33.4 mm). During the summer, the average monthly maximum precipitation is 36.0 mm. The highest average monthly maximum precipitation is in June (42.7 mm), while the lowest is in August (32.1 mm). The average monthly maximum precipitation for the autumn is 25.2 mm, with the highest in September (34.9 mm) and the lowest in October (22.4 mm).

Fig.5.60. Average monthly values of maximum precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of precipitation maximum for the period from 1992 to 2022 at the Križevíci is 66.2 mm. The highest recorded precipitation amount of 108.0 mm was observed in 2003. The lowest maximum precipitation, recorded at 39.6 mm, occurred in March 1993. Extreme maximum precipitation values during the thirty-year period were recorded for the following months: January: 49.1 mm (2007), February: 59.5 mm (2012), March: 39.6 mm (1993), April: 51.5 mm (2017), May: 81.5 mm (2014), June: 77.9 mm (2009), July: 55.9 mm (2016), August: 55.8 mm (2005), September: 68.2 mm (1996), October: 108.0 mm (2003), November: 64.8 mm (2021), December: 83.5 mm (1999).

Fig. 5.61. Maximum monthly precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the maximum recorded precipitation on an annual level for the period from 1992 to 2022 is 55.8 mm. The highest recorded annual maximum precipitation of 108.0 mm occurred in 2003, while the lowest annual maximum value of 32.9 mm was registered in October 2000. During the reference period, 18 years showed lower values of the maximum recorded precipitation compared to the long-term average. The linear trend analysis reveals an increase in the maximum recorded precipitation by 7.9 mm, with 5 years out of the last 10 having annual maximum exceeding the long-term average.

Fig. 5.62. Extreme maximum precipitation values on an annual basis for the period 1992-2022.

At the Križeviči location, the average number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is 15.5. The highest number of such days, 17.7, was recorded in December. The minimum value for this precipitation indicator (average of 12.7 days) was observed in August. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm is slightly lower, at 11.4, with the maximum occurring in May (average of 12.8 days) and the minimum in August (average of 9.3 days). The amount of precipitation ≥ 5.0 mm occurs on average for 8.2 days per month. The maximum number of days with this precipitation indicator was recorded in April (average of 9.3 days), while the minimum occurred in December (average of 5.5 days). The average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 4.4. The highest number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm was 4.9, recorded in December, while the minimum was 3.4, recorded in February. Precipitation values ≥ 20.0 mm occur on average over 1.4 days per month. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm is 2 (average monthly value for September), while the minimum is 0.8 (average monthly value for April). The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm is 0.04. The maximum values for this precipitation amount were recorded in May and November, both with an average of 0.3 days.

Fig. 5.63. Average monthly values of the number of days with precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

On an annual basis, precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm occurs on average for 15.5 days, with a maximum of 18 days recorded in 1995 and a minimum of 13 days in 2000. Precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm occurs on average for 11.4 days annually. The maximum value of 13.6 days was recorded in 2002, while the minimum of 9.6 days was observed in 2008. On average, precipitation ≥ 5.0 mm occurs for 8.2 days annually, with the maximum number of days, 9.8, recorded in 2018, and the minimum of 7.3 days observed in 2015. Precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm occurs on average for 4.4 days per year. The maximum of 5.6 days was registered in 1999, while the minimum of 3.3 days was recorded in 2015. On average, precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm occurs for 1.4 days annually. The maximum of 2.1 days with this precipitation indicator was recorded in 2017, while the minimum of 0.9 days occurred in 2003. Precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm occurs on average for 0.04 days annually, with maximum values of 0.2 days recorded in 2018 and 2021. A linear trend on an annual scale revealed a growth rate of 0.2 days for precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm and 0.1 day for precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm. A decline rate of 0.3 days was observed for precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm, 0.3 days for precipitation ≥ 5.0 mm, and 0.2 days for precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm, while the number of days for precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm remained completely balanced.

Fig. 5.64. Average annual values of the number of days with precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly snowfall for the period with recorded snow cover (2015-2022) is 6.3 cm. The months without snow cover are May, June, July, August, September, and October. The highest amount of snowfall occurs in January, with an average monthly value of 19.2 cm. During the winter, an average of 16 cm of snow falls, with the maximum in January (annual maximum snowfall) and a minimum in February (11.9 cm). In the spring, an average of 7.8 cm of snow falls, with the maximum in March (13.8 cm) and no snow in May. There is no snow in the summer, while in the autumn, snow is observed only in November, with an average monthly value of 4.1 cm.

Fig. 5.65. Average monthly snow cover height values for the period 2015-2022.

From 2015 to 2022, a linear decrease of 27.0 cm in snow cover depth was observed at the Križeviči site. Within the analyzed period, there were annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of snow depth. The long-term average snow depth is 75.6 cm. The highest annual precipitation total was recorded in 2017, amounting to 130.2 cm, while the lowest total was recorded in 2016 at 44.9 cm.

Fig. 5.66. Average annual snow cover height values for the period 2015-2022.

The average maximum snow cover depth for the period 2015–2022 was 14.8 cm. During this period, the maximum monthly extreme snow cover depth was 41.7 cm, recorded in March 2015. The months without snow cover were May, June, July, August, September, and October. In the seven-year period of snow depth measurements, the maximum values were recorded in the following months: January 30.8 cm (2017), February 19.1 cm (2020), March 41.7 cm (2015), April 32.1 cm (2017), November 12.9 cm (2021), and December 41.4 cm (2017).

Fig. 5.67. Maximum snow cover heights by month for the period 2015-2022.

An analysis of the available data revealed a decrease in the maximum snow cover depth by 15.6 cm in the period from 2015 to 2022. The average maximum snow cover depth per year is 26.5 cm. The maximum annual snow cover depth was 41.7 cm, measured in 2015, while the minimum value was 14.8 cm, recorded in 2016.

Fig.5.68. Maximum snow cover depth on an annual basis for the period 2015-2022.

5.1.3 BLIDINJE – DUGO POLJE

5.1.3.1 INSOLATION

The average monthly insolation at the Dugo Polje – Blidinje location for the period 1992–2022 is 153.6 hours. The lowest average monthly insolation was recorded in December, with 54.9 hours, while the highest average insolation was recorded in July, with 255.3 hours.

Fig.5.69. Average monthly insolation for the period 1992-2022.

The average insolation for the winter is 70.1 hours, with the lowest number of sunshine hours at Blidinje in December (annual minimum), and the highest in February with 89.4 hours. The average sum of sunshine hours for the spring is 168.3 hours. The lowest sunshine in the spring occurs in March with 144.3 hours, and the highest in May with 195.9 hours. During the summer climatological season, the average sunshine is 243.6 hours, with the highest sunshine in July (annual maximum of 255.3 hours) and the lowest in August (248.3 hours). The average monthly sunshine in the autumn is 133 hours, with maximum values in September (178.3 hours) and the minimum in November with an average of 80.1 hours of sunshine.

Fig. 5.70. Average sunshine by season for the period 1992-2022.

The average multi-annual sunshine value is 1843.0 hours. Eighteen years have an annual sunshine greater than the average multi-annual value, while thirteen years have a value below the multi-annual average. In the last 10 years, 7 years had higher sunshine, while only 3 years had lower insolation compared to the multi-annual average. The maximum average annual insolation of 2094.7 hours was recorded in 2012, while the minimum average annual insolation of 1578.3 hours was recorded in 2010. The increase in sunshine over the last thirty years (1992-2022) has been constant and correlates with solar radiation and the rise in air temperatures. The linear trend indicates that sunshine has increased by 46 hours during this period.

Fig. 5.71. Total annual insolation for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.3.2 RADIATION

The average monthly radiation value for the period 1992–2022 is 103.8 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly radiation was recorded in December, with 39.9 kWh/m², while the highest average solar radiation was recorded in July, with 178.5 kWh/m². The average radiation for the winter is 46.3 kWh/m², with the lowest value in December, which also represents the annual minimum, and the highest in February with 56.8 kWh/m². The average sum of radiation for the spring is 124.4 kWh/m². The lowest radiation in the spring occurs in March with 96.7 kWh/m², and the highest in May with 152.9 kWh/m². During the summer climatological season, the average radiation is 169.7 kWh/m², with the highest in July (178.5 kWh/m²) and the lowest in August (163.7 kWh/m²). The average monthly radiation in the autumn is 74.8 kWh/m², with maximum values in September (108.5 kWh/m²) and the minimum in solar radiation in November (40.6 kWh/m²).

Fig. 5.72. Average monthly radiation for the period 1992-2022.

A linear trend has shown an increase in radiation at the Dugo Polje – Blidinje location from 1992 to 2022, amounting to 38 kWh/m². The average multi-annual radiation value is 1245.5 kWh/m². Eighteen years have an annual radiation higher than the average multi-annual value, while thirteen years have a value below the multi-annual average. In the last 10 years, 7 years had higher radiation, while 3 years had lower radiation compared to the multi-annual average. The maximum average annual radiation of 1419.6 kWh/m² was recorded in 2000, while the minimum average annual solar radiation of 1069.2 kWh/m² was recorded in 2010.

Fig. 5.73. Annual radiation for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.3.3 AIR TEMPERATURE

The average monthly temperature at the Blidinje – Dugo Polje location for the period 1992–2022 is 6.9°C. The lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January, with -3.0°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in July, with 16.9°C. The average temperature for the winter is -2.0°C, with the lowest temperature recorded in January at -3.0°C, and the highest in December at -1.1°C. The average temperature for the spring is 5.8°C. The lowest average temperature in the spring is in March with 1.0°C, and the highest in May with 10.5°C. During the summer climatological season, the average temperatures are 15.9°C. The average monthly temperature recorded in June is 14.3°C (the lowest average monthly temperature of the summer), while July and August have almost identical average monthly temperatures of 16.9°C (July) and 16.7°C (August). The average monthly temperature in the autumn is 8.0°C. The coldest month is November with 3.7°C, while the warmest is September with 12.2°C.

Fig. 5.74. Average monthly temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The general trend of rising temperatures over the past thirty years (1992-2022) at the Blidinje location shows a consistent increase. A linear trend indicates that the temperature has risen with a warming value of 1.3°C . The average multi-annual temperature value is 6.9°C . Eighteen years have an annual temperature higher than the average multi-annual value, while thirteen years have a value below the multi-annual average. In the last 12 years, there has been an uninterrupted sequence of years with average annual temperatures higher than the multi-annual average. The maximum average annual temperature of 8.1°C was recorded in 2022, while the minimum average annual temperature of 5.6°C was recorded in 2005.

Fig. 5.75. Average annual temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

In addition to the overall increase in temperatures, a linear trend has shown a rise in temperatures (at different values) across all climatological seasons. Specifically, the temperature increase in the summer is 1.5°C, in autumn 1.3°C, in spring 0.8°C, and in winter 1.8°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter is 1.5°C, recorded in 2014, while the minimum temperature of -5.2°C was recorded in 2012. The maximum average annual temperature during the spring is 7.7°C, recorded in 2018. The lowest average annual temperature for the spring is 3.6°C, recorded in 1997. The maximum average annual temperature for the summer is 19.0°C, recorded in 2012, while the minimum temperature values were recorded in 2005, with an average value of 14.4°C. During the winter, the maximum temperatures were recorded in 2012, with an average value of 10.2°C, while the minimum temperature values of 5.2°C were recorded in 2007.

Fig. 5.76. Average temperature values by season for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum monthly temperature for the period 1992–2022 is 19.9°C. The lowest average maximum monthly temperature was recorded in January at 9.6°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in August at 30.1°C. The average maximum temperature for the winter is 10.1°C, with the lowest maximum temperature recorded in January at 9.6°C, and the highest in February at 10.7°C. The average maximum temperature for the spring is 19.9°C. The lowest average maximum temperature in the spring is in March at 15.1°C, and the highest in May at 23.6°C. During the summer climatological season, the average maximum temperature is 29.2°C. The lowest average monthly maximum temperature was recorded in June at 27.5°C. The highest maximum temperature during this climatological season was recorded in August at 30.1°C. The average monthly maximum temperature during the autumn is 20.6°C. The month with the lowest maximum temperature in this season is November at 16.1°C, while the highest value was recorded in September at 25.2°C.

Fig. 5.77. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average values of extreme maximum recorded temperatures for the period 1992–2022 at the Dugo polje location are 24.7°C. The highest air temperature was recorded in August 2017 (34.7°C), while the lowest maximum temperature was recorded in January 2002 (13.6°C). On a monthly level, the extreme maximum temperatures in the thirty-year period had the following values: January 13.6°C (2002), February 17.5°C (2021), March 24.1°C (2001), April 23.9°C (2012), May 26.8°C (1994), June 32.2°C (2022), July 33.3°C (2022), August 34.7°C (2017), September 31.8°C (2015), October 23.3°C (2012), November 21.3°C (2022), and December 13.8°C (2014). From these indicators, it is evident that in 9 months of the last 10 years, record maximum temperature values were recorded.

Fig. 5.78. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Based on the collected and analyzed meteorological data, an increase in extreme maximum air temperature values has been observed for the period 1992-2022, amounting to 2.0°C. The average value of the maximum measured temperatures for the period 1992-2022 is 31.0°C. The highest maximum temperature of 34.7°C was recorded in August 2007, while the lowest maximum temperature of 27.5°C was recorded in July 1995.

Fig. 5.79. Maximum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures of $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ records the highest values during the summer months, while the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures of $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ shows increased values during the winter months. The average number of days with extreme maximum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 3.4 days per month. The maximum number of days with $T_{\text{max}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 11.4 days recorded in January. The months from May to September do not have maximum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum temperatures $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a higher average monthly number of days compared to the previously analyzed indicator. The average monthly value is 3.6 days. The maximum number of days with $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 16.6 days recorded in August. December, January, February, and March do not have extreme maximum air temperatures $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum air temperatures $T_{\text{max}} \geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 0.5 days, with the maximum average number of days (2.6) in August. During the winter, spring, and autumn seasons (except for September), there are no days with a maximum air temperature $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.80. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperature values in the period 1992-2022.

The average minimum monthly temperature at the Dugo Polje-Blidinje location for the period 1992–2022 is -3.8°C . The lowest average minimum monthly temperature was recorded in January, at -14.4°C , while the highest was measured in July, at 6.8°C . The average minimum temperature for the winter is -12.9°C . The lowest value of the average minimum temperature was recorded in January (annual minimum), and the highest in December, at -11.6°C . The average minimum temperature measured for the spring is -5.1°C . The lowest average minimum temperature in the spring was in March, at -10.6°C , and the highest in May, at 0.2°C . During the summer climatological season, the average minimum temperatures are 5.6°C . The lowest average minimum temperature for the season was measured in June, at 3.8°C , while the highest average minimum temperature was recorded in July, at 6.8°C . The average monthly minimum temperature in the autumn is -2.8°C . According to this indicator, the coldest month of the season is November, at -7.5°C , while the warmest is September, with 2.0°C .

Fig. 5.81. Average monthly minimum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average values of extreme minimum temperatures for the period 1992–2022 are -10.1°C . The lowest average extreme minimum temperature was -23.7°C , recorded in January 2006. The highest average extreme minimum temperature was recorded in July 2000, at 3.0°C . During the mentioned thirty-year period, extreme minimum average monthly temperature values were recorded as follows: January -23.7°C (2006), February -21.8°C (2012), March -22.2°C (2005), April -11.2°C (2003), May -3.1°C (2005), June -2.2°C (1997), July 3.0°C (2000), August 1.6°C (2006), September -2.0°C (2018), October -9.6°C (1997), November -13.9°C (1995), and December -16.5°C (2009). From these indicators, it is evident that extreme minimum temperature records were set in only two months in the last 10 years, while the remaining minimum values were recorded in the first two decades of the observed period.

Fig. 5.82. Minimum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the measured minimum temperatures for the period 1992–2022 is -16.5°C . The highest minimum temperature of -11.8°C was recorded in January 2020, while the lowest minimum temperature of -23.7°C was recorded in January 2006. Although fluctuations were observed on an annual basis, extreme minimum temperature values show a tendency to increase. The linear trend indicates a growth value of 0.4°C , which is significantly lower compared to the trend of increasing extreme maximum temperatures.

Fig. 5.83. Minimum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Analysis of the available data reveals significant differences in the number of days with minimum temperatures of $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 5 cm above the ground. Extreme minimum temperatures $T_{\text{min}} \leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 1 day. The maximum number of days with temperatures $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 4 days, recorded in January. The months from April to September do not experience minimum temperatures of $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme minimum temperatures $T_{\text{min}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a monthly average of 9.6 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 24.7 days, recorded in January. June, July, and August have no days with extreme minimum air temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. The number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ has an average monthly value of 0 days, with the maximum average number of days being 0.1 in July and August. In all other months, there are no days with minimum temperatures $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Indicators for the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 5 cm ($T_{\text{min}5}$) above the ground have values quite similar to those for temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. The monthly average number of days

with this temperature indicator is 9.9 days. The maximum value for the number of days with $T_{min5} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was recorded in January, with 27.0 days. The months of the summer have no days when the temperature at 5 cm above the ground surface is $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.84. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.3.4 RELATIVE HUMIDITY

The average monthly relative humidity for the period 1992–2022 at Blidinje is 78.2%. The lowest average monthly relative humidity was recorded in April, at 71.4%, while the highest relative humidity was recorded in December, at 85.0%. The average relative humidity for the winter is 83.1%, with the lowest values measured in February at 80.3%, and the highest in December (annual maximum). The average measured values of relative humidity for the spring are somewhat lower, at 73.9%. The lowest average relative humidity in the spring was recorded in April (annual minimum), while the highest values were measured in March at 75.7%. During the summer climatological season, the average relative humidity is 74.9%. The highest recorded value was in June at 76.1%, while the lowest was in July at 74.2%. The average monthly relative humidity is slightly higher in the autumn, at 81.1%. The lowest relative humidity during this season was in September at 79.6%, while the highest was in November at 82.7%.

Fig. 5.85. Average monthly values of air relative humidity for the period 1992-2022.

The average values of the maximum average air humidity for the Dugo Polje-Blidinje location for the period 1992–2022 are 88.3%. The highest average air humidity during the analysed thirty-year period was 92.9%, recorded in December 2022. The lowest maximum average air humidity was measured in April 2014, at 81.4%. During this thirty-year period, the maximum values of average air humidity were recorded as follows: January 92.0% (2019), February 90.5% (2018), March 92.9% (2013), April 81.4% (2014), May 85.0% (2019), June 85.8% (2018), July 83.5% (1994), August 89.6% (1995), September 89.4% (1995), October 88.1% (2015), November 90.6% (1998), and December 92.9% (2022).

Fig. 5.86. Maximum average monthly values of air rel.humid. for the period 1992-2022.

The average values of the minimum average air humidity for the period 1992–2022 are 76.4%. The highest minimum average air humidity at Blidinje during the analysed thirty-year period was 76.4%, recorded in January 2008. The lowest minimum average air humidity was measured in August 2012, at 58.1%. During the analysed period, the minimum values of average air humidity recorded for each month were as follows: January 76.4% (2008), February 70.9% (1998), March 62.4% (2022), April 60.0% (2007), May 68.2% (1992), June 65.9% (2000), July 62.1% (2000), August 58.1% (2012), September 69.4% (1992), October 68.9% (1993), November 74.7% (2009), and December 73.3% (2016).

Fig. 5.87. Minimum aver. monthly values of air rel. humid. for the period 1992-2022.

Over the past thirty years (1992–2022), air relative humidity at Blidinje has shown a balanced value with a slight increase. The linear trend indicates that relative humidity has risen by 2.1% over the examined thirty-year period. The average multi-year relative humidity value is 78.2%. The average relative humidity values above the multi-year average occurred in 16 years, while 15 years recorded values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, only 7 years have had higher values compared to the multi-year average. The maximum average annual relative humidity of 84.6% was recorded in 1995, while the minimum average annual relative humidity of 71.4% was recorded in 2000.

Fig. 5.88. Average annual values of air relative humidity for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.3.4 PRECIPITATION

The average annual precipitation for the period 1992–2022 is 129.6 mm. The least amount of precipitation occurs during the summer months, while a significantly higher amount is recorded during the remaining three climatological seasons. Specifically, the lowest average precipitation is in July (48.9 mm), while the highest amount is in December (229.2 mm).

Fig. 5.89. Average monthly precipitation totals for the period 1992-2022.

During the winter, the highest amount of precipitation is recorded, with an average of 183.5 mm. The maximum precipitation for this season occurs in December, which also represents the annual maximum, and the minimum in February with 158.6 mm. In the spring, the average precipitation is 106.7 mm, with a maximum in March (114.3 mm) and a minimum in May (95.8 mm). During the summer, the average precipitation is 75.6 mm, with the highest amount recorded in June (98.8 mm) and the lowest in July (annual minimum). In the autumn, 152.6 mm of precipitation is recorded, with the maximum in November (170.8 mm) and the minimum in September (128.2 mm). Over the period of 1992–2022, certain seasonal variations in precipitation amounts were observed, with increases in spring and winter precipitation and decreases in summer and autumn precipitation. Specifically, during the thirty-year period, precipitation in the autumn decreased by 17 mm, while summer precipitation decreased by 13 mm. In contrast, winter precipitation increased by 41 mm, and spring precipitation increased by 16 mm.

Fig. 5.90. Average precip. totals by climatological seasons for the period 1992-2022.

A linear trend shows a slight increase in precipitation at Blidinje for the period 1992–2022, amounting to 83.2 mm. Within this thirty-year period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of precipitation amounts. The average multi-year precipitation value is 1555.2 mm. The maximum annual precipitation total was recorded in 2010, amounting to 2584.3 mm, while the minimum was 1115.2 mm in 2011. In the analysed period, 14 years had annual precipitation totals higher than the long-term average, while 17 years had lower totals.

Fig. 5.91. Annual precipitation totals for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly values of the maximum recorded precipitation for the period 1992-2022 are 41.4 mm. The highest precipitation values at the Dugo Polje - Blidinje location occur in December, with an average maximum of 99.8 mm. The lowest average monthly maximum precipitation is recorded in July, with 4.3 mm. The average monthly maximum precipitation for the winter is 81.9 mm, with the lowest values in January (68.5 mm) and the highest in December, which represents the annual maximum. The average monthly maximum precipitation for the spring is 21.2 mm, with the lowest values in May (17.7 mm) and the highest in March (26.5 mm). During the summer climatological season, the average monthly maximum precipitation is at its lowest, amounting to 17.7 mm. The highest value in this season is in August (26.0 mm), while the lowest is in July (4.3 mm), which also represents the annual minimum. The average monthly maximum precipitation for the autumn is 44.8 mm, with the highest values recorded in October (60.5 mm) and the lowest in September (27.4 mm).

Fig. 5.92. Average monthly maximum precipitation values for the period 1992-2022.

The average extreme maximum precipitation values for the period 1992-2022 are 81.0 mm. The highest precipitation on Blidinje of 174.0 mm was measured on 2nd December 2004. The lowest extreme maximum precipitation of 25.4 mm was measured on 28th July 2010. During this thirty-year period, extreme monthly maximum precipitation values were recorded in January 106.5 mm (2015), February 119.7 mm (2012), March 49.5 mm (2004), April 48.9 mm (2018), May 69.1 mm (2014), June 87.7 mm (2009), July 25.4 mm (2010), August 66.9 mm (2020), September 80.8 mm (2020), October 142.8 mm (2003), November 112.9 mm (2021), and December 174.0 mm (2004).

Fig. 5.93. Maximum monthly precipitation totals for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the maximum recorded precipitation on an annual basis for the period 1992-2022 is 105.7 mm. The highest value of the maximum annual precipitation, 174.0 mm, was recorded in 2004, while the lowest maximum value, 78.9 mm, was recorded in February 2013. A linear trend indicates an increase in the annual maximum precipitation totals by 2.7 mm.

Fig. 5.94. Maximum annual precipitation totals for the period 1992-2022.

At the Dugo Polje location, based on the collected and analysed data, significant differences are observed in the average values of the number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm, ≥ 1.0 mm, ≥ 5.0 mm, ≥ 10.0 mm, ≥ 20.0 mm, and ≥ 50.0 mm. The highest average number of days with all of the aforementioned precipitation amounts is observed during the winter period, while somewhat lower values are recorded during the summer, autumn, and spring periods.

The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is 15.5. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 23.0, which corresponds to the average monthly value for December, while the minimum value of days (9.2) was recorded in July. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm is 11.8, with a maximum of 18.2 days in December and a minimum of 6.2 days in July. Precipitation amounts ≥ 5.0 mm have an average monthly value of 7 days. The maximum number of days with this precipitation amount was recorded in February (on average 11.1 days), while the minimum was recorded in July (on average 2.3 days). The average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 4.6. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 7.9, observed in December, while the minimum

number of days with this precipitation amount is 2.0, recorded in July. Precipitation amounts ≥ 20.0 mm occur on average for 2.3 days per month. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm is 5.6 (average monthly value for December), while the minimum number of days is 1 (average monthly value for February). The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm is 0.3. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 1.5, which represents the average monthly value for December. Several months (May, June, and July) have no days with precipitation above 50.0 mm in the analysed period of 1992-2022.

Fig. 5.95. Average monthly values of the number of days with precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly maximum snow depth for the period 2015-2022 is 13.9 cm. The months without snow cover are May, June, July, August, and September. The highest snow depth is recorded in February, with an average monthly value of 35.4 cm. During the winter, an average of 32.5 cm of snow falls, with the maximum snow depth occurring in February (annual maximum) and the minimum in December (28.1 cm of snow). During the spring, an average of 17.8 cm of snow falls, with the maximum in March (32.2 cm) and the minimum in May (0 cm). There is no snow precipitation during the summer. In the autumn, September sees no snow, while October (1.8 cm) and November (13.9 cm) are the months with snow cover.

Fig. 5.96. Average monthly values of the maximum snow cover depth for the period 2015-2022.

A linear trend indicates a decrease in the maximum snow cover depth by 48.2 cm between 2015 and 2022. Within the analysed period, there are certain annual oscillations in the increase and decrease of snow cover depth. The average multi-annual value of the maximum snow depth is 166.3 cm. The highest annual precipitation total was recorded in 2017, amounting to 210 cm, while the lowest value of 122 cm was recorded in 2020.

Fig. 5.97. Total maximum snow cover depth on an annual basis for 2015-2022.

The average maximum snow cover depth for the period 2015-2022 is 27.5 cm. During this period, the maximum monthly extreme snow cover depth was 70 cm, which occurred in January 2019. The months without snow cover are May, June, July, August, and September. During this seven-year period of snow cover measurements, the following maximum values were recorded on a monthly basis: January 70 cm (2019), February 62 cm (2018), March 57 cm (2018), April 38 cm (2017), October 7 cm (2016), November 36 cm (2017), and December 60 cm (2018).

Fig. 5.98. Maximum snow cover depth by month for the period 2015-2022.

As the linear trend has generally indicated a decrease in precipitation totals, the same methodological concept has shown a reduction in the maximum snow cover depth by 8.6 cm in the period from 2015 to 2022.

Fig. 5.99. Maximum snow cover depth on an annual basis for the period 2015-2022.

The average value of the maximum snow cover depth on an annual basis is 47.3 cm. The maximum snow cover depth for the year is 70 cm, measured in 2019, while the minimum value is 28 cm, recorded in 2016.

5.1.4 RADIMLJA

5.1.4.1 INSOLATION

The average monthly insolation for Radimlja for the period 1992-2022 is 203 hours. The lowest average monthly insolation was recorded in December, amounting to 114.1 hours, while the highest average monthly insolation was recorded in July, with a value of 334.8 hours.

Fig. 5.100. Average monthly insolation for the period 1992–2022.

This indicator shows significant differences across various periods of the year, which is the result of influencing factors. Throughout the year at the Radimlja site, not a single month has an average of fewer than 100 hours of sunshine, although there are pronounced seasonal fluctuations. More specifically, the average insolation for the winter is 122.3 hours, with the lowest number of sunshine hours in December at 114.1 hours, which also represents the annual minimum, and the highest in February at 131.6 hours. The average sunshine duration for the spring is 206.2 hours. The lowest sunshine duration in the spring is in March at 175.3 hours, and the highest is in May at 251.8 hours. During the summer climatological season, the average sunshine duration is 311.3 hours, with the highest sunshine duration in July (334.8 hours) and the lowest in June (287.6 hours). The average monthly sunshine duration in the autumn is 172.2 hours, with maximum values in September (224.4 hours) and a minimum in November, which has fewer than 114.1 hours of sunshine.

Fig. 5.101. Average sunshine duration by season for the period 1992–2022.

The values of annual sunshine duration over the last thirty years (1992–2022) have shown a consistent increase. Specifically, it has been determined that sunshine duration during this period increased by 33.6 hours. Within this thirty-year period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the rise and fall of sunshine. The long-term average annual sunshine duration is 2436 hours. Fourteen years recorded an average annual sunshine duration higher than the long-term average, while seventeen years recorded values below the long-term average. In the last 10 years, 4 years had higher and 6 years had lower insolation compared to the long-term average. The maximum average annual insolation of 2663.9 hours was recorded in 2003, while the minimum average annual insolation of 2168.8 hours was recorded in 2002.

Fig. 5.102. Total annual insolation for the period 1992–2022.

5.1.4.2 RADIATION

The average monthly solar radiation at the Radimlja site for the period 1992–2022 is 137.0 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly solar radiation was recorded in November at 57.8 kWh/m², while the highest average radiation was recorded in July at 234.0 kWh/m². The average radiation for the winter is 81.4 kWh/m², with the lowest in January at 77.4 kWh/m² and the highest in February at 83.7 kWh/m². The average total radiation for the spring is 152.6 kWh/m². The lowest radiation in the spring is in March at 117.4 kWh/m², and the highest is in May at 196.5 kWh/m². During the summer climatological season, the average radiation is 217.4 kWh/m², with the highest solar radiation values in July (234.0 kWh/m², which also represents the annual maximum) and the lowest in August (205.2 kWh/m²). The average monthly radiation in the autumn is 96.6 kWh/m², with maximum values in September (136.5 kWh/m²) and a minimum in November (57.8 kWh/m²).

Fig. 5.103. Average monthly solar radiation for the period 1992–2022.

Over the last thirty years, solar radiation at the Radimlja site has shown a consistent increase. During the period 1992–2022, a linear trend analysis revealed an increase in solar radiation by 23 kWh/m². The long-term average annual solar radiation is 1644 kWh/m². Fourteen years recorded an average annual solar radiation higher than the long-term average, while seventeen years recorded values below the long-term average. In the last 10 years, 4 years had higher and 6 years had lower radiation compared to the long-term average. The maximum average annual solar radiation of 1811.7 kWh/m² was recorded in 2003, while the minimum average annual solar radiation of 1459.6 kWh/m² was recorded in 2002.

Fig. 5.104. Total annual radiation for the period 1992–2022.

5.1.4.3 AIR TEMPERATURE

The average monthly temperatures throughout the year at the Radimlja site do not fall below 0°C, which differs somewhat from other analysed locations in Bosnia and Herzegovina and is the result of the influence of climatic factors (latitude, altitude, and maritime influences of the Adriatic Sea). Specifically, the average monthly temperature at the Radimlja site for the period 1992–2022 is 15.7°C. The lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January at 5.8°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in July at 26.5°C. The average temperature for the winter is 6.7°C, with the lowest temperature recorded in January (the annual minimum) and the highest in February at 7.4°C. The average temperature for the spring is 14.7°C. The lowest average temperature in the spring is in March at 10.5°C, and the highest are in May at 19.3°C. During the summer climatological season, the average temperatures are 25.5°C. The highest average monthly temperatures were recorded in July (26.5°C) and August (26.4°C), while the lowest average monthly temperature in the summer was recorded in June at 23.7°C. The average monthly temperature in the autumn is 15.9°C. The lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in November at 11.0°C, while the highest was in September with a monthly average of 20.7°C.

Fig. 5.105. Average monthly temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

Over the last thirty years (1992–2022), temperatures at the Radimlja site, as well as at other locations, have shown a consistent increase. Based on a linear trend analysis, it has been determined that temperatures have risen with a warming value of 1.3°C . The long-term average annual temperature is 15.7°C . Nineteen years recorded average annual temperatures higher than the long-term average, while twelve years recorded values below the long-term average. Over the last twelve years, average annual temperatures have consistently been higher than the long-term average. The maximum average annual temperature of 16.9°C was recorded in 2022, while the minimum average annual temperature of 14.6°C was recorded in 2005.

Fig. 5.106. Average annual temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

In addition to the overall increase in temperatures on an annual level, a linear trend analysis has identified temperature rises (with varying magnitudes) across all climatological seasons. Specifically, the temperature increase in the summer is 1.6°C, in autumn 1.7°C, in spring 0.8°C, and in winter 1.2°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter is 8.9°C, recorded in 2014, while the minimum temperature is 4.1°C, recorded in 2012. The maximum average annual temperature during the spring is 16.4°C, recorded in 2007. The lowest average annual temperature for the spring is 13.0°C, recorded in 1995. The maximum average annual temperature during the summer is 27.8°C, recorded in 2003, while the minimum values were recorded in 2014 with an average of 23.4°C. During the autumn, the highest temperatures were recorded in 2018 with an average value of 17.8°C, while the lowest temperatures of 14.0°C were recorded in 1996.

Fig. 5.107. Average seasonal temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average monthly maximum temperatures at the Radimlja site for the period 1992–2022 are 27.5°C. The lowest average monthly maximum temperature was recorded in January at 15.4°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in August at 39.1°C. The average maximum air temperature for the winter is 16.7°C. The lowest recorded value of average maximum temperatures during this season was in January (the annual minimum), while the highest value was recorded in February at 18.7°C. The recorded average maximum temperature for the spring is 27.4°C. The lowest average maximum temperature in the spring is in March at 23.2°C, and the highest are in May at 31.6°C. During the summer climatological season, the average maximum temperatures are 38.2°C. The highest average monthly maximum temperature was recorded in August (39.1°C) and July (39.0°C), while in June, the maximum temperatures are slightly lower at 36.6°C. The average monthly maximum temperatures during autumn are 27.8°C. The coldest month during this season is November at 22.2°C, while the warmest is September at 33.4°C.

Fig. 5.108. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average values of extreme maximum recorded temperatures for the period 1992–2022 are 31.8°C. The maximum air temperature recorded at the Radimlja site was 43.1°C, measured on 24 August 2007. The lowest maximum temperature was recorded on 6 December 2020 and was 19.4°C. During this thirty-year period, the following extreme maximum temperatures were recorded on a monthly basis: January: 20.0°C (2022), February: 24.9°C (2021), March: 26.6°C (2019), April: 31.6°C (2018), May: 35.6°C (2008), June: 41.2°C (2006), July: 42.5°C (2007), August: 43.1°C (2007), September: 38.6°C (2008), October: 30.9°C (2012), November: 27.4°C (2022), and December: 19.4°C (2020).

Fig. 5.109. Maximum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average value of the maximum recorded temperatures at the Radimlja site during the period 1992–2022 is 40.0°C. The highest maximum temperature of 43.1°C was recorded in August 2007, while the lowest maximum temperature of 35.6°C was recorded in August 2014. Extreme values of maximum air temperatures, as well as average monthly air temperatures, show an increasing trend. A linear trend analysis determined that the increase in maximum annual air temperatures during the period 1992–2022 was 1.5°C.

Fig. 5.110. Maximum annual air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

Based on the collected data, the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures with values $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was analysed. The number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures ($\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$) records the highest values during the summer months, which is certainly consistent with the average and maximum air temperature trends, while the number of days with air temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ has higher values during the winter. Analysis of the available data reveals significant differences in the number of days with maximum temperatures that are: $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum temperatures with values $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ are almost non-existent throughout the year. The average monthly value for the number of days with this indicator is 0.1. The maximum average number of days with temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 0.3 days, recorded in January. Months from April to November have no maximum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum temperatures with $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a higher average monthly number of days compared to the previously analysed indicator. The average monthly number of days is 11.6. The maximum number of days with temperatures $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 30.2 days, recorded in July. December, January,

and February have no extreme maximum air temperatures with values $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum air temperatures $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 6.6 days. The maximum average number of days with this temperature indicator was recorded in August with a value of 25. The months of January, February, March, November, and December have no days with maximum air temperatures $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.111. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average minimum monthly temperature for the period 1992–2022 is 5.5°C . The lowest average minimum monthly temperature was recorded in January at -3.0°C , while the highest temperature was recorded in July (15.7°C) and August (15.6°C). The average minimum temperature for the winter is -2.4°C , with the lowest temperatures recorded in January (the annual minimum) and the highest in December at -2.1°C . The recorded average minimum temperature for spring is 4.3°C . The lowest average minimum temperature in the spring is in March at 0.1°C , and the highest are in May at 9.0°C . During the summer climatological season, the average maximum temperatures are 14.5°C . The lowest value of the average monthly

minimum temperature during this season was recorded in June (12.2°C), while the highest values were recorded in July and August, which represent the annual maxima for this climatological indicator. The average monthly minimum temperature in the autumn is 5.7°C . The lowest recorded value of average monthly minimum temperatures is in November at 1.2°C , and the highest is in September at 10.4°C .

Fig. 5.112. Average monthly minimum temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average values of extreme minimum recorded temperatures for the period 1992–2022 at the Radimlja site are 1.0°C . The lowest average minimum air temperature was -9.3°C , recorded in January 2017. The highest average minimum temperature was recorded in July 1993 and measured 11.1°C . During this thirty-year period, the following extreme minimum average monthly temperatures were recorded: January: -9.3°C (2017), February: -7.4°C (2012), March: -5.7°C (2005), April: -1.2°C (2003), May: 5.9°C (2019), June: 8.0°C (2005), July: 11.1°C (1993), August: 10.7°C (1995), September: 7.4°C (2008), October: 2.6°C (1997), November: -2.6°C (2004), and December: -7.8°C (2009).

Fig. 5.113. Minimum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the measured minimum temperatures at the Radimlja site for the period 1992-2022 is -4.3°C . The highest minimum (extreme) temperature of -0.9°C was recorded on 16th December 2007. The lowest minimum temperature of -9.3°C was recorded on 8th January 2017. Unlike other temperature-related indicators, the extreme values of minimum temperatures show a tendency to decrease, or a slight increase in numerical values with a negative sign. A linear trend indicates a decrease in the average minimum temperatures from -4.20°C to -4.45°C , representing a decline of -0.25°C over a thirty-year period (1992-2022).

Fig. 5.114. Minimum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Based on the available indicators, data on the number of days with extreme minimum temperatures ($\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$) for the period 1992-2022 were analysed. Due to the geographic location and physical-geographical conditions of the area, no days with extreme minimum temperatures $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ were recorded at the Radimlja site. Extreme minimum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 1.4 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 6.4, recorded in January. The months of May, June, July, August, and September have no days with minimum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. The average number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 3.8. The maximum value for the average number of days with this indicator was recorded in July, with 17 days. The indicators for the number of days with extreme minimum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 5 cm above the ground ($T_{\text{min}5}$) show similar trends to those for the number of days with temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. The average monthly number of days is 2.3 days. The maximum value for the number of days with $T_{\text{min}5} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was recorded in January, with 11.9 days. The months of May, June, July, and August have no days with recorded air temperatures at 5 cm above the ground $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.115. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.4.4 RELATIVE HUMIDITY

The average monthly value of relative air humidity for the Radimlja site for the period 1992–2022 is 62.3%. The lowest average monthly value of relative humidity was recorded in July, at 54.2%, while the highest relative humidity was recorded in November, at 71.1%. The average value of relative humidity for the winter is 64.6%, with the lowest values recorded in February (60.9%) and the highest in December (67.8%). During the spring, the average measured relative humidity is 60.9%, with a minimum average value in March (58.6%) and a maximum average value in May (62.2%). During the summer climatological season, the average relative humidity is 56.5%. The maximum value was recorded in June at 59.7%, and the minimum average value was recorded in July (54.2%). The average monthly value of relative humidity in the autumn is 67.2%. The lowest values of air humidity in the Radimlja area during this season were in September (62.7%), while the highest values were in November (71.1%).

Fig. 5.116. Average monthly values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

At the Radimlja site, the average values of the maximum extreme average relative air humidity for the period 1992–2022 were found to be 78.5%. The highest average humidity value during the analysed thirty-year period was 87.5%, recorded in December 2022. The lowest maximum average humidity value was recorded in June 2020 at 71.6%. Based on the analysed data, it can be observed that in the last ten years, all months have experienced maximum average relative humidity values. Specifically, during the reference period (1992–2022), the maximum average relative humidity values were recorded in: January 81.4% (2014), February 77.2% (2016), March 79.4% (2018), April 71.8% (2012), May 78.5% (2019), June 71.6% (2020), July 75.1% (2014), August 73.5% (2014), September 82.4% (2014), October 78.6% (2020), November 85.2% (2019), and December 87.5% (2022).

Fig. 5.117. Maximum average values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the minimum average relative air humidity for the period 1992–2022 is 49.6%. The highest minimum average relative humidity during the defined period was 59.5%, recorded in November 2001. The lowest minimum average relative humidity (38.3%) was recorded in August 2012. The lowest monthly average relative humidity values were recorded in the following months: January 52.1% (2006), February 43.0% (1993), March 41.6% (1997), April 50.4% (2011), May 55.2% (1994), June 49.2% (2005), July 44.7% (1996), August 38.3% (2012), September 50.6% (2012), October 58.0% (1995), November 59.5% (2001), and December 52.5% (2016). Unlike the maximum average relative humidity values (where most extreme values occurred in the last decade), a reverse trend is observed for the minimum average values. The analysed data shows that in the first two decades, nine months have recorded the lowest average relative humidity values.

Fig. 5.118. Minimum average monthly values of rel. air hum. for the period 1992-2022.

During the analysed period, the relative air humidity at the Radimlja site has been continuously increasing. A linear trend indicates that the relative humidity increased by 8.2% from 1992 to 2022. Within this thirty-year period, there were certain annual oscillations in the increase and decrease of relative humidity values, with the maximum oscillation reaching 16.8%. The average multi-year value of air humidity for the Radimlja site is 62.3%. The average relative humidity values higher than the multi-year average were recorded in 12 years, while 19 years had values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, relative humidity has consistently been above the multi-year average. The highest average annual relative humidity of 73.8% was recorded in 2014, while the lowest average annual value of 57.0% was recorded in 2003.

Fig. 5.119. Average annual values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.4.5 PRECIPITATION

The average monthly precipitation in the Radimlja area for the period 1992–2022 is 119.4 mm. The smallest average amount of precipitation occurs in July (52.9 mm), while the largest amount of precipitation occurs in November (191.1 mm).

Fig. 5.120. Average monthly precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

During the winter, the average precipitation is 153.1 mm, with a maximum in December of around 190.0 mm and a minimum in February of 124.8 mm. During the spring, the average precipitation is also 108.7 mm, with a maximum in April (122.9 mm) and a minimum in May (87.9 mm). In the summer, the average precipitation is slightly lower than in the previous seasons, with an average of 60 mm. The highest precipitation occurs in June (67.1 mm), while the lowest is in July (52.9 mm). In the autumn, the average precipitation is 156.0 mm, with a maximum in November, which is the annual maximum, and a minimum in September at 134.6 mm. Over the thirty-year period from 1992 to 2022, an increase in precipitation during the spring and winter seasons was observed, while a decrease in precipitation was noted during the summer and autumn. During the autumn climatological season, precipitation decreased by 21 mm, while during the summer, it decreased by 10 mm. In the same period (1992-2022), the amount of precipitation during the winter increased by 33 mm, while during the spring, it increased by 25 mm.

Fig. 5.121. Average precipitation by climatological seasons for the period 1992-2022.

When analysing annual precipitation totals for the period 1992-2022, a linear trend indicates an increase of 90 mm. Within this thirty-year period, there were certain annual oscillations in the increase and decrease of precipitation. The average multi-year value is 1433 mm of precipitation. The maximum annual precipitation sum was recorded in 2010, at 2490.7 mm, while the minimum value was 872.5 mm in 2011. In the analysed period, 13 years recorded annual precipitation totals greater than the multi-year average, while 18 years had lower totals.

Fig. 5.122. Annual precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of the maximum measured precipitation for the period 1992-2022 is 37.6 mm. The highest precipitation values at the Radimlja site occur in November, with an average of 52.4 mm. The lowest average monthly maximum precipitation value was recorded in June, at 23.7 mm. The average monthly maximum precipitation value for the winter is 39.6 mm, with the lowest measured values in February (36.6 mm) and the highest in December (41.9 mm). The average maximum precipitation value for the spring is 34.4 mm. The lowest average maximum precipitation in spring was recorded in May (30.1 mm), while the highest was in April (38.8 mm). During the summer climatological season, the average maximum precipitation value is slightly lower at 25.3 mm. The highest monthly average maximum precipitation was recorded in August, at 27.3 mm, while the lowest was in June (23.7 mm). The average monthly maximum precipitation value during the autumn is 50.9 mm, with all three months of this season having approximately the same average maximum precipitation, with a peak in November (52.4 mm) and a minimum in October (49.8 mm).

Fig. 5.123. Average monthly values of maximum precip. for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum precipitation value for the period 1992-2022 at the Radimlja site is 95.7 mm. The highest recorded precipitation of 127.0 mm was measured on 26.09.2010. The lowest maximum precipitation of 47.3 mm was recorded on 02.06.2009. During the thirty-year period, the extreme maximum monthly precipitation values were recorded as follows: in January, 94.6 mm in 2001, in February, 124.2 mm in 2013, in March, 90.3 mm in 2005, in April, 85.7 mm in 1992, in May, 72.3 mm in 2016, in June, 47.3 mm in 2009, in July, 79.3 mm in 2019, in August, 88.9 mm in 1996, in September, 127.0 mm in 2010, in October, 120.5 mm in 2015, in November, 125.0 mm in 1993, and in December, 92.9 mm in 2000.

Fig. 5.124. Maximum monthly precipitation values for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the maximum measured annual precipitation for the period 1992-2022 is 83.7 mm. The highest annual maximum precipitation of 127.0 mm was recorded in 2010, while the lowest annual maximum value of 46.0 mm was recorded in October 2020. A linear trend shows a decrease in the maximum annual precipitation value by 7.0 mm.

Fig. 5.125. Maximum annual precipitation values for the period 1992-2022.

At the Radimlja location, during the period 1992-2022, the highest number of days with a certain amount of precipitation (≥ 0.1 mm, ≥ 1.0 mm, ≥ 5.0 mm, ≥ 10.0 mm, ≥ 20.0 mm, and ≥ 50.0 mm) occurred during the winter and spring, while a slightly lower number of days with precipitation occurred during the autumn and summer seasons. Specifically, the average number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is 10.2. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 13.3, which is the average monthly value for December, while the minimum value of 6.4 was recorded in August. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm is 8.2, with a maximum of 11.4 days in December and a minimum of 4.4 days in July. The quantity of precipitation ≥ 5.0 mm has an average monthly value of 5.2 days. The maximum number of days with this precipitation threshold occurred in November (an average of 8.0 days), while the minimum was recorded in July (an average of 2.5 days). The average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 3.9. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 6.3, also recorded in December, while the minimum was 1.7 days in July. Precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm occurred on average in 1.9 days per month. The maximum

number of days with precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm was 3.5, recorded in December, while the minimum was 0.6 days in July. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm is 0.3. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 0.8, which corresponds to the average monthly values of October and November. No days with precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm were recorded in July and August.

Fig. 5.126. Average monthly values of the number of days with precipitation in the period 1992-2022.

Snow cover data were measured in the same manner as at other locations in Bosnia and Herzegovina from 2015 to 2022. Based on the collected data, it can be stated that, during the mentioned seven-year period, there were almost no recorded snowfalls at the Radimlja location. Specifically, the years 2022, 2020, 2017, 2016, and 2015 did not have any registered snow precipitation. Snowfall was recorded in 2021 (2 cm in April), 2019 (11 cm in January), and 2018 (3 cm in April).

5.1.5 RAVANJSKA VRATA

5.1.5.1 INSOLATION

The average monthly insolation in the Ravanjska Vrata area for the period 1992–2022 is 147.5 hours. The lowest average monthly insolation was recorded in December, amounting to 54.7 hours, while the highest average insolation was recorded in July, amounting to 253.4 hours.

Fig. 5.127. Average monthly insolation for the period 1992–2022.

In the Ravanjska Vrata area, as well as at other locations, there are significant differences in the amount of insolation (sunshine hours) during different periods of the year. The average insolation for the winter is 73.0 hours, with the lowest number of sunshine hours in December (54.7 hours) and the highest in February (94.6 hours). The average sum of sunshine hours for the spring is 161.7 hours. The lowest insolation in the spring occurs in March (138.5 hours), while the highest is in May (188.9 hours). During the summer climatological season, the average sunshine hours amount to 237.8 hours, with the highest insolation in July (253.4 hours) and the lowest in June (219.8 hours). The average monthly sunshine hours in the autumn is 117.4 hours, with maximum values in September (157.3 hours) and a minimum in November, with an average of 71.0 hours of sunshine.

Fig. 5.128. Average sunshine by season for the period 1992–2022.

Based on the linear trend, it has been determined that the insolation at the Ravanjska Vrata location increased by 227 hours in the period from 1992 to 2022. Within this thirty-year period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of insolation. The average multiyear insolation value is 1770.0 hours. Sixteen years have an annual insolation higher than the multiyear average, while fifteen years have values below the multiyear average. In the last 10 years, 6 years have higher insolation, while 4 years have lower insolation compared to the multiyear average. The maximum average annual insolation of 2159.8 hours was recorded in 2022, while the minimum average annual insolation of 1445.9 hours was recorded in 1996.

Fig. 5.129. Total annual insolation for the period 1992–2022.

5.1.5.2 RADIATION

Solar radiation at the Ravanjska Vrata location during the analyzed thirty-year period (1992–2022) correlates with insolation and air temperatures. The average monthly radiation value for the period 1992–2022 is 100.0 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly solar radiation was recorded in December, amounting to 39.7 kWh/m², while the highest average radiation was recorded in July, amounting to 177.1 kWh/m². The average radiation for the winter is 48.1 kWh/m², with the lowest value in December (39.7 kWh/m²) and the highest in February (60.2 kWh/m²). The average sum of radiation for the spring is 119.6 kWh/m². The lowest radiation in the spring is in March (92.8 kWh/m²), while the highest is in May (147.4 kWh/m²). During the summer climatological season, the average solar radiation is 165.9 kWh/m², with the highest radiation in July (177.1 kWh/m²) and the lowest in August (157.8 kWh/m²). The average monthly solar radiation during the autumn is 66.5 kWh/m², with maximum values in September (95.1 kWh/m²) and a minimum in November (36.7 kWh/m²).

Fig. 5.130. Average monthly radiation for the period 1992–2022.

In the period from 1992 to 2022, a linear trend at the Ravanjska Vrata location indicates an increase in solar radiation of 141.6 kWh/m^2 . The average multiyear radiation value is 1200.2 kWh/m^2 . Sixteen years have a higher annual radiation than the multiyear average, while fifteen years have values below the multiyear average. In the last 10 years, 6 years have higher radiation, while 4 years have lower radiation compared to the multiyear average. The maximum average annual radiation of 1456.4 kWh/m^2 was recorded in 2022, while the minimum average annual radiation of 991.9 kWh/m^2 was recorded in 1996.

Fig. 5.131. Annual radiation for the period 1992–2022.

5.1.5.3 AIR TEMPERATURE

As the Ravanjska Vrata area is located at higher altitudes, the temperatures are somewhat lower compared to other analyzed areas in the central parts of Bosnia and Herzegovina. The average monthly temperature for the given location in the period 1992–2022 is 7.0°C. The lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January, amounting to -3.1°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in July, amounting to 17.3°C. The average temperature for the winter is -2.1°C, with all months of this season having average temperatures below 0.0°C. The lowest recorded temperature was in January (annual minimum), while the highest was in December, at -1.5°C. The average recorded temperature for the spring is 6.0°C, with significant deviations in the average monthly temperature values. Specifically, the lowest average temperatures in the spring occur in March (0.9°C), while the highest are in May (11.0°C). During the summer climatological season, the average temperature is 16.5°C. The average monthly temperature recorded in July is 17.3°C, which is the highest average monthly temperature of the summer. The lowest average monthly temperature in the summer is in June, amounting to 15.3°C. The average monthly temperature in the autumn is 7.5°C. The coldest month is November, with 2.9°C, while the warmest is September, with 11.9°C.

Fig. 5.132. Average monthly temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

A linear trend indicates that the temperature in the reference thirty-year period has increased by 1.7°C. As with other locations, the Ravanjska Vrata location also exhibits certain annual fluctuations in temperature increases and decreases within this thirty-year period. The average multiyear temperature value is 7.0°C. Seventeen years have annual temperatures higher than the multiyear average, while fourteen years have values below the multiyear average. The last 11 years have consistently had average annual temperatures above the multiyear average. The maximum average annual temperature of 8.1°C was recorded in 2022, while the minimum average annual temperature of 5.5°C was recorded in 1996.

Fig. 5.133. Average annual temperature values for the period 1992–2022.

In addition to the overall increase in temperatures, a linear trend indicates temperature increases (at varying values) across all climatological seasons. Specifically, the temperature increase during the summer is 1.9°C, in autumn 1.6°C, in spring 0.9°C, and in winter 2.2°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter was 1.6°C, recorded in 2014, while the minimum temperature was -5.1°C, recorded in 2012. The minimum average annual temperature during the spring was 3.8°C, recorded in 1998. The maximum average annual temperature for the spring was 7.7°C, recorded in 2018. The maximum average annual temperature for the summer was 18.9°C, recorded in 2012, while the minimum temperature was 14.0°C, recorded in 1995. During the winter, the maximum temperatures were recorded in 2012, with an average value of 9.3°C, while the minimum temperature of 5.1°C was recorded in 2007.

Fig. 5.134. Average temperature values by season for the period 1992–2022.

The average maximum monthly temperatures at the Ravanjska Vrata location for the period 1992–2022 are 21.7°C. The lowest maximum average monthly temperature was recorded in January, amounting to 11.8°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in July, reaching 32.0°C. The average maximum air temperatures for the winter 12.4°C. The recorded average maximum temperatures in December (12.6°C) and February (11.6°C) are similar, while the average maximum monthly temperature in January is slightly lower, at 11.8°C. The recorded average maximum temperatures for the spring are 21.1°C, with the lowest average value in March (16.3°C) and the highest in May (25.7°C). During the summer climatological season, the average maximum temperatures are 31.3°C. The average monthly maximum temperatures recorded in August (31.9°C) and July (32.0°C – annual maximum) are almost identical, while in June, the maximum temperatures are lower, at 30.1°C.

The average maximum monthly temperature during the autumn is 22.2°C, with the lowest value in November (17.5°C) and the highest in September (26.5°C).

The average maximum monthly temperatures at the Ravanjska vrata site for the period 1992–2022 amount to 21.7 °C. The lowest average maximum monthly temperature was measured in January at 11.8 °C, while the highest was recorded in July at 32.0 °C. The average maximum air temperature for the winter season is 12.4 °C. The measured average maximum temperatures in December (12.6 °C) and February (11.6 °C) are similar, whereas in January the average value is slightly lower at 11.8 °C. During spring, the average maximum temperature is 21.1 °C, with the lowest average recorded in March (16.3 °C) and the highest in May (25.7 °C). In the summer climatological season, the average maximum temperature is 31.3 °C. The average monthly maximum measured in August (31.9 °C) and July (32.0 °C – the annual maximum) are almost the same, while in June it is lower at 30.1 °C.

In autumn, the average monthly maximum temperature is 22.2 °C, with the lowest value in November (17.5 °C) and the highest in September (26.5 °C).

Fig. 5.135. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average maximum measured temperature values for the period 1992–2022 are 27.1°C. The highest recorded temperature at the Ravanjska Vrata location was 36.3°C, measured on August 24, 2007. The lowest maximum temperature was recorded on January 22, 1993, at 15.1°C. During the mentioned thirty-year period, the extreme maximum monthly temperature values were as follows: January 15.1°C (1993), February 19.9°C (2008), March 20.3°C (2001), April 25.3°C (2012), May 29.4°C (2001), June 34.5°C (2021), July 36.1°C (2013), August 36.3°C (2007), September 33.0°C (2008), October 26.1°C (2012), November 22.5°C (2022), and December 26.8°C (1992).

Fig. 5.136. Maximum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

At the Ravanjska Vrata location, a linear trend indicates an increase in the maximum annual air temperature by 1.3°C for the period 1992–2022. The average value of the highest measured temperatures during this period is 32.4°C. The highest recorded maximum temperature of 36.3°C occurred in August 2007, while the lowest maximum temperature of 29.9°C was recorded in August 2014.

Fig. 5.137. Maximum annual air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures records the highest values during the summer months, except for $T_{max} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, where the trend follows the same pattern as for extreme minimum temperatures, with a higher number of days during the winter. Analysis of the available data shows significant differences in the number of days with maximum temperatures of: $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum temperatures $T_{max} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 1.4 days. The maximum number of days with $T_{max} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 11 days, recorded in January. The months from May to November do not have maximum temperatures below 0.0°C . Extreme maximum temperatures $T_{max} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a higher average monthly number of days compared to the previously analyzed indicator. The average monthly value is 6.1 days. The maximum number of days with $T_{max} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 22 days, recorded in July. December, January, and March do not have extreme maximum temperatures of $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum temperatures $T_{max} \geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 2.1 days. The highest average number of days with this temperature indicator was recorded in September, with a value of 7.5. The months of January, February, March, April, November, and December have no days with maximum air temperatures of $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.138. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

The average minimum monthly temperature at the Ravanjska vrata location for the period 1992–2022 is -6.0°C . The lowest average minimum monthly temperature was recorded in January, at -16.2°C , while the highest temperature was recorded in July at 4.3°C . The average minimum temperature for the winter is -15.2°C , with the lowest temperatures recorded in January (annual minimum) and the highest in December at -14.2°C . The average minimum temperature for the spring is -7.2°C . The lowest average minimum temperature in the spring occurred in March at -12.4°C , while the highest were in May at -2.3°C . During the summer climatological season, the average minimum temperature is 3.3°C . The lowest average monthly minimum temperature during this season was recorded in June at 2.1°C , while the highest was in July at 4.3°C . The average minimum temperature during the autumn is -5.1°C . The coldest month is November at -9.5°C , while the warmest is September at -0.3°C .

Fig. 5.139. Average monthly minimum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

At the Ravanjska vrata site, the average values of extreme minimum measured air temperature for the period 1992-2022 is -21.8°C . The lowest average minimum temperature was recorded in January 2017 at -28.5°C . The highest average minimum temperature was recorded in August 1993 at 0.4°C . In the specified thirty-year period, extreme minimum average monthly temperatures were recorded for: January -28.5°C (2017), February -26.8°C (2012), March -24.9°C (2005), April -11.5°C (2003), May -5.2°C (2019), June -4.2°C (1997), July -0.2°C (2000), August 0.4°C (1993), September -4.2°C (2018), October -9.7°C (2011), November -15.8°C (1995), and December -25.5°C (2009).

Fig. 5.140. Minimum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The extreme values of minimum temperatures show a tendency to increase. The linear trend indicates a temperature rise of 1.8°C. The average value of measured minimum temperatures at the Ravanjska vrata site for the period 1992-2022 is -19.8°C. The highest minimum (extreme) temperature of -12.5°C was recorded on 07.01.2020. The lowest minimum temperature of -28.5°C was registered on 26.01.2000.

Fig. 5.141. Annual minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Based on available indicators, data on the number of days with extreme minimum temperatures (≤ -10.0 °C, < 0.0 °C, ≥ 20.0 °C, and < 0.0 °C) for the period 1992-2022 were analyzed. Extreme minimum temperatures ($T_{min} \leq -10.0$ °C) have an average monthly value of 1.4 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures ≤ -10.0 °C is 7.4 days, recorded in January. The months from May to September do not have minimum temperatures ≤ -10.0 °C. Extreme minimum temperatures ($T_{min} < 0.0$ °C) have an average monthly value of 10.1 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures < 0.0 °C is 27.2 days, recorded in January. The months of June, July, and August do not have minimum temperatures < 0.0 °C. No extreme minimum air temperatures of ≥ 20.0 °C were recorded at the study site. Indicators for the number of days with extreme minimum temperatures < 0.0 °C at 5 cm above the ground (T_{min5}) are almost identical to the indicators for the number of days with temperatures < 0.0 °C. The monthly average number of days is 11.3 days. The maximum number of days with $T_{min5} < 0.0$ °C is recorded in January and amounts to 28.4 days. During the summer (June, July, and August), there is not a single day with air temperatures at 5 cm above the ground below 0.0 °C.

Fig. 5.142. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.5.4 RELATIVE HUMIDITY

The average monthly value of relative humidity at the Ravanjska vrata site for the period 1992–2022 is 79.6%. The lowest average monthly relative humidity was recorded in June at 70.5%, while the highest relative humidity was recorded in January at 95.2%. The average value of relative humidity for the winter is 86.9%, with the lowest values recorded in December at 78.0% and the highest in January (annual maximum). The average measured value of relative humidity for the spring is 79.0%. The lowest average value of relative humidity in the spring is in May at 73.0%, while the highest value of relative humidity was recorded in March at 84.9%. During the summer climatological season, the average relative humidity is 74.0%. The maximum value was recorded in August at 76.6%, while the minimum values were recorded in

June at 70.0%. The average monthly value of relative humidity in the autumn is 78.5%. The lowest values of air humidity during this season are in November at 75.8%, while the highest values are in October at 80.6%.

Fig. 5.143. Average monthly values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the maximum extreme average air humidity at the Ravanjska vrata site for the period 1992-2022 is 86.6%. The highest average air humidity value during the analyzed thirty-year period was 99.0%, measured in January 2009. The lowest maximum average air humidity value was measured in June 1994 and was 76.0%. In the analyzed period (1992-2022), the maximum values of average air humidity on a monthly level were as follows: January 99.0% (2009), February 96.0% (2010), March 93.7% (1995), April 86.5% (1994), May 79.7% (2010), June 76.0% (1994), July 84.7% (1994), August 85.2% (2006), September 85.3% (2002), October 84.6% (2005), November 81.9% (2021), and December 86.2% (2015).

Fig. 5.144. Maximum average values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

At the Ravanjska Vrata site, the mean value of the minimum average air humidity for the period 1992–2022 is 71.2%. The highest minimum average air humidity value in the reference period was 87.8%, recorded in January 2007. The lowest minimum average air humidity value (61.6%) was measured in June 1993. During the analyzed period, the lowest monthly average air humidity values were recorded for: January 87.8% (2007), February 80.6% (2022), March 76.1% (1998), April 68.0% (2007), May 65.7% (1997), June 61.6% (1993), July 63.2% (2007), August 67.0% (2012), September 71.2% (1992), October 68.8% (1993), November 70.7% (1996), and December 73.6% (2016).

Fig. 5.145. Minimum average monthly rel. humidity values for the period 1992-2022.

During the reference period, the relative humidity at the Ravanjska vrata location shows a slight increase. A linear trend analysis indicates that relative humidity increased by 1.7% from 1992 to 2022. Within this thirty-year period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of relative humidity, with a maximum fluctuation of 8.1%. The average multi-year value of relative humidity at the Ravanjska vrata location is 79.6%. The average relative humidity values above the multi-year average were recorded in 16 years, while 15 years recorded values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, four years had higher values compared to the multi-year average. The highest average annual relative humidity value of 83.0% was recorded in 2010, while the lowest average annual relative humidity value of 74.9% was recorded in 1993.

Fig. 5.146. Average annual values of air relative humidity for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.5.5. PRECIPITATION

The average annual precipitation at the Ravanjska vrata location for the period 1992-2022 is 94.2 mm. The lowest average amount of precipitation occurs in March (72.4 mm), while the highest amount of precipitation occurs in April (115.2 mm).

Fig. 5.147. Average monthly rainfall sum for the period 1992-2022.

The amount of precipitation shows certain monthly and seasonal fluctuations. The highest precipitation occurs during the spring and autumn, while slightly less precipitation is observed during the winter and summer seasons. During the winter, an average of 89.9 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum of 108.4 mm in December and a minimum of 79.0 mm in February. During the spring, an average of 95.9 mm of precipitation is recorded, with the maximum in April (annual maximum) and the minimum in March (72.4 mm). In the summer, the average precipitation is 83.1 mm, with the highest recorded in June at 97.2 mm, and the lowest in July at 73.0 mm. During the autumn, the average precipitation is slightly higher at 108.0 mm, with the maximum in September at 112.0 mm and the minimum in November at 105.9 mm.

In the period from 1992 to 2022, seasonal differences were observed in the increase and decrease of annual precipitation. Specifically, precipitation increased during the spring and winter, while it decreased during the summer and autumn. In the analyzed period (1992-2022),

during the autumn climatological season, the amount of precipitation decreased by 17 mm, while during the summer, precipitation decreased by 6 mm. During the same period, during the winter climatological season, precipitation increased by 12 mm, and during the spring climatological season, it increased by 9 mm.

Fig. 5.148. Average precipitation amount by climatological seasons for 1992–2022.

The linear trend indicates a slight increase in the annual precipitation amount of 36.4 mm. Within the examined thirty-year period, there are certain annual oscillations in the increase and decrease of precipitation. The average long-term value is 1130.7 mm of precipitation. The maximum annual precipitation sum was recorded in 2014 at 1417.9 mm, while the minimum value of 825.5 mm was recorded in 2011. In the analyzed period, 13 years have an annual precipitation amount higher than the long-term average, while 18 years have a lower precipitation sum.

Fig. 5.149. Annual precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of the maximum recorded precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022 at the Ravanjska vrata location is 47.5 mm. The highest precipitation amount occur in April, with an average value of measured maxima being 60.6 mm. The lowest average monthly maximum precipitation amount was measured in July, at 29.5 mm. The average monthly maximum precipitation for the winter is 48.8 mm, with the lowest recorded values in January at 45.1 mm and the highest in December at 54.1 mm. The average maximum precipitation for the spring is 50.3 mm, with the lowest values in March at 40.5 mm and the highest in April at 60.6 mm. During the summer climatological season, the average maximum precipitation is somewhat lower than for the rest of the year, at 37.5 mm. The highest average monthly maximum precipitation is recorded in June at 42.6 mm, while the lowest values were measured in July at 29.5 mm. The average monthly maximum precipitation is highest during the autumn, with a value of 53.4 mm, peaking in October at 59.3 mm and reaching its minimum in November at 46.0 mm.

Fig. 5.150 Average monthly values of the maximum precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of extreme precipitation maxima for the Ravanjska vrata location for the period 1992-2022 is 81.0 mm. The highest recorded precipitation amount of 103.6 mm was in December 1999. The lowest precipitation maximum of 62.5 mm was measured in July 2008. During the mentioned thirty-year period, the extreme maximum precipitation values on a monthly level are as follows: January 89.6 mm (1996), February 68.7 mm (1999), March 80.5 mm (2005), April 91.2 mm (2004), May 75.7 mm (2022), June 79.8 mm (2019), July 70.8 mm (2017), August 62.5 mm (2008), September 86.7 mm (2012), October 84.4 mm (2015), November 79.0 mm (1997), and December 103.6 mm (1999).

Fig. 5.151. Maximum Precipitation Amounts for the Period 1992-2022.

For the Ravanjska vrata, it has been determined that the maximum precipitation amounts have decreased by 3.2 mm over the thirty-year period from 1992 to 2022. The average annual maximum recorded precipitation during this period is 75.3 mm. The highest annual maximum recorded precipitation amount of 103.6 mm was measured in December 1999, while the lowest annual maximum precipitation amount of 54.8 mm was recorded in October 2000.

Fig. 5.152. Maximum precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022.

At the Ravanjska Vrata site, indicators of the number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm, ≥ 1.0 mm, ≥ 5.0 mm, ≥ 10.0 mm, ≥ 20.0 mm, and ≥ 50.0 mm were analysed. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is 14.1. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 16.9, representing the average monthly value for December, while the minimum value of 9.4 was recorded in August. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm is slightly lower at 10.2. The maximum, with an average of 12 days, was recorded in December, while the minimum was in August (7.3 days on average). For precipitation ≥ 5.0 mm, the average monthly value is 4.8 days. The maximum of 6.3 days was recorded in April, while the minimum of 3.4 days was observed in March. The average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 2.5. The maximum (3.3 days) was recorded in November, while the minimum (1.4 days) was in March. Precipitation events ≥ 20.0 mm occur on average 0.8 days per month. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm is 1.4, representing the average monthly value for September, while the minimum number of days (0.3) was recorded

in March. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm is 0.06. The maximum value, 0.3 days, represents the average monthly number of days for July. No days with precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm were recorded in January, February, March, April, August, September, October, or November.

Fig. 5.153. Average monthly values of the number of days with precip. in 1992-2022.

The average monthly snowfall for the period 2015-2022 is 5.6 cm. The months without snow cover are May, June, July, August, September, and October. The highest snowfall occurs in January, with an average monthly value of 16.8 cm. During the winter, an average of 14.2 cm of snow falls, with a maximum in January (annual maximum) and a minimum in February (12.8 cm of snowfall). In the spring, an average of 6.1 cm of snow falls, with a maximum in March (11.6 cm) and a minimum in May (0 cm). There is no snowfall during the summer, while in the autumn, only November has snowfall, with an average monthly value of 6.4 cm.

Fig. 5.154. Average monthly snow cover depth values for the period 2015-2022.

A linear trend has indicated a decrease in snow cover depth at the Ravanjska Vrata site by 22.6 cm over the period from 2015 to 2022. Within the analysed period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of snow cover depth. The multi-year average snow depth is 67.3 cm. The maximum annual snowfall was recorded in 2015, amounting to 106.4 cm, while the minimum value of 25.7 cm was recorded in 2020.

Fig. 5.155. Average annual snow cover depth values for the period 2015-2022.

The mean value of the maximum snow cover for the period 2015-2022 is 16.5 cm. The maximum monthly extreme snow cover value during this period was 48.2 cm, recorded in January 2019. The months without snow cover are May, June, July, August, September, and October. In the mentioned seven-year period, the maximum snow cover values recorded on a monthly basis were: January 48.2 cm (2019), February 24.5 cm (2019), March 38.4 cm (2015), April 25.8 cm (2021), November 14.1 cm (2015), and December 47.0 cm (2018).

Fig. 5.156. Maximum snow cover depths by months for the period 2015-2022.

The average value of the maximum snow cover depth at the Ravanjska vrata site on an annual basis is 27.6 cm. The maximum snow cover depth recorded annually is 48.2 cm, measured in 2019, while the minimum value is 9.0 cm, measured in 2020. A linear trend analysis shows a decrease in snow cover depth, with a reduction of 9.8 cm in the maximum values of snow cover height during the period 2015-2022.

Fig. 5.157. Maximum snow cover height on an annual basis for 2015-2022.

5.1.6 SARAJEVO

5.1.6.1 INSOLATION

Analysis of the collected meteorological data for insolation reveals that the average monthly insolation for the period 1992-2022 is 159.5 hours. The lowest average monthly insolation was recorded in December, with 63.1 hours, while the highest average insolation was observed in July, with 259.9 hours.

Fig. 5.158. Average monthly insolation for the period 1992-2022.

Due to natural and anthropogenic factors (atmospheric pollution), significant differences in the amount of insolation (sunshine hours) occur throughout different periods of the year. The average insolation for the winter is 82.6 hours, with the lowest number of sunshine hours in Sarajevo occurring in December at 63.1 hours, and the highest in February at 103.9 hours. The average total sunshine for the spring is 168.6 hours. The lowest sunshine in the spring is in March, with 147.6 hours, and the highest in May, with 198.5 hours. During the summer, the average sunshine is 244.6 hours, with the greatest sunshine in July (259.9 hours) and the lowest in June (233.2 hours). The average monthly sunshine in the autumn is 142 hours, with the highest in September (174.9 hours) and the lowest in November, which falls below 100 hours of sunshine.

Fig. 5.159. Average sunshine duration by season for the period 1992-2022.

The increase in sunshine hours over the last thirty years (1992-2022) has been constant and correlates with the rise in air temperatures. The overall trend of increasing sunshine is best expressed through a linear trend. Based on this linear trend, it has been determined that sunshine has increased by 200 hours over the given period. Within the specified thirty-year period, there have been certain annual oscillations in the increase and decrease of sunshine. The average multi-year value of sunshine is 1913.8 hours. Fourteen years have had a greater annual sunshine than the average multi-year value, while seventeen years had values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, 7 years had higher, and only 3 years had lower sunshine hours compared to the multi-year average. The highest average annual insolation of 2204.1 hours was recorded in 2022, while the lowest average annual insolation of 1594.7 hours was recorded in 1996.

Fig. 5.160. Total annual sunshine duration for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.6.2 RADIATION

Solar radiation in the analyzed thirty-year period (1992-2022) correlates with sunshine duration and air temperatures. The average monthly radiation value for the period 1992-2022 is 107.4 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly radiation was measured in December, amounting to 45.9 kWh/m², while the highest average radiation was recorded in July at 181.6 kWh/m². The average radiation for the winter is 54.6 kWh/m², with the lowest values in December (45.9 kWh/m²) and the highest in February (66.1 kWh/m²). The total average radiation for the spring is 124.6 kWh/m², with the lowest radiation in March (99 kWh/m²) and the highest in May (120 kWh/m²). During the summer, the average radiation is 171 kWh/m², with the highest values in July (181 kWh/m²) and the lowest in August (158.7 kWh/m²). The average monthly radiation in the autumn is 79.4 kWh/m², with maximum values in September (106.4 kWh/m²) and a minimum in November (47.5 kWh/m²).

Fig. 5.161. Average monthly radiation for the period 1992-2022.

The linear trend indicates an increase in solar radiation in Sarajevo from 1992 to 2022 by 129 kWh/m². The average multi-year radiation value is 1288.4 kWh/m². Thirteen years had annual radiation greater than the average multi-year value, while eighteen years had values below the long-term average. In the last 10 years, seven years had higher radiation, and three years had lower radiation compared to the multi-year average. The maximum and minimum annual radiation values closely correlate with solar insolation. The highest average annual radiation of 1483.9 kWh/m² was recorded in 2022, while the lowest average annual solar radiation of 1073.6 kWh/m² was recorded in 1996.

Fig. 5.162. Annual radiation for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.6.3 AIR TEMPERATURE

An analysis of the collected meteorological data for temperature revealed that the average monthly temperature for the period from 1992 to 2022 is 10.7°C. The lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January at 0.3°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in July and August at 20.6°C. The average temperature for the winter is 1.3°C, with the lowest temperatures in January (0.3°C) and the highest in February (2.1°C). The average temperature for the spring is 10.3°C, with the lowest in March (5.7°C) and the highest in May (15.0°C). During the summer, the average temperature is 20°C. The average monthly temperature recorded in June is 18.8°C, while the temperatures in July and August are the same, at 20.6°C. The average monthly temperature during the autumn is 11.0°C, with the coldest month being November (6.4°C) and the warmest being September (15.5°C).

Fig. 5.163. Average monthly temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

In the past thirty years (1992-2022), temperatures have shown a steady increase. The general trend of rising temperatures is best represented by a linear trend, which acts as a dynamic average of the entire temperature series of measured data. Based on the linear trend, it has been determined that the temperature has increased by 1.5°C. Within this thirty-year period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the rise and fall of temperatures. The average multi-year temperature is 10.7°C. There were 17 years with average annual temperatures above the long-term average, while 14 years had values below the long-term average. In the last 11 years, temperatures have consistently been higher than the long-term average. The highest average annual temperature of 11.8°C was recorded in 2022, while the lowest average annual temperature of 9.1°C was recorded in 2005.

Fig. 5.164. Average annual temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

A linear trend has shown an increase in temperatures across all climatological seasons (winter, spring, summer, and autumn). Specifically, the linear trend indicates an increase in temperature during the summer by 1.9°C. During the autumn, the temperature increased by 1.6°C over the thirty-year analyzed period. In the spring, temperatures rose by 1.0°C, while in the winter, the temperature increased by 1.8°C. The highest average annual temperature during the winter was 5.2°C, recorded in 2014, while the lowest temperature of -1.9°C was recorded in 2012. The highest average annual temperature during the spring was 12.3°C, measured in 2018. The lowest average annual temperature for the spring was 8.1°C, recorded in 1997. The highest average annual temperature for the summer was 22.9°C, recorded in 2012, while the lowest temperatures were recorded in 2005, with an average value of 18.1°C. During the autumn, the highest temperatures were recorded in 2019, with an average value of 13.3°C, while the lowest temperatures of 8.2°C were recorded in 2007.

Fig. 5.165. Average temperature values by season for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum monthly temperature for the period 1992-2022 is 24.8°C. The lowest average maximum monthly temperature was recorded in January at 13.4°C, while the highest temperature was measured in August at 20.7°C. The average maximum temperature for the winter is 14.3°C, with the lowest temperature recorded in January at 13.4°C and the highest in February at 15.7°C. The average maximum temperature for the spring is 25.3°C, with the lowest in March at 20.8°C and the highest in May at 29.7°C. During the summer, the average maximum temperatures are 34.5°C, with the lowest values measured in June at 33.2°C, while in July and August, the values are almost the same, 35.0°C (July) and 35.2°C (August). The average maximum monthly temperature during the autumn is 25.3°C. The coldest month is November at 20.1°C, while the hottest month is September at 30.0°C.

Fig. 5.166. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average values of the maximum measured temperature for the period 1992-2022 is 29.5°C. The highest recorded temperature in Sarajevo was 38.8°C, measured in July 2007. The lowest maximum temperature was measured in December 2009 at 17.8°C. In the mentioned thirty-year period, extreme maximum temperature values were recorded for the following months: January 18.2°C (2007), February 22°C (2021), March 26.6°C (2001), April 29.8°C (2003), May 33.2°C (2008), June 38.3°C (2021), July 38.5°C (2021), August 38.8°C (2021), September 38.0°C (2015), October 28.4°C (2013), November 24.4°C (2022), and December 17.8°C (2009). These indicators show that, in the past five years, four months and, in the past ten years, six months recorded new maximum temperature records.

Fig. 5.167. Maximum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average of the maximum measured temperature for the period 1992-2022 is 36.1°C. The highest recorded maximum temperature was 38.8°C, measured in August 2007, while the lowest maximum temperature of 32.2°C was recorded in July 2018. In general, extreme maximum temper. values show a rising trend. The linear trend indicates an increase of 2.4°C.

Fig. 5.168. Maximum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

According to the available meteorological data, an analysis was carried out on the number of days with maximum air temperatures that have values $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum temperatures $T_{\text{max}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the Sarajevo area have an average monthly value of 1.7 days. The maximum number of days with a temperature $T_{\text{max}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 7.8 days, recorded in January. The months from April to September do not have maximum temperatures below 0.0°C . Extreme maximum temperatures $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 8.2 days. The maximum number of days with a temperature $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 25.5 days, recorded in July. December, January, and March do not have extreme maximum air temperatures of $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum air temperatures $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 2.8 days, with the maximum average number of days (12.9) in August. The months of January, February, March, April, October, November, and December do not have any days with maximum air temperatures of $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.169. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average minimum monthly temperature for the period 1992-2022 is -1.0°C . The lowest average minimum monthly temperature was recorded in January at -12.2°C , while the highest was in August, at 9.2°C . The average minimum temperature for the winter is -10.5°C , with the lowest recorded in January and the highest in February at -9.7°C . The average minimum

temperature for the spring is -1.5°C , with the lowest in March at -6.3°C and the highest in May at 3.3°C . During the summer, the average minimum temperature is 8.3°C . The lowest average minimum temperature in this season was recorded in June at 6.9°C , while the highest was in July at 9.2°C . The average minimum temperature for the autumn is -0.3°C , with November being the coldest month at -4.6°C , and September the warmest at 4.2°C .

Fig. 5.170. Average monthly minimum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average minimum temperature measured for the period 1992-2022 is -7.2°C . The lowest average minimum temperature recorded in Sarajevo was -22.2°C , in January 2007. The highest average minimum temperature was in July 2000, at 5.4°C . During the 30-year period, extreme minimum monthly average temperatures were recorded as follows: January -22.2°C (2017), February -19°C (2012), March -16.8°C (2005), April -6.2°C (2003), May -0.1°C (2019), June 0.8°C (1997), July 5.4°C (2000), August 4.8°C (1995), September 0.5°C (2018), October -7.4°C (1997), November -10.8°C (1995), and December -16.4°C (1999). These figures show that in four months of the last 10 years, records for minimum temperatures were set, while the remaining extreme values were recorded in the first two decades of the observed period.

Fig. 5.171. Minimum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average measured minimum temperature for the period 1992-2022 is -14.2°C . The highest minimum temperature of -9.6°C was recorded in February 2021, while the lowest minimum temperature of -22.2°C was observed in January 2018. Although fluctuations have been detected on an annual basis, extreme minimum temperature values show a rising trend. A linear trend analysis shows a growth rate of -0.9°C , which is significantly lower compared to the rising trend of extreme maximum temperatures.

Fig. 5.172. Minimum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Based on the available meteorological data for the Sarajevo location from 1992 to 2022, significant differences are visible in the number of days with minimum temperatures ≤ -10.0 °C, < 0.0 °C, ≥ 20.0 °C, and < 0.0 °C. Extreme minimum temperatures $T_{min} \leq -10.0$ °C have an average monthly value of 0.3 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures ≤ -10.0 °C was 3 days recorded in January. The months from April to November do not have minimum temperatures ≤ -10.0 °C. On average, 6.7 days experience extreme minimum air temperatures (T_{min}) < 0.0 °C. The maximum number of days with temperatures < 0.0 °C was 22 days recorded in January. The months of May, June, July, August, and September do not have minimum temperatures < 0.0 °C. Extreme minimum temperatures ≥ 20.0 °C have an average monthly value of 0.1 day, with the maximum average number of days in August being 0.4. The months of January, February, March, April, May, November, and December do not have any days with minimum temperatures ≥ 20.0 °C. The average monthly number of days with extreme minimum temperatures < 0.0 °C at 5 cm (T_{min5}) above the ground surface is 7.0 days, with the maximum value of 24 days recorded in January. Additionally, there are months (May, June, July, and August) where no days had temperatures < 0.0 °C at 5 cm above the ground surface.

Fig. 5.173. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.6.4 RELATIVE HUMIDITY

The average monthly relative humidity for the period 1992–2022 in Sarajevo is 69.8%. Monthly values of relative humidity are fairly uniform throughout the year, with noticeable lower values during the spring and summer periods. The lowest average monthly relative humidity was recorded in April at 63.4%, while the highest relative humidity was measured in December at 80.0%. The average relative humidity values for the winter is 76.3%, with the lowest values recorded in February at 71.5% and the highest in December at 80%. The average measured relative humidity values for the spring are 64.4%, with the lowest values in April at 63.4%, while the values for March (65.2%) and May (65.3%) are almost identical. During the summer, the average relative humidity is 65%. The highest value was recorded in June at 65.8%, while the lowest was in July at 64.8%. The average monthly relative humidity for the autumn is 73.5%, with the lowest values in September at 71% and the highest in November at 75.9%.

Fig. 5.174. Average monthly values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

The average values of maximum average air humidity for the period 1992–2022 is 80.1%. The highest average relative humidity in Sarajevo during the thirty-year period analyzed was 91.8%, recorded in December 2015. The lowest maximum average relative humidity was measured in May 2002 and was 73.5%. During this thirty-year period, the highest values of average relative humidity were recorded in the following months: January 82.8% (2009), February 79.4% (1996), March 76.1% (2008), April 74.5% (2008), May 73.5% (2002), June 76.2% (2008), July 74.5% (2008), August 80.5% (1995), September 81.0% (1995), October 83.5% (2007), November 87.1% (1999), and December 91.8% (2015). From these indicators, it is evident that in the last ten years, only one month (December 2015) recorded maximum average relative humidity, while all other maximum average humidity values were recorded between 1995 and 1999.

Fig. 5.175. Maximum average monthly values of air relative humidity for 1992-2022.

The average of the minimum average air humidity for the period 1992-2022 is 57.7%. The highest minimum average air humidity in Sarajevo during the analyzed thirty-year period was 71.9%, recorded in January 2005. The lowest minimum average air humidity was recorded in August 2012, with a value of 41.8%. In the analyzed period, the minimum average air humidity values were recorded as follows: January 71.9% (2005), February 62.9% (2021), March 52.0% (2022), April 47.6% (2020), May 54.7% (2021), June 52.2% (2012), July 51.6% (2012), August 41.8% (2012), September 59.8% (2012), October 61.5% (1993), November 65.6% (2002), and December 70.6% (2016). In contrast to the maximum average air humidity values, which have scarcely occurred in the last decade, a contrary trend is observed for the minimum average values. Specifically, the analyzed data shows that the nine months in the last ten years have had the lowest average air humidity values, while only three values were recorded in the previous two decades.

Fig. 5.176. Minimum average monthly values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

Over the past thirty years (1992-2022), the relative humidity in Sarajevo has been consistently declining. The linear trend indicates a decrease of 2.3% in relative humidity during this period. Within these three decades, there have been annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of relative humidity, with a maximum fluctuation of 12.3%. The average long-term relative humidity value for Sarajevo is 69.8%. The mean values of relative humidity above the long-term average occurred in 17 years, while 14 years showed values below the long-term average. In the last 10 years, only two years had higher values compared to the long-term average. The highest average annual relative humidity value of 76.3% was recorded in 1995, while the lowest average annual value of 64% was recorded in 2011.

Fig. 5.177. Average annual values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

5.1.6.5 PRECIPITATION

Based on monthly average precipitation values, significant irregularity in this parameter can be observed for Sarajevo. The average annual precipitation for the period 1992-2022 is 78.17 mm. The lowest average precipitation occurs in August (63.7 mm), while the highest amount is recorded in December (92.12 mm).

Fig. 5.178. Average monthly precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

During the winter, an average of 76 mm of precipitation falls, with a maximum in December (around 92 mm) and a minimum in February (65.7 mm). In the spring, the average precipitation is also 76 mm, with a maximum in May (85 mm) and a minimum in March (65 mm). During the summer, the average precipitation is approximately the same as in the previous seasons, amounting to 73 mm. The highest precipitation in summer occurs in June (84.7 mm), while the lowest is in August (63.7 mm). Autumn receives the highest average precipitation, 87.1 mm, with nearly uniform amounts distributed across all months.

Also, for the Sarajevo location in the period from 1992 to 2022, seasonal differences in the increase and decrease of annual precipitation amounts were identified. Specifically, an increase in precipitation was found during the autumn and summer, while a decrease in precipitation was observed during the winter and spring. During the analyzed period, the precipitation amount in the autumn climatological season increased by 27 mm, while in the

summer, it increased by 6 mm. In the same period (1992-2022), the winter and spring show opposite trends in precipitation. Specifically, in the spring climatological season, precipitation decreased by 10 mm, while in the winter, it decreased by 8 mm.

Fig. 5.179. Average precipitation amounts by climatological seasons for 1992-2022.

Analyzing the annual precipitation amounts from 1992 to 2022, a linear trend indicates a decline of 45 mm. Within this 30-year period, there are notable annual fluctuations in precipitation increases and decreases. The long-term average precipitation is 938 mm. The highest annual precipitation was recorded in 1999, totaling 1248.9 mm, while the lowest value was observed in 2022, amounting to 671.2 mm. Over the analyzed period, 15 years had annual precipitation above the long-term average, while 16 years recorded values below it.

Fig. 5.180. Annual precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly values of the maximum recorded precipitation for the period 1992–2022 is 23.51 mm. The highest maximum precipitation in Sarajevo occurs in November, with an average measured peak of 28.89 mm. The lowest average maximum monthly precipitation was recorded in March, amounting to 17.8 mm. The average maximum monthly precipitation for the winter is 21.8 mm, with the lowest values recorded in January (20.9 mm) and the highest in December (23.4 mm). During the spring, the average measured maximum precipitation is 20.9 mm, with the lowest in March (17.4 mm) and the highest in May (25.4 mm). In the summer, the average maximum precipitation is slightly higher, reaching 22.9 mm. The highest recorded value in this season is in June (24.1 mm), while July and August have nearly identical values, around 22 mm. The highest average maximum monthly precipitation occurs during the autumn, reaching 28.3 mm, with all three months of this season having nearly evenly distributed maximum precipitation values.

Fig. 5.181. Average monthly values of maximum precip. for the period 1992-2022.

The average values of precipitation maximum for the period 1992–2022 is 62.13 mm. The highest recorded daily precipitation in Sarajevo was 118.5 mm, measured on October 23, 2003. The lowest maximum daily precipitation of 40.0 mm was recorded on March 26, 1993. During this 30-year period, extreme maximum precipitation for the following months were: January: 45.0 mm (2007), February: 65.7 mm (2012), March: 40.0 mm (1993), April: 48.7 mm (2017), May: 73.3 mm (2014), June: 58.7 mm (2009), July: 45.0 mm (2016), August: 45.4 mm (2005), September: 61.3 mm (1996), October: 118.5 mm (2003), November: 64.8 mm (2021), December: 79.2 mm (1999).

Fig. 5.182. Maximum monthly precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the highest recorded annual precipitation in the period 1992–2022 is 50.89 mm. The highest annual maximum precipitation of 118.5 mm was measured in 2003, while the lowest annual maximum precipitation of 31.0 mm was recorded in October 2000.

Fig. 5.183. Maximum annual precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

For the Sarajevo location, the average values of the number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm, ≥ 1.0 mm, ≥ 5.0 mm, ≥ 10.0 mm, ≥ 20.0 mm, and ≥ 50.0 mm were analyzed. The maximum number of days with different precipitation values was recorded during the winter and spring seasons, while the minimum number of days was observed during the summer.

Specifically, the average monthly value for days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is 13.5. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is 15.7, which is the average monthly value recorded in December. The minimum value (10.7) of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm was observed in August. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm is 9.4, with the maximum number of days in May (10.8 days) and the minimum in August (7.3 days). On average, 4.5 days per month experience precipitation ≥ 5.0 mm. The maximum number of days with this precipitation level was recorded in December (on average 5.3 days), while the minimum was recorded in September (on average 3.4 days). The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 2.6. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 3.3, recorded in December, while the minimum number of days with this precipitation value was 1.8, recorded in February. Precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm is observed on average for 0.8 days per month. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm is 1.2 (average monthly value for December), while the minimum number of days is 0.5 (average monthly value for February). The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm is 0.02. The maximum number of days with this level of precipitation is 0.1, which represents the average monthly value for May and November.

Fig. 5.184. Aver. monthly values of the number of days with precip. for 1992-2022.

The average monthly snowfall for the period 2015–2022 is 6.2 cm. Months without snow cover include May, June, July, August, September, and October. The highest snowfall occurs in January, with an average monthly value of 18.1 cm. During the winter, an average of 15 cm of snow falls, with a maximum in January (18.1 cm) and a minimum in February (13.1 cm). In the spring, there is an average of 7.75 cm of snow, with a maximum in March (13 cm) and a minimum in May (0 cm). No snowfall occurs during the summer, while in autumn, only November records snowfall, with an average monthly value of 4.5 cm.

Fig. 5.185. Average Monthly Snow Cover Depth 2015–2022.

A linear trend indicates a decline in snow cover depth by 26.8 cm over the period from 2015 to 2022. Within the analyzed period, there are annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of snow cover depth. The multi-year average snow depth is 74.8 cm. The maximum annual snow depth was recorded in 2017 at 127 cm, while the minimum value of 44 cm was recorded in 2016.

Fig. 5.186. Average annual snow cover height for the period 2015-2022.

The average value of the maximum snow cover depth for the period 2015-2022 is 14.6 cm. During this period, the maximum monthly extreme snow cover depth was 42 cm, recorded in March 2015. The months without snow cover are May, June, July, August, September, and October. In the seven-year period during which snow cover depth was measured, the following maximum monthly snow cover depths were recorded: January 29 cm (2017), February 21 cm (2020), March 42 cm (2015), April 31 cm (2017), November 14 cm (2021), and December 39 cm (2017).

As the linear trend indicates a general decrease in precipitation, the same methodological concept has been used to establish a reduction in the maximum snow cover depth by 16 cm in the period from 2015 to 2022. The average annual maximum snow cover depth is 25.5 cm. The maximum snow cover depth recorded on an annual level is 42 cm, measured in 2015, while the minimum value is 14 cm, recorded in 2016.

Fig. 5.187. Maximum snow cover heights by month for the period 2015-2022.

Fig. 5.188. Maximum annual snow cover height for the period 2015-2022.

5.2 SERBIA SELECTED SITES

5.2.1 PERUĆAC

5.2.1.1 INSOLATION

The analysis of the collected meteorological data for solar insolation at the Perućac location for the period 1992-2022 revealed that the average monthly insolation is 173.8 hours. The lowest average monthly insolation was recorded in December, amounting to 54.6 hours, while the highest average insolation was recorded in July, with a value of 299.0 hours.

Fig. 5.189. Average monthly insolation for the period 1992-2022.

Solar insolation exhibits seasonality for the Perućac area, which is the result of seasonal influences. The average insolation for the winter is 71.0 hours, with the minimum number of sunshine hours in December (54.6 hours) and the highest in February (92.3 hours). The average sunshine duration for the spring (188.1 hours) is significantly higher compared to the winter. The lowest sunshine duration in the spring occurs in March (151.6 hours), while the highest is in May (230.9 hours). During the summer, the average sunshine duration is 279.7 hours, with the maximum sunshine recorded in July (299.0 hours), and the minimum in June (256.2 hours). The average monthly sunshine duration in the autumn at Perućac is 142.1 hours, with the highest values in September (193.5 hours) and the lowest in November (83.9 hours).

Fig. 5.190. Average sunshine duration by seasons for the period 1992-2022.

5.2.1.1 RADIATION

The average monthly solar radiation at the Perućac for the period 1992–2022 is 115.4 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly solar radiation was measured in December, amounting to 39.8 kWh/m², while the highest average value was recorded in July, at 208.9 kWh/m². The average radiation for the winter is 46.5 kWh/m², with the lowest in December (39.8 kWh/m²) and the highest in February (58.7 kWh/m²). During the spring, the average radiation sum is 139.5 kWh/m². All three months of this season have an average radiation sum exceeding 100 kWh/m². Specifically, the lowest radiation in the spring is in March (101.6 kWh/m²), while the highest is in May (180.2 kWh/m²), with April at 136.6 kWh/m². During the summer, the average radiation is 195.3 kWh/m², with the highest solar radiation in July (208.9 kWh/m²) and the lowest in August (187.1 kWh/m²). The average monthly radiation during the autumn at Perućac is 80.0 kWh/m², with the highest values in September (117.7 kWh/m²) and the lowest in November (42.5 kWh/m²).

Fig. 5.191. Average monthly radiation for the period 1992-2022.

Between 1992 and 2022, the linear trend indicates an increase in solar radiation at the Perućac of 77 kWh/m². The average multi-year radiation value is 1377.7 kWh/m². Sixteen years recorded a higher annual radiation than the average multi-year value, while fifteen years had values below the average. In the last 10 years, seven years exhibited higher radiation, and three years showed lower radiation compared to the multi-year average, confirming the increasing trend of this indicator, as determined by the linear trend. The maximum average annual radiation of 1624.4 kWh/m² was recorded in 2000, while the minimum average annual radiation was registered in 2005, amounting to 1164.3 kWh/m².

Fig. 5.192. Annual radiation for the period 1992-2022.

5.2.1.2 AIR TEMPERATURE

The average monthly temperature for the Perućac for the period 1992-2022 is 12.3°C. The lowest average monthly temperature does not have negative values. The lowest average temperature over the years was recorded in January, with a value of 1.5°C. The highest average monthly temperature was recorded in July, with a value of 22.7°C. The average temperatures for the winter are 2.6°C, with the lowest temperatures in January (1.5°C) and the highest in February (3.5°C). The average temperatures for the spring are 12.3°C, with the lowest in March (7.4°C) and the highest in May (17.2°C). The average temperature for the summer is 22°C. The lowest average temperature during the summer was recorded in June (21.0°C), while the highest average temperature was recorded in August (22.3°C). The average monthly temperature for the autumn is 12.3°C, with the coldest month being November (7.3°C) and the warmest being September (17.3°C).

Fig. 5.193. Average monthly temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

In accordance with the processes of global warming, temperatures in the Perućac area have been steadily rising over the last thirty years (1992-2022). The general trend of temperature increase, defined by a linear trend, shows that the temperature has risen by 1.8°C. The average multi-year temperature value is 12.3°C. Seventeen years have had average annual temperatures higher than the multi-year average, while fourteen years had values below the multi-year average. Over the past 11 years, the average annual temperatures have consistently been above the multi-year average. The maximum average annual temperature of 13.6°C was recorded in 2019, while the minimum average annual temperature of 10.6°C was recorded in 1996.

Fig. 5.194. Average annual temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

Based on the collected data, an increase in temperatures has been observed in all climatological seasons (winter, spring, summer, and autumn). The linear trend indicates an increase of 1.9°C in the summer. For the autumn, the temperature has increased by 1.6°C over the thirty-year period analyzed. During the spring, temperatures rose by 0.9°C, while in the winter, the temperature increased by 2.4°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter is 4.7°C, recorded in 2014, while the minimum temperature is -2.4°C, recorded in 2012. The maximum average annual temperature during the spring is 11.5°C, recorded in 2018. The lowest average annual temperature for the spring is 7.4°C, recorded in 1997. The maximum average annual temperature for the summer is 22.3°C, recorded in 2012, while the minimum temperature was recorded in 2005 with an average value of 17.5°C. During autumn, the maximum temperatures were recorded in 2019, with an average value of 12.9°C, while the minimum temperature of 7.7°C was recorded in 2007.

Fig. 5.195. Average temperature values by season for the period 1992-2022

The average maximum monthly temperature for the Perućac from 1992 to 2022 is 27.3°C. The lowest average maximum monthly temperature was recorded in January at 17.3°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in August at 36.3°C. The average maximum temperatures for the winter are 18.0°C. The average maximum temperatures for December (17.6°C) and January (17.3°C) are nearly identical, while February had an average of 19.2°C. The average maximum temperature for the spring is 27.5°C. The lowest average maximum temperature in the spring is recorded in March at 24.1°C, and the highest in May at 31.1°C. During the summer, the average maximum temperature is 35.6°C. The lowest monthly average maximum temperature is recorded in June at 34.3°C, while the highest is in August at 36.3°C, with July also reaching similar values at 36.1°C. The average maximum monthly temperature during the autumn is 28.0°C. The lowest average maximum temperature for this season is in November at 23.8°C, while the highest is in September at 32.0°C.

Fig. 5.196. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the maximum recorded temperature for the Perućac area from 1992 to 2022 is 32.4°C. The highest recorded temperature was 42.3°C, measured in July 2007. The lowest value for the maximum recorded temperature was 21.6°C, measured in January 1995. In the reference thirty-year period, following extreme maximum temperature values were recorded: January: 21.6°C (1995), February: 25.6°C (2008), March: 30.2°C (2001), April: 32.0°C (2003), May: 34.6°C (2003), June: 37.6°C (2021), July: 42.3°C (2007), August: 41.0°C (2012), September: 39.0°C (2015), October: 31.7°C (2013), November: 29.1°C (1996), December: 23.5°C (2009). The indicators show that record high maximum temperatures for four months were recorded in the last 10 years.

Fig. 5.197. Maximum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The linear trend shows a balance in the maximum measured temperature for the Perućac from 1992 to 2022, with a linear growth rate of 0.1°C . The average multi-year value of the annual temperature maxima measured during the period from 1992 to 2022 is 37.4°C . The highest maximum temperature of 42.3°C was recorded in July 2007, while the lowest maximum temperature of 33.6°C was recorded in September 2018.

Fig. 5.198. Maximum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Based on the collected and analyzed data, it is evident that the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures of $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ reaches its highest values during the summer months, while the number of days with extreme maximum temperatures of air $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is highest during the winter months. The average number of days with extreme maximum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ has an average monthly value of 1 day. The maximum number of days with air temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 5.5 days, recorded in January. The months from May to October do not have maximum temperatures below 0.0°C . Extreme maximum temperatures $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 9.1 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 26.4 days, recorded in August. December, January, and February do not have extreme maximum air temperatures of $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum air temperatures $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 3.5 days, with the highest average number of days in August, at an average of 14.3 days. In November, December, January, February, and March, extreme maximum air temperatures above 30.0°C were not recorded.

Fig. 5.199. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

The average of the minimum monthly temperature for the period from 1992 to 2022 is 0.7°C . The lowest average minimum monthly temperature was recorded in January at -11.1°C , while the highest temperature was measured in July at 11.9°C . The average minimum temperatures for the winter are -9.4°C , with the lowest temperatures recorded in January (-11.1°C), and average minimum temperatures for February and December both at -8.5°C . The measured average minimum temperatures for the Perućac during the spring are 0.4°C . The lowest average minimum temperature in the spring was in March at -4.4°C , while the highest was in May at 5.2°C . The summer is characterized by slightly higher average minimum temperatures (10.8°C). The average monthly minimum temperature in this season was measured in June at 9.6°C , with the highest temperature in July at 11.9°C . The average monthly minimum temperature during autumn for the area is 1.1°C . The lowest value of the average minimum temperature for this season was recorded in November at -3.0°C , while the month with the highest values was September with 6.1°C .

Fig. 5.200. Average monthly minimum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of extreme minimum temperatures for the period from 1992 to 2022 is -5.6°C . The lowest average minimum air temperature at the Perućac was -20.6°C , recorded in February 2012. The highest average minimum temperature was recorded in July 1993 at 8.0°C . Significant oscillations in the values of extreme minimum average temperatures were found on a monthly level over the thirty-year period analyzed. Specifically, the following values were recorded on a monthly basis: January -19.0°C (2000), February -20.6°C (2012), March -15.5°C (2005), April -5.4°C (2003), May 0.6°C (2005), June 4.3°C (1997), July 8.0°C (1993), August 7.4°C (1993), September 1.5°C (2018), October -3.9°C (1997), November -8.0°C (2018), and December -16.5°C (1996). From these indicators, it is evident that five months have extreme minimum average values below the annual average. Additionally, only three months in the last 10 years recorded extreme minimum values of air temperature, while the other extreme minimum monthly values were recorded in the first two decades of the observed period.

Fig. 5.201. Minimum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Extreme values of minimum temperatures have a tendency to increase, i.e. decrease in temperature values with a negative sign. The linear trend indicates a growth value of 5.2°C. The average value of measured minimum temperatures at the Perućac location for the period from 1992 to 2022 is -13.6°C. The highest extreme minimum temperature of -6.0°C was recorded on December 23, 2007. The lowest minimum temperature of -20.6°C was recorded on February 9, 2012.

Fig. 5.202. Minimum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

At the Perućac location, extreme minimum temperatures $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 0.3 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 1.5 days, with the highest monthly average recorded in January. The months from April to November do not have minimum temperatures $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme minimum temperatures $T_{\text{min}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a slightly higher average monthly value compared to the previously analyzed indicator. The average monthly number of days for this temperature indicator is 5.2 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 18.9 days, recorded in January. May, June, July, August, and September do not have minimum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme minimum temperatures $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 0.5 days, with the highest monthly average recorded in August at 2.3 days. The months of winter, spring, and autumn seasons (except September) do not have any days with minimum air temperatures $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.203. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures during the period 1992-2022.

5.2.1.3 RELATIVE HUMIDITY

The average monthly value of relative humidity at the Perućac location for the period 1992-2022 is 74.1%. The lowest average monthly relative humidity was measured in July, at 67.4%, while the highest relative humidity was measured in December, at 83.6%. The average relative humidity for the winter is 80.1%, with the lowest values recorded in February (76.7%) and the highest in December (83.6%). During the spring, the average measured relative humidity is 68.6%, with the minimum value recorded in April (67.5%) and balanced values in March (69.3%) and May (69.0%). During the summer, the average relative humidity is 68.4%, with the highest value measured in July (69.5%) and the lowest value in July (67.4%). The average monthly values of relative humidity during the autumn are 78.5%, with the lowest values recorded in September (74.4%) and the highest in November (81.9%).

Fig. 5.204. Average monthly values of relative humidity for the period 1992-2022.

Average value of extreme maximum monthly relative humidity for Perućac during the 1992-2022 period is 83.1%. The highest average relative humidity during the analyzed thirty-year period was 92.0%, recorded in January 1997. The lowest maximum average relative humidity was measured in May 2014, at 75.0%. Based on the analyzed data, it can be observed that in the last ten years, three months had the highest average relative humidity, while all other monthly maximum average humidity values were recorded in the previous two decades. Specifically, during the reference period (1992-2022), the following maximum values of average relative humidity were recorded per month: January 92.0% (1997), February 88.0% (2005), March 77.0% (1996), April 78.0% (2008), May 75.0% (2014), June 77.0% (1995), July 77.0% (2005), August 83.0% (2005), September 85.0% (2014), October 87.0% (2015), November 89.0% (2020), and December 89.0% (1995). Additionally, based on the analyzed available data, slight monthly oscillations in relative humidity values across the seasons are visible. Specifically, during the spring and summer seasons (from March to August), all months have average monthly values lower than the annual average. In contrast, all months of the winter and autumn seasons have average relative humidity values higher than the annual average.

Fig. 5.205. Maximum average values of relative humidity for the period 1992-2022.

At the Perućac, the average value of the minimum monthly relative humidity for the period 1992-2022 was 63.1%. The highest minimum average relative humidity during the defined period was 75.0%, recorded in January 2007. The lowest minimum average relative humidity (48.0%) was measured in August 2012. The lowest values of average relative humidity were recorded by month as follows: January 75.0% (2007), February 68.0% (2020), March 57.0% (2012), April 56.0% (2020), May 60.0% (2003), June 58.0% (2000), July 58.0% (2000), August 48.0% (2012), September 63.0% (2012), October 72.0% (2018), November 73.0% (2000), and December 72.0% (2017). Unlike the maximum average relative humidity values (where most extreme values occurred in the first decades), a different trend is observed in the minimum average relative humidity. Based on the analyzed indicators, it is evident that seven months in the last decade had the lowest average relative humidity values, thus showing a tendency for a reduction in this meteorological indicator in the recent period.

Fig. 5.206. Minimum aver. monthly values of relative humidity for the period 1992-2022.

During the analyzed period, relative humidity at the Perućac has been in constant decline. A linear trend indicates a decrease of 2.3% in relative humidity from 1992 to 2022. Within this thirty-year period, there were annual fluctuations in the rise and fall of relative humidity values, with a maximum fluctuation of 12.5%. The average multi-year relative humidity value for the Perućac is 74.1%. There were 16 years with relative humidity values higher than the multi-year average, while 15 years had values below the average. In the last 10 years, only four years showed higher values than the multi-year average. The maximum average annual relative humidity of 79.8% was recorded in 2005, while the minimum average annual value of 67.3% was recorded in 2000.

Fig. 5.207. Average annual values of relative humidity for the period 1992-2022.

5.2.1.4 PRECIPITATION

The average annual precipitation at the Perućac location for the period 1992-2022 is 73.6 mm. The lowest average monthly precipitation occurs in February (55.3 mm), while the highest amount of precipitation is recorded in June (108.4 mm).

Fig. 5.208. Average monthly precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

During the winter, an average of 64.4 mm of precipitation is recorded, with the maximum precipitation in December (76.3 mm) and the minimum in February (the lowest annual precipitation). During the spring, an average of 71.7 mm of precipitation is recorded, with the maximum in May (88.8 mm) and the minimum in April (62.2 mm). In the summer, the average precipitation is 85.4 mm, with the highest amount occurring in June (the annual maximum) and the lowest in August (71.1 mm). During the autumn, an average of 72.5 mm of precipitation is recorded, with nearly uniform precipitation amounts across all months: September 72.9 mm, October 74.0 mm, and November 70.7 mm.

At the Perućac location, seasonal differences in the increase and decrease of annual precipitation were determined for the period 1992-2022. Based on the data analyzed, an increase in precipitation during the spring and winter seasons was found, while a decrease in precipitation was noted during autumn, and there was an almost balanced state in precipitation during summer. During the analyzed period, in the autumn climatological season, precipitation

decreased by 17 mm. The amount of precipitation during the summer in the analyzed thirty-year period decreased by only 1 mm. In the period from 1992-2022, during the winter climatological season, the amount of precipitation increased by 6 mm, while during the spring climatological season, precipitation increased by 29 mm.

Fig. 5.209. Average precipitation amounts per climatological seasons for the period 1992-2022.

From 1992 to 2022, in addition to certain annual oscillations, an increase in precipitation of 49.6 mm was observed. The average multi-year value of precipitation is 855.3 mm. The maximum annual precipitation sum was recorded in 2014 at 1242.4 mm, while the minimum value was 529.2 mm in 2000. In the analyzed period, 20 years recorded annual precipitation amounts higher than the long-term average, while 11 years had lower sums of precipitation.

Fig. 5.210. Annual precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly values of the maximum measured precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022 is 23.0 mm. The highest precipitation values at the Perućac occur in June, with the average maximum value measured at 32.2 mm. The lowest average monthly maximum precipitation was recorded in February, amounting to 16.8 mm. The average monthly maximum precipitation for the winters 18.5 mm, with the lowest values measured in February (annual minimum) and the highest in December at 20.0 mm. The measured average maximum precipitation value for the spring is 20.3 mm. The lowest average maximum precipitation in the spring occurred in April at 17.5 mm, and the highest in May at 25.2 mm. During the summer, the average maximum precipitation value is slightly higher, at 28.5 mm. The highest average monthly precipitation value was recorded in June (annual maximum), while the lowest values were measured in August at 25.6 mm. The average monthly maximum precipitation during the autumn is 24.8 mm, with the highest precipitation in October at 25.6 mm and the lowest in November at 23.7 mm.

Fig. 5.211. Average monthly value of maximum precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the maximum precipitation for the Perućac site during the period from 1992 to 2022 is 60.2 mm. The highest recorded precipitation amount was 110.0 mm in May 2014. The lowest recorded value for the maximum precipitation was 32.6 mm, measured in February 2017.

During the period from 1992 to 2022, extreme maximum precipitation values recorded by month were as follows: January: 34.6 mm (1998), February: 32.6 mm (2017), March: 35.3 mm (1993), April: 38.9 mm (2014), May: 110.0 mm (2014), June: 76.4 mm (2022), July: 64.1 mm (1999), August: 67.6 mm (2014), September: 56.0 mm (1993), October: 92.3 mm (2003), November: 66.5 mm (2021), December: 48.5 mm (1999).

Fig. 5.212. Maximum precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the maximum recorded precipitation on an annual level during the period from 1992 to 2022 is 54.1 mm. The highest maximum precipitation recorded in a year was 110.0 mm in 2014, while the lowest maximum value was 27.1 mm, recorded in October 2011. Linear trend analysis indicates a slight increase in the values of maximum precipitation. However, this methodology shows that the maximum precipitation values have decreased by 2.3 mm over the thirty-year period from 1992 to 2022.

Fig. 5.213. Maximum precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of the maximum snow depth for the period 1992-2022 is 6.8 cm. The months without snow cover are May, June, July, August, September, and October. The highest average snow depth was recorded in December (8.4 cm). During the winter, the average snow maximum is 8.2 cm, with the highest recorded value in December (8.4 cm of snow) and the minimum average maximum in February (8.0 cm of snow). During the spring, the average snow maximum is 3.4 cm, with the highest average value in March (5.6 cm) and the minimum snow depth in May (0 cm). During the autumn, snowfalls were recorded only in November, with an average snowfall maximum of 5.9 cm.

Fig. 5.214. Average monthly values of the maximum snow cover height for 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of the extreme maximum snow cover for the period 1992-2022 is 16.5 cm. During this period, the maximum monthly extreme value of snow cover was 31.0 cm, which occurred in December 1999. The months without snow cover are: May, June, July, August, September, and October. In the given thirty-year period, the following maximum values of snow precipitation were recorded on a monthly level: January 25.0 cm (2005), February 28.0 cm (2012), March 20.0 cm (2005), April 14.0 cm (2021), November 17.0 cm (2013), and December 31.0 cm (1999).

Fig. 5.215. Maximum snow cover sizes by month for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum snow cover on an annual basis is 13.8 cm. The maximum snow cover height for the year is 31.0 cm, measured in December 1999, while the lowest annual maximum value is 4.0 cm, measured in February 2020. From 1992 to 2022, a linear trend showed a decrease in the height of the maximum snow cover on an annual basis by 0.7 cm.

Fig. 5.216. Maximum snow cover height on an annual basis for the period 1992-2022.

For the location of Perućac, in the period from 1992 to 2022, the average number of days with precipitation values of ≥ 0.1 mm, ≥ 1.0 mm, and ≥ 10.0 mm was analyzed. The average number of days with ≥ 0.1 mm of precipitation is 12.2. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 14, which is the average monthly value for December.

Fig. 5.217. Average monthly values of the number of days with precip. for 1992-2022.

The minimum value of days with ≥ 0.1 mm is 8.5. The average number of days with ≥ 1.0 mm is slightly lower at 8.7, with the maximum number of days occurring in June (10.7 days) and the minimum in August (6.7 days). The average monthly number of days with ≥ 10.0 mm is 2.4. The maximum number of days with ≥ 10.0 mm of precipitation is 3.6, recorded in June, while the minimum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 1.8, recorded in February.

5.3 CROATIA SELECTED SITES

5.3.1 SPLIT AND VELIKA CISTA

5.3.1.1 INSOLATION

For the Velika Cista location, the average monthly insolation from 1992 to 2022 is 204.2 hours. The lowest average monthly insolation was recorded in December, and was 92.9 hours, while the highest average insolation was measured in July, reaching 343.0 hours.

At the Split location, the total solar insolation is somewhat higher compared to the Velika Cista location. The average monthly insolation at the Split location during the analysed period is 219.2 hours. The lowest average monthly insolation was recorded in January, amounting to 131.0 hours, while the highest average insolation was recorded in July, amounting to 345.6 hours.

Fig. 5.218. Average monthly insolation for the period 1992-2022.

There are significant differences in the amount of insolation (sunshine hours) on a monthly, seasonal, and annual basis. The average insolation at the Velika Cista for the winter is 112.2 hours, with the lowest sunshine recorded in December (92.9 hours) and the highest in February (135.1 hours). The average total sunshine for the spring is 216.7 hours, with the lowest in

March (189.3 hours) and the highest in May (257.9 hours). During the summer, the average insolation is 318.6 hours, with the highest recorded in July (343.0 hours) and the lowest in June (294.7 hours). The average monthly sunshine duration in the autumn is 169.1 hours, with the maximum in September (228.5 hours) and the minimum in November (103.5 hours).

At the Split location, the average insolation for the winter is 134.9 hours, with the lowest sunshine duration in January (131.0 hours) and the highest in February (141.2 hours). The average total sunshine duration for the spring is 223.0 hours, with the lowest in March (189.3 hours) and the highest in May (263.1 hours). During the summer climatological season, the average sunshine duration is 325.3 hours, with the highest in July (345.6 hours) and the lowest in June (308.1 hours). The average monthly sunshine duration in the autumn is 193.5 hours, with the maximum in September (247.7 hours) and the minimum in November (135.6 hours).

Fig. 5.219. Average sunshine duration by season for the period 1992–2022.

The amount of sunshine from 1992 to 2022 for Velika Cista and Split has remained relatively stable, showing a slight downward trend. This overall decline in sunshine is most clearly expressed through the linear trend, which reveals a decrease of 17 hours (at the Velika Cista)

and 15 hours (at the Split) over the observed period. Within the thirty-year span, there are certain annual fluctuations, with both increases and decreases in sunshine hours. The average year sunshine value at the Velika Cista is 2450.0 hours. The annual sunshine total was above the multi-year average in 18 years, while 13 years had values below the multi-year average. For the Velika Cista, the annual sunshine for every year within the reference thirty-year period has not fallen below 2000 hours. In the last 10 years, 5 years had higher sunshine totals, while 5 years had lower totals compared to the multi-year average. The maximum average annual sunshine of 2699.2 hours was recorded in 2003, while the minimum average annual sunshine of 2070.6 hours was recorded in 2014.

The average multi-annual sunshine duration for the Split location is 2630.1 hours. Eighteen years recorded annual sunshine duration above the multi-annual average, while thirteen years had values below the long-term average. In the last ten years, five years had higher and five years had lower sunshine duration compared to the long-term average. The maximum average annual sunshine duration of 2879.4 hours was recorded in 2003, while the minimum average annual sunshine duration of 2250.8 hours was recorded in 2014.

Fig. 5.220. Total annual sunshine duration for the period 1992-2022.

5.3.1.2 RADIATION

Solar radiation at the Velika Cista site over the thirty-year period (1992–2022) correlates with insolation. The average monthly solar radiation for this period is 138.0 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly solar radiation was recorded in November at 52.4 kWh/m², while the highest was in July at 239.8 kWh/m². There are significant differences in solar radiation at the monthly, seasonal, and annual levels. Specifically, the average radiation for the winter is 74.3 kWh/m², with the lowest in December at 67.6 kWh/m² and the highest in February at 85.9 kWh/m². The average solar radiation for the spring is 160.2 kWh/m², with the lowest in March at 126.8 kWh/m² and the highest in May at 201.3 kWh/m². The strongest solar radiation occurs during the summer. In this season, the average solar radiation is 222.5 kWh/m², with the highest value in July (the annual maximum) and the lowest in June (218.2 kWh/m²). The average monthly solar radiation for the autumn is 95.1 kWh/m², with the highest in September at 139.4 kWh/m² and the minimum in November (the multi-year minimum).

The average monthly solar radiation value for the Split locality for the period 1992–2022 is 147.7 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly solar radiation was recorded in November at 68.7 kWh/m², while the highest average radiation was recorded in July at 241.6 kWh/m². The average radiation for the winter is 90.0 kWh/m², with the lowest recorded value in January (83.6 kWh/m²) and the highest in December (96.5 kWh/m²). The total average radiation for the spring is 165.0 kWh/m², with the lowest radiation in March (126.8 kWh/m²) and the highest in May (205.3 kWh/m²). The highest seasonal solar radiation intensity is observed during the summer climatological season. During this season, the average solar radiation is 227.4 kWh/m², with the highest values in July (241.6 kWh/m²) and the lowest in August (212.3 kWh/m²). The average monthly radiation for the autumn is 108.3 kWh/m², with the highest solar radiation values in September (150.7 kWh/m²) and the lowest in November (68.7 kWh/m²).

Fig. 5.221. Average Monthly Radiation for the Period 1992–2022.

Based on the established methodology, a slight decrease in solar radiation was determined, mirroring the trend found for insolation. The linear trend analysis for solar radiation from 1992 to 2022 reveals a decrease of 14 kWh/m² (at the Velika Cista) and 12 kWh/m² (at the Split). The average multi-year solar radiation value is 1656.0 kWh/m². The annual solar radiation at the Velika Cista was above the average multi-year value in 19 years, while 12 years had values below the average. In the last 10 years, 5 years had higher solar radiation and 5 years had lower radiation compared to the multi-year average, which correlates with the values of insolation at the analyzed location. The maximum annual solar radiation of 1833.9 kWh/m² was recorded in 2003, while the minimum annual radiation was recorded in 1996 at 1398.3 kWh/m².

For the location of Split, the average multi-year radiation value is 1771.9 kWh/m². The annual radiation higher than the average multi-year value occurred in 18 years, while 13 years had values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, 5 years had higher radiation, and 5 years had lower radiation compared to the multi-year average. The maximum average annual radiation of 1949.3 kWh/m² was recorded in 2003, while the minimum average annual radiation of 1513.7 kWh/m² was registered in 2014.

Fig. 5.222. Annual radiation for the period 1992-2022.

5.3.1.3 AIR TEMPERATURE

Based on the collected data, it can be concluded that the air temperatures in both analyzed localities Split and Velika Cista are quite high, with no long-term average monthly temperatures falling below 0°C . At the Velika Cista location, the average monthly temperature for the period 1992–2022 is 13.5°C . The lowest average monthly temperature occurred in January, at 4.7°C , while the highest was recorded in July, at 23.4°C . For the winter, the average temperature is 5.3°C . January holds the lowest temperature of the year and is also the coldest month of the year, while the highest average temperature in winter is in December, at 5.8°C . The spring has an average temperature of 12.1°C , with the lowest temperature in March (8.3°C) and the highest in May (16.3°C). In the summer, the average temperature is 22.4°C , with July and August having similar temperatures (around 23.3°C and 23.4°C , respectively), while June has slightly cooler temperatures at 20.6°C . In the autumn, the average temperature is 14.1°C , with the lowest monthly average in November (9.7°C) and the highest in September (18.3°C).

The average monthly temperature for the Split location from 1992 to 2022 is 15.3°C . The lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January, at 6.5°C , while the highest average monthly temperature was recorded in July, at 25.3°C . The average temperature for the winter

is 7.1°C. The lowest temperature of the winter is the average temperature of January, which is also the lowest annual temperature at the Velika Cista location, while the highest average temperature is in December, at 7.9°C. The average temperature for the spring is 13.6°C. The lowest average temperature in the spring is in March, at 9.8°C, and the highest is in May, at 17.8°C. During the summer, the average temperature is 24.3°C. The average monthly temperatures recorded in July (25.3°C) and August (25.3°C) are the same, while the average temperature in June is slightly lower, at 22.4°C. The average monthly temperature in the autumn is 16.0°C. The lowest average monthly temperature during the autumn is in November, at 11.3°C, and the highest is in September, with an average monthly value of 20.8°C.

Fig. 5.223. Average monthly temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

When analyzing the average annual temperatures, aside from some yearly fluctuations, an overall increase is observed in the period from 1992 to 2022. The linear trend indicates a temperature rise of 1.3°C at the Velika Cista. The long-term average temperature is 13.5°C. The average annual temperatures exceeded the long-term average in 16 years, while 15 years recorded values below the long-term average. In the last 10 years, two years had lower average temperatures compared to the long-term average. The maximum annual average temperature of 14.9°C was recorded in 2022, while the minimum annual average temperature of 12.3°C occurred in 1995.

At the Split site, during the reference period (1992–2022), air temperatures increased by 1.7°C. The long-term average annual air temperature is 15.3°C. Seventeen years recorded average annual temperatures higher than the long-term average, while fourteen years recorded values below the long-term average. In the last 10 years, only one year had a lower average air temperature compared to the long-term average. The maximum average annual temperature of 16.8°C was recorded in 2022, while the minimum average annual temperature of 14.0°C was recorded in 1995.

Fig. 5.224. Average annual temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

In addition to the overall increase in temperatures for both locations, a rise in temperatures has been observed across all climatological seasons. For the Split site, a linear trend analysis determined an increase in temperature during the summer by 2.3°C. For the autumn, temperatures rose by 2.6°C. During the spring, temperatures increased by 0.8°C, while in the winter, temperatures rose by 0.7°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter is 9.7°C, recorded in 2014, while the minimum temperature is 4.9°C, recorded in 2017. The maximum average annual temperature during the spring is 15.0°C, recorded in 2007. The lowest average annual temperature for the spring is 11.8°C, recorded in 1995. The maximum

average annual temperature for the summer are 26.7°C, recorded in 2003, while the minimum values were recorded in 1995 with an average of 22.3°C. During the autumn, the highest temperature was recorded in 2019 with an average value of 18.0°C, while the lowest temperature of 13.7°C was recorded in 1995.

At the Velika Cista site, similar seasonal temperature fluctuations were observed as at the Split site. For Velika Cista, a temperature increase during the summer of 2.2°C was also determined. For the autumn, during the thirty-year analysed period, temperatures rose by 2.3°C. During the spring, temperatures increased by 0.8°C, while in the winter, temperatures rose by 0.3°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter is 7.8°C, recorded in 2014, while the minimum temperature is 3.2°C, recorded in 2017. The maximum average annual temperature during the spring is 13.5°C, recorded in 2007. The lowest average annual temperature for the spring is 10.4°C, recorded in 1995. The maximum average annual temperature for the summer is 24.7°C, recorded in 2003, while the minimum values were recorded in 1995 with an average of 20.5°C. During the autumn climatological season, the highest air temperatures 16.0°C was recorded in 2019, while the lowest temperature of 12.0°C was recorded in 1995.

Fig. 5.225. Average seasonal temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average of extreme values of the maximum monthly temperatures at the Velika Cista for the period 1992–2022 is 23.7°C. The lowest maximum average monthly temperature was recorded in January, at 14.4°C, while the highest extreme average temperature was recorded in August, at 33.6°C. The average maximum temperatures for the winter are 15.1°C, with the lowest values recorded in January (the lowest annual value of the extreme maximum average temperatures), and the highest in February, at 15.7°C. The average maximum air temperatures for the spring is 22.7°C. The lowest maximum temperature in spring was in March, at 18.9°C, while the highest value was in May, at 27.0°C. During the summer, the average maximum temperature is 32.7°C. The lowest extreme monthly average maximum temperature was recorded in June, at 31.2°C, while the highest was in August, at 33.6°C. The average monthly maximum temperature during the autumn 24.2°C. In this season, the lowest value of this climate indicator was recorded in November, at 20.3°C, and the highest in September, at 28.3°C.

At the Split site, the average values of extreme maximum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992–2022 show similar trends to those at the Velika Cista site. Specifically, for the reference period, the average value of extreme maximum monthly air temperatures is 25.7°C. The lowest maximum average monthly temperature was recorded in January at 16.7°C, while the highest extreme average temperature was recorded in August at 35.0°C. The average maximum temperature for the winter is 17.4°C. The lowest value of maximum average monthly temperatures during the winter was recorded in January (16.7°C – the annual minimum), while the highest value was recorded in February at 17.9°C. The average maximum temperature for the spring is 24.7°C. The lowest value of average maximum air temperature in the spring is in March at 21.0°C, and the highest is in May at 29.1°C. During the summer climatological season, the average maximum temperature is 34.0°C, with the lowest average value in July at 33.4°C and the highest value in August at 35.0°C. The average monthly maximum temperature during the autumn climatological season is 26.6°C. During the autumn, the lowest value of average maximum air temperatures was recorded in November at 22.4°C, while the highest value was recorded in September at 31.2°C.

Fig. 5.226. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum recorded temperature for the period 1992–2022 is 27.8°C. The highest recorded temperature at the Velika Cista location was 36.5°C, measured in August 2017. The lowest maximum temperature was recorded in December 2022 at 18.2°C. In the analyzed 30-year period (1992–2022), extreme maximum temperature values per month were: January: 19.8°C (2022), February: 19.5°C (2011), March: 22.1°C (1993), April: 25.7°C (2012), May: 30.9°C (2008), June: 35.2°C (2006), July: 36.1°C (2007), August: 36.5°C (2017), September: 32.3°C (2015), October: 28.7°C (1993), November: 28.3°C (2004), December: 18.2°C (2022). From the data above, it is evident that maximum monthly temperatures were recorded in four months for the last ten years.

Fig. 5.227. Maximum monthly air temperatures at the Velika Cista for 1992-2022.

The average values of the maximum recorded temperature at the Split site for the period 1992–2022 is 30.3°C. The maximum air temperature was 39.1°C, recorded in August 2017, while the lowest maximum temperature was recorded in December 1994 and measured 20.7°C. During this thirty-year analysed period, the extreme maximum air temperatures on a monthly level have the following values: January: 22.4°C (2022), February: 21.9°C (2011), March: 24.4°C (1993), April: 27.8°C (2012), May: 33.2°C (2008), June: 37.8°C (2006), July: 38.8°C (2015), August: 39.1°C (2017), September: 35.3°C (2015), October: 31.2°C (1993), November: 30.9°C (2004), and December: 20.7°C (1994).

Fig. 5.228. Maximum monthly air temperatures at the Split location for 1992–2022.

The average value of the extreme maximum temperatures measured at the Velika Cista for the period 1992–2022 is 34.3°C. The highest maximum recorded temperature was 36.5°C in August 2017, while the lowest maximum temperature of 31.5°C was recorded in August 2014. Extreme maximum temperature values are nearly balanced, with a slight downward trend. Using linear regression, a decrease of 0.3°C was identified in the extreme maximum temperatures over this period.

Additionally, at the Split site, during the period 1992–2022, a linear trend analysis determined a decrease in extreme maximum temperatures on an annual level by 0.4°C. The average value of extreme maximum recorded temperature at this site is 36.8°C. The highest maximum temperature of 39.1°C was recorded in August 2017, while the lowest maximum temperature of 33.9°C was recorded in August 2014.

Fig. 5.229. Maximum annual air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

During the period 1992–2022, at the Velika Cista and Split sites, the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ has an average monthly value of 0.1 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures $T_{\text{max}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 0.7 days, recorded in January. Months from March to November have no maximum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum temperatures $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 8.3 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 28.5 days, which is the average monthly value for August. December, January, February, and March have no extreme maximum air temperatures with values $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum air temperatures $T_{\text{max}} \geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 3.5 days. The maximum average number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 17.6. This maximum value represents the average monthly value recorded in August. From November to April, the Velika Cista site has no days with maximum air temperatures $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.230. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

During the period 1992–2022, on an annual level, maximum air temperature $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average value of 0.1 days, with a minimum of 0 days on average (14 years within the analysed series) and a maximum of 0.8 days on average in 2012. The average number of days for this temperature indicator shows a decreasing trend of 1 day over the analysed time period. Maximum air temperature $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ were recorded on average 8.1 days per year. This temperature indicator recorded a maximum of 10.6 days on average in 2003, while the minimum average was 6 days recorded in 2019. Additionally, a linear trend analysis over the thirty-year period determined an increasing trend in the average number of days with this temperature indicator by 0.3 days. Air temperature $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ were recorded on average 3.4 days per year, with a decreasing trend over the last 8 years by 0.1 days. The maximum average number of days was 5.6, recorded in 2017, while the minimum average was 0.9 days, recorded in 2014.

Fig. 5.231. Average annual values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average extreme minimum monthly temperature for the Velika Cista in the period from 1992 to 2022 is 5.3°C. The lowest recorded average minimum temperature was in January, at -4.0°C, while the highest extreme minimum temperatures were measured at 15.9°C in both July and August. The average minimum temperature for the winter is -3.3°C, with the lowest recorded in January (the annual minimum) and the highest in February, at -2.9°C. For the spring, the average minimum temperatures are 4.4°C, while are lowest in March (0.0°C) and the highest in May (9.2°C). During the summer, the average extreme minimum temperature is 14.8°C. The lowest monthly minimum temperature in this season was recorded in June at 12.9°C, while the highest extreme minimum temperature was recorded in July and August, at 15.9°C. For the autumn, the average extreme minimum temperature is 5.3°C. The lowest value was observed in November at 0.5°C, while the highest was in September, with 10.4°C.

The average extreme minimum monthly temperature at the Split site for the reference period is 6.6°C. The lowest minimum average monthly air temperature was recorded in January (-2.7°C), while the highest value of the analysed indicator was recorded in July (17.5°C). The

average minimum temperature for the winter is -2.0°C , with the lowest value recorded in January (-2.7°C) and the highest in February at -1.6°C . The average minimum temperature for the spring is 5.4°C . The lowest average maximum temperature in the spring is in March at 1.0°C , and the highest is in May at 10.3°C . During the summer climatological season, the average maximum temperatures are 16.4°C . The lowest value of the average monthly minimum air temperature during this season was recorded in June at 14.2°C , while the highest value of extreme average minimum temperature was recorded in July at 17.5°C . The average monthly minimum temperature in the autumn is 6.7°C . The lowest average extreme minimum value was recorded in November (1.5°C), and the highest was recorded in September (12.3°C).

Fig. 5.232. Average monthly minimum temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average extreme minimum measured temperatures for the Velika Cista location from 1992 to 2022 is 0.2°C . The lowest average extreme minimum temperature was recorded in January 2017, at -11.4°C , while the highest average extreme minimum temperature was observed in July 2013, at 13.1°C . During the analyzed 30-year period, extreme minimum average monthly temperatures were: January: -11.4°C (2017), February: -8.6°C (2012), March: -6.2°C (2005), April: -1.0°C (2003), May: 5.3°C (2019), June: 6.6°C (2006), July: 13.1°C (2013), August: 10.8°C (1995), September: 6.8°C (2007), October: 0.2°C (2005), November: -5.2°C (1995),

December: -8.3°C (2014). The data shows that for five months record-low extreme minimum temperatures were recorded in the last 10 years.

Fig. 5.233. Minimum monthly air temper. at the Velika Cista for the period 1992-2022.

At the Split site, the average monthly values of extreme minimum air temperature for the reference thirty-year period (1992–2022) is 1.3°C . The lowest average minimum air temperature was -10.4°C , recorded in January 2017. The highest average minimum air temperature was recorded in July 2008 with a value of 14.8°C . During this thirty-year period, the extreme minimum average air temperatures on a monthly level had the following values: January: -10.4°C (2017), February: -7.6°C (2012), March: -5.4°C (2005), April: -0.3°C (2003), May: 6.3°C (2019), June: 7.7°C (2013), July: 14.6°C (2008), August: 12.1°C (1995), September: 8.5°C (2007), October: 1.2°C (2005), November: -4.4°C (1995), and December: -7.2°C (2014). From these indicators, it is evident that for five months in the last 10 years, record low air temperatures were recorded, while for the remaining months, record low temperatures were recorded in the previous two decades.

Fig. 5.234. Minimum monthly air temperatures for the Split site, period 1992–2022.

Based on the analyzed data, there is a trend of increasing extreme minimum air temperatures. From 1992 to 2022, at the Velika Cista linear trend analysis showed a growth rate of 0.9°C per year for the annual extreme minimum temperatures. The average value of the measured minimum temperatures during the analyzed period is -5.5°C . The highest minimum temperature of -2.3°C was recorded in March 2011, while the lowest minimum temperature of -11.4°C was observed in January 2017.

Additionally, during the same period (1992–2022), a linear trend analysis at the Split site determined an increase in annual extreme minimum air temperature by 1.2°C . The average value of recorded minimum temperature during the analysed period is -4.3°C . The highest minimum temperature of -1.3°C was recorded in March 2011, while the lowest minimum temperature of -10.4°C was recorded in January 2017.

Fig. 5.235. Minimum annual air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

At the Velika Cista and Split sites during the period 1992–2022, no extreme minimum temperature $T_{min} \leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was recorded. The average monthly value of 2 days has extreme minimum temperature $T_{min} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. The maximum number of days with temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 8.1, which represents the average monthly value in January. From May to October, no days with extreme minimum temperature $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was recorded. Extreme minimum temperature $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 4.9 days, with the maximum average number of days in August at 21.8. Months from October to April have no days with minimum temperature $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.236. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

During the period 1992–2022, minimum air temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ were recorded on average 1.9 days per year. This temperature indicator recorded a maximum of 3.9 days on average in 1993, while the minimum average was 0.5 days recorded in 2014. A linear trend analysis over the thirty-year period determined a decreasing trend of 1.5 days on average for this temperature indicator. Minimum air temperatures $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ recorded average values of 4.7 days, with a linear increasing trend of 1 day over the thirty-year period. The maximum average number of days with this temperature indicator was 6.9, recorded in 2008, while the minimum average was 2.9 days, recorded in 2005.

Fig. 5.237. Average annual values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

5.3.1.4 RELATIVE HUMIDITY

The average monthly relative humidity at the Velika Cista for the analyzed 30-year period (1992–2022) is 63.4%. The lowest average monthly relative humidity was recorded in July at 51.1%, while the highest was measured in November at 70.0%. The average monthly values of relative humidity remain relatively stable throughout the year, with slightly lower values during the summer. Winter: The average relative humidity is 68.5%, with the lowest value recorded in February (67.1%) and the highest in December (69.7%). Spring: The average relative humidity is 63.2%, with the lowest in March (62.3%) and the highest in April (64.5%). Summer: The average relative humidity is lower at 54.7%, with the highest value in June (59.2%) and the lowest in July (51.1%). Autumn: The average relative humidity is 67.2%, with the lowest value in September (63.1%) and the highest in November, which also represents the annual maximum.

The lowest average monthly relative humidity was recorded in July, amounting to 53.3%, while the highest relative humidity was recorded in November at 71.7%. The average relative humidity value for the winter amount to 69.9%, with the lowest value recorded in February at 68.6% and the highest in December at 71.2%. The measured average relative humidity value during spring amount to 65.2%. The lowest average relative humidity values in the spring were recorded in March at 63.9%, while the highest values were recorded in April at 66.6%. During the summer climatological season, the average relative humidity is 57.0%. The maximum value was recorded in June at 61.7%, while the lowest was in July at 53.3%. The average monthly relative humidity values in the autumn amount to 69.1%. The lowest humidity values during this season were recorded in September at 65.0%, while the highest relative humidity values were recorded in November (71.7%).

Fig. 5.238. Average monthly relative humidity values for the period 1992-2022.

The average values of the maximum extreme relative humidity for the period 1992-2022 for the Velika Cista location is 77.5%, while for the Split location, they is 79.8%. For Velika Cista, the highest average maximum relative humidity in the analysed thirty-year period was 97.0%,

recorded in February 2015. The lowest maximum average relative humidity was recorded in July 1996 and was 61.0%. In the analysed period for Velika Cista, the average maximum monthly relative humidity values are as follows: in January, 77.1% in 2019; in February, 97.0% in 2015; in March, 73.9% in 1996; in April, 74.7% in 2000; in May, 79.4% in 2009; in June, 79.5% in 2009; in July, 61.0% in 1996; in August, 68.4% in 2013; in September, 79.2% in 2013; in October, 77.2% in 2007; in November, 80.1% in 1993; and in December, 82.2% in 2007.

Fig. 5.239. Maximum average values of relative humidity for the Velika Cista location in the period 1992-2022.

At the Split location, the maximum average relative humidity in the period 1992-2022 was 99.1%, recorded in February 2015, while the lowest maximum average relative humidity was measured in July 1996, amounting to 63.7%. During the analysed period, the average maximum relative humidity values on a monthly level were as follows: January 78.5% (2019), February 99.1% (2015), March 75.9% (1996), April 77.1% (2000), May 82.3% (2009), June 82.9% (2009), July 63.7% (1996), August 71.1% (2013), September 81.7% (2013), October 79.4% (1993), November 82.0% (2007), and December 84.0% (2007).

Fig. 5.240. Maximum average relative humidity values for the Velika Cista location in the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the mean minimum air humidity for the period 1992-2022 for the Velika Cista location is 51.5%. The highest minimum mean air humidity value in the reference period was 60.6%, measured in October 1996. The lowest minimum mean air humidity value (40.5%) was recorded in August 2012. During the analysed period, the lowest values of the mean monthly air humidity were recorded as follows: January 54.6% (2000), February 49.9% (2004), March 49.9% (2003), April 53.7% (2022), May 49.5% (2003), June 47.3% (2001), July 41.9% (1999), August 40.5% (2012), September 53.0% (2019), October 60.6% (1996), November 59.4% (1999), and December 57.2% (2002).

Fig. 5.241. Minimum average monthly values of relative air humidity for the Velika Cista location in the period 1992-2022.

At the Split location, the average minimum air humidity values are quite similar to those at the Velika Cista location. The average minimum air humidity value is 53.0%. The highest minimum average air humidity value in the observed period was 62.3%, measured in October 1996, while the lowest air humidity value was recorded in August 2012 (42.1%). In the period from 1992 to 2022, the lowest values of average monthly air humidity on a monthly basis were as follows: January 55.6% (2000), February 51.0% (2004), March 51.2% (2003), April 55.4% (2022), May 51.4% (2003), June 49.3% (2001), July 43.7% (1999), August 42.1% (2012), September 54.6% (2019), October 62.3% (1996), November 60.8% (1999), and December 58.4% (2002).

Fig. 5.242. Minimum average monthly values of relative air humidity for the Split location in the period 1992-2022.

During the reference period, the relative air humidity at both investigated locations has been steadily decreasing. A linear trend analysis showed that the relative humidity at the Velika Cista location decreased by 1.9% from 1992 to 2022, while at the Split location, it decreased by 2.0%. At the Velika Cista location, the average multi-year value of air humidity is 63.4%. The average relative air humidity values above the multi-year average were recorded in 14 years, while in 17 years, the values were below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, only 4 years had values higher than the multi-year average. The maximum average annual value of relative air humidity, 69.1%, was recorded in 1992, while the minimum average annual value, 57.2%, was recorded in 2003.

At the Split location, the average multi-year value of air humidity is 65.3%. Similarly, at the Split location, the average relative air humidity values above the multi-year average were recorded in 14 years, while in 17 years, the values were below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, only 4 years had values higher than the multi-year average. The maximum average

annual value of relative air humidity, 71.2%, was recorded in 1992, while the minimum average annual value, 58.9%, was recorded in 2003.

Fig. 5.243. Average annual values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

5.3.1.5 PRECIPITATION

During the period from 1992 to 2022, the average annual precipitation for the Velika Cista was 113.0 mm. The lowest average monthly precipitation occurs during the summer months, while the highest precipitation is recorded in autumn and winter. Specifically, the lowest average monthly precipitation was recorded in July (37.7 mm), while the highest precipitation was observed in December (208.5 mm).

Fig. 5.244. Average monthly precipitation totals for the period 1992-2022.

During the winter an average of 153.6 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum in December (around 200 mm) and a minimum in February (115.5 mm). In the spring, an average of 102.2 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum in March (113.3 mm) and a minimum in May (91.3 mm). The summer has significantly lower precipitation compared to the rest of the year, with an average of 50.7 mm. The highest precipitation in this season occurs in June (63.1 mm), while the lowest is in July (37.7 mm). During the autumn, an average of 145.4 mm of precipitation is recorded. The driest month in this season is September, with an average of 113.3 mm, while the wettest month is November, with 200.1 mm (the annual maximum).

At the Velika Cista location, during the period from 1992 to 2022, an increase in precipitation was observed during the spring and winter seasons, while a decrease in precipitation was recorded during the summer and autumn seasons. Specifically, during the autumn climatological season, precipitation decreased by 44 mm, while during the summer, precipitation decreased by 19 mm. In the same period, during the winter climatological season, precipitation increased by 59 mm, while during the spring climatological season, precipitation increased by only 7 mm.

Fig. 5.245. Average precipitation amounts by climatological seasons for the Split location for the period 1992-2022.

At the Split location, due to the physical-geographical conditions and proximity to the area, similar trends in the total amount of precipitation by climatological seasons are observed as at the Velika Cista location. In the reference period (1992-2022), an increase in precipitation was also observed during the spring and winter seasons, while a decrease in precipitation was recorded during the summer and autumn seasons. Specifically, during the autumn climatological season, precipitation decreased by 47 mm, while during the summer, precipitation decreased by 21 mm. In the same period, during the winter climatological season, precipitation increased by 63 mm, while during the spring climatological season, precipitation increased by 7 mm.

Fig. 5.246. Average precipitation amounts by climatological seasons for the Velika Cista location for the period 1992-2022.

The average annual precipitation for the Split location is 118.9 mm. The lowest average monthly precipitation value was recorded in July (40.5 mm), while the highest precipitation occurred in December (218.8 mm). During the winter climatological season, an average of 160.5 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum in December of about 218.8 mm and a minimum in February of 120.4 mm. During the spring, an average of 107.3 mm of precipitation is recorded. The highest amount of precipitation during this season occurs in March (118.3 mm), while the minimum is recorded in May (97.0 mm). The average amount of precipitation during the summer climatological season is 54.4 mm. The most precipitation is recorded in June (67.9 mm), while the least is recorded in July (40.5 mm). During the autumn, an average of 153.5 mm of precipitation is recorded. The least precipitation in this season occurs in September, with an average value of 120.5 mm, while the most precipitation occurs in November (210.4 mm).

The linear trend analysis has determined a balanced amount of precipitation for the Velika Cista over the 30-year period (1992–2022). Using this methodology, a slight decrease in precipitation of 6.6 mm has been observed. The average annual precipitation for the reference period is 1350.7 mm. Within this 30-year period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of precipitation amounts. The maximum annual precipitation total was recorded in 2010, amounting to 1961.9 mm, while the minimum value of 897.2 mm was recorded in 2011. In the analyzed dataset, 14 years had annual precipitation amounts above the long-term average, while 17 years had precipitation amounts below the long-term average.

At the Split location, the linear trend indicates an increase in precipitation during the period from 1992 to 2022. Using the mentioned methodology, an increase in precipitation of 92 mm was determined. The average annual precipitation for the reference period is 1426.8 mm. The maximum annual precipitation total was recorded in 2010, amounting to 2061.1 mm, while the minimum value of 948.3 mm was recorded in 2011. Similarly, for the Split location in the analyzed period, there were 14 years with annual precipitation totals higher than the long-term average, while 17 years had lower totals.

Fig. 5.247. Annual precipitation totals for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of the maximum recorded precipitation amounts at the Velika Cista for the period 1992–2022 is 37.7 mm. The highest precipitation amounts in Velika Cista occur in December, with an average recorded maximum of 56.0 mm. The lowest precipitation values are recorded in the summer months, with the lowest average monthly maximum precipitation recorded in July (21.9 mm).

When analysing this climatological element by seasons, significant differences emerge. Winter: The average monthly maximum precipitation is 43.2 mm. The lowest measured values occur in February (37.2 mm), while the highest are recorded in December (56.0 mm). Spring: The average monthly maximum precipitation is 33.0 mm. The lowest values occur in April (30.8 mm), while the highest are recorded in March (35.0 mm). Summer: The average monthly maximum precipitation is lower, at 27.1 mm. The highest values occur in June (33.7 mm), while the lowest are recorded in July (21.9 mm). Autumn: The average monthly maximum precipitation is 47.4 mm. The highest values are recorded in November (49.9 mm), while the lowest occur in September (45.8 mm).

At the Split location, the average monthly value of the maximum measured precipitation for the period from 1992 to 2022 is 39.7 mm. The maximum precipitation amounts (58.8 mm) occur in December, while the minimum precipitation value is recorded in July (23.5 mm). The average monthly maximum precipitation value for the winter is 45.2 mm, with the lowest values recorded in January (37.9 mm) and the highest in December (58.8 mm). The average monthly maximum precipitation value for the spring is 34.7 mm. The lowest average maximum precipitation value in the spring occur in April (32.2 mm), while the highest is recorded in March (36.5 mm). During the summer climatological season, the average maximum precipitation value is slightly lower, at 29.1 mm. The highest value of the average monthly maximum precipitation during this season is recorded in June (36.3 mm), while the lowest maximum precipitation value is recorded in July (23.5 mm). During the autumn, the average monthly maximum precipitation value is 50.0 mm. The maximum precipitation during this season is recorded in November (52.5 mm), while the minimum is recorded in September (48.7 mm).

Fig. 5.248. Average monthly values of maximum precipitation for 1992-2022.

The average value of precipitation maximum for Velika Cista in the period 1992–2022 is 113.7 mm. The highest recorded precipitation was measured in December 2004, reaching 157.4 mm. The lowest precipitation maximum, 71.4 mm, was recorded in February 2018. The maximum precipitation values recorded per month during the 1992–2022 period are as follows: January: 92.5 mm (2006), February: 71.4 mm (2018), March: 102.4 mm (2004), April: 79.6 mm (1997), May: 108.2 mm (1996), June: 137.0 mm (2009), July: 150.5 mm (1992), August: 139.4 mm (2002), September: 115.6 mm (2006), October: 116.8 mm (2003), November: 93.5 mm (2004), December: 157.4 mm (2004).

Fig. 5.249. Maximum precipitation at the Velika Cista for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of precipitation maxima for the Split location in the analyzed period from 1992 to 2022 is 120.3 mm. The maximum precipitation was recorded in December 2004, amounting to 165.1 mm. The lowest precipitation maximum value of 74.4 mm was recorded in February 2018. In the period from 1992 to 2022, the maximum precipitation values by month were as follows: January 96.3 mm (2006), February 74.4 mm (2018), March 106.9 mm (2004), April 83.2 mm (1997), May 114.9 mm (1996), June 147.4 mm (2009), July 161.6 mm (1992), August 149.4 mm (2002), September 123.0 mm (2006), October 123.1 mm (2003), November 98.5 mm (2004), and December 165.1 mm (2004).

Fig. 5.250. Maximum precip. amounts for the Split location for the period 1992–2022.

The average annual maximum recorded precipitation at the Velika Cista for the period 1992–2022 is 91.3 mm. The highest annual maximum precipitation of 157.4 mm was recorded in December 2004, while the lowest extreme maximum annual precipitation of 40.0 mm was observed in December 2012. A linear trend analysis indicates an increase in extreme maximum precipitation values by 52 mm over the 1992–2022 period.

For the Split location in the period 1992–2022, the average annual maximum recorded precipitation is 96.7 mm. The highest annual maximum precipitation of 165.1 mm was measured in December 2004, while the lowest extreme maximum precipitation value of 42.0 mm was recorded in December 2012. A linear trend has determined a decrease in extreme maximum precipitation values at the Split location by 55 mm over the analysed period.

Fig. 5.251. Maximum precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022.

In the period from 1992 to 2022 at the Velika Cista and Split locations, seasonal fluctuations are evident in the average values of the number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm, ≥ 1.0 mm, ≥ 5.0 mm, ≥ 10.0 mm, ≥ 20.0 mm, and ≥ 50.0 mm. The highest number of days with precipitation occurs during the winter and spring months, while the lowest number of days with precipitation is recorded during the summer climatological season.

The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is 7.5. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 10.5, which corresponds to the average monthly value for November, while the minimum value of 3.5 days is recorded in July. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm is 6.7, with a maximum of 9.8 days recorded in November and a minimum of 3.2 days in July. Precipitation amounts ≥ 5.0 mm have an average monthly value of 4.7 days. The maximum number of days with this precipitation threshold is recorded in November (an average of 7.5 days), while the minimum is recorded in July (an average of 1.8 days). The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 3.3. The maximum

number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 5.9, also recorded in November, while the minimum number of days with this threshold is 1.1, recorded in July. Precipitation amounts ≥ 20.0 mm occur on average 1.7 days per month. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm is 3.5, which is the average for November, while the minimum is 0.5, recorded in July. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm is 0.3. The maximum value for this threshold is 0.6, corresponding to the average number of days for November and December, while the minimum number of days with precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm is recorded in April and July (average monthly value of 0.1 day).

Fig. 5.252. Average monthly values of the number of days with precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

On an annual basis, an average of 7.5 days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is recorded, with a maximum of 11.3 days in 2010 and a minimum of 2.3 days in 2020. Precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm occurs on average in 4.7 days per year, with a maximum of 7.3 days in 2010 and a minimum of 1.2 days in 2020. On average, precipitation ≥ 5.0 mm occurs in 1.7 days annually, with a maximum of 2.8 days in 2010 and a minimum of 0.3 days in 2020. Precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is

recorded on average in 6.7 days per year, with a maximum of 10.5 days in 2010 and a minimum of 2.3 days in 2020. Precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm occurs on average in 3.3 days annually, with a maximum of 5.9 days in 2010 and a minimum of 0.8 days in 2020. Precipitation amounts exceeding 50.0 mm are recorded on average in 0.3 days per year, with a maximum of 0.9 days in 1996.

Fig. 5.253. Average monthly values of the number of days with precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The linear trend analysis shows a decrease in the number of days per year: 1.5 days for precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm, 0.5 days for precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm, 0.4 days for precipitation ≥ 5.0 mm, 0.1 days for precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm, 0.3 days for precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm, and 0.5 days for precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm.

5.4 MONTENEGRO SELECTED SITE

5.4.1 ŽUGIĆA BARE ŽABLJAK

5.4.1.1 INSOLATION

The average monthly value of insolation for Žabljak for the period 2000–2022 is 168.4 hours. The lowest average monthly insolation was recorded in December - 92.3 hours, while the highest average monthly insolation was recorded in July - 271.0 hours.

Fig. 5.254. Average monthly insolation for the period 2000–2022.

During the winter, the average insolation is 101.2 hours, with the lowest number of sunshine hours recorded in December, which also marks the annual minimum, and the highest in February at 111.3 hours. The average sunshine duration for the spring is 172.9 hours, with the lowest in March at 154.4 hours and the highest in May at 192.9 hours. In the summer, the average sunshine duration does not fall below 200 hours in any month. The highest value of sunshine occurs in July, with 271.0 hours, while the lowest is in June at 221.0 hours. The average monthly sunshine duration during the autumn is 154.4 hours, with maximum values in September (185.3 hours) and a minimum in November at 112.3 hours.

Fig. 5.255. Average sunshine duration by season for the period 2000-2022.

The annual sunshine duration in the analyzed period (2000-2022) has been steadily increasing. It was found that sunshine duration increased by 278.6 hours during this period. The average long-term sunshine duration is 1973.4 hours. 14 years have annual sunshine values greater than the long-term average, while 9 years have values below the long-term average. In the last 10 years, 8 years have higher sunshine durations, while only 2 years have lower sunshine compared to the long-term average. The highest average annual sunshine duration of 2271.4 hours was recorded in 2017, while the lowest average annual sunshine duration of 1617.1 hours was recorded in 2009.

Fig. 5.256. Total annual sunshine duration for the period 2000-2022.

5.4.1.2 RADIATION

The average monthly radiation value for Žabljak in the analyzed period (1992-2022) is 113.0 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly solar radiation was measured in November at 56.9 kWh/m², while the highest average radiation was recorded in July at 189.4 kWh/m². The average radiation for the winter is 67.3 kWh/m², with the lowest value in January at 63.9 kWh/m² and the highest in February at 70.7 kWh/m². The average radiation for the spring is 127.6 kWh/m². The lowest radiation in spring occurs in March at 103.5 kWh/m², and the highest is in May at 150.5 kWh/m². During the summer, solar radiation does not fall below 150 kWh/m² in any month. The average value of solar radiation for the summer is 171.2 kWh/m², with the highest value in July (189.4 kWh/m²) and the lowest in August (160.5 kWh/m²). The average monthly radiation in the autumn for the Žabljak location is 86.1 kWh/m², with maximum values in September (112.7 kWh/m²) and the minimum in November (56.9 kWh/m²), which represents the annual minimum.

Fig. 5.257. Average monthly solar radiation for the period 2000-2022.

A linear trend has shown an increase in solar radiation in Žabljak during the period from 2000 to 2022, amounting to 116 kWh/m². The average multi-year value of radiation is 1356.5 kWh/m². The annual average radiation exceeded the multi-year average in 11 years, while 12 years showed values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, 6 years have had higher radiation, and 4 years have had lower radiation compared to the multi-year average. The maximum average annual radiation of 1520.2 kWh/m² was recorded in 2017, while the minimum average annual radiation was recorded in 2009, amounting to 1090.2 kWh/m².

Fig. 5.258. Annual radiation for the period 2000-2022.

5.4.1.3 AIR TEMPERATURE

The average monthly temperature for the Žabljak location for the period 2000-2022 is 6.1°C. The lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January, with a value of -3.4°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in August, at 15.8°C. The average temperature for the winter is -2.5°C, with the lowest temperatures recorded in January, representing the annual minimum of -3.4°C, and the highest temperatures in December, at -1.7°C. The average temperature for the spring is 4.9°C, with the lowest temperature in March (0.3°C) and the highest in May (9.8°C). During the summer, the average temperature is 15.1°C. The average monthly temperatures in July (15.5°C) and August (15.8°C) are nearly the same, representing the highest average monthly temperature for the summer as well as the maximum annual temperature. The lowest average monthly temperature during the summer is in June, at 14.1°C.

Fig. 5.259. Average monthly temperatures for the period 2000-2022.

Unlike many other analyzed locations where significant warming is observed, at the Žabljak site, based on the collected and analyzed data, a linear trend shows a nearly stable state of average annual temperatures in the period from 2000 to 2022. The average annual temperature in this period increased by 0.04°C . The long-term average temperature value is 6.1°C . The average annual temperatures above the long-term average were recorded in 14 years, while 9 years had temperatures below the long-term average. In the last 10 years, 6 years had average annual temperatures higher than the long-term average, while 4 years had temperatures lower than the long-term average. The maximum average annual temperature of 7.1°C was recorded in 2014, while the minimum average annual temperature of 4.0°C was recorded in 2016.

Fig. 5.260. Average annual temperature values for the period 2000-2022.

Although a nearly balanced state of average annual air temperatures has been determined, significant differences were found in the temperatures across seasons. Using the previously applied methodology and linear trend analysis, both increases and decreases in temperatures (at different values) were determined across all climatic seasons. Specifically, the average annual temperature decreased by 0.16°C during the summer and by 1.25°C during the spring. On the other hand, the average annual temperature increased by 0.42°C during the autumn and by 1.17°C during the winter.

The maximum average annual temperature during the winter was 0.7°C , recorded in 2014, while the minimum temperature was -5.4°C , recorded in 2012. The maximum average annual temperature during the spring was 6.9°C , recorded in 2018, while the lowest average temperature for the spring was 3.0°C , recorded in 2015. The maximum average annual temperature for the summer was 17.7°C , recorded in 2012, while the minimum temperatures were recorded in 2016, with an average value of 9.5°C . During the winter, temperature maxima were recorded in 2012, with an average value of 8.9°C , while the minimum temperature values of 4.5°C were registered in 2007.

Fig. 5.261. Average seasonal temperature values for the period 2000-2022.

The average maximum monthly temperature at the Žabljak location for the period 2000–2022 is 19.4°C. The lowest average maximum monthly temperature was recorded in January, at 10.4°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in August, reaching 29.0°C. During the winter, the average maximum air temperature is 11.0°C. The highest average maximum temperature values are in February (11.2°C), while the lowest values occur in January (10.4°C), which represents the annual minimum. During the spring, the average maximum temperature is 18.3°C. The lowest average maximum temperature in the spring is in March (14.0°C), while the highest is in May (22.6°C). In the summer, the average maximum temperature is 27.6°C. The highest value for the average monthly maximum temperature is recorded in August at 29.0°C (which represents the annual maximum), while the lowest values occur in June, with an average of 26.8°C. During the autumn, the average monthly maximum temperature is 20.5°C. The lowest average monthly maximum temperature is recorded in November (16.7°C), while the highest is in September (23.7°C).

Fig. 5.262. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 2000–2022.

The average extreme maximum temperature for the period 2000–2022 is 24.1°C. The highest temperature recorded at the Žabljak location was 32.4°C, measured on 23.08.2007. The lowest maximum temperature was recorded on 17.01.2020, at 14.3°C. In the referenced period, the extreme maximum monthly temperatures were as follows: January 14.3°C (2020), February 18.8°C (2020), March 17.8°C (2001), April 22.5°C (2003), May 28.3°C (2003), June 31.2°C (2021), July 31.2°C (2007), August 32.4°C (2007), September 28.9°C (2015), October 23.8°C (2012), November 23.6°C (2004), and December 16.4°C (2014).

Fig. 5.263. Maximum monthly air temperatures for the period 2000-2022.

Unlike most other locations, a linear trend analysis for Žabljak shows a decrease in the maximum annual air temperatures over the period from 2000 to 2022, amounting to 1.1°C. The average value of the maximum measured temperatures during the analyzed period is 29.6°C. The highest recorded maximum temperature of 32.4°C was measured in August 2007, while the lowest maximum temperature of 25.6°C was recorded in August 2018.

Fig. 5.264. Maximum annual air temperatures for the period 2000-2022.

According to the physical-geographical conditions and the geographical position of the Žabljak locality, extreme minimum air temperatures have much higher values in terms of the number of days compared to extreme maximum air temperatures. The number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ reaches its highest values during the summer months, while the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is higher during the winter months. The average number of days with extreme maximum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 2.7 days per month. The maximum number of days with a Tmax $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 9.7 days, recorded in January. There are no days with Tmax $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ from May to September. Extreme maximum temperatures Tmax $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 1.9 days. The maximum number of days with Tmax $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 8.9 days, recorded in August. October, November, December, January, February, March, and April have no days with extreme maximum temperatures $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. The average monthly number of days with extreme maximum temperatures Tmax $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 0.1. The maximum value of this indicator is recorded

in August, with an average monthly value of 1 day. During the winter, spring, and autumn seasons, there are no days with air temperatures $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.265. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperature values for the period 2000-2022.

The average minimum monthly temperature at the Žabljak location for the period 1992 – 2022 is -5.8°C . The lowest average minimum monthly temperature was recorded in January at -18.0°C , while the highest was recorded in August at 4.7°C . The average minimum temperature for the winter is -15.9°C , with the lowest temperatures in January, which also represents the annual minimum, and the highest in December at -14.8°C . The recorded average minimum temperature for the spring is -6.4°C . The lowest average minimum temperatures in spring occur in March at -11.0°C , while the highest are in May at -1.4°C . During the summer climatological season, the average values of extreme minimum temperatures are 3.9°C . The lowest average minimum monthly temperature during this season was recorded in June at 2.3°C , while the highest was recorded in August at 4.7°C . The average minimum monthly temperature during the autumn is -4.6°C . The lowest recorded value was in November at -9.3°C , while the highest was in September at -0.4°C .

Fig. 5.266. Average monthly minimum temperatures for the period 2000-2022.

The average value of extreme minimum recorded temperature for the period 2000-2022 is -1.9°C . The lowest average minimum temperature recorded at Žabljak was -25.7°C , measured in January 2000. The highest average minimum temperature was 18.0°C , recorded in August 2000. In the reference period, the extreme minimum monthly values were as follows: January -25.7°C (2000), February -21.5°C (2012), March -24.6°C (2005), April -14.6°C (2003), May -5.5°C (2019), June -2.8°C (2005), July 0.6°C (2000), August 1.8°C (2000), September -3.3°C (2022), October -11.2°C (2009), November -15.2°C (2008), and December -20.2°C (2012).

Fig. 5.267. Monthly minimum air temperatures for the period 2000-2022.

The average value of measured minimum temperatures at Žabljak in the period 2000-2022 is -19.9°C . The highest minimum (extreme) temperature of -14.2°C was recorded on 23 January 2020. The lowest minimum temperature of -25.7°C was recorded on 7 January 2000. The linear trend indicates an increase of 2.82°C , or a decrease in temperature with a negative sign.

Fig. 5.268. Annual minimum air temperatures for the period 2000-2022.

Unlike other analyzed locations, Žabljak has recorded extreme minimum air temperature on a large number of days. Analysis of the available data shows that extreme minimum temperature values $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ are prevalent. Extreme minimum air temperatures $\geq 20.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ were recorded only on two days (one day each in July and August 2007) during the analyzed period from 2000 to 2022. Extreme minimum temperatures $T_{\text{min}} \leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 2.3 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 10.1 days, recorded in January. The months from May to October do not have minimum temperatures $\leq -10.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme minimum temperatures $T_{\text{min}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a higher average monthly value of days compared to the previously analyzed indicator. The monthly average number of days is 12.2 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 28.6 days, recorded in January. Throughout the entire analyzed period (2000-2022), only July and August do not have minimum air temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.269. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 2000-2022.

5.4.1.4 RELATIVE HUMIDITY

The average monthly relative humidity value for Žabljak in the period from 2000 to 2022 is 76.4%. The lowest average monthly relative humidity was measured in August, at 69.8%, while the highest relative humidity was measured in December, at 83.1%. The average relative humidity value for the winter is 81.8%, with the lowest value recorded in February (80.3%) and the highest in December (83.1%). The average measured relative humidity value for the spring is 74.8%. The lowest average relative humidity in the spring was recorded in May (73.3%), while the highest value was measured in March (77.3%). During the summer climatological season, the average relative humidity is 70.0%. The maximum value was measured in June (71.1%), and the lowest relative humidity during this season was recorded in August (69.8%). The average monthly relative humidity value for the autumn is 78.8%. The lowest humidity value during this season was recorded in September (76.8%), while the highest value was recorded in November (80.5%).

Fig. 5.270. Average monthly values of air relative humidity for the period 2000-2022.

The average value of the maximum extreme monthly average air humidity at the Žabljak location for the period 2000-2022 is 85.2%. The highest average humidity value during the analyzed period is 90.0%, measured in December 2009. The lowest maximum average air humidity was recorded in August 2014 at 78.0%. The maximum monthly average air humidity values are as follows: January 90.0% (2010), February 89.0% (2010), March 84.0% (2018), April 86.0% (2014), May 80.0% (2014), June 80.0% (2013), July 80.0% (2010), August 78.0% (2014), September 87.0% (2014), October 90.0% (2010), November 88.0% (2013), and December 90.0% (2009). In the last decade, seven months have recorded the highest average air humidity values, while the other highest average humidity values were measured in the previous decade.

Fig. 5.271. Maximum average values of relative air humidity for the period 2000-2022.

At the Žabljak site, the average value of the minimum average air humidity for the period 2000-2022 is 66.2%. The highest minimum average humidity in the reference period was 74.0%, measured in February 2007. The lowest minimum average humidity (53.0%) was recorded in July 2007. During the analyzed period, the lowest values of average monthly air humidity are as follows: January 71.0% (2007), February 74.0% (2007), March 70.0% (2012), April 66.0% (2016), May 67.0% (2021), June 62.0% (2012), July 53.0% (2007), August 54.0% (2012), September 69.0% (2012), October 70.0% (2019), November 69.0% (2011), and December 69.0% (2016). In the last ten years, eight months recorded the lowest average values of air humidity, while only three values were recorded in the previous decade.

Fig. 5.272. Minimal average monthly values of relative humidity for 2000-2022.

In the reference period, the relative humidity at the Žabljak location has been on a slight increase. The linear trend shows that the relative humidity increased by 3.7% during the period from 2000 to 2022. Within this period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of relative humidity, with a maximum fluctuation of 11.1% between the maximum and minimum humidity values. The average multi-year value of air humidity for the Žabljak location is 76.4%. Ten years have average relative humidity values higher than the multi-year average, while 13 years have values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, only eight years have higher values than the multi-year average. The highest average annual relative humidity value of 82.7% was recorded in 2014, while the lowest average annual value of 71.6% was recorded in 2000.

Fig. 5.273. Average annual values of relative air humidity for the period 2000-2022.

5.4.1.5 PRECIPITATION

The average annual precipitation for the period 1992-2022 is 128.8 mm. The lowest average precipitation occurs in August (63.7 mm), while the highest amount of precipitation occurs in November (222.1 mm).

Fig. 5.274. Average monthly precipitation totals for the period 2000-2022.

At the Žabljak location, during the winter, spring, and autumn seasons, the average precipitation exceeds 100 mm, while the summer is somewhat drier. Specifically, during the winter, an average of 158.2 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum in December of around 197.5 mm and a minimum in January of 135.8 mm. During the spring, an average of 112.4 mm of precipitation is also recorded. April (104.1 mm) and May (104.9 mm) have almost equal amounts of precipitation, while March sees slightly more precipitation, at 128.3 mm. During the summer, precipitation is somewhat lower, with a seasonal average of 77.7 mm. The highest amount of precipitation occurs in June, with 93.0 mm, while the least occurs in August, with 63.7 mm of precipitation. During the autumn, an average of 167.0 mm of precipitation is recorded, with the maximum in November (222.1 mm), which also represents the annual maximum, and the minimum in September, with 119.2 mm of precipitation.

According to the linear trend, from 2000 to 2022, there has been an increase in precipitation during the winter, spring, and summer, while autumn precipitation has decreased. Specifically, during the autumn, precipitation has decreased by 34 mm. During the winter, precipitation has increased by 29 mm, while in the spring, it has increased by 19 mm, and in the summer, it has increased by 9 mm.

Fig. 5.275 Average Precipitation Amount by Climatological Seasons for 1992-2022.

If we analyze the annual precipitation amounts for Žabljak for the period 2000-2022, a linear trend shows an increase of 59 mm. Within this thirty-year period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of precipitation amounts. The average long-term value is 1555.0 mm of precipitation. The maximum annual precipitation sum was recorded in 2010, with a total of 2255.8 mm, while the minimum value of 1074.5 mm was recorded in 2011. In the analyzed series, 9 years had annual precipitation amounts higher than the long-term average, while 14 years had lower totals.

Fig. 5.276. Annual precipitation total for the period 2000-2022.

The average monthly value of the maximum measured precipitation for the period 2000-2022 is 39.1 mm. The highest precipitation value in Žabljak occur in November, with an average of 67.4 mm, which correlates with the average monthly precipitation amount. The lowest average monthly value for the maximum precipitation was recorded in August, at 23.2 mm. The average monthly maximum precipitation for the winter is 44.3 mm, with the lowest value measured in January at 38.8 mm, and the highest in December at 53.6 mm. The average measured maximum precipitation for the spring is 35.6 mm. The lowest average maximum precipitation in spring occurs in May (30.3 mm), while the highest occurs in March (43.1 mm). During the summer, the average maximum precipitation value is slightly lower, at 23.9 mm. The highest average monthly maximum precipitation was recorded in July at 24.5 mm, while the lowest values were observed in August, with 23.2 mm. The average monthly maximum precipitation during the autumn is 52.4 mm, with the maximum in November (67.4 mm, the annual maximum) and the minimum in September with 37.5 mm.

Fig. 5.277. Average monthly value of the maximum precip. amount for 2000-2022.

The average value of extreme precipitation maxima for the Žabljak location for the period 2000-2022 is 91.7 mm. The maximum amount of precipitation, 114.3 mm, was recorded in April 2022. The lowest value of the precipitation maximum, 53.1 mm, was measured in June 2009. During the specified period, extreme maximum precipitation values on a monthly level were as follows: January 77.9 mm (2003), February 85.1 mm (2003), March 95.7 mm (2016), April 114.3 mm (2022), May 61.6 mm (2010), June 53.1 mm (2009), July 64.4 mm (2013), August 59.8 mm (2002), September 86.0 mm (2007), October 137.3 mm (2002), November 141.3 mm (2010), and December 124.2 mm (2000).

Fig. 5.278. Maximum precipitation amounts for the period 2000-2022.

The average maximum precipitation amounts on an annual level for the period 2000-2022 is 95.9 mm. The highest maximum annual precipitation amount of 141.3 mm was recorded in November 2010, while the lowest maximum value of 53.5 mm was recorded in November 2021. The linear trend indicates a slight decrease in the maximum precipitation amounts. This methodology shows that the maximum precipitation values decreased by 15.0 mm over the analyzed period from 2000 to 2022.

Fig. 5.279. Maximum rainfall for the period 2000-2022.

At the Žabljak location, based on the analyzed data on the number of days with precipitation (≥ 0.1 mm, ≥ 1.0 mm, ≥ 10.0 mm), an increase in precipitation is visible during the spring and winter seasons, while a decrease is observed during the summer and late autumn seasons, which is generally a characteristic of most of the analyzed locations. The average number of days with ≥ 0.1 mm of precipitation is 14.9. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 18. The maximum number of days with this precipitation indicator corresponds to the average monthly value of December. The minimum number of days (on average 11 days) with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm corresponds to the average monthly value of September. On average, there are 10.7 days per month with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm, with the highest number of days in December (on average 13 days) and the lowest in August (on average 7.7 days). The average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 3.8. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 5.7, recorded in November, while the minimum number of days with this precipitation indicator is 2.1, recorded in August.

Fig. 5.280. Average monthly values of the number of days with precipitation in the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of the maximum snow height for the period 2000-2022 is 31.9 cm. The months without snow cover are July and August. The highest amount of snow is recorded in March, with an average monthly value of 97.8 cm. During the winter, an average of 69.4 cm of snow falls, with a maximum in February (93.8 cm of snow) and a minimum in December (40.1 cm of snow). During the spring, an average of 48.3 cm of snow falls, with the maximum in March (97.8 cm) and the minimum snowfall in May (long-term monthly average 2.2 cm). During the summer, snow is recorded in June with an average of 0.6 cm, while there are no snowfalls in the other summer months. During the autumn, an average of 9.9 cm of snow falls, with the maximum snowfall in November (22 cm) and the minimum in September (0.3 cm).

Fig. 6.281. Average monthly values of the maximum snow cover height 2000-2022.

The linear trend indicates a decrease in snow cover height by 113 cm from 2000 to 2022. Within the analyzed period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of snow cover height. The average multi-year value of snow height is 383.3 cm. The maximum annual snowfall amount recorded was 847 cm in 2005, while the minimum snow cover height of 154 cm was recorded in 2014.

Fig. 5.282. Average annual values of snow cover height from 2000-2022.

The average values of the maximum snow cover for the period from 2000-2022 are 81.0 cm. During this period, the maximum monthly extreme value of snow cover was 230.0 cm, which occurred in February 2005. The months without snow cover are July and August. During this period, the following maximum snow cover values were recorded on a monthly basis: January 148.0 cm (2013), February 230.0 cm (2005), March 229.0 cm (2005), April 115.0 cm (2015), May 14.0 cm (2015), June 13.0 cm (2005), September 4.0 cm (2002), October 51.0 cm (2009), November 81.0 cm (2004), and December 87.0 cm (2005).

Fig. 5.283. Maximum snow cover sizes by month for the period 2000-2022.

The average value of the maximum snow cover amount on an annual basis is 110.3 cm. The maximum snow cover height on an annual level is 230.0 cm, measured in February 2005, while the lowest annual maximum value is 41.0 cm, measured in April 2014. From 2000 to 2022, the linear trend indicates a decrease in the height of the maximum snow cover values by 42.8 cm.

Fig. 5.284. Maximum snow cover height on an annual basis for the period 2000-2022.

5.5.AUSTRIA SELECTED SITES

5.5.1 HUNDSKIRCHE

5.5.1.1 INSOLATION

The average monthly insolation at the Hundskirche location for the period 1992–2022 is 154.6 hours. The lowest average monthly insolation was measured in December, amounting to 91.2 hours, while the highest average insolation was measured in July, with a value of 195.5 hours.

Fig. 5.285. Average monthly insolation for the period 1992-2022.

The average insolation for the winter is 120.6 hours, with the lowest number of sunshine hours in December (the annual minimum value) and the highest in February (152.3 hours). The average sum of sunshine hours for the spring is 169.9 hours. The lowest sunshine in the spring occurs in April (162.8 hours), and the highest in March (177.6 hours). During the summer climatological season, the average sunshine duration is 186.5 hours, with the highest sunshine in July (195.5 hours) and the lowest in June (173.1 hours). The average monthly sunshine during the autumn is 141.4 hours, with maximum values in September (172.3 hours) and the minimum in November (105.2 hours of sunshine).

Fig. 5.286. Average sunshine by seasons for the period 1992-2022.

The annual sunshine in the reference period has been steadily increasing and correlates with the rise in radiation and air temperatures. It has been determined that sunshine in the period from 1992 to 2022 at the Hundskirche location increased by 182.4 hours. The average multi-year value of sunshine is 1837.0 hours. 17 years had an annual sunshine higher than the average multi-year value, while 14 years had values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, 5 years had higher, and 5 years had lower sunshine compared to the multi-year average. The maximum average annual sunshine of 2127.1 hours was recorded in 2003, while the minimum average annual sunshine of 1374.5 hours was recorded in 1993.

Fig. 5.287. Total annual insolation for the period 1992-2022.

5.5.1.2 RADIATION

The average monthly radiation value at the Hundskirche site for the period 1992-2022 is 103.3 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly solar radiation was measured in November, amounting to 53.3 kWh/m², while the highest average radiation was measured in July at 136.6 kWh/m². The average radiation for the winter is 79.7 kWh/m², with the lowest value in December (66.7 kWh/m²) and the highest in February (96.8 kWh/m²). The average radiation sum for the spring is 124.5 kWh/m². The lowest radiation in the spring is in March (119.0 kWh/m²), while the highest is in May (132.2 kWh/m²). During the summer climatological season, the average radiation is 130.2 kWh/m², with the highest in July (136.6 kWh/m²) and the lowest in August (125.9 kWh/m²). The average monthly radiation during the autumn is 78.9 kWh/m², with maximum values in September (105.0 kWh/m²) and the minimum in November (53.3 kWh/m²).

Fig. 5.288. Average monthly radiation for the period 1992-2022.

Analysis of the annual sum of solar radiation for the period 1992-2022 shows an increase in this climatic element by 60.8 kWh/m². The average long-term value of radiation is 1240.0 kWh/m². The average annual radiation exceeds the long-term average value in 14 years, while 17 years have values below the long-term average. In the last 10 years, 4 years have higher, and 6 years have lower radiation compared to the long-term average. The maximum average annual radiation of 1430.8 kWh/m² was recorded in 2003, while the minimum average annual radiation was recorded in 1996, amounting to 1044.2 kWh/m².

Fig. 5.289. Annual radiation for the period 1992-2022.

5.5.1.3 AIR TEMPERATURE

The average monthly temperature for the Hundskirche location for the period 1992-2022 is 8.2°C. The lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January, at -2.7°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in July, at 18.3°C. The average temperatures for the winter are -1.6°C, with the lowest temperatures recorded in January (-2.7°C, which represents the annual minimum) and the highest in February (-0.8°C). The average temperature for the spring is 7.8°C. The lowest average temperatures in spring are in March (3.3°C), and the highest are in May (12.5°C). During the summer climatological season, the average temperature is 17.6°C. The highest average monthly temperature for the summer was recorded in July, at 18.4°C, while the lowest value was recorded in June, at 16.5°C. The average monthly temperatures in the autumn are 9.0°C. The coldest month is November, with an average of 3.8°C, while the warmest month is September, with an average of 13.7°C.

Fig. 4.290. Average monthly temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Over the past thirty years at the Hundskirche location, temperatures have been steadily increasing. The linear trend shows that the temperature has risen with a warming value of 1.3°C . The average multi-year temperature is 8.2°C . There were 16 years with annual average temperatures higher than the multi-year average, while 15 years had values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, 8 years had higher average annual temperatures compared to the multi-year average. The maximum average annual temperature of 9.2°C was recorded in 2015. The approximate maximum temperature values were recorded in 2018, 2019, and 2022, with an annual average of 9.1°C , while the minimum average annual temperature of 6.7°C was recorded in 1996.

Fig. 5.291. Average annual temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

In addition to the overall increase in temperature at the Hundskirche location, a linear trend shows an increase in temperature (at various values) across all climatological seasons. Specifically, the temperature increase for the summer is 1.6°C, for autumn 1.9°C, for spring 0.5°C, and for winter 1.1°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter is 0.5°C, measured in 2020, while the minimum temperature was -4.6°C, measured in 2005. The maximum average annual temperature during the spring is 9.6°C, measured in 2007. The lowest average temperature for the spring was 5.8°C, recorded in 2021. The maximum average annual temperatures for summer reached 19.7°C, recorded in 2003, while the minimum temperatures were recorded in 2006, with an average value of 16.2°C. During the winter, temperature maxima were recorded in 2006 with an average value of 10.9°C, while the minimum temperature of 7.0°C was recorded in 1993.

Fig. 5.292. Average seasonal temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum monthly air temperature for the period 1992 – 2022 is 19.2°C. The lowest average maximum monthly temperature was measured in December at 7.2°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in July at 28.9°C. The average maximum air temperature for the winter is 8.7°C. The lowest value of the average maximum temperature during this season was measured in December (7.2°C), which also represents the annual minimum. The highest values of the average maximum monthly air temperature during the winter were recorded in February at 11.2°C. The average maximum temperature measured for the spring is 20.4°C. The lowest average maximum temperature in the spring is in March at 16.5°C, and the highest in May at 24.4°C. During the summer climatological season, the average maximum temperature is 28.5°C. The average monthly maximum temperatures during the summer are not below 28°C. The highest value of this climatic element during the summer was recorded in July at 28.9°C, while the lowest value was recorded in June at 28.0°C. The average monthly maximum temperature during the autumn is 19.3°C. The coldest month is November with 13.9°C, while the warmest is September with 23.9°C.

Fig. 5.293. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average annual value of the maximum measured temperatures for the period 1992-2022 is 24.2°C. The highest temperature recorded was 34.4°C, measured in June 2019. The lowest maximum temperature was measured in December 2016 and was 11.9°C. During the thirty-year period, extreme maximum monthly temperature values were recorded as follows: January 14.2°C (2008), February 17.9°C (1998), March 20.5°C (1993), April 25.2°C (2012), May 29.0°C (2009), June 34.4°C (2019), July 32.6°C (2015), August 33.5°C (2015), September 28.5°C (2006), October 23.5°C (2009), November 18.8°C (2022), and December 11.9°C (2016).

Fig. 5.294. Maximum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Based on the analyzed indicators of maximum annual air temperature, an increase of 1.9°C has been determined for the period 1992-2022. The average value of the maximum measured temperature is 30.2°C. The highest maximum temperature of 34.4°C was recorded in June 2019, while the lowest maximum temperature of 26.2°C was observed in September 1997. In general, extreme values of maximum temperatures show a tendency to increase.

Fig. 5.295. Maximum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

At the Hundskirche location, as at all other analyzed locations, the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures of $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ are highest during the summer months, while the number of days with extreme maximum air temperature of $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is elevated during the winter months. The average number of days with extreme maximum temperature $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ has an average monthly value of 2.7 days. The maximum number of days with $T_{\text{max}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 12.6 days, recorded in January. The months from April to September do not have maximum temperature $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum temperature $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly number of 1.9 days. The maximum number of days with $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 8 days, recorded in August. October, November, December, January, February, and March do not have extreme maximum air temperature of $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum air temperature $T_{\text{max}} \geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 0.1 day, with the maximum average number of days (0.9) in August. During the winter, spring, and autumn seasons, there are no days with a maximum air temperature of $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.296. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

The average minimum monthly air temperature for the period 1992 – 2022 is -2.3°C . The lowest average minimum temperature was recorded in January at -14.9°C , while the highest was recorded in July at 9.9°C . The average minimum temperature for the winter is -13.7°C , with the lowest temperature recorded in January (the annual minimum) and the highest in December at -11.8°C . The average minimum temperature for the spring is -3.0°C , with the lowest in March at -10.2°C and the highest in May at 3.7°C . During the summer climatological season, the average minimum temperature is 8.7°C . The lowest average minimum temperature in this season was recorded in June at 7.6°C , while the highest was in July at 9.9°C . The average minimum temperature during the autumn is -1.1°C . The coldest month is November at -5.8°C , while the warmest is September at 3.7°C .

Fig. 5.297. Average Monthly Minimum Temperatures for the Period 1992-2022.

The average values of extreme minimum temperature for the 30-year period is -8.1°C . The lowest average minimum temperature was recorded in March 2005, at -23.8°C . On the other hand, the highest average minimum temperature was recorded in July of the same year (2005), at 6.2°C . In this thirty-year period, the extreme average minimum monthly temperature were: January -21.3°C (2006), February -22.3°C (1996), March -23.8°C (2005), April -6.7°C (2003), May 0.0°C (2019), June 2.9°C (2006), July 6.2°C (2005), August 5.4°C (1995), September -0.5°C (1995), October -8.5°C (1997), November -10.8°C (1995), and December -17.6°C (2009). From this data, it can be concluded that in the last ten years, records for minimum temperatures were set for only one month, while the other extreme minimum temperatures were recorded in the first part of the observed period.

Fig. 5.298. Monthly minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the measured extreme minimum temperature for the period 1992-2022 is -16.6°C . The highest extreme minimum temperature of -11.2°C was recorded in January 2016. The lowest minimum temperature of -23.8°C was recorded in March 2005. Like other temperature indicators, extreme values of minimum temperature show a rising trend. A linear trend analysis for the reference period determined an increase of 1.1°C in extreme minimum air temperatures at the Hundskirche location.

Fig. 5.299. Minimum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Analysis of available meteorological data shows that the Hundskirche site exhibits slightly higher values for the average monthly number of days with extreme minimum values compared to extreme maximum values. Significant differences are also visible in the number of days with air temperatures that are ≤ -10.0 °C, < 0.0 °C, ≥ 20.0 °C, and < 0.0 °C. Extreme minimum temperatures $T_{min} \leq -10.0$ °C has an average monthly value of 1.4 days. The maximum number Fig. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022. of days with temperatures ≤ -10.0 °C is 7.2 days, recorded in January. The months from April to October do not experience minimum temperatures of ≤ -10.0 °C. Extreme minimum temperature $T_{min} < 0.0$ °C have an average monthly value of 10.2 days. The maximum number of days with temperatures < 0.0 °C is 28.9 days, recorded in January. The months of May, June, July, August, and September do not experience minimum temperatures of < 0.0 °C. Extreme minimum temperatures ≥ 20.0 °C have an average monthly value of 0.02 days, with the highest average number of days in July at 0.2. Only the months of July (average 0.2 days) and August (average 0.1 days) have average monthly values for the number of days with minimum temperatures ≥ 20.0 °C.

Fig. 5.300. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

5.5.1.4 RELATIVE HUMIDITY

The average monthly relative humidity value for Hundskirche for the period 1992-2022 is 76.8%. The lowest average monthly relative humidity was recorded in June at 70.8%, while the highest relative humidity was recorded in December at 84.9%. The average relative humidity for the winter is 80.8%, with the lowest values recorded in February at 76.4% and the highest in December at 84.9%. The average relative humidity value for the spring is 71.8%. The lowest average relative humidity value in the spring is in May at 71.0%, while the highest values was recorded in March at 72.3%. During the summer, the average relative humidity is 72.4%. The maximum value was recorded in August at 75.3%, while the minimum value was recorded in June at 70.8%. The average monthly relative humidity value in the autumn is 82.3%. The lowest value of air humidity during this season was recorded in September at 80.1%, while the highest value was recorded in November at 84.4%.

Fig. 5.301. Average monthly values of air relative humidity for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of extreme maximum air humidity for the Hundskirche locality for the period 1992-2022 is 85.1%. The highest average air humidity value during the analyzed thirty-year period was 93.3%, recorded in November 2019. The lowest maximum average air humidity value was measured in July 2012, at 77.3%. The maximum monthly values of average air humidity during the analyzed period were as follows: January 89.6% (1996), February 87.6% (2018), March 81.8% (2018), April 79.9% (2019), May 80.6% (2018), June 78.4% (1997), July 77.3% (2012), August 82.7% (1999), September 88.1% (2017), October 89.6% (1992), November 93.3% (2019), and December 92.5% (1995).

Fig. 5.302. Maximum average values of relative air humidity for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the minimum air humidity for the period 1992-2022 is 66.7%. The highest minimum average air humidity in the reference period was 74.8%, recorded in October 2017. The lowest minimum average air humidity (59.0%) was recorded in April 2020. In the analyzed period, the lowest monthly average humidity values were recorded in: January 67.9% (2020), February 61.6% (2020), March 59.4% (2022), April 59.0% (2020), May 63.3% (2020), June 62.5% (2021), July 62.7% (2022), August 69.1% (2015), September 74.5% (2021), October 74.8% (2017), November 74.2% (1995), and December 71.5% (2016).

Fig. 5.303. Minimum average monthly values of air relative humidity for 1992-2022.

In the reference period, the air relative humidity at the studied location has been consistently decreasing. The linear trend shows that the relative humidity at Hundskirche has decreased by 2.2% during the period from 1992 to 2022. The average multi-year relative humidity value is 76.9%. The average values of relative humidity higher than the multi-year average were recorded in 14 years, while 17 years had values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, only 4 years showed values higher than the multi-year average. The maximum average annual relative humidity of 79.7% was recorded in 1993, while the minimum average annual value of 73.1% was recorded in 2020.

Fig. 5.304. Average annual values of air relative humidity for the period 1992-2022.

5.5.1.5 PRECIPITATION

The average annual precipitation at the Hundskirche location for the period 1992-2022 is 109.7 mm. The smallest average amount of precipitation occurs in February (54.0 mm), while the largest amount of precipitation occurs in August (180.1 mm).

Fig. 5.305. Average monthly precipitation totals for the period 1992-2022.

At the Hundskirche site, the least amount of precipitation is recorded during the winter, with an average of 66.6 mm. The maximum precipitation during this season is recorded in December, with around 88.3 mm, and the minimum in February with 54.0 mm. During the spring, a slightly higher amount of precipitation is recorded, with an average of 86.7 mm. The maximum precipitation during this season occurs in May (115.3 mm), and the minimum in March (63.1 mm). During the summer, the average amount of precipitation is 149.5 mm. The most precipitation occurs in August (180.1 mm), and the least in June (118.7 mm). In the autumn, a smaller amount of precipitation is recorded compared to the summer. On average, 136.1 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum in November (146.4 mm) and a minimum in September (120.3 mm).

In the period from 1992 to 2022, an increase in the amount of precipitation was observed during all climatological seasons. The greatest seasonal increase in precipitation was recorded during the winter climatological season. Specifically, during the thirty-year period, the amount of precipitation increased by 81 mm. A slightly smaller increase in precipitation was recorded

during the spring, with a total increase of 15 mm. Almost the same total increase in precipitation (14 mm) was recorded during the autumn climatological season, while the increase during the summer was 33 mm.

Fig. 5.306. Average precipitation by climatological seasons for the period 1992-2022.

In the thirty-year period (1992-2022), an increase in the annual total precipitation of 456 mm was observed. The average multi-year value is 1310.2 mm of precipitation. The maximum annual precipitation total was recorded in 2021 at 2091.1 mm, while the minimum value of 948.3 mm was recorded in 1995. In the analyzed series, 14 years have annual precipitation totals greater than the long-term average, while 17 years have lower precipitation totals.

Fig. 5.307. Annual sum of precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of precipitation maxima at the Hundskirche site for the period 1992-2022 is 32.4 mm. The maximum precipitation values are recorded in September, with an average value of the measured maxima being 44.0 mm. The lowest average monthly value of the maximum precipitation amount was measured in February, amounting to 22.0 mm.

The average monthly maximum precipitation amount for the winter is 25.6 mm, with the lowest values measured in February at 22.0 mm and the highest in December at 29.8 mm. The measured average maximum precipitation amount for the spring is 27.0 mm. The lowest average maximum precipitation amount in the spring was in March (25.2 mm) and April (25.2 mm), while the highest was in May at 30.5 mm.

During the summer, the average maximum precipitation amount is 35.9 mm. The highest average monthly maximum precipitation values were measured in August, at 43.4 mm, while the lowest value of precipitation maxima was measured in June at 29.1 mm. The average monthly maximum precipitation amount during the autumn is 41.1 mm, with the maximum precipitation recorded in October at 44.0 mm and the minimum in September at 38.2 mm.

Fig. 5.308. Average monthly value of maximum precipitation amounts for 1992-2022.

The average value of extreme maximum precipitation at the studied location for the period 1992-2022 is 88.9 mm. The maximum amount of precipitation of 116.1 mm was recorded in November 1996. The lowest value of the precipitation maximum of 67.3 mm was measured in June 2011. In the aforementioned thirty-year period, extreme maximum precipitation values on a monthly level were as follows: January 83.9 mm (2001), February 102.5 mm (2019), March 70.5 mm (2014), April 78.9 mm (2017), May 72.0 mm (2011), June 67.3 mm (2011), July 103.4 mm (2016), August 98.2 mm (2014), September 79.9 mm (2012), October 103.9 mm (1996), November 116.1 mm (1996), and December 90.3 mm (2020).

Fig. 5.309. Maximum precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of the maximum measured precipitation on an annual level for the period 1992-2022 is 74.1 mm. The highest maximum precipitation amount on an annual level of 116.1 mm was measured in November 1996, while the lowest maximum value of annual precipitation of 66.6 mm was recorded in June 1997. A linear trend analysis indicates an increase in the maximum precipitation amount over the thirty-year period from 1992-2022, amounting to 13.6 mm.

Fig. 5.310. Maximum amounts of precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

In the period 1992-2022, at the Hundskirche location, an analysis was conducted on the number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm, ≥ 1.0 mm, ≥ 5.0 mm, ≥ 10.0 mm, ≥ 20.0 mm, and ≥ 50.0 mm, based on which it is evident that this location exhibits reverse trends in the number of days with precipitation compared to most other locations. The smallest number of days with precipitation is recorded during the winter, while the increased number of days with precipitation is observed during the summer, and for some indicators, the autumn climatological season as well.

Specifically, the average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is 11. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 14.8, which is the average monthly value for June and July, while the minimum value of 16.3 is recorded in January. The average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm is 8.6, with the maximum number of days in August (average 11.9 days) and the minimum in January (average 4.5 days). On average, 5.2 days per month experience precipitation ≥ 5.0 mm. The maximum number of days

with this precipitation indicator is recorded in July (average 8.4 days), while the minimum is recorded in January (average 2.1 days). The average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 3.4. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 5.3, recorded in July, while the minimum number of days (average value 1.2) with this precipitation indicator is recorded in January and February. Precipitation values ≥ 20.0 mm are recorded on average in 1.5 days per month. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm is 2.9 (average monthly value in October), while the minimum number of days is 0.4 (average monthly value in February). The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm is 0.2. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 0.5, which represents the average monthly value for October and November, while March has no days when precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm is recorded.

Fig. 5.311. Average monthly values of the number of days with precipitation in the period 1992-2022.

5.6 GERMANY SELECTED SITES

5.6.1 UNSLEBEN AND KLEINBARDORF

5.6.1.1 INSOLATION

The average monthly insolation for Kleinbardorf and Unsleben for the period 1995–2022 (for which continuous data have been measured) is 136.8 hours. The lowest average monthly insolation was measured in December and is 23.6 hours, while the highest average insolation was measured in July and is 233.8 hours.

Fig. 5.312. Average monthly insolation for the period 1995-2022.

The average insolation for the winter is 42.0 hours, with the lowest number of sunshine hours in December (23.6 hours) and the highest in February (66.5 hours). The average sunshine total for the spring is 171.4 hours. The lowest sunshine in the spring is in March (143.0 hours), while the highest is in May (202.4 hours). During the summer, the average sunshine is 228.2 hours, with the maximum sunshine in July (233.8 hours) and the minimum in August (220.1 hours). The average monthly sunshine in the autumn is 105.4 hours, with the highest values in September (161.7 hours) and the minimum in November (49.0 hours).

Fig. 5.313. Average sunshine by seasons for the period 1992-2022.

Sunshine has been steadily increasing on an annual basis. It has been established that sunshine increased by 619.2 hours over the given period. Within this thirty-year period, there are certain annual fluctuations in the increase and decrease of sunshine. The average multi-year value of sunshine is 1641.0 hours. Twelve years have annual sunshine values higher than the multi-year average, while sixteen years have values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, no year has had lower sunshine than the multi-year average. The maximum average annual sunshine of 1958.9 hours was recorded in 2022, while the minimum average annual sunshine of 1118.3 hours was recorded in 1999.

Fig. 5.314. Total annual sunshine for the period 1995-2022.

5.6.1.2 RADIATION

Solar radiation in the analyzed period (1995-2022) correlates with sunshine and air temperatures. The average monthly value of radiation for the locations of Kleinbardorf and Unsleben for the period 1995 – 2022 is 93.5 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly solar radiation was recorded in December and amounts to 17.4 kWh/m², while the highest average radiation was recorded in June and amounts to 170.7 kWh/m².

The average radiation for the winter is 27.5 kWh/m², with the lowest value of solar radiation measured in December (17.4 kWh/m²) and the highest in February (42.3 kWh/m²). The average radiation sum for the spring is 126.9 kWh/m². The minimum solar radiation in the spring was recorded in March (95.8 kWh/m²), while the maximum solar radiation was recorded in May (157.9 kWh/m²). During the summer climatological season, the average solar radiation is 159.8 kWh/m², with the highest value in June (170.7 kWh/m²) and the lowest in August (145.2 kWh/m²). The average monthly solar radiation in the autumn is 59.9 kWh/m². The maximum values of solar radiation during this season were recorded in September (98.4 kWh/m²), while the minimum values were recorded in November (24.8 kWh/m²).

Fig. 5.315. Average monthly radiation for the period 1995-2022.

A linear trend has shown an increase in annual radiation in the period from 1995 to 2022, amounting to 427.2 kWh/m². The average multi-year value of radiation is 1122.1 kWh/m². The average annual radiation higher than the multi-year average value occurred in 16 years, while 12 years had values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, no year had lower radiation than the multi-year average. The maximum and minimum annual radiation fully correlates with solar insolation. The maximum average annual radiation of 1358.5 kWh/m² was recorded in 2022, while the minimum average annual radiation was recorded in 1999 and amounted to 810.6 kWh/m².

Fig. 5.316. Annual radiation for the period 1995-2022.

5.6.1.3 AIR TEMPERATURE

The average monthly temperature for the Kleinbardorf location for the period 1992-2022 is 9.0°C, while for Unsleben it is slightly lower at 8.8°C. For Kleinbardorf, the lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January at 0.3°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in July at 18.3°C. For Unsleben, the lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January at 0.0°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in July at 18.1°C. At Kleinbardorf, the average temperature for the winter is 0.9°C, with the lowest temperatures recorded in January at 0.3°C (representing the annual minimum) and the highest in February at 1.3°C. The average temperatures for the spring are 8.7°C, with the lowest temperatures in March at 4.4°C and the highest in May at 13.0°C. During the summer, the average temperature is 17.6°C, with the highest average monthly temperature recorded in July at 18.3°C, while the lowest temperature was in June at 16.3°C. The average monthly temperature in the autumn is 8.9°C, with November being the coldest month at 4.4°C and September being the warmest at 13.5°C.

At Unsleben, the average temperature for the winter is 0.6°C, with the lowest temperatures recorded in January at 0.0°C and the highest in December at 1.0°C. The average temperature for the spring is 8.5°C, with the lowest temperatures in March at 4.1°C and the highest in May at 12.9°C. During the summer, the average temperature is 17.4°C, with the highest average monthly temperature recorded in July at 18.1°C, while the lowest temperature was in June at 16.5°C. During the autumn, the average monthly temperatures are 8.5°C, with the lowest average temperature recorded in November at 4.0°C and the highest in September at 13.1°C.

Fig. 3.317. Average monthly temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

As with other locations, the temperatures at the Kleinbardorf site have been steadily increasing over the last thirty years. The linear trend shows a temperature rise of 0.7°C. The average multi-year temperature value is 9.0°C. The average annual temperatures greater than the multi-year average value occurred in 17 years, while 14 years had values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, 8 years had average annual temperatures higher than the multi-year average. The highest average annual temperature of 10.2°C was recorded in 2018. The lowest average annual temperature of 7.0°C was recorded in 1996.

Similarly, the temperature at the Unsleben site has also increased over the last thirty years. It has been determined that the temperature has risen by 1.0°C. The average multi-year

temperature value is 8.8°C. The average annual temperatures greater than the multi-year average value occurred in 13 years, while 18 years had values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, 7 years had average annual temperatures higher than the multi-year average. The highest average annual temperature of 9.9°C was recorded in 2018. The lowest average annual temperature of 6.6°C was recorded in 1996.

Fig. 5.318. Average annual temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

In addition to the overall increase in temperature at the Kleinbardorf site, a linear trend has shown temperature increases (at varying values) during the summer, autumn, and winter, with a slight decrease in temperature during the spring climatological season. Specifically, the temperature increase in the summer is 1.0°C, in the autumn is 1.3°C, and in the winter is 1.0°C, while during the spring, the average temperature decreased by 0.5°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter is 3.1°C, measured in 2020, while the minimum temperature was -3.1°C, measured in 2010. The maximum average annual temperature during the spring is 10.2°C, measured in 2018. The lowest average annual temperature for the spring is 6.6°C, recorded in 2013. The maximum average annual temperature for the summer is 20.4°C, registered in 2003, while the minimum temperature values were recorded in 1996, with

an average value of 15.9°C. During the winter, the maximum temper. was recorded in 2006, with an average value of 11.1°C, while the minimum temp. of 6.5°C was recorded in 1993.

Also, in the thirty-year analyzed period, a linear trend for temperature increases during the winter, summer, and autumn was established at the Unsleben site, while a slight decrease in temperature during the spring was found. The temperature increase in the summer is 1.4°C, in the autumn is 1.6°C, while the decrease in the spring is 0.1°C, and in the winter is 1.2°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter is 2.9°C, measured in 2020, while the minimum temperature was -3.5°C, measured in 2010. The maximum average annual temperature during the spring is 9.8°C, measured in 2018. The lowest average annual temperature for the spring is 6.4°C, recorded in 2013. The maximum average annual temperature for the summer is 20.3°C, registered in 2003, while the minimum temperature values were recorded in 1996, with an average value of 15.6°C. During the winter, the maximum temperature was recorded in 2006, with an average value of 10.8°C, while the minimum temperature of 6.2°C was recorded in 1993.

Fig. 5.319. Average seasonal temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum monthly air temperature for the Kleinbardorf location from 1992 to 2022 is 21.8°C. The lowest average maximum temperature was recorded in January, at 10.2°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in July, at 32.4°C. Similar values were observed for the maximum monthly air temperatures at the Unsleben location. The average maximum monthly temperatures for this location from 1992 to 2022 are also 21.8°C. The lowest average maximum temperature was recorded in January, at 10.5°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in July, at 32.6°C.

Additionally, when it comes to seasonal values of average maximum air temperatures, both Kleinbardorf and Unsleben locations have nearly identical indicators, with average monthly deviations in values ranging from 0.1 to 0.3°C. For Kleinbardorf, the average maximum air temperature for the winter is 11.2°C. The lowest value of the average maximum temperature during this season was recorded in January (10.2°C), and the highest value was recorded in February at 12.3°C. The average maximum temperature for the spring is 23.1°C, with the lowest average maximum temperature in March at 18.1°C and the highest in May at 27.7°C. During the summer climatological season, the average value of maximum temperatures is 31.9°C. The highest value of the climatic element analyzed during the summer was recorded in July at 32.4°C, while the lowest value was recorded in June at 31.2°C. The average monthly maximum temperature during the autumn is 20.8°C. The lowest value of the maximum air temperature during the autumn was recorded in November (14.3°C), while the highest value was recorded in September, with an average value of 26.8°C.

For Unsleben, the average maximum air temperature for the winter is 11.1°C. The lowest value of the average maximum temperature during this season was recorded in January (10.9°C), and the highest value was recorded in February at 11.9°C. The average maximum temperature for the spring 23.0°C, with the lowest average maximum temperature in March at 17.6°C and the highest in May at 27.7°C. During the summer climatological season, the average value of maximum temperatures is 32.1°C. The highest value of the climatic element analyzed during the summer was recorded in July at 32.6°C, while the lowest values were recorded in June at 31.3°C. The average monthly maximum temperature during the autumn is 20.8°C. The lowest value of the maximum air temperature during the autumn was recorded in November at 14.3°C, while the highest value was recorded in September, with an average value of 27.0°C.

Fig. 5.320. Average annual of the maximum temperature for the period 1992-2022.

The average annual value of the maximum recorded temperatures for the Kleinbardorf location from 1992 to 2022 is 26.5°C. The highest recorded temperature was 37.5°C, measured in July 2022. The lowest maximum temperature was recorded in January 2002, at 13.7°C. During the thirty-year period, the extreme maximum temperature values at the monthly level were as follows: January 13.7°C (2002), February 18.0°C (2021), March 22.7°C (2021), April 29.6°C (2012), May 31.4°C (2005), June 34.4°C (2019), July 37.3°C (2022), August 37.5°C (2015), September 31.4°C (2016), October 25.9°C (2011), November 19.8°C (2022), and December 16.6°C (2022).

Fig. 5.321. Maximum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average annual value of the maximum recorded temperature for the location of Unsleben for the period 1992-2022 is 26.5°C. The highest recorded air temperature was 39.1°C, measured in July 2019. The lowest maximum temperature was recorded in January 2015, at 14.0°C. In the specified thirty-year period, the extreme maximum values of temperature on a monthly level were as follows: January 14.0°C (2015), February 18.2°C (2019), March 23.0°C (2012), April 29.9°C (2012), May 31.6°C (2008), June 36.0°C (2019), July 39.1°C (2019), August 38.2°C (2015), September 31.7°C (2016), October 26.8°C (2011), November 20.0°C (2020), and December 17.0°C (2022).

Fig. 5.322. Maximum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Extreme values of maximum temperatures have a tendency to increase. For Kleinbardorf, the annual increase in maximum air temperature for the period 1992-2022 is 2.5°C, while for Unsleben, the increase in maximum air temperature over the same period is 3.1°C. The average value of the highest recorded air temperature at Kleinbardorf is 34.2°C. The highest maximum temperature of 37.5°C was recorded in June 2015, while the lowest maximum temperature of 31.1°C was recorded in September 1993. The average value of the highest recorded air temperatures at Unsleben is similar to Kleinbardorf, at 34.4°C. The highest maximum temperature of 39.1°C was recorded in June 2019, while the lowest maximum temperature of 31.0°C was recorded in September 1996.

Fig. 5.323. Maximum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Based on the analysis of available data, it can be concluded that both locations, Unsleben and Kleinbardorf, have quite similar trends in the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures ($< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$). Specifically, for the location of Unsleben, the average monthly number of days with extreme maximum temperature $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 1.5 days. The maximum number of days with temperature $T_{\text{max}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was 7.1 days, recorded in January. The months from April to October do not have maximum temperature below 0.0°C . The average monthly number of days with extreme maximum temperature $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 3.8 days. The maximum number of days with temperature $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was 14.5 days, recorded in July. The months of November, December, January, and March do not have an extreme maximum temperature of air with $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum air temperature $T_{\text{max}} \geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was recorded on average for 0.9 days per month. The maximum value of this temperature parameter was 4.4 days, recorded in July. The months of January, February, March, April, October, November, and December did not have days with maximum air temperatures $T_{\text{max}} \geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

For the location of Kleinbardorf, the average monthly number of days with extreme maximum temperature $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 1.4 days. The maximum number of days with extreme temperature $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ was 7.7 days, recorded in January. The months from April to October do not have maximum temperatures lower than 0.0°C . The average monthly number of days with extreme maximum temperature $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 3.7 days. The maximum number of days with extreme air temperature above 25.0°C was 13.5 days, recorded in July. The months of October, November, December, January, and March do not have extreme maximum air temperature with $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. The average monthly number of days with extreme maximum air temperature $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 0.8 days. The maximum number of days with extreme temperature above 30.0°C was recorded in July, with a value of 4.1 days. Extreme air temperature exceeding 30.0°C were not recorded in the months of January, February, March, April, October, November, and December.

Fig. 5.324. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

The average minimum monthly air temperature for the location of Kleinbardorf for the period 1992–2022 is -3.8°C . The lowest average minimum temperature was recorded in January at -13.2°C , while the highest temperature was recorded in July at 5.4°C . The average minimum temperature for the winter is -12.0°C , with the lowest temperature recorded in January (which

also represents the annual minimum), and the highest in December at -11.3°C . The measured average minimum temperature for the spring is -4.7°C . The lowest average minimum temperature in the spring occurred in March at -7.9°C , and the highest in May at -0.8°C . During the summer climatological season, the average minimum temperature is 4.4°C . The lowest recorded average monthly minimum temperature during this season occurred in June at 3.1°C , while the highest value of the analyzed climatic parameter occurred in July at 5.4°C . The average monthly minimum temperature during the autumn is -2.9°C . The lowest recorded value of the minimum air temperature was measured in November (-6.3°C), while the highest value was recorded in September at 0.9°C .

Also, similar to other parameters, the locations of Kleinbardorf and Unsleben have similar values for minimum air temperatures. Specifically, the average minimum monthly air temperature for the location of Unsleben for the period 1992–2022 is -3.5°C . The lowest average minimum temperature was recorded in January at -12.9°C , while the highest temperature was recorded in July at 5.7°C . The average minimum temperature for the winter is -11.9°C , with the lowest temperatures recorded in January (-12.9°C , which represents the annual minimum), and the highest in December at -11.0°C . The measured average minimum temperature for the spring is -4.3°C . The lowest average minimum temperatures in the spring occurred in March at -7.9°C , and the highest in May at -0.6°C . During the summer climatological season, the average minimum temperatures are 4.8°C . The lowest recorded average monthly minimum temperature during this season occurred in June at 3.6°C , while the highest value of the analyzed climatic parameter occurred in July at 5.7°C . The average monthly minimum temperature during the autumn is -2.8°C . The lowest recorded value of the minimum air temperature was measured in November (-6.3°C), while the highest value was recorded in September at 1.1°C .

Fig. 5.325. Average monthly minimum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average extreme minimum temperature for the period 1992-2022 is -10.3°C . The lowest average minimum temperature at the Kleinbardorf location was -24.0°C , measured in December 2010. The highest average minimum temperature was measured in July 2019, at 2.8°C . During the aforementioned thirty-year period, extreme minimum average monthly temperature values were recorded as follows: January -22.3°C (2010), February -22.9°C (2021), March -15.9°C (2005), April -11.0°C (2020), May -5.8°C (2011), June 0.2°C (1997), July 2.8°C (2019), August 1.5°C (2016), September -3.0°C (2019), October -9.6°C (1997), November -13.3°C (2005), and December -24.0°C (2010). These indicators show that four months in the last ten years recorded extreme minimum temperature values, while the remaining minimum values were recorded in the first two decades of the observed period.

Fig. 5.326. Minimum monthly air temperatures at the Kleinbardorf location for the period 1992-2022.

The average extreme minimum air temperature measured at the Unsleben location for the period 1992-2022 is -9.8°C . The lowest average minimum temperature recorded was -22.5°C , measured in February 2021. The highest average minimum temperature was recorded in July 2005 and was 3.4°C . In the analysed thirty-year period, extreme average minimum monthly temperatures had the following values: January -21.8°C (2002), February -22.5°C (2021), March -17.5°C (2013), April -10.5°C (2003), May -5.4°C (2011), June 0.4°C (2009), July 3.4°C (2005), August 1.9°C (2016), September -1.6°C (2018), October -8.1°C (1997), November -13.9°C (1993), and December -21.8°C (2010).

Fig. 5.327. Monthly minimum air temperat. at the Unsleben location for 1992-2022.

The average annual minimum air temperature measured for the period 1992–2022 is -16.2°C for Kleinbardorf and -16.1°C for Unsleben. The highest minimum (extreme) temperature of -9.2°C for Kleinbardorf and -8.2°C for Unsleben was recorded in December 2014. The lowest minimum temperature of -24.0°C for Kleinbardorf was recorded in December 2010, while for Unsleben, the lowest value of -22.5°C was recorded in February 2021. As with other temperature indicators, extreme minimum temperatures show a rising trend. The linear trend analysis for the 30-year period revealed an increase in minimum air temperatures of 0.2°C for Kleinbardorf and 1.3°C for Unsleben.

Fig. 5.328. Annual minimum air temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

As with the indicators of the number of days with extreme maximum temperature, the number of days with extreme minimum temperature ($\leq -10.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $< 0.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 20.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $< 0.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) at both locations, Unsleben and Kleinbardorf, is almost identical. These similarities are certainly a result of the natural-geographical characteristics of the area and the proximity of the analyzed locations. At the Unsleben site, the average monthly number of days with extreme minimum temperature $\leq -10.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 0.9 days. The maximum number of days with temperature $\leq -10.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 3.8 days, recorded in January. Months from April to October do not have minimum temperature equal to or below $-10.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme minimum temperature $< 0.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a monthly average of 8.6 days. The maximum number of days with temperature $< 0.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 19.8 days, recorded in January. The months of June, July, August, September, and October do not have minimum temperature below $0.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The average monthly number of days with extreme minimum temperature of $\geq 20.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was not recorded at either location, Unsleben or Kleinbardorf. At the Kleinbardorf site, the average monthly number of days with extreme minimum temperature $\leq -10.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 0.8 days. The maximum number of days with temperature $\leq -10.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 4 days, with the average monthly value recorded in January. The months from May to October do not have registered extreme minimum temperature equal to or below $-10.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme minimum temperature $< 0.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ have a monthly average of 8.3 days. The maximum

number of days with temperature $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 19, which represents the average monthly value for January. The months of June, July, and August do not have minimum temperatures below 0.0°C .

Fig. 5.329. Average monthly of number of days with extreme maximum temperature for the period 1992–2022.

5.6.1.4 RELATIVE HUMIDITY OF KLEINBARDORF

The average monthly value of relative humidity for the Kleinbardorf site from 2006 to 2022 is 78.7%. The lowest average monthly value of relative humidity was recorded in April at 69.9%, while the highest relative humidity was measured in December at 89.4%. The average relative humidity value for the winter is 86.6%, with the lowest value recorded in February at 83.3%, and the highest in December at 89.4%. The average measured relative humidity for the spring is 72.6%. The lowest average relative humidity in the spring is in April at 69.9%, while the highest was recorded in March at 75.5%. During the summer climatological season, the average relative humidity is 71.6%. The maximum value was measured in June at 72.8%, and the minimum value was recorded in July at 70.3%. The average monthly relative humidity in the autumn is 84.0%. The lowest relative humidity in the autumn was recorded in September at 77.1%, while the highest was measured in October at 89.3%.

For the Unsleben site, the average monthly value of relative humidity for the period 2006 to 2022 is 79.1%. The lowest average monthly value of relative humidity was recorded in July at 70.1%, while the highest relative humidity was measured in November at 89.7%. The average relative humidity value for the winter is 86.8%, with the lowest value recorded in February at 84.0%, and the highest in December at 89.6%. The average measured relative humidity for the spring is 73.1%. The lowest average relative humidity in the spring is in April at 70.3%, while the highest was recorded in March at 76.4%. During the summer climatological season, the average relative humidity is 71.7%. The maximum value was measured in June at 72.6%, and the minimum value of relative humidity was recorded in July at 70.1%. The average monthly value of relative humidity in the autumn is 84.9%. The lowest relative humidity in the autumn was recorded in September at 78.6%, while the highest was measured in November at 89.7%, which also represents the highest annual value for this site.

Fig. 5.330. Fig. Average monthly values of air relative humidity for 2006-2022.

The average value of extreme maximum relative humidity for the Kleinbardorf site in the period 2006–2022 is 85.1%. The highest average relative humidity value during this thirty-year period was 93.0%, recorded in November 2014. The lowest maximum average relative humidity value was measured in July 2021, at 78.3%. In the analyzed period (2006-2022), the maximum values of average relative humidity on a monthly basis are as follows: January 91.5% (2016),

February 86.3% (2007), March 81.0% (2016), April 78.8% (2008), May 82.1% (2013), June 81.2% (2016), July 78.3% (2021), August 81.7% (2010), September 85.5% (2017), October 88.6% (2016), November 93.0% (2014), and December 92.7% (2016).

Fig. 5.331. Maximum average values of relative air humidity for the Kleinbardorf location in the period 2006-2022.

The average value of the maximum extreme average relative humidity at the Unsleben location for the period 2006-2022 is 86.6%. The highest average relative humidity value in the analyzed thirty-year period was 95.4%, measured in November 2014. The lowest maximum average relative humidity value was measured in April 2008 and was 77.2%. In the analyzed period, the monthly maximum average relative humidity values were as follows: January 91.5% (2016), February 86.3% (2007), March 81.0% (2016), April 78.8% (2008), May 82.1% (2013), June 81.2% (2016), July 78.3% (2021), August 81.7% (2010), September 85.5% (2017), October 88.6% (2016), November 93.0% (2014), and December 92.7% (2016).

Fig. 5.332. Maximum average values of relative air humidity for the Unsleben location in the period 2006-2022.

The average value of the minimum average relative air humidity for the Kleinbardorf location in the period 2006-2022 is 71.0%. The highest minimum average relative air humidity recorded during the analyzed period was 86.6%, measured in December 2007. The lowest minimum average relative air humidity, 57.5%, was measured in August 2022. During the analyzed period, the lowest values of the minimum monthly air humidity were recorded in the following months: January 80.8% (2007), February 79.3% (2012), March 66.6% (2022), April 59.5% (2020), May 63.9% (2011), June 65.2% (2022), July 59.1% (2022), August 57.5% (2022), September 69.1% (2020), October 79.2% (2018), November 85.3% (2009), and December 86.6% (2007). The analyzed indicators show that eight months in the last decade have record low values of the minimum average air humidity.

Fig. 5.333. Average monthly minimum values of air relative humidity for the Kleinbardorf location in the period 2006-2022.

At the Unsleben location, the indicators for average minimum air humidity values are quite similar to those at the Kleinbardorf location. The average minimum air humidity value for Unsleben for the period 2006-2022 is 70.4%. The highest minimum average air humidity value during the observed period was 85.2%, recorded in December 2007. The lowest minimum average air humidity value was 56.2%, recorded in July 2018. During the analyzed period, the lowest values of monthly minimum air humidity were recorded as follows: January 79.7% (2007), February 79.1% (2012), March 66.3% (2022), April 58.8% (2020), May 62.9% (2011), June 65.0% (2010), July 56.2% (2018), August 59.2% (2022), September 69.3% (2018), October 78.7% (2018), November 84.6% (2010), and December 85.2% (2007).

Fig. 5.334. Minimum average monthly values of air relative humidity for the Unsleben location in the period 2006-2022.

In the analyzed period, air relative humidity for the Kleinbardorf location has been steadily decreasing, while for the Unsleben location, it shows a balanced value with a slight increase of 0.4% over the examined period. Based on the collected data, it was determined that relative humidity decreased by 2.6% in the period from 2006 to 2022. The average multi-year value of air humidity for Kleinbardorf is 78.7%, while for Unsleben, it is 79.1%. For both locations, there are 8 years where the average relative humidity values are higher than the multi-year average, and 9 years with values below the multi-year average. For Kleinbardorf, the maximum average annual relative humidity value of 81.2% was recorded in 2014, while the minimum average annual value of 74.7% was recorded in 2022. The maximum average annual relative humidity value for Unsleben of 84.1% was recorded in 2014, while the minimum average annual value of 74.9% was recorded in 2028.

Fig. 5.335. Average annual values of air relative humidity for the period 2006-2022.

5.6.1.5 PRECIPITATION

The average annual precipitation for the period 1992-2022 at Kleinbardorf is 49.4 mm, while at Unsleben it is 51.8 mm.

Fig. 5.336. Average monthly precipitation sum for the period 1992-2022.

At Kleinbarndorf, the smallest average monthly precipitation occurs in April (35.4 mm), while the largest amount is in July (76.3 mm). During the winter, an average of 44.0 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum of 51.8 mm in December and a minimum of 35.4 mm in February. In the spring, the precipitation is roughly the same as in the winter, with a seasonal average of 44.2 mm, the maximum being 61.6 mm in May and the minimum of 35.4 mm in April. In the summer, the average precipitation is 62.2 mm, with the most precipitation recorded in July (76.3 mm) and the least in August (53.9 mm). During the autumn, an average of 47.2 mm of precipitation is recorded. The maximum amount of precipitation for this season is in September, with an average monthly value of 50.8 mm, while October (45.3 mm) and November (45.5 mm) receive roughly the same amount of precipitation. From 1992 to 2022, a decrease in precipitation was observed in all climatological seasons at Kleinbarndorf. Precipitation decreased by different amounts depending on the season. Specifically, during the summer climatological season, the amount of precipitation decreased by 18 mm. In the autumn climatological season, a decrease of 11 mm was recorded. During the winter months,

precipitation decreased by 10 mm, and in the summer months, a decrease of 8 mm was noted in the period from 1992 to 2022.

Fig. 5.337. Average Precipitation per climatological season for the Kleinbardorf location for the period 1992-2022.

At the Unsleben location, similar trends in the seasonal changes of precipitation amounts over the thirty-year period (1992-2022) were observed, as at the Kleinbardorf location. During the specified period, a decrease in precipitation was found during the spring, summer, and autumn, while a slight increase in the annual total precipitation was recorded during the winter. In the summer climatological season, the precipitation amount decreased by 17 mm. Similarly, during the autumn climatological season, a decrease of 17 mm in precipitation was registered. In the period analyzed, precipitation in the spring months decreased by 8 mm, while the winter climatological season saw an increase of 2 mm in precipitation.

Fig. 5.338. Average precipitation per climatological seasons for the Unsleben locality for 1992-2022.

At the Unsleben locality, the smallest average monthly precipitation occurs in April (34.0 mm), while the largest amount is recorded in July (69.2 mm). During the winter, the average precipitation is 56.8 mm, with the maximum in December at 66.1 mm and the minimum in February at 43.8 mm. During the spring, 44.1 mm of precipitation is recorded, with the highest amount in May (55.2 mm) and the lowest in April (34.0 mm). During the summer, the average precipitation is 57.2 mm. The most precipitation falls in July (69.2 mm), while the least is in June (49.5 mm). During the autumn climatological season, the average precipitation is 49.3 mm. The maximum precipitation during autumn occurs in November, with an average of 51.0 mm, while the minimum occurs in September with an average value of 46.9 mm.

From 1992 to 2022, a linear trend analysis revealed a decrease in annual precipitation at the Kleinbardorf site by 143 mm, while at the Unsleben site, a decrease of 120 mm was observed. The average multi-year precipitation value for Kleinbardorf is 592.0 mm, while for Unsleben it is 622 mm. At Kleinbardorf, the maximum annual precipitation sum was recorded in 1995 with 824.1 mm, while the minimum value of 404.6 mm occurred in 2003. In the analyzed period,

there were 15 years with annual precipitation above the multi-year average, and 16 years with lower precipitation sums. In the last 10 years, only two years had an annual sum of precipitation above the multi-year average.

At the Unsleben site, the maximum annual precipitation sum recorded during the analyzed 30-year period was in 1998 with 793.0 mm, while the minimum value of 437.4 mm was recorded in 2003. Similarly to Kleinbardorf, at Unsleben, there were 15 years with annual precipitation greater than the multi-year average, and 16 years with lower precipitation sums. In the last 10 years, only one year had an annual sum of precipitation above the multi-year average.

Fig. 5.339. Annual sum of precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

At the Kleinbardorf site, the average monthly value of the maximum recorded precipitation for the period 1992-2022 is 13.6 mm. The highest precipitation values occur in July, with an average maximum value of 22.5 mm. The lowest average monthly maximum precipitation value was measured in March, at 8.8 mm.

The average monthly maximum precipitation for the winter is 11.5 mm, with the lowest values recorded in February (9.3 mm) and the highest in December (13.4 mm). The average maximum precipitation for the spring is also 11.5 mm, with the lowest values in March (8.8 mm) and the highest in May (15.8 mm). During the summer, the average monthly maximum precipitation is

slightly higher, at 18.5 mm, with the highest value recorded in July (22.5 mm) and the lowest in August (16.1 mm). The average monthly maximum precipitation is highest during the autumn, at 12.9 mm, with a maximum in September (15.2 mm), while in October (11.6 mm) and November (11.8 mm) similar average maximum precipitation values were recorded.

At the Unsleben site, the annual trends of maximum precipitation are similar to those at Kleinbardorf. The average monthly value of the maximum recorded precipitation for the period 1992-2022 at Unsleben is 13.9 mm. The highest values of maximum precipitation on an annual level were recorded in July, with an average maximum value of 20.0 mm. The lowest average monthly maximum precipitation was measured in April, at 9.6 mm. Average monthly maximum precipitation shows some fluctuations at the seasonal level. Specifically, for the winter, the average value of maximum precipitation is 14.0 mm. The lowest values of precipitation maxima during this season were recorded in February (11.6 mm) and the highest in January (15.4 mm). The average maximum precipitation for the spring is 11.9 mm, with the lowest values in April (9.6 mm) and the highest in May (15.8 mm). During the summer, the average value of precipitation maxima is slightly higher at 16.6 mm, with the highest value recorded in July (20.0 mm) and the lowest in August (14.8 mm). The average monthly maximum precipitation during the autumn is 13.1 mm. The maximum value of this indicator during the season was recorded in September (15.1 mm), while the minimum value in November was 11.2 mm.

Fig. 5.340. Average monthly value of the maximum amount of precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of extreme rainfall maxima for the Kleinbardorf location for the period 1992-2022 is 33.4 mm. The maximum rainfall of 67.1 mm was recorded in July 2004. The lowest rainfall maximum of 15.3 mm was measured in March 2000. In the analyzed thirty-year period, the extreme maximum rainfall values on a monthly level had the following values: January 31.0 mm (2003), February 26.9 mm (1997), March 15.3 mm (2000), April 25.4 mm (2009), May 30.6 mm (2019), June 43.9 mm (2007), July 67.1 mm (2004), August 34.7 mm (2007), September 34.0 mm (2022), October 28.6 mm (2002), November 23.8 mm (2004), and December 39.0 mm (1993).

Fig. 5.341. Maximum rainfall amounts for the Kleinb. for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of extreme rainfall maxima for the Unsleben location for the reference period 1992-2022 is 33.8 mm. The maximum rainfall amount of 64.5 mm was recorded in July 2004. The lowest value of rainfall maximum, 17.8 mm, was measured in March 2015. During the analyzed period, extreme maximum rainfall values at the monthly level were recorded as follows: January 34.6 mm (2003), February 24.2 mm (2021), March 17.8 mm (2015), April 23.1 mm (2016), May 50.1 mm (2016), June 35.8 mm (1997), July 64.5 mm (2004), August 31.7 mm (2000), September 32.6 mm (2022), October 30.6 mm (2002), November 22.7 mm (2004), and December 37.6 mm (1993).

Fig. 5.342. Maximum rainfall amounts for the Unsleben location, period 1992-2022.

The average maximum rainfall value on an annual level for the period 1992-2022 for the Kleinbardorf location are 31.2 mm, while for the Unsleben location, it is 31.8 mm. The highest maximum rainfall for Kleinbardorf on an annual level, 67.1 mm, was measured in 2004, while the lowest maximum rainfall value on an annual level, 21.0 mm, was recorded in October 2008. A linear trend shows that the maximum rainfall value have slightly decreased, which correlates with the decline in the annual total rainfall sums. This methodology has determined that the maximum rainfall values in the 30-year period from 1992 to 2022 have decreased by 3.4 mm. The highest maximum rainfall for the Unsleben location on an annual level, 64.5 mm, was measured in 2004, while the lowest maximum rainfall value on an annual level, 18.7 mm, was recorded in October 2015.

A linear trend shows that the maximum rainfall values have slightly decreased at both locations, which correlates with the decline in the annual total rainfall sums. Using this methodology, it has been determined that the maximum rainfall values in the 30-year period from 1992 to 2022 decreased by 3.4 mm for Kleinbardorf and by 9.9 mm for Unsleben.

Fig. 5.343. Average monthly value of the maximum rainfall for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of the maximum snow amount for the period during which the snow cover was measured (1992-2022) is 1.6 cm for the Kleinbardorf locality and 2.1 cm for the Unsleben locality. The months without snow cover for both localities are May, June, July, August, and September, as well as October for Unsleben. The highest average maximum snow amount occurs in January, with an average monthly value of 5.7 cm for Kleinbardorf and 7.9 cm for Unsleben.

At the Kleinbardorf locality, during the winter, the average maximum snow amount is 3.7 cm, with a peak in January (the annual precipitation maximum) and a minimum in February at 3.8 cm of precipitation. During the spring, the average maximum snow cover is 1.0 cm, with a peak in March (2.5 cm) and a minimum in May (0 cm). There is no snowfall during the summer, whereas in the autumn, October has an average maximum snow amount of 0.1 cm, while November has an average monthly value of 1.3 cm.

At the Unsleben locality, during the winter, the average maximum snow amount is 6.7 cm, with a peak in January (7.9 cm) and a minimum in February at 6.0 cm of precipitation. During the spring, the average maximum snow cover is 1.0 cm, with a peak in March (2.8 cm) and a minimum in May, where no snow cover was recorded. There is no snowfall during the summer, whereas in the autumn, November is the only month with snowfall, with an average monthly value of snow maxima at 1.3 cm.

Fig. 5.344. Average monthly values of the maximum snow cover depth 1992-2022.

The average values of the maximum snow cover depth at the Kleinbardorf location for the period 1992-2022 is 12.1 cm. During this period, the maximum monthly extreme snow cover depth was 50.0 cm, recorded in December 2010. The months without snow cover are May, June, July, August, and September. In the period during which snow cover depth measurements were conducted, the maximum monthly values recorded were 39.0 cm in January 2011, 18.0 cm in February 2010, 12.0 cm in March 2006, 12.0 cm in April 2022, 4.0 cm in October 2012, 10.0 cm in November 2010, and 50.0 cm in December 2010.

Fig. 5.345. Maximum snow cover depths for the Kleinbardorf location by months in the period 1992-2022.

The average values of the maximum snow cover depth at the Unsleben location for the period 1992-2022 are slightly lower compared to the Kleinbardorf location. The average value of the maximum snow cover depth amounts to 9.8 cm. During the specified period, the maximum monthly extreme snow cover depth was 38.0 cm, recorded in December 2010. Months without snow cover are May, June, July, August, September, and October. During the specified period, the maximum snow cover depths at the monthly level were as follows: January 30.0 cm (2011), February 25.0 cm (2010), March 11.0 cm (1995), April 4.0 cm (2022), November 10.0 cm (2021), and December 38.0 cm (2010).

Fig. 5.346. Maximum snow cover depths by month for the Unsleben location in the period 1992-2022.

Analysis of the available data for the period 1992-2022 has determined an increase in the maximum snow cover depth values by 6.3 cm for the Kleinbardorf location and 5.5 cm for the Unsleben location. The average maximum annual snow cover depth is 9.7 cm for Kleinbardorf and 11.5 cm for Unsleben. At the Kleinbardorf location, the maximum annual snow cover depth is 50.0 cm, recorded in 2010, while the minimum value is 2.0 cm, recorded in 1992 and 2019. At the Unsleben location, the maximum annual snow cover depth is 38.0 cm, recorded in 2010, while the minimum value is 4.0 cm, also recorded in 1992 and 2019.

Fig. 5.347. Maximum annual snow cover depth in the period 2015-2022.

In the period from 1992 to 2022, the number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm, ≥ 1.0 mm, ≥ 5.0 mm, ≥ 10.0 mm, ≥ 20.0 mm, and ≥ 50.0 mm has increased number of days during the winter climatological season, while these values decrease during the autumn and spring. Both locations nearly have no precipitation ≥ 50.0 mm, with only one day recorded at the Unsleben location in August 1994 with precipitation above this threshold. At the Unsleben location, the average number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is 13.5. The maximum number of days with this amount of precipitation is 17.5, which is the average monthly value for December, while the minimum value is 10.7, recorded in April. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm is slightly lower at 9, with the maximum number of days in December (an average of 11.3 days) and the minimum in April (an average of 7.1 days). Precipitation of ≥ 5.0 mm occurs on average 3.4 days per month. The maximum number of days with this level of precipitation is recorded in December (an average of 4.9 days), while the minimum is in April (an average of 2.0 days). The average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 1.3. The maximum number of days with ≥ 10.0 mm precipitation is 2, recorded in December, while the minimum number of days with this level of precipitation is 0.7, recorded in April. Precipitation of ≥ 20.0 mm occurs on average 0.2 days per month. The maximum number of

days with precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm is 0.4 (average monthly value for July), while the minimum number of days is 0.0 (March and November).

At the Kleinbardorf location, the average number of days with precipitation ≥ 0.1 mm is 12.7. The maximum number of days with this level of precipitation is 15.3, which is the average monthly value for December, while the minimum value is 10.8, also recorded in April, similar to Unsleben. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm is 8.3, with the maximum number of days in July (an average of 9.9 days) and the minimum in April (an average of 7 days). Precipitation of ≥ 5.0 mm occurs on average 3.1 days per month. The maximum number of days with this level of precipitation is recorded in July (an average of 4.3 days), while the minimum is in February, March, and April (an average of 2.2 days). The average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 1.1. The maximum number of days with ≥ 10.0 mm precipitation is 1.8, recorded in July, while the minimum number of days with this level of precipitation is 0.5, recorded in March. The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm is 0.2 days. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 20.0 mm is 0.8, which is also the average monthly value for July, while the minimum is 0.0 days in March.

Fig. 5.348. Average monthly values of the number of days with precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

5.7 MALTA SELECTED SITES

5.7.1 MDINA RABAT

5.7.1.1 INSOLATION

The average monthly insolation at the Mdina Rabat site for the period 1992–2022 is 250.0 hours. The lowest average monthly insolation was recorded in December, amounting to 167.9 hours, while the highest average insolation was recorded in July, totaling 367.5 hours.

Fig. 5.349. Average monthly sunshine duration for the period 1992–2022.

The average sunshine duration for the winter is 175.5 hours, with the lowest number of sunshine hours during this season recorded in December (167.9 hours, which is the annual minimum), and the highest in February with 188.0 hours. The average sunshine duration for the spring is 260.4 hours. The lowest sunshine in the spring is recorded in March with 223.7 hours, and the highest in May with 308.6 hours. During the summer climatological season, the average sunshine duration is 347.2 hours, with the highest sunshine in July (annual maximum with 367.5 hours) and the lowest in June (335.5 hours). The average monthly sunshine duration in the autumn is 216.9 hours, with maximum values in September (253.4 hours) and minimum values in November with an average of 180.1 hours of sunshine.

Fig. 5.350. Average sunshine duration by seasons for the period 1992-2022.

The average multi-year sunshine duration is 3000.1 hours. Thirteen years have an annual sunshine duration higher than the average multi-year value, while eighteen years are below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, 6 years had higher sunshine duration, and only 4 years had lower sunshine duration compared to the multi-year average. The maximum average annual sunshine duration of 3194.6 hours was recorded in 2012, while the minimum average annual sunshine duration of 2822.2 hours was recorded in 1992. The sunshine duration has been steadily increasing over the last thirty years (1992-2022). The linear trend indicates that the sunshine duration increased by 70.4 hours during this period.

Fig. 5.351. Total annual sunshine duration for the period 1992-2022.

5.7.1.2 RADIATION

The average monthly radiation value for the period 1992–2022 is 168.2 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly radiation was recorded in November, amounting to 91.2 kWh/m², while the highest average solar radiation was recorded in July, at 256.9 kWh/m².

The average radiation for the winter is 116.8 kWh/m², with the lowest solar radiation recorded in January at 108.8 kWh/m² and the highest in December at 122.2 kWh/m². The average total radiation for the spring is 192.6 kWh/m². The lowest value of solar radiation in the spring is in March at 149.9 kWh/m², while the highest is in May at 240.8 kWh/m². During the summer, the average solar radiation is 242.9 kWh/m², with the highest in July (256.9 kWh/m²) and the lowest in August (223.3 kWh/m²). The average monthly radiation during the autumn is 120.6 kWh/m², with maximum values in September (154.2 kWh/m²) and the minimum solar radiation in November (91.2 kWh/m²)

Fig. 5.352. Average monthly radiation for the period 1992-2022.

The linear trend shows an increase in radiation at the Mdina Rabat location from 1992 to 2022 by 49.8 kWh/m². The average multi-year radiation value is 2018.7 kWh/m². Fourteen years have an annual radiation higher than the average multi-year value, while seventeen years have a value below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, 6 years have higher radiation, and 4 years have lower radiation compared to the multi-year average. The highest average annual radiation of 2158.7 kWh/m² was recorded in 2012, while the lowest average annual solar radiation of 1889.5 kWh/m² was recorded in 1992.

Fig. 5.353. Annual radiation for the period 1992-2022.

5.7.1.3 AIR TEMPERATURE

The average monthly temperature for the location Mdina Rabat for the period 1992-2022 is 19.5°C. The lowest average monthly temperature recorded was in February, at 12.7°C, while the highest temperature was measured in August, at 27.6°C. The average temperature for the winter is 13.4°C, with the lowest recorded temperatures in February (annual minimum), and the highest in December at 14.6°C. The average recorded temperature for the spring is 16.9°C. The lowest average temperature in the spring is in March at 14.0°C, and the highest in May at 20.2°C. During the summer, the average temperature is 26.3°C. The highest average temperature during this season was recorded in August at 27.6°C. The lowest average monthly temperature during the summer is in June, at 24.4°C. The average monthly air temperature during the autumn is 21.5°C. The lowest value of the average temperature during this season was recorded in November at 17.9°C, while the highest value was recorded in September at 25.0°C.

Fig. 5.354. Average monthly temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average annual air temperature values at the location Mdina Rabat over the last thirty years (1992-2022) have been steadily increasing. The linear trend shows that the temperature has risen by 0.6°C . The average long-term air temperature is 19.5°C . The average annual temperatures above the long-term average were recorded in 18 years, while 13 years had values below the long-term average. In the last 10 years, the average annual temperatures have been higher than the long-term average. The highest average annual air temperature of 20.1°C was recorded in 2016, while the lowest average annual temperature of 18.7°C was recorded in 2005.

Fig. 5.355. Average annual temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

A linear trend has determined an increase in temperature across all climatological seasons. The temperature rise in the summer is 1.0°C, in autumn 0.5°C, in spring 0.4°C, and in winter 0.4°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter was 14.4°C, recorded in 2014, while the minimum temperature was 11.9°C, recorded in 2005. The maximum average annual temperature during the spring was 18.0°C, recorded in 2001. The lowest average annual temperature for the spring was 16.0°C, recorded in 2004. The maximum average annual temperature for the summer was 27.9°C, recorded in 2021, while the minimum temperature values were recorded in 1992, with an average value of 25.0°C. During the summer, temperature maxima were recorded in 2012, with an average value of 22.5°C, while the minimum temperature values of 20.4°C were measured in 2005.

Fig. 5.356. Average seasonal temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum monthly temperature at the Mdina Rabat location for the period 1992–2022 is 27.8°C. The lowest average maximum monthly temperature recorded was in January, at 19.1°C, while the highest temperature was measured in July and August, both at an identical average value of 37.3°C. The average maximum air temperature for the winter is 19.3°C. The highest recorded value of the analysed climatic element was in December, at 20.8°C, while the lowest average maximum monthly air temperature was recorded in January, at 19.1°C. The measured average maximum temperature for the spring is 26.1°C. The lowest average maximum air temperature in the spring was recorded in March, at 22.6°C, while the highest was in May, at 30.0°C. During the summer, the average maximum temperatures are 36.5°C. July and August have identical average values for the average monthly maximum temperature (37.3°C), which represent the maximum temperatures of the summer and the annual maximum. A lower temperature value than the seasonal average was recorded in June, at 35.0°C. During the autumn, the average monthly maximum temperature is 28.9°C. The month with the lowest average monthly maximum air temperature is November, at 25.0°C, while the highest average value was recorded in September, at 32.9°C.

Fig. 5.357. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992–2022.

The average value of the maximum recorded temperature for the period 1992–2022 is 33.2°C. The highest recorded air temperature at the Mdina Rabat location was 43.8°C, measured in August 1999. The lowest maximum temperature was recorded in December 2009 and amounted to 23.6°C. In the mentioned thirty-year period, extreme maximum temperature values recorded on a monthly level are as follows: January 25.8°C (2021), February 24.2°C (2010), March 33.5°C (2001), April 29.1°C (2016), May 35.3°C (2006), June 41.5°C (2021), July 42.6°C (1998), August 43.8°C (1999), September 36.6°C (2001), October 34.5°C (1999), November 28.2°C (1998), and December 23.6°C (2009).

Fig. 5.358. Maximum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average annual value of the maximum recorded temperatures at the Mdina Rabat location for the period 1992-2022 is 38.8°C. The highest maximum temperature on an annual level, 43.8°C, was recorded in August 1999, while the lowest maximum temperature of 34.7°C was recorded in August 2014. A linear trend analysis determined a decrease in extreme maximum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022, amounting to 0.5°C.

Fig. 5.359. Maximum annual air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average minimum monthly temperature for the location Mdina Rabat for the period 1992–2022 is 11.9°C. The lowest average minimum monthly temperature was recorded in February, at 5.2°C, while the highest temperature was measured in August, at 20.4°C. The average minimum temperature for the winter is 5.9°C. The lowest value of the average minimum temperature was recorded in February (5.2°C, which also represents the annual minimum), and the highest in December at 6.9°C. The measured average minimum temperature for the spring is 9.2°C. The lowest average minimum temperature in the spring was in March at 6.7°C, and the highest in May at 12.3°C. During the summer, the average minimum temperature is 18.6°C. The lowest average monthly minimum temperature during this season was recorded in June, at 15.8°C, while the highest value of the average minimum temperature was recorded in August at 20.4°C. The average monthly minimum temperature during the autumn is 13.8°C. The lowest value of the average minimum temperature during this season was recorded in November at 10.0°C, while the highest value of this indicator was recorded in September at 17.4°C.

Fig. 5.360. Average monthly minimum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of extreme minimum temperatures for the period 1992-2022 is 8.7°C. The lowest average extreme minimum temperature during this period was 2.1°C, recorded in January 2015. The highest extreme minimum temperature was recorded in August 1997 with an average value of 17.6°C. The extreme minimum average air temperatures, on a monthly level, during the analyzed period had the following values: January 2.1°C (2015), February 2.1°C (1999), March 3.4°C (1996), April 5.4°C (1994), May -9.6°C (1992), June 13.8°C (2013), July 16.9°C (1996), August 17.6°C (1997), September 15.1°C (2004), October 10.8°C (2007), November 5.0°C (1995), and December 2.8°C (2014). From these indicators, it is evident that in only three months over the past 10 years, records of minimum air temperature values were recorded, while the remaining minimum values were registered in the first two decades of the observed period.

Fig. 5.361. Minimum monthly air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average annual value of measured minimum temperatures for the period 1992-2022 is 4.4°C. The highest minimum temperature on an annual basis, 6.2°C, was recorded in April 1997, while the lowest minimum temperature, 2.1°C, was recorded in February 1999. Although fluctuations in the increase and decrease of extreme minimum temperatures have been identified on an annual basis, extreme minimum temperature values show a rising trend. The linear trend indicates a growth value of 0.2°C.

Fig. 5.362. Annual minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

5.7.1.4 RELATIVE HUMIDITY

The average monthly relative humidity for the period 2011-2022 (the period for which data is available) at the location Mdina Rabat is 78.9%. The lowest average monthly relative humidity was measured in June at 70.8%, while the highest average relative humidity was measured in November at 82.8%. The average relative humidity value for the winter is 81.4%, with the lowest values recorded in December at 80.8% and the highest in February at 81.8%. The average measured relative humidity value for the spring is 79.3%. The lowest average relative humidity in the spring was in May at 74.7%, while the highest value was measured in March at 82.4%. During the summer, the average relative humidity is 73.4%. The highest measured value was in August at 76.4%, while the lowest was in June at 70.8%. The average monthly relative humidity value during the autumn is 81.4%. The lowest humidity values during this

season were recorded in October at 79.9%, while the highest values were in November at 82.8%, which also represents the annual maximum value.

Fig. 5.363. Average monthly values of relative air humidity for the period 2011-2022.

The average value of maximum air humidity for the location Mdina Rabat for the period 2011-2022 is 91.5%. The highest average air humidity value recorded during the analyzed period was 94.4%, measured in April 2019. The lowest maximum average air humidity value was measured in April 2016 and was 87.5%. During the mentioned twelve-year period, the maximum values of average air humidity were recorded for: January 92.0% (2022), February 93.0% (2017), March 91.5% (2019), April 94.4% (2019), May 89.2% (2018), June 89.2% (2018), July 87.7% (2018), August 87.5% (2016), September 94.0% (2021), October 93.5% (2019), November 93.2% (2020), and December 92.9% (2019).

Fig. 5.364. Maximum average monthly values of relative air humidity for 2011-2022.

The average value of minimum relative air humidity for the period 2011-2022 is 63.0%. The highest minimum average value of air humidity at the Mdina Rabat location during the analyzed period was 72.0%, measured in February 2012. The lowest minimum average value of air humidity was measured in June 2022, and it amounted to 44.5%. During the analyzed period, the minimum average air humidity values for each month were recorded as follows: January 71.7% (2014), February 72.0% (2012), March 70.5% (2013), April 66.3% (2013), May 49.7% (2022), June 44.5% (2022), July 61.4% (2022), August 67.0% (2013), September 68.3% (2014), October 50.9% (2014), November 65.3% (2013), and December 67.8% (2012).

Fig. 5.365. Minimum average monthly values of relative air humidity for 2011-2022.

In the reference period (2011-2022), the relative air humidity at the Mdina Rabat location shows a balanced value with a slight increase. The linear trend indicates that the relative humidity increased by 13.3% during the analyzed twelve-year period. The average multi-year value of air humidity is 78.9%. The average values of relative air humidity above the multi-year average occurred in 6 years, while 6 years had values below the multi-year average. The maximum average annual value of relative air humidity, 88.7%, was recorded in 2020, while the minimum average annual value of 67.8% was recorded in 2013.

Fig. 5.366. Average annual relative humidity values for the period 2011-2022.

5.7.1.5 PRECIPITATION

The average annual precipitation at the Mdina Rabat location for the period 1992-2022 is 44.8 mm. The lowest average precipitation is recorded in July (0.1 mm), while the highest amount is recorded in November (95.3 mm).

Fig. 5.367. Average monthly rainfall for the period 1992-2022.

Based on the collected and analyzed meteorological data, it is evident that the Mdina Rabat location exhibits pronounced seasonal fluctuations in precipitation. During the winter, an average of 73.0 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum in December (78.2 mm) and a minimum in February (64.7 mm). During the spring, the average precipitation is also 22.4 mm, with a maximum in March (39.8 mm) and a minimum in May (9.9 mm). During the summer, the average precipitation is 5.1 mm, with the highest in August (9.6 mm) and the lowest in July (0.1 mm), which represents the annual minimum. During the autumn, an average of 78.7 mm of precipitation is recorded, with a maximum in November (95.3 mm) and a minimum in September (59.6 mm).

From 1992 to 2022, linear trend analysis shows a decrease in precipitation across all climatological seasons. Due to varying amounts of precipitation in different seasons, the reduction in rainfall also differs across the 30-year period. The largest decrease in precipitation was recorded during the winter climatological season, with a reduction of 34 mm. A significantly

smaller reduction in precipitation was recorded during the spring months, amounting to 12 mm. A decrease in precipitation was also observed during the autumn, with a reduction of 5 mm, and during the summer with a modest reduction of 2 mm.

Fig. 5.368. Average precipitation amounts by climatological seasons for 1992-2022.

The linear trend shows a decrease in the total amount of annual precipitation over the period from 1992 to 2022, with a decrease of 150 mm. The average multi-year value is 537.8 mm of precipitation. The highest annual precipitation total was recorded in 2003, with 900.5 mm, while the lowest value was 324.8 mm in 2016. In the analyzed period, 13 years had annual precipitation amounts greater than the long-term average, while 18 years had lower totals.

Fig. 5.369. Annual precipitation totals for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of the maximum measured precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022 is 17.2 mm. The highest precipitation values at the Mdina Rabat location occur in November, with an average value of the measured maxima being 34.1 mm. The lowest average monthly maximum precipitation value was measured in July and was 0.1 mm.

The average monthly maximum precipitation amount for the winter is 22.2 mm, with the lowest values measured in January at 20.0 mm, and the highest in December at 24.8 mm. The measured average maximum precipitation amount for the spring is 10.3 mm. The lowest average maximum precipitation amount in the spring is in May at 6.1 mm, while the highest is in March at 15.6 mm.

During the summer, the average maximum precipitation amount are the lowest, at 4.0 mm. The highest average monthly maximum precipitation during this season was measured in August at 7.1 mm, while the lowest values were recorded in July at 0.1 mm.

The average monthly maximum precipitation amounts are the highest during the autumn, at 32.6 mm, with a peak in November at 34.1 mm and a minimum in October at 31.0 mm.

Fig. 5.370. Average monthly maximum precipitation values for the period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of extreme precipitation maxima for the locality of Mdina Rabat for the period 1992-2022 is 70.8 mm. The highest amount of precipitation, 120.3 mm, was recorded in October 2010. The lowest value of the precipitation maximum, 0.8 mm, was recorded in July 2019. In the aforementioned thirty-year period, extreme maximum precipitation values on a monthly level are as follows: January 55.0 mm (1992), February 117.0 mm (2018), March 43.6 mm (2010), April 92.4 mm (1994), May 29.6 mm (1992), June 63.4 mm (2007), July 0.8 mm (2019), August 37.1 mm (1997), September 112.7 mm (1995), October 102.2 mm (2010), November 120.3 mm (1999), and December 75.2 mm (2007).

The average value of the maximum measured precipitation amounts on an annual basis for the period 1992-2022 is 63.7 mm. The highest maximum precipitation amount of 120.3 mm was recorded in 1999, while the lowest maximum precipitation amount of 22.9 mm was recorded in October 2001. The linear trend shows that the values of the maximum precipitation amounts have decreased by 22.1 mm over the thirty-year period (1992-2022).

Fig. 5.371. Maximum precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022.

Fig. 5.372. Maximum precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022.

5.8 FRANCE SELECTED SITE

5.8.1.CAEN

5.8.1.1INSOLATION

The average monthly sunshine duration at the Caen location for the period 1992-2022 is 145.5 hours. The lowest average monthly sunshine duration was recorded in December with 67.2 hours, while the highest average sunshine duration was recorded in July, with 218.5 hours.

The average sunshine duration for the winter is 76.0 hours, with the smallest number of sunshine hours at Caen in December (annual minimum), and the highest in February, with 90.2 hours. The average sunshine duration for the spring is 171.3 hours. The lowest sunshine duration in the spring is in March, with 130 hours, while the highest is in May, with 203.4 hours. During the summer climatological season, the average sunshine duration is 212 hours, with the greatest sunshine in July (annual maximum at 218.5 hours) and the lowest in August, with 204.8 hours. The average monthly sunshine duration in the autumn is 123.3 hours, with the maximum value in September (170.9 hours) and the minimum in November, with an average of 81.9 hours of sunshine.

Fig. 5.373. Average monthly insolation for the period 1992-2022.

5.8.1.2. RADIATION

The average monthly radiation value for the period 1992–2022 is 98.8 kWh/m². The lowest average monthly radiation was measured in November, at 41.5 kWh/m², while the highest average solar radiation was measured in May, at 158.7 kWh/m².

The average radiation for the winter is 50.4 kWh/m², with the lowest in January (45.0 kWh/m²) and the highest in February (57.3 kWh/m²). The average radiation sum for the spring is 126.8 kWh/m². The lowest radiation in the spring is in March (87.1 kWh/m²), while the highest is in May (158.7 kWh/m²).

During the summer climatological season, the average radiation is 148.4 kWh/m², with the highest in June (157.4 kWh/m²) and the lowest in August (135.0 kWh/m²). The average monthly radiation in the autumn is 69.4 kWh/m², with maximum values in September (104 kWh/m²) and the minimum in solar radiation in November (41.5 kWh/m²).

Fig. 5.373. Average monthly radiation for the period 1992-2022.

5.8.1.3 AIR TEMPERATURES

The average monthly temperature for the Caen location for the period 1992-2022 is 11.3°C. The lowest average monthly temperature was recorded in January, at 5.5°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in August, at 17.8°C. The average temperature for the winter is

5.9°C, with all months of this season having average temperatures above 0.0°C. The lowest temperature was recorded in January (annual minimum), while the highest was in December at -6.1°C. The average temperature for the spring is 10.1°C. The lowest average temperature in the spring was recorded in March at 7.7°C, while the highest was in May at 12.9°C. During the summer, the average temperature is 17.1°C. The average monthly temperature recorded in August is 17.8°C, which is the highest monthly average temperature of the summer. The lowest average monthly temperature during the summer was in June, at 15.8°C. The average monthly temperature during the autumn is 12.1°C. The coldest month is November at 8.6°C, while the warmest is September, with an average of 15.4°C.

Fig. 5.735. Average monthly temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The linear trend has shown that the temperature during the reference thirty-year period has increased with a warming value of 0.7°C. The average multi-year temperature is 11.3°C. There are 16 years with average annual temperatures higher than the multi-year average, while 15 years have values below the multi-year average. In the last 10 years, 7 years have had average annual temperatures higher than the multi-year average. The maximum average annual temperature of 12.3°C was recorded in 2022, while the minimum average annual temperature of 10.1°C was recorded in 1996.

Fig. 5.376. Average annual temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

In addition to the overall increase in temperatures, the linear trend has shown an increase in temperatures (at different values) across all climatological seasons. Specifically, the temperature increase for the summer is 1.1°C, for autumn 1.3°C, for spring 0.1°C, and for winter 0.6°C. The maximum average annual temperature during the winter is 7.5°C, measured in 2020, while the minimum temperature was 2.7°C, measured in 2010. The minimum average annual temperature during the spring is 8.0°C, measured in 2013. The maximum average annual temperature for the spring is 11.1°C, recorded in 2011. The maximum average annual temperature for summer is 18.9°C, registered in 2003, while the minimum values of temperature were recorded in 1995, with an average value of 15.9°C. During the winter, the maximum temperature values were recorded in 2006, with an average value of 13.8°C, while the minimum temperature values of 9.4°C were registered in 1993.

Fig. 5.377. Average temperature values by season for the period 1992-2022.

The average maximum monthly temperature for the period 1992–2022 is 15.4°C. The lowest average maximum monthly temperature was measured in January at 8.3°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in August at 23.2°C. The average maximum temperature for the winter is 8.7°C, with the lowest recorded in January at 8.3°C and the highest in February at 9.1°C. The average maximum temperature for the spring is 14.5°C. The lowest average maximum temperature in the spring was in March at 11.7°C, and the highest in May at 17.4°C. During the summer, the average maximum temperature is 22.2°C. The lowest average maximum temperature was recorded in June at 20.5°C, and the highest temperature during this season was in August at 23.2°C, which also represents the annual maximum. The average maximum monthly temperature during the autumn is 16.1°C. The month with the lowest maximum temperature during this season is November, with 11.8°C, while the highest value was recorded in September at 20.4°C.

Fig. 5.378. Average monthly maximum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of extreme maximum temperatures measured for the period 1992-2022 at the Caen location is 28.0°C. The highest air temperature was recorded in July 2002 (40.1°C), while the lowest maximum temperature was measured in January 2002 (16.8°C). On a monthly basis, the extreme maximum temperature values during the given thirty-year period are as follows: January 16.8°C (2002), February 20.8°C (1996), March 24.9°C (2002), April 26.6°C (2001), May 30.4°C (1995), June 35.2°C (2001), July 40.1°C (2002), August 38.9°C (2000), September 33.5°C (1996), October 29.6°C (2002), November 21.6°C (2001), and December 17.3°C (2002).

Fig. 5.379. Extreme maximum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The number of days with extreme maximum air temperature $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ records the highest values during the summer months, while the number of days with extreme maximum air temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is higher during the winter months. The average number of days with extreme maximum temperature $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 0.1 day. The maximum number of days with $T_{\text{max}} < 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 0.6 days, recorded in January. From March to October, there are no days with maximum temperatures $< 0.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum temperature $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ has a higher average monthly value in terms of the number of days compared to the previously analyzed indicator. The average monthly value is 2.0 days. The maximum number of days with $T_{\text{max}} \geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 7.8 days, recorded in July. December, January, February, and March have no extreme maximum air temperatures $\geq 25.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extreme maximum air temperatures $T_{\text{max}} \geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ have an average monthly value of 0.3 days, with the highest average number of days (1.6) in August. During the winter, spring, and autumn seasons (except September), there are no days with maximum air temperatures $\geq 30.0^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5.380. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme maximum air temperature values for the period 1992-2022.

The average minimum monthly temperature at the Caen location for the period 1992–2022 is 7.5°C. The lowest average minimum monthly temperature was recorded in February at 2.8°C, while the highest temperature was recorded in August at 13.3°C. The average minimum temperature for the winter is 3.0°C. The lowest value of average minimum temperature was registered in February (annual minimum), and the highest in December at 3.3°C. The average minimum temperature measured for the spring is 6.1°C. The lowest average minimum temperature in the spring was in March at 4.2°C, and the highest in May at 8.5°C. During the summer climatological season, the average minimum temperature is 12.5°C. The lowest average minimum monthly temperature during this season was recorded in June at 11.2°C, while the highest value of average minimum temperature was registered in August at 13.3°C. The average monthly minimum temperature in the autumn is 8.5°C. According to this indicator, the coldest month in this season is November at 5.6°C, while the warmest is September at 11.1°C.

Fig. 5.381. Average monthly minimum temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

The average value of extreme minimum temperature for the period 1992-2022 is 3.8°C. The lowest average minimum temperature was -19.0°C, recorded in January 1998. The highest average extreme minimum temperature was recorded in July 1996 (4.7°C). In the mentioned thirty-year period, extreme minimum average monthly temperatures were recorded for: January -19.0°C (1998), February -16.0°C (1995), March -7.0°C (1996), April -5.0°C (1997), May 0.0°C (2001), June 1.0°C (1996), July 4.7°C (1996), August 4.0°C (1997), September 1.8°C (1994), October -3.0°C (1999), November -6.0°C (1998), and December -1.0°C (1994). These indicators show that the record low values of air temperature were recorded in the first decade of the analyzed period.

Fig. 5.382. Extreme monthly minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

Analysis of the available data reveals significant differences in the number of days with minimum temperatures of: ≤ -10.0 °C and < 0.0 °C. Extreme minimum temperatures $T_{min} \leq -10.0$ °C have an average monthly value of 0.02 days. The maximum number of days with a temperature ≤ -10.0 °C is 0.1 days, recorded in January and February, while other months do not record such temperature values on any day. Extreme minimum temperatures $T_{min} < 0.0$ °C have a monthly average value of 2.4 days. The maximum number of days with a temperature < 0.0 °C is 7.6 days, recorded in January. May, June, July, August, and September do not have any days where extreme minimum temperatures < 0.0 °C were recorded.

Fig. 5.383. Average monthly values of the number of days with extreme minimum air temperatures for the period 1992-2022.

5.8.1.4 PRECIPITATION

The average annual precipitation at the Caen location for the period 1992-2022 is 59.2 mm. The smallest average amount of precipitation is recorded in March (46.4 mm), while the largest amount of precipitation occurs in December with 78.3 mm.

Fig. 5.384. Average monthly rainfall sum for the period 1992-2022.

The rainfall has a balanced annual pattern with smaller monthly and seasonal fluctuations. During the winter, an average of 63.4 mm of rainfall is recorded, with a maximum in December of about 78.3 mm and a minimum in February of 50.6 mm. In the spring, the average rainfall is 51.5 mm, with a maximum in May of 58.4 mm and a minimum in March of 46.4 mm. During the summer, the average rainfall is 56.3 mm, with the highest rainfall occurring in August (61.9 mm) and the lowest in July (50.4 mm). In the autumn, an average of 65.8 mm of rainfall is recorded, with the maximum in November of 74.0 mm and the minimum in September of 51.4 mm.

In the Caen locality, from 1992 to 2022, a linear trend indicates a decrease in rainfall across all climatological seasons. In the analyzed period (1992-2022), rainfall during the autumn decreased by 27 mm, in the summer by 29 mm, in the winter by 9 mm, and in the spring by 13 mm.

Fig. 5.385. Average rainfall by climatological seasons for the period 1992-2022.

In addition to the decrease in precipitation on a seasonal level, a linear trend analysis at the annual level has shown a reduction in precipitation by 231 mm. Within this 30-year period, there are certain annual oscillations with increases and decreases in precipitation. The average multi-year value is 711 mm of precipitation. The maximum annual precipitation total was recorded in 1994, reaching 966 mm, while the minimum value of 366 mm was recorded in 2019. In the analyzed period, 14 years had annual precipitation totals above the long-term average, while 17 years had lower totals.

Fig. 5.386. Annual Precipitation Sum for the Period 1992-2022.

The average monthly value of the maximum measured precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022 at the Caen location is 15.7 mm. The highest precipitation values occur in August, with the average measured maximum of 22.6 mm. The lowest average monthly value of maximum precipitation was measured in February, at 10.5 mm.

The average monthly maximum precipitation value for the winter is 12.7 mm, with the lowest values measured in February (10.5 mm) and the highest in December (15.0 mm). The measured average maximum precipitation for the spring is 14.1 mm, with the lowest average maximum precipitation in April (13.5 mm) and the highest in March (14.7 mm).

During the summer, the average maximum precipitation amounts to 19.6 mm. The highest average monthly maximum precipitation was measured in August (22.6 mm), while the lowest values were recorded in July (16.2 mm). The average monthly maximum precipitation during the autumn is 16.3 mm, with the maximum precipitation occurring in October (17.9 mm) and the minimum in September (13.7 mm).

Fig. 5.387. The average monthly value of the maximum precipitation amount for the period 1992-2022 is 15.7 mm.

The average extreme maximum precipitation value for the Caen location for the period 1992-2022 is 59.0 mm. The highest amount of precipitation, 184 mm, was recorded in August 1996. The lowest value of the precipitation maximum, 22 mm, was measured in February 2010. The extreme maximum monthly precipitation values for the period are as follows: January 28 mm (1995), February 22 mm (2010), March 102 mm (2004), April 41 mm (2018), May 29 mm (2008), June 93 mm (2006), July 49 mm (2000), August 184 mm (1996), September 28 mm (2012), October 52 mm (1992), November 48 mm (2021), and December 32 mm (1999).

Fig. 5.388. Maximum precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022.

It was determined for the Caen location that the value of the maximum precipitation amounts in the thirty-year period from 1992 to 2022 decreased by 34 mm. The average value of the maximum measured precipitation on an annual level during the reference period is 42 mm. The highest maximum annual precipitation of 186 mm was measured in August 1996, while the lowest maximum annual value of 21 mm was recorded in June 2016.

Fig. 5.389. Maximum annual precipitation amounts for the period 1992-2022.

At the Caen location, based on collected and analyzed data, significant differences are visible in the average number of days with precipitation amounts of ≥ 1.0 mm, ≥ 5.0 mm, and ≥ 10.0 mm. The highest average number of days with all of the previously mentioned amounts of precipitation is observed during the winter period, while somewhat lower values are observed during the summer, autumn, and spring periods.

The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 1.0 mm has an average monthly value of 10.5, with the maximum number of days occurring in December (average of 14.2 days) and the minimum in July (average of 8.0 days). The average number of days with precipitation ≥ 5.0 mm is 4.2 per month. The maximum number of days with this level of precipitation is recorded in December (average of 5.9 days), while the minimum is recorded in July (average of 2.9 days). The average monthly number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 1.6. The maximum number of days with precipitation ≥ 10.0 mm is 2.3, recorded in December, while the minimum number of days with this precipitation level is 1.0, recorded in February.

Fig. 5.390. Average monthly values of the number of days with precipitation for the period 1992-2022.

6. GENERAL CLIMATIC CHARACTERISTICS OF EUROPE AND RESEARCH SITES

6.1. GENERAL CLIMATIC FACTORS

The consideration of climatic characteristics and climatic types within the spatial zones of the designated research sites cannot be analyzed in isolation without a climatic interpretation of the broader European environment. For this reason, concise introductory clarifications are provided here, pertaining to the climatic characteristics of the European continent as a basis for a detailed and representative presentation of the climate and climatic types of the investigated areas.

The European continent is part of the vast Eurasian landmass, covering approximately 1/5 of its total territory. It exhibits significantly different general physico-geographical conditions compared to the Asian part, logically resulting in distinct climatic features, which is why it is considered a separate continent. The climate of Europe is the result of complex interactions among a series of diverse factors, the most important of which are:

- Physico-geographical position,
- Geomorphological characteristics,

- Geographical distribution of land and sea,
- Regional peculiarities of atmospheric circulation,
- Ocean currents.

The mutual relationships of these prominent factors directly influence both the quantitative-spatial dynamics of the thermo-pluviometric regime and the prevalence and spatial distribution (associated with them) of climatic types.

The European continent is located in the Northern Hemisphere, with a total area of 10,519,458 km², of which approximately 3,450,000 km² is occupied by islands. Its northernmost point is at 71°10' N, located at the North Cape of Mageröy Island, while its southernmost land point is at 36°00' S at Cape Tarifa. The westernmost point is at Cape Roca, 9°30' W, and the easternmost point lies in the northern Ural Mountains at 65°00' E.

In its general appearance, the European continent resembles a right-angled triangle (Map 6.1). The hypotenuse of this triangle follows the Atlantic and North Sea coasts, enabling, on one hand, the deep inland penetration of maritime air masses and, on the other, significantly mitigating the effects of cold polar air in the extreme northern and northeastern regions. One side is represented by the Mediterranean Sea coasts, which notably "soften" the tropical influences of the African continent. Across the other side (formed by the Ural Mountains and the Ural and Manych rivers), Europe has broad contact with the vast Asian landmass, whose pronounced continental thermal characteristics amplify climatic contrasts.

This positional configuration of Europe has facilitated the formation of several distinct geographical types of air masses:

- Arctic maritime (North Ice Sea) and continental (large northern peninsulas and islands),
- Polar maritime (North Atlantic) and continental (eastern and northeastern Europe),
- Tropical maritime (tropical Atlantic) and continental (northeastern Africa) air masses (Map 6.2).

Their individual spatial coverage, speed, and direction of movement are primarily seasonal in nature. Along their mutual contact zones, various types of air fronts form. For the weather and climate of the European continent, the most significant are the Atlantic and Mediterranean sectors of the polar front and the Arctic front.

Map 6.1. Fundamental Astronomical-Mathematical and Morphological Characteristics of Europe
(Authors: N. Drešković, S. Radulović)

Europe is the most indented continent, with a coastline stretching 37,200 km, i.e., approximately 4.1 km of coastline per 1,000 km². This fact highlights the pronounced regional differentiation of its climate, dominated by large islands, peninsulas, and numerous inland seas, particularly the Mediterranean and Baltic Seas, as well as the Caspian Lake. Their climatic influence is expressed through the magnitude of hydro-thermal modification of the air masses moving above them. The most indented coastlines include the Norwegian, northern Adriatic, Greek, and Spanish coasts.

In terms of elevation, the largest part of Europe consists of vast lowlands that stretch almost continuously from the central Atlantic coast to the Ural Mountains. This topographic predisposition facilitates the formation of so-called zonal air circulation, whereby warm and moisture-rich air masses from the Atlantic Ocean are transported toward the continental interior. The absence of significant relief forms in the northern regions, except for the predominantly subdued Scandinavian Mountains, also results in meridional circulation. Very often, vast quantities of cold and dry Arctic air flow unimpeded across European plains and hills toward the south via these currents.

Map

6.2. Spatial Position and Basic Trajectories of Air Mass Movement over the European Continent (Authors: N. Drešković, S. Radulović)

The southern part of Europe is characterized by young folded mountain ranges, beginning from the far northwest of Spain as the Cantabrian and Pyrenees Mountains. These connect, with a brief interruption, to the most powerful mountain chain in Europe - the Alps. These mountains formed during Cenozoic folding (approximately ten million years ago), a process that continues today, and are primarily composed of limestone sediments. Through their northern branch, via a series of morphological discontinuities and depressions, they transition almost meridionally into the Carpathians and further into the Balkan and Pontic Mountains. The central part connects to the Dinaric Alps and extends to the Taurus Mountains in Asia Minor, while the southern branch links to the Apennines.

This massive and largely unified system of high mountains (over 1,500 m a.s.l.), with their steep coastal slopes, almost entirely confines Mediterranean influences on a narrow coastal belt. This is specifically manifested through the precipitation of moisture from maritime air masses flowing along windward slopes and the formation of a so-called rain shadow effect on the leeward mountain sides. Conversely, these mountains also act as an insurmountable barrier to northern and northeastern air currents, which penetrate through depressions in the

Carpathian-Balkan Mountain system into the Pannonian Basin. Here, particularly during the winter season, they stagnate as "lakes of cold polar air," which occasionally break through into the interior of the Dinaric Mountain system via major river valleys. Similarly, the Cantabrian and Pyrenees Mountains on the Iberian Peninsula restrict Atlantic influences. From these facts, it can be concluded that the young folded mountain system of southern Europe also represents a climatic boundary between the subtropical and temperate climatic zones in Europe (Map 6.3). Under the influence of the aforementioned factors, out of a total of seven distinct thermal belts, four are present in Europe. The largest portion of the European continent lies within the northern temperate climatic zone. Only the extreme southern regions belong to the northern part of the northern subtropical climatic zone, while the extreme northern areas extend into the northern subpolar and polar climatic zones (Map 6.3). These prominent factors have also defined the predominant climatic characteristics: the temperate-continental climate type, with maritime and continental variants, dominates the European region.

Map 6.3. General Spatial Position of Project Necropolises Within Two Climatic Zones (Authors: N. Drešković, S. Radulović)

The influences of basic climatic factors directly affect the quantitative values and spatiotemporal dynamics of fundamental thermo-pluviometric indicators - air temperature and precipitation levels.

6.2. GENERAL THERMO-PLUVIOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF EUROPE

A basic analysis of the thermal regime of the European continent was conducted at the level of average annual thermal indicators (Map 6.4). January isotherms are characterized by low values, ranging from $-12,0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the northern and northeastern regions to $10,0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the extreme southern areas of the European continent (Map 4). In the continental interior, they are shifted southward and exhibit a predominantly zonal direction of extension. Their shape largely conforms to existing positive macroforms of the land relief, where their density is also the greatest.

Map 6.4. Geographical Distribution of Annual Isotherms in the European Region (*Editors: S. Radulović, N. Drešković*)

Under the influence of heat from the Atlantic Ocean, isotherms in coastal areas curve northward, adopting a predominantly meridional direction of extension. The zero isotherm in the extreme eastern parts of Europe occupies areas above the Black and Azov Seas, curving southward and bypassing the Alps via the Mediterranean and Atlantic facades, before bending meridionally northward. In the Baltic Sea, it turns zonally westward, following the orography of the Scandinavian Mountains to above the Arctic Circle, where it curves toward Iceland. Based on the position described of the zero isotherm, it can be concluded that northern, eastern, and central Europe experience average winter temperatures below 0,0 °C. Positive winter temperatures are primarily associated with coastal zones, where the thermal influence of the Atlantic Ocean and Mediterranean Sea outweighs continental effects.

The spatial distribution of July isotherms is constrained by stronger heating of the continental interior compared to oceanic and marine surfaces, resulting in a dominant northwest-southeast orientation of isotherms. Climatic contrasts are best illustrated by the quantitative values of isotherms: below 10,0 °C in the far north and over 25,0 °C in the Mediterranean region. The annual air temperature amplitude ranges from 7,0 °C – 10,0 °C in Atlantic coastal areas to 23,0 °C – 25,0 °C in the extreme eastern regions. In the European Mediterranean, it ranges between 10,0 °C and 18,0 °C. Precipitation levels across the broader European continent exhibit pronounced spatial and temporal (seasonal) variability, reflecting the interconnected spatio-quantitative dynamics of this climatic element with atmospheric circulation and dominant topographic features. A general rule is that the most precipitation-rich areas are those above which cyclonic trajectories are most frequent, as well as regions where local conditions favor cloud formation and thermally convective precipitation (Map 6.5).

Map 6.5. Geographical Distribution of Annual Isohyets in the European Region (*Editors: N. Drešković, S. Radulović*)

In Europe, zonal air circulation dominates, directed from the Atlantic across the European lowlands toward the east. Associated with this is the average annual precipitation amount, which is highest in the Atlantic coastal region (London 640 mm) and gradually decreases across Central Europe (Warsaw 550 mm) to the far east (Astrakhan 160 mm). Higher average annual precipitation amounts also characterize mountainous regions such as the Alps, Pyrenees, Carpathians, and Scandinavian Mountains, where it exceeds 1,500 mm or even 2,000 mm in the highest mountain terrains.

Map 6.6. Geographical Distribution of Basic Climatic-Vegetation Zones in the European Region (Authors: S. Radulović)

Annually, two periods can be distinguished during which the largest portion of precipitation occurs: the first in autumn (September - November) and the second in spring (March - May).

6.3. OVERVIEW OF GENERAL THERMO-PLUVIOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF BROADER AREAS OF INVESTIGATED PROJECT SITES

In accordance with the defined research methodology, the identification of climatic specificities and the definition of climatic types for broader areas of the project sites during the recent

climatic period were fundamentally based on investigations of annual and monthly trends within the corresponding thermal and pluviometric regimes. More specifically, all conducted analyses of the quantitative-spatial dynamics of isotherms and isohyets for the broader investigated areas were carried out to theoretically establish and spatially define climatic types according to W. Köppen's climate classification. The definition of climatic types under this classification and the determination of their spatial distribution were realized based on detailed studies of mean monthly and annual air temperatures, as well as average monthly and annual precipitation amounts. The spatial distribution of both climatic elements was interpreted in detail from both horizontal and vertical (elevational) perspectives.

Research on the horizontal distribution of the mean annual air temperature determined that its average value in the broader spatial zones of the project sites is approximately 11,0 °C, with the important note that significant thermal variations exist, defined by the spatial positioning of these sites within two corresponding climatic zones (Map 1). Specifically, in the northern temperate climatic zone, the average annual temperature is below the aforementioned average, at 9,0 °C, while in the northern subtropical climatic zone, its average value is elevated to 14,0 °C. Climatic analyses also confirmed that thermal contrasts within the broader spatial zones of the project sites, from a hypsometric perspective, are highly pronounced, given that the mean annual temperature varies over a very wide range: from 4,0 °C (mountain-basin areas of the Balkan Peninsula, necropolis Ravanjska vrata – 1,650 m) to approximately 15,0 °C (Malta Island, necropolis M'Dina Rabat).

Analysis of pluviometric regimes revealed that the average annual precipitation amount for the broader areas of the investigated project sites is approximately 1,200.0 mm, with spatial distribution variations being highly pronounced and ranging from 700,0 mm in the immediate drainage basin of the Sava and Danube rivers to 3,000.0 mm (in coastal mountain zones of the Balkan Peninsula). Differences in the spatial distribution of precipitation in the broader spatial zones of the project sites are also markedly pronounced at the level of major climatic regions. In the continental climatic region, the average annual precipitation amount is approximately 900,0 mm, varying between 700,0 mm and 1.100.0 mm. In the Mediterranean and sub-Mediterranean regions, precipitation totals increase to values of 1,200.0 mm to approximately 1,300.0 mm, with extreme variations from 950,0 mm (peri-Pannonian basin) to 3,000.0 mm (areas of coastal orographic systems on the Balkan Peninsula). In the third climatic zone, under the direct influence of humid air masses from the Atlantic Ocean, annual

precipitation totals vary from 750,0 mm (along the western European lowlands) to approximately 1,500.0 mm (in zones of prominent mountain morphostructures).

It can generally be concluded that the pluviometric regime in the broader spatial zones of the project sites exhibits pronounced spatiotemporal variations, particularly when observed from the perspective of major climatic regions. In this regard, two main pluviometric types can be distinguished: continental and maritime. In the continental pluviometric type, the majority of precipitation occurs during the second half of spring and autumn, while in the maritime pluviometric type, the period with maximum precipitation is positioned in the colder part of the year (late autumn and early winter). The zone separating the maritime from the continental type is defined by determining the degree of continentality of the area. The isocontinental line $q = 50\%$ in Europe largely coincides with the orographic boundary of the highest mountain peaks in Southern and Central Europe.

7. OVERVIEW OF CLIMATIC TYPES AT PROJECT SITES

7.1. GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF W. KÖPPEN CLIMATIC TYPES IDENTIFIED AT RESEARCH SITES

Based on collected data on monthly and annual trends of thermal and pluviometric regimes, as well as other baseline indicators of quantitative-spatial dynamics of air temperature, precipitation amounts, and intensity, the climatic specificities of the investigated sites were identified.

The identification of climatic types for broader areas of the investigated sites was performed according to the criteria of W. Köppen's climate classification. Based on the results of conducted studies of thermal and pluviometric models, it was determined that two climatic classes are represented in the broader areas of the project sites: C and D.

7.1.1. CLIMATIC CLASS C

Climatic class C encompasses areas whose thermal regime is based on the warmest month – July, with a mean temperature: $t > 10.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, provided that at least three additional months have a mean monthly temperature: $t \geq 10.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The mean monthly temperature of the coldest month is $t > -3.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Essential determinants of this climate also include temperature amplitudes. As already emphasized, their magnitude is directly dependent on the continentality of the location. Greater maritime influence corresponds to smaller temperature amplitudes, up to a maximum

of 20.0 °C, though during summer, due to increased sky clarity, they are larger than in winter when persistent cloudiness dominates general weather conditions over the European continent. With increasing continentality of the location, the magnitude of the annual temperature amplitude rises to over 22.0 °C. Similar applies to daily temperature amplitudes. The average annual temperature across the entire distribution area is approximately 11.0 °C, varying within average boundary temperature values between 8.0 °C and 16.0 °C, directly dependent on the degree of thermal continentality of the area.

The main pluviometric characteristic of the annual precipitation pattern in the spatial zones of the investigated project sites within this climatic class is pronounced regional differentiation, directly dependent on the climatological region. Specifically, in the continental region, there are certain time intervals with elevated or reduced periodic precipitation amounts, but there are no markedly prolonged dry periods, thus indicating a predominantly even distribution of annual precipitation amounts. The average annual precipitation amount in the continental part of climatic class C exceeds 1,000.0 mm, varying within boundary values of annual isotherms from 750.0 mm to approximately 1,600.0 mm. The primary pluviometric characteristic in the annual precipitation pattern of climatic class C under stronger maritime influence is the concentration of precipitation during the colder period of the year, while clear and dry weather dominates during the summer climatological season. Annual precipitation amounts in this part of the region are characterized by an elevated average value compared to the continental part, at approximately 1,500.0 mm, though it can be noted that their degree of variation here is also highly pronounced. Specifically, annual trends of the pluviometric regime in climatic class C under maritime influence are bounded by annual isohyet values from 950.0 mm (Mediterranean Sea) to 3,500.0 mm (mountainous areas of Southeastern Europe).

7.1.2. CLIMATIC CLASS D

Climatic class D in the broader spatial zones of the research sites occupies a unique hypsometric belt, generally starting from the contour line of 1,000 m a.s.l. up to elevation zones closed by the contour line of 1,800 m a.s.l. Specifically, climatic class D continuously extends from climatic class C (in hypsometric zones above 800 m) to climatic class E, with its polar boundary forming isolated spatial areas tied to dominant mountain morphostructures via the contour line of approximately 1,800.0 m (regions of Southeastern and Central Europe). The basic thermal characteristics regarding the temperature regime of July are similar to climatic class C, except that the mean January temperature is generally below -3.0 °C. Mean annual

temperatures vary markedly within boundary values from 2.0 °C to approximately 8.0 °C, with the annual average for the entire zone being approximately 5.5 °C.

The annual trend of the pluviometric regime in this climatic class, in addition to direct influences of regional circulation, is also defined by thermoconvective processes. Specifically, in mountain-basin regions of Europe, all positive morphological preconditions exist for intensive heating of flat or gently sloping soil complexes, thereby intensifying evaporation processes, cloud formation, and thermoconvective precipitation formation. The average annual precipitation amount is approximately 1,100.0 mm, with quantitative-spatial dynamics showing pronounced variation, defined in the broader spatial zones of the project sites by annual isohyets from 700.0 mm (minimum isohyet) to 3,000.0 mm (maximum isohyet). The fundamental pluviometric feature of the annual precipitation pattern is the absence of markedly dry or rainy periods, resulting in precipitation being more or less evenly distributed.

7.2. MAIN CLIMATIC TYPES

According to the pluviometric regime, climatic classes C and D can be differentiated into main climatic types (Map 7.). Specifically, in the broader areas of the investigated project necropolises, climatic class C occurs at the level of two main climatic types: Cf and Cs, while climatic class D occurs only at the level of the Df main climatic type.

7.2.1. CF - MODERATELY WARM AND HUMID CLIMATES

The Cf main climatic type continuously occupies areas of lowlands, hills, and mountainous regions of Western, Central, and (partially) Southern Europe up to approximately 1.000 m a.s.l. At the level of individual climatic subtypes (Cfa, Cfb, and Cfc), this climate may also appear as isolated surface-distributed areas (e.g., isolated mountain massifs). Its primary climatic characteristic is that no pronounced dry period can be distinguished in the average annual pluviometric regime; precipitation is fairly evenly distributed throughout the year, such that the driest month has an average precipitation amount: $p > 40.0$ mm and more than 1/3 of precipitation relative to the month with the highest average precipitation. Considering the highlighted pluviometric determinants (and analyses from the previous chapter), it can be concluded that this climatic type is widely distributed in regions of Western, Central, and (partially) Southern Europe, making it one of the most spatially prevalent climates in Europe (Map 7). In Cf climate zones, annual precipitation averages between 700.0 mm and 1,200.0 mm, distributed relatively evenly throughout the year.

7.2.2. CS - MEDITERRANEAN CLIMATES

The Cs main climatic type is distributed only in the Mediterranean climatic region of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Its primary climatic characteristic is a pronounced dry period in the annual pluviometric regime, positioned during the summer climatological season. Typically, the driest month is July, with the following pluviometric characteristics: $p \leq 40.0$ mm and $p < 1/3$ of precipitation relative to the month with the highest average precipitation. Based on the July thermal regime indicators, its dominant spatial distribution in this climatological region lies within an average elevation range of 0 m to 900 m a.s.l. Its northern boundary, adjacent to D climates, is defined by the mean July isotherm: $t \geq 18$ °C. The average annual precipitation total in Cs climate zones ranges between 950.0 mm and approximately 3,260.0 mm, with over 80% concentrated in the colder period of the year. The warmer period is characterized by anticyclonic weather conditions dominated by clear, very hot, and windless weather.

7.2.3. DF – HUMID BOREAL CLIMATES

The Df main climatic type, according to the established indicators for general thermal and pluviometric regime characteristics in the broader spatial zones of the project sites, appears as the sole precipitation variant of climatic class D. This practically means that the previously described distribution of climatic class D simultaneously represents the distribution zone of the Df climatic type. Consequently, the fundamental climatic feature of this type in the pluviometric regime is a predominantly even distribution of precipitation, with no pronounced dry period identifiable in the annual precipitation pattern.

7.3. CLIMATIC SUBTYPES

Based on the thermal regime of characteristic months—specifically, mean monthly temperatures of January and July - the previously highlighted main climatic types in the broader spatial zones of the project sites are further differentiated into climatic subtypes by adding a third letter to the designation (Map 7.).

Within the Cf main climatic type, the following climatic subtypes can be distinguished based on the quantitative-spatial dynamics of mean annual and July isotherms (as outlined in the previous chapter):

Cfa: Moderately warm and humid climate with hot summer,

Cfb: Moderately warm and humid climate with warm summer.

Within the Cs main climatic type, similar to the Cf type, further climatic differentiation can be performed based on the quantitative-spatial dynamics of mean annual and July isotherms. In the broader spatial zones of the project sites, the following climatic subtypes are distinguished under this main climatic type:

Csa: Mediterranean climate with hot summer,

Csb: Mediterranean climate with warm summer.

In the Df climatic type, two additional climatic subtypes can be identified based on the quantitative-spatial dynamics of mean annual, January, and July isotherms:

Dfb: Moderately humid climates with warm summer.

Further detailed W. Köppen climatic differentiation of these subtypes is based on the temporal distribution of precipitation maxima and minima throughout the year, allowing identification of numerous subtype variants that almost fully reflect local climatic specificities. Specifically, in the annual pluviometric regime trends of the broader spatial zones of the project sites, two more or less pronounced temporal periods of precipitation maxima and two more or less pronounced periods of precipitation minima can be distinguished, alternating between maxima.

One precipitation maximum in the broader spatial zones of the project sites is typically positioned in late autumn and early winter, peaking in November or December. The second precipitation maximum generally occurs in the second half of spring and early summer climatological season, peaking in May or June.

Precipitation minima in the broader spatial zones of the project sites are distributed between precipitation maxima. One period of precipitation minima typically occurs during the second half of summer (July -August), with the minimum in July. The second precipitation minimum generally appears at the end of winter and beginning of spring climatological season, with the minimum in February or (less frequently) March.

Map 7.1. Geographical Distribution of Main Climatic Types According to the W. Köppen Climate Classification in the European Region (Author: N. Drešković, S. Radulović)

Based on the presented facts about the quantitative-spatial dynamics of mean January, July, and annual isohyets in the broader spatial zones of the project sites, the following additional index symbols can be added as a fourth identifier:

x'' - Moderately warm rainy climate without a dry period and with two precipitation maxima.

Variant: **x''w** - The primary precipitation maximum is positioned in late autumn and early winter,

peaking in November or December. The secondary precipitation maximum generally occurs in the second half of spring and the first half of the summer climatological season, peaking in May or June. Precipitation minima are temporally positioned between them. The primary precipitation minimum in the broader spatial zones of the project sites typically occurs during the second half of summer (July - August), with the minimum in July. The secondary precipitation minimum generally appears at the end of winter and beginning of spring climatological season, with the minimum in February or (less frequently) March.

Variant: **x”s** - The primary precipitation maximum generally occurs in the second half of spring and the first half of the summer climatological season, peaking in May or June. The secondary precipitation maximum is positioned in late autumn and early winter, peaking in November or December. The primary precipitation minimum in all spatial zones of the project sites typically occurs during the second half of summer (July - August), with the minimum in July. The secondary precipitation minimum generally appears at the end of winter and beginning of spring climatological season, with the minimum in February or (less frequently) March.

sx” – Mediterranean climate with a summer dry period and two precipitation maxima.

In the annual pluviometric regime of this climatic subvariant, characteristic precipitation periods can also be distinguished. The primary precipitation maximum is temporally positioned in the second half of autumn and the first half of the winter climatological season (October - December). The primary precipitation minimum occurs during the summer climatological season (June - August), when an average of only 83.5 mm (about 30.0% of the annual monthly average) is recorded in one month. The secondary precipitation maximum typically occurs in February, while the secondary precipitation minimum is less distinctly defined, though it generally appears at the end of winter and the first half of spring (March–April).

According to the aforementioned climatic indices, the following climatic subtypes with their subvariants can be distinguished in the broader spatial zones of the project sites:

Cfax”s - Moderately warm and humid climate with hot summer and no dry period;

Cfbx”s - Moderately warm and humid climate with warm summer and no dry period;

Csasx” - Mediterranean climate with hot summer and a summer dry period;

Dfbx”w - Forest-snow climate with warm summer and no dry period;

7.4. VARIANTS OF CLIMATIC TYPES IN THE ZONES OF PROJECT SITES

7.4.1. CFA³S - MODERATELY WARM AND HUMID CLIMATE WITH HOT SUMMER AND NO DRY PERIOD

The primary climatic determinant for distinguishing this subtype is the mean monthly temperature of the warmest month (July): $t \geq 22.0$ °C. The average annual temperature in the entire area varies minimally, ranging from 11.0 °C to 11.5 °C (Graph 5.1.). The extremely flat terrain of this region (comprising very low-lying lowland complexes - below 200 m a.s.l.) is the main reason for intense daily heating of the active absorption surface. Given the very low energetic potential of the relief (within the first energy class: 0–30 m), there are minimal morphological preconditions for disrupting the stable anticyclonic atmospheric conditions over these areas, leading to intense heating during the summer climatological season.

In other words, high July air temperatures, as well as those of other summer months, result from intense heating of the Pannonian Basin, parts of the Po River Basin, and similar morphological units under the direct influence of the northeastern branch of the Azores High during this season. This results in weather dominated by clear skies and windless conditions. In addition to the vast lowland area of this basin (with low elevations - below 200 m a.s.l.) and high daily solar elevation, the dominance of grasses in natural vegetation (which minimally mitigate daily heating) further intensifies warming. Persistent nighttime clear skies also enhance nocturnal radiative cooling of the topographic surface, increasing daily and annual temperature amplitudes, which often exceed 23.0 °C.

The winter season is characterized by intense cooling of the surface due to low daytime temperatures, prolonging snow cover retention in this area. The thermal regime during this season is dominated by the western branch of the Siberian High, which generally causes cloudy, dry, and very cold weather. Due to these specificities, particularly extreme temperature values, this subtype was historically classified as a distinct climate type: the western variant of the Pannonian moderately continental climate, which exhibits quasi-steppe characteristics.

In the broader spatial zones of the project sites, this climatic subtype is identified at two necropolises: Radimlja and Mramorje. The broader areas of these sites belong to zones where summer anticyclonic air masses flow unimpeded by morphological barriers (from both the Adriatic Sea and the Pannonian Basin to the north), resulting in pronounced clear skies and high air temperatures.

Quantitative-spatial dynamics in the annual pluviometric regime are the next critical determinant for defining the general climatic characteristics of this subtype. Specifically, in the pluviometric regime, there is no pronounced dry period, as the average precipitation of the driest month is not below 1/3 of the month with the highest precipitation. Thus, a more or less uniform annual precipitation distribution can be observed. The average annual precipitation in this climatic subtype is among the lowest in the broader spatial zones of the project sites, ranging from 750.0 mm to 800.0 mm. However, deviations from the average can still be noted in the annual precipitation pattern, allowing identification of two characteristic precipitation periods. As previously emphasized, this irregularity results from the general distribution of air pressure during major climatological seasons.

Graph 7.1. Annual Trends of Thermal and Pluviometric Regime in Climatic Subtype **Cfx**'s. Climatic Representatives: Radimlja and Perućac.

During winter, this area is under the dominant influence of dry, cold air from Arctic and polar regions of the Eurasian landmass, resulting in low mean January precipitation. Specifically, this precipitation zone is bounded by the January isohyet of approximately 40.0 mm, among the lowest values in the broader spatial zones of the project sites. The July pluviometric regime is

spatially defined by July isohyets of 75.0 mm in the wider Sava and Danube River basins, slightly below the average for the Pannonian Basin. Summer precipitation is largely linked to thermal convection, meaning it is short-lived but intense, often damaging agricultural activities (especially when occurring as hail). Winter precipitation is primarily associated with frontal disturbances generated by cyclogenetic activity along the **Vb** cyclone track.

The primary precipitation maximum is temporally positioned in the first half of the summer climatological season (June - July), with a seasonal average of 88.0 mm (about 135.0% of the monthly mean). The primary precipitation minimum occurs during the second half of winter and early spring (February - March), with an average of 50.0 mm (about 75.0% of the annual mean). The secondary precipitation maximum falls in November - December, averaging 80.0 mm (slightly above the annual mean). The secondary precipitation minimum is less pronounced and occurs in the first half of autumn (September - October), with an average of 57.0 mm (about 80.0% of the annual mean for the broader area). Based on the temporal distribution and quantitative values of these precipitation extremes, this climatic type at the fourth and fifth symbol levels is labeled: x"s – two precipitation maxima, with the primary positioned in the first half of the summer climatological season.

7.4.2. CFBX"S - MODERATELY WARM AND HUMID CLIMATE WITH WARM SUMMER AND NO DRY PERIOD

This climatic subtype is (more or less) continuously distributed spatially, extending from the Cfax"s climate zone and encompassing areas from Ireland to the Black Sea, and from the Apennine to Scandinavian Peninsulas. In the broader spatial zones of the project sites, its continuous distribution lies within a hypsometric range of 150.0 m a.s.l. (lowland relief) to 1,000.0 m a.s.l. (zones of prominent mountain morphostructures in Southern and Central Europe). Climatically, at the first differentiation level, its boundary toward the Cfcx"s and Dfcx"s subtypes is defined by the mean July isotherm: $t \geq 18.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The average annual temperature across the entire region is approximately 10.0 °C, with significant variation ranging from 7.5 °C to 12.5 °C (Graph 5.2.). The mean July temperature is 19.5 °C, though spatially variable. In January, the mean temperature is -0.5 °C, with thermal variation bounded by upper limits of -2.5 °C to 3.0 °C. Through the valleys of major rivers like the Sava, this subtype deeply penetrates mountain-basin morphological regions of Central and Southern Europe. Specifically, the thermal features of warm summer extend continuously

along river valleys, contributing to vegetation-ecological contrasts in these parts of Europe.

Graph 7.2. Annual Trends of Thermal and Pluviometric Regime in Climatic Subtype **Cfbx**'s. Climatic Representatives: Caen, Klainberdorf, Unsleben, Sarajevo, Križeviči, Kopošiči, Hundskirche.

The average annual precipitation in this climatic subtype is approximately 1,000.0 mm, with highly pronounced spatial variations. For a comprehensive analysis of the annual pluviometric regime, it is necessary to examine seasonal isohyets at a detailed level.

During the winter climatological season, this area is under the dominant influence of dry, cold air from Arctic and polar regions of the Eurasian landmass, resulting in low mean January precipitation. As previously noted, its northern-northeastern boundary in Europe is defined by the January isohyet of approximately 40.0 mm, while its southernmost parts are bounded by the mean July isohyet of 100.0 mm. During the summer climatological season, the pluviometric regime has dual genesis: precipitation linked to cyclogenetic activity along the Vb cyclone track and thermoconvective precipitation processes. July isohyet values range from 80.0 mm to 130.0 mm.

In the annual pluviometric regime of the broader spatial zones of the project sites, periods with

elevated or reduced values relative to the annual average can be distinguished. To illustrate this quantitative-temporal precipitation dynamics, data from Graph 3. (fully representative of the analyzed climatic subtype) are used. The primary precipitation maximum (similar to the previous type) is temporally positioned in the latter part of spring and the first half of the summer climatological season (May - June), with a seasonal average of 100.0 mm (about 125.0% of the annual mean). The primary precipitation minimum occurs in February -March, with an average of 60.0 mm (about 75.0% of the annual mean). The secondary precipitation maximum is positioned in November–December, averaging 85.0 mm (about 105.0% above the annual mean). The secondary precipitation minimum falls in September–October, with a seasonal average of 70.0 mm (about 80.0% of the annual mean for the broader area).

Similar to the previous subtype, this climatic subtype can be characterized at the fourth and fifth symbol levels as x"s – two precipitation maxima, with the primary positioned in the first half of the summer climatological season.

7.4.3. CSASX" - MEDITERRANEAN CLIMATE WITH HOT SUMMER AND A SUMMER DRY PERIOD

The primary climatic determinant for distinguishing this subtype is the mean July isotherm of $t \geq 22.0$ °C, marking the thermal class: hot summer (Graph 5.3.). The average annual temperature for the entire region is approximately 14.0 °C, with boundary values defining its annual range from 12.5 °C to 16.0 °C. Analysis of the mean July isotherm map reveals that the highest mean temperatures occur in the Mediterranean region of Europe, specifically in morphologically flat or gently undulating areas up to 500.0 m a.s.l.

In the broader spatial zones of the project sites, the continuous distribution area with this mean July air temperature ($t \geq 22.0$ °C) spans Malta and the Mediterranean part of the Balkan Peninsula, particularly zones of predominantly flat or mildly undulating limestone platforms.

Pronounced Mediterranean characteristics of this region are evident in the average number of July days with a mean daily temperature ≥ 25.0 °C (summer days), which total 25–28 days across the area. This region often exhibits tropical traits, as the average number of tropical days (mean daily temperature ≥ 30.0 °C) in July ranges from 15–18 days. Its southern and southwestern margins extend to the Adriatic coast in Croatia. Notably, the predominantly bare limestone terrain of this region, exhibiting holokarst features, amplifies daily heating and nocturnal radiative cooling. These conditions slightly increase daily temperature amplitudes

during July.

Graph 7.3. Annual Trends of Thermal and Pluviometric Regime in Climatic Subtype **Csax**". Climatic Representatives: Split, Velika Cista, Mдина Rabat.

From the perspective of mean January temperatures, the key thermal characteristic is $t > 5.0$ °C (mild winter), clearly demarcating its boundary from the Csb climatic type. In the Mediterranean part of the Balkan Peninsula, this isotherm encompasses the Neretva River valley (up to Mostar) and the Adriatic coastal area (up to 500 m a.s.l.), as well as the entirety of Malta. According to the general distribution of permanent and seasonal atmospheric action centers, the highest January precipitation within this climatic subtype occurs in areas exposed to barometric depressions along the Vd cyclone track. Specifically, exposure to winter rain-bearing winds blowing SSE–NNW (when cyclones are positioned over the Mediterranean and Adriatic Seas) is the primary factor in the seasonal precipitation distribution across the entire Mediterranean climatic region. Extending this spatial analogy north and northeast of the Bay of Kotor reveals that the southernmost and southeastern parts of the Mediterranean climatic region are the "richest" in precipitation, based on January and annual isohyets. From this zone, January precipitation gradually decreases on the leeward (northern and northwestern) slopes

of coastal mountain morphostructures of the Adriatic Sea.

In this climatic subtype, the area is bounded by January isohyets of 150.0 mm to 220.0 mm, representing the highest January precipitation amounts. A similar conclusion applies to annual precipitation totals, which average 1,550.0 mm with wide variation, directly influenced by orography. The annual pluviometric regime clearly features a summer dry period lasting at least four months.

During the rest of the year, precipitation occurs through one distinct and one less pronounced maximum. Between them, a weakly defined secondary precipitation minimum period occurs, typically in February–March, with the minimum in February. The primary precipitation maximum is temporally positioned in the second half of autumn and first half of winter (November–December), with a seasonal average of 210.0 mm (about 160.0% of the annual mean). The secondary precipitation maximum shifts to the first half of spring (March–April), averaging 140.0 mm (slightly above the annual mean). The secondary precipitation minimum remains positioned in February, with an average of 120.0 mm (about 95.0% of the annual mean for the broader area). Based on the temporal distribution and quantitative values of precipitation extremes, this climatic type at the fourth and fifth symbol levels is characterized as *sx*” – two precipitation maxima, with the primary positioned in the first half of the winter climatological season. The dry period lasts approximately four months, during which less than 30.0% of the total annual precipitation is recorded.

7.4.5. DFBX”W - FOREST-SNOW CLIMATE WITH WARM SUMMER AND NO DRY PERIOD

The broader transition zone from climatic class C to D is predominantly represented in the mountain-basin morphological region of the Central Dinaride. Within these areas, flat or gently inclined morphologic segments of valley-basin regions often experience intense heating during the summer climatological season due to high solar radiation angles, clearer atmosphere, and low cloud cover. An additional positive factor for intensified summer heating is the strong morphological isolation of these areas from regional disturbances, allowing continuous surface heating over extended periods.

The result of these dynamics is the potential for these regions to heat intensely during summer months, particularly July, leading to high average air temperatures despite their high elevations. Specifically, these areas have a mean monthly temperature of the warmest month

(July): $t \geq 18.0$ °C, thereby attaining the thermal status of warm summer (Graph 7.4.).

Graph 7.4. Annual Ravanjska vrata of Thermal and Pluviometric Regime in Climatic Subtype Dfbx'w. Climatic Representatives: Ravanjska vrata, Dugo polje-Blidinje and Žabljak.

Conversely, during winter, mountain-basin regions undergo intense cooling under the influence of inverse thermal factors. The dominant process contributing to extremely low winter temperatures is the pooling of cold air at the base of morphologically enclosed valleys and basins, a consequence of intense surface cooling.

The aforementioned temperature-lowering process is further intensified by radiation-type temperature inversions, which are phenomenally frequent and temporally prolonged. The direct consequence of these dynamics is a sharp decline in air temperatures, reaching significantly negative average values during winter months. Accordingly, these areas within the spatial zones of the project research sites (Dugo polje, Ravanjska vrata, Žugića bare) exhibit a negative mean January air temperature: $t < -3.0$ °C, thereby attaining the thermal status of very cold winter. Based on the highlighted interpretations, the existence and highly specific spatial

distribution of this climatic subtype can be explained.

Specifically, its "warmer" thermal boundary is defined by the $t \geq 18.0$ °C isotherm from climatic subtypes: Cfb (moderately warm and humid climate with warm summer) and Csb (Mediterranean climate with warm summer), rather than (as might logically be expected) the boundary zone of the Cfc climatic subtype. The spatial result of these dynamics is a direct transition from the Cfb climatic subtype (continental side) or Csb climatic subtype (Mediterranean side) to the Dfb climatic subtype. However, these transitions do not have continuous spatial representation; instead, they typically appear as isolated areas of varying sizes in contact zones between mid-mountain relief morphoforms and morphologically enclosed valley-basin spatial units.

The mean annual air temperature in these regions depends on their belonging to a specific climatological region and morphological specificities, ranging between 8.2 °C and 8.8 °C.

Pluviometric characteristics also exhibit transitional traits between the Cfb and Dfc climatic subtypes. Annually, approximately 1,300.0 mm of precipitation is recorded, with pronounced spatial and quantitative variation. The primary precipitation maximum occurs in the second half of the autumn climatological season (October–November), with a seasonal average of 125.0 mm (about 120.0% of the annual mean). The primary precipitation minimum is positioned in the second half of summer (July–August), averaging 90.0 mm (about 85.0% of the annual mean). The secondary precipitation maximum shifts to the second half of spring and first half of summer (May–June), with a seasonal average of 115.0 mm (above the annual mean). The secondary precipitation minimum occurs in February - March (peaking in March), with a seasonal average of 99.0 mm (about 90.0% of the annual mean for the entire distribution area).

Following the hypsometric factor in temperature variation and the position of extreme precipitation periods, the Dfb climatic subtype at the fourth and fifth symbol levels can be characterized as x"w – two precipitation maxima, with the primary positioned in the first half of the winter climatological season.

8 COMPILING AND OPTIMISING CLIMATE GIS DATABASE FOR THE AREAS OF SELECTED SITES FOR MONITORING AND CONSERVATION

8.1 CREATION OF CLIMATE GIS DATABASE:

To streamline and optimise research, a Geographic Information System (GIS) database can be compiled for the selected sites. This GIS database should include the climate data derived from the station data and the ERA5-Land and ECAD datasets, remote sensing information, as well as details about each site's physical and cultural characteristics. GIS can integrate this variety of data within a single platform. This enables to visualise regional climate patterns, assess their impacts at each site, and compare data across different sites and time periods. The mapping capability of GIS is particularly useful for visualising spatial patterns and trends in vulnerability, which can inform targeted and effective conservation strategies.

The GIS database forms an essential repository of information that can underpin all subsequent stages of research. With comprehensive and reliable data at the outset, researchers can more effectively pursue further study into climate vulnerabilities, deeper understanding of the threats each site faces, modelling of future climate scenarios, and development of effective strategies to safeguard the Stećci. By conducting a comprehensive vulnerability assessment and creating an optimised GIS database, it becomes possible to gain a holistic understanding of the threats posed by climate change to the Stećci. Such a proactive step ensures these invaluable historical monuments are preserved for future generations. The process will no doubt shed light on the urgency of climate change, as well as the steps we can take to curtail its impact on our shared cultural heritage. In the case of climate data like ERA5, spatial interpolation can be used to estimate climate variables at unsampled locations based on the values from nearby sampled locations. However, GIS interpolation methods, while useful for making estimates, may not fully account for the complex physical processes and micro-climates at a local scale. Also, downscaling can introduce additional biases and uncertainties. High-quality station data is usually helpful towards the validation of downscaling exercises. GIS software like QGIS or ArcGIS do support basic raster interpolation, which may be employed as, a method of downscaling.

Data collection and analysis of the spatial distribution of climatic factors are based on a 30-year data set covering the most recent climatic period (1992-2022). The data was prepared in

excel format and organized by climatic elements. Air temperature and precipitation are the fundamental climate components that define the various climate types. However, in order to define climate indices that will be used to analyze and determine the impact of climate elements on the destruction of compact rock masses (monumental heritage), additional climate parameters, such as (insolation, radiation, snow height, extreme temperature values and precipitation amounts, snow height, and the number of days with extreme temperature and precipitation values and the duration of snow cover). In addition to average daily values, the climate data for air temperatures includes average air temperatures measured at 7:00, 2:00, and 9:00 p.m. In addition, air temperature data contain data from average daily maximum (Tmax), minimum (Tmin), and minimum air temperatures at a height of 5 cm above the ground (Tmin5).

According to the existing climatic data, it was essential to collect data on extreme temperatures such as maximum (Tmax), minimum (Tmin), and minimum temperatures at a height of 5 cm (Tmin5), as well as dates of measured extreme air temperature values. Precipitation data was collected monthly ($\sum R$) during a certain climatic period. Climate data on the highest amount of precipitation, as well as the dates of measured extreme values, were collected. Climate data on precipitation included the gathering of data on snow height expressed in centimetres (cm), which was recorded at specific sites. In addition to average values and extreme values of air temperatures and precipitation for all sites, according to available climate data, it was necessary to collect data on the number of days with extreme temperatures (Tmin, Tmax: ≤ 00.0 ; < 0.0 ; ≥ 20.0 ; < 0.0 ; ≥ 25.0 ; ≥ 30.0 ; < 0.0), extreme precipitation (R; ≥ 0.1 ; ≥ 1 ; ≥ 5 ; ≥ 10 ; ≥ 20 ; ≥ 50) and the duration of snow cover (Snow: ≥ 1 ; ≥ 10 ; ≥ 30 ; ≥ 50)

Furthermore, it was important to collect data on solar radiation as one of the extremely significant direct elements of physical, but indirect factor in chemical and organogenic processes of degradation of compact rock masses (monumental heritage). Insolation was measured in hourly values on a monthly basis (h), as well as total solar radiation (kWh/m²).

Given the lack of meteorological stations at the research sites (cultural-historical heritage sites), it was required to collect the defined climatic parameters from surrounding (typically two) meteorological stations for data interpolation, based on availability.

Also, it was required to collect data on solar radiation as one of the extremely significant direct variables of physical, but indirect factors in chemical and organogenic processes of

degradation of compact rock masses (monumental heritage). Data were obtained for monthly insolation represented in hourly values (h) and total solar radiation (kWh/m²).

Given the lack of meteorological stations at the research sites (cultural-historical heritage sites), it was required to collect the defined climatic parameters from surrounding (typically two) meteorological stations for data interpolation.

Based on the measured climate data on a monthly level at the nearest meteorological stations and their altitudes, the gradient of climate parameter changes with altitude was defined by the method of interpolating meteorological data by altitude. Linear changes in climate elements with altitude were identified in areas that have the same or similar orographic terrain characteristics and have the same characteristics of general air circulation. Conversely, it was found that there are more pronounced differences in basic climate elements if there are significant differences in previously identified climate factors. The high mountain systems of the Dinarides and Alps, which separate the continental part of Europe from the sea, act as a barrier and in this way reduce the influence of the sea on the exchange of climate elements.

The climate database was created using official data gathered from the hydrometeorological institutes of all countries involved in the project's implementation. When developing digital databases, data was formatted and evaluated to ensure optimal theoretical alignment and adaptability to the research goals and activities. The data was then interpolated by combining complete climate data from surrounding meteorological stations. Data interpolation was performed for practically all sites that are significantly far from meteorological stations where climate elements are measured or have considerable discrepancies in climate variables. The interpolation method is based on a linear regression model that establishes a link between recorded climate elements (average monthly climate data), orographic terrain characteristics, and general air circulation. To decrease the likelihood of mistakes, interpolation of missing data was not done for certain meteorological stations with longer-term climate data sets. Geographic characteristics such as latitude, orographic parameters (height, vertical diversification, and terrain exposure), proximity to the sea, and atmospheric circulation were all included while interpolating climatic data, resulting in local micro location climate conditions.

To streamline and optimize research, a Geographic Information System (GIS) database can be compiled for the selected sites. This GIS database should include the climate data derived from the station data and the ERA5-Land and ECAD datasets, remote sensing information, as

well as details about each site's physical and cultural characteristics. GIS can integrate this variety of data within a single platform. This enables to visualise regional climate patterns, assess their impacts at each site, and compare data across different sites and time periods. The mapping capability of GIS is particularly useful for visualising spatial patterns and trends in vulnerability, which can inform targeted and effective conservation strategies.

The GIS database forms an essential repository of information that can underpin all subsequent stages of research. With comprehensive and reliable data at the outset, researchers can more effectively pursue further study into climate vulnerabilities, deeper understanding of the threats each site faces, modelling of future climate scenarios, and development of effective strategies to safeguard the Stećci. By conducting a comprehensive vulnerability assessment and creating an optimised GIS database, it becomes possible to gain a holistic understanding of the threats posed by climate change to the Stećci.

Such a proactive step ensures these invaluable historical monuments are preserved for future generations. The process will no doubt shed light on the urgency of climate change, as well as the steps we can take to curtail its impact on our shared cultural heritage. In the case of climate data like ERA5, spatial interpolation can be used to estimate climate variables at unsampled locations based on the values from nearby sampled locations. However, GIS interpolation methods, while useful for making estimates, may not fully account for the complex physical processes and micro-climates at a local scale. Also, downscaling can introduce additional biases and uncertainties. High-quality station data is usually helpful towards the validation of downscaling exercises. GIS-software like QGIS or ArcGIS do support basic raster interpolation, which may be employed as a method of downscaling.

Maps 8.1. Google Earth selected STECCI sites

Maps 8.2. Orography of selected sites Selected sites

Maps 8.3. Bioregions of selected sites

Maps 8.4 Biophysical regions of STECCI sites

Map 8.5. Soil map of STECCI sites

Map 8.6. Climatic map of STECCI sites

Map 8.7. Geological map of STECCI sites

9. CONCLUSION

The climatic framework of Europe and the STECCI research sites arises from complex interactions among geographical, atmospheric, and oceanic dynamics. This analysis highlights the continent's climatic diversity and focuses on the spatial zones of designated necropolises, while also outlining the methodologies and findings of the STECCI project.

The results indicate that the project sites fall into two distinct classes:

Class C (Temperate): Cfa (No dry season): Warm summer (July $\geq 22^{\circ}\text{C}$), e.g., Radimlja, Perućac, Cfb (No dry season): Hot summer (July $\geq 18^{\circ}\text{C}$), Caen, Klainberdor, Unsleben, Križeviči, Kopošiči, Sarajevo, Hundskirche, Csa (Mediterranean): Warm summers with drought, Split, Velika Cista, Mdina Rabat.

Class D (Continental): Dfb (Humid boreal): Cold winters (January $\leq -3^{\circ}\text{C}$), e.g., Ravanjska vrata, Dugo polje, Žabljak.

The following Climatic subtypes and variants were identified: Moderately Warm Climates (Cf): Cfx"s, Cfbx"s, Mediterranean Climates (Cs): Csasx", Continental Climates (Df): Dfbx"w:

9.1. NEXT STEPS

During this phase, a substantial amount of climate data, totaling 7TB, was collected, downloaded and tested onto the STECCI UNSPMF server. As outlined in the STECCI workplan, the next steps will include the following activities:

1. ERA5 data will be tested for Köppen climate classification maps.
2. Extreme indices will be calculated and compared with the station provided data.
3. Reusable GIS maps and codes will be produced for Digital atlas

APPENDIX 1. STECCI CLIMATE DATABES

STECI D2.1 Analysis report on recent climatic characteristics and climatic types for STECCI case study sites [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15167427> The dataset is openly available on Zenodo

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